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Chemical Sciences

HYDRODECHLORINATION OF 1,2,4-TRICHLOROBENZENE

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The adsorption properties of 1,2,4 - trichlorobenzene (TCB) and hydrogen chloride on Ni / -Al₂O₃ and Ni / expanded clay, catalysts for the hydrodechlorination of chlorobenzenes, were studied. It has been established that the surface treated with hydrogen is able to absorb 1,2,4 - TCB and hydrogen chloride more than the surface treated with nitrogen.

The most controversial issue in periodic publications is the mechanism of the reaction of hydrodechlorination of chlorine-containing aromatic compounds. This is all the more important because, depending on the composition of the catalytic system, the mechanism of the hydrodechlorination reaction changes significantly [1, 2].

Our studies [3,4] have shown that the highest selectivity for mono- and dichlorobenzenes formed as a result of the hydrogenolysis reaction of 1,2,4-trichlorobenzene (1,2,4-TCB) has a previously undescribed catalytic system, where as Expanded clay is used as a carrier, and nickel is used as an active mass. In this case, catalytic systems turned out to be less selective: expanded clay; nickel deposited on aluminum oxide, etc.

To explain this behavior of the described catalytic systems in the heterogeneous catalytic reaction of 1,2,4-TCB hydrogenolysis, in this work we studied the adsorption properties of catalytic systems, which are one of the characteristics of their catalytic properties.

It is known that the process of hydrodechlorination without significant activation of hydrogen is not efficient enough [1]. The main component of the catalytic system responsible for the adsorption activation of hydrogen is the active component deposited on the support.

In the studied catalytic systems, nickel was used as an active component, which is inferior to palladium by 3–4 orders of magnitude in terms of the intensity of hydrogen adsorption [5].

However, the carrier used makes a significant contribution to the adsorption activation of hydrogen by the active component [3].

The study of the adsorption of 1,2,4-TCB and hydrogen chloride on various catalytic systems was carried out by the method of gas adsorption chromatography, in the temperature range 473-673K, gravimetric and volume-vacuum research methods [7-9].

Nickel-containing expanded clay and γ -Al₂O₃ were used as catalysts, which were obtained by impregnating the carriers with a solution of nickel nitrate, followed by drying at 383K and calcining at 773K for 4 hours.

Expanded clay is prepared from clay of the Zyk deposit, by calcining with a gradual rise in temperature from 573K to 1473K for one hour, dried at 353K sample. At the maximum temperature, the clay is kept for 5 minutes.

The specific surface determined by low-temperature nitrogen adsorption by the chromatographic method [6] for expanded clay and γ -Al₂O₃ is 14.5 m²/g and 220 m²/g, respectively.

Before the study, 1,2,4-TCB with the content of the main component of 96.8% was dehydrated with sodium metal, distilled off and passed through a silica gel column. Hydrogen chloride was obtained by the interaction of hydrochloric acid with sulfuric acid and dried by

passing through a column of calcium chloride. The hydrogen used was 99.0% pure. Nitrogen was used as the carrier gas.

Before each measurement, fresh adsorbent was treated at a given temperature for at least two hours in a carrier gas flow.

The apparent heats of adsorption are determined by the slope of the direct dependence of the logarithm of the apparent equilibrium adsorption constants ($k=V_r/RT$) on the inverse adsorption temperature.

The temperature dependence of the retained volume of 1,2,4-TCB on the expanded clay base catalysts upon preliminary activation with nitrogen shows that the adsorption of 1,2,4-TCB on the 15% Ni/expanded clay catalyst up to a temperature of 543 K is higher than that of 30% Ni/expanded clay and on expanded clay without applying nickel. Whereas with an increase in temperature, the adsorption of 1,2,4-TCB on 30% Ni/expanded clay does not decrease as sharply as on other catalyst samples and becomes 1.5–2 times higher. This, apparently, explains the increased yield of compaction products by 30% Ni/expanded clay [3].

The retained volume of 1,2,4-TCB by expanded clay and 30% Ni/expanded clay is practically the same at 473 K (~0.4 ml/g catalyst).

Regardless of the activation temperature on the 15% Ni/expanded clay catalyst, with an increase in the adsorption temperature from 473K to 643K, the retained volume of 1,2,4-TCB decreases. The largest amount of 1,2,4-TCB is retained on the surface of 15% Ni/expanded clay activated at 723 K in a nitrogen flow.

To obtain information on the adsorption of 1,2,4-TCB on a pretreated nickel deposited surface with hydrogen, experiments were carried out with a 15% Ni/expanded clay catalyst pretreated with hydrogen at various temperatures.

The specific retention volume of 1,2,4-TCB increases with increasing temperature of the treatment of the 15% Ni/expanded clay catalyst with hydrogen. Based on this, it can be assumed that an increase in the temperature of the hydrogen treatment of the surface of the 15% Ni/expanded clay catalyst is accompanied by the appearance of a large number of adsorption centers.

A comparison of the results shows that when the 15% Ni/expanded clay catalyst is treated with hydrogen, the retained volume of 1,2,4-TCB is not only higher than when treated with nitrogen, but also increases with an increase in the adsorption temperature at its treatment temperatures of 723 K and higher. This suggests that the increase in the retention volume of 1,2,4-TCB is associated with the interaction of the latter with hydrogen adsorbed on the catalyst surface. The fact that when the catalyst is activated with 15% Ni/expanded clay with nitrogen, the minimum apparent heat of adsorption of 1,2,4-TCB corresponds to a temperature of 723K and is equal to 38.2 kJ/mol, while when the catalyst is activated with hydrogen at a temperature of 723K and 773K apparent heats of adsorption are close to zero, and the retained volumes of 1,2,4-TCB are much larger, suggesting that the 15% Ni/expanded clay catalyst treated with hydrogen has a larger number of adsorption sites at a lower adsorption strength, which is in good agreement with research data [9]. When investigating the dependence of 1,2,4-TCB adsorption on a 15% Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst on the nitrogen treatment temperature of the catalyst and on the adsorption temperature, it was found that the specific retention volume of 1,2,4-TCB increases with increasing nitrogen treatment temperature, but decreases with increasing adsorption temperature. Thus, a high adsorption capacity of the 15% Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst is observed compared to the 15% Ni/expanded clay catalyst. The regular decrease in the apparent heats of adsorption in this case indicates that this is most likely due to a large number of adsorption centers of reduced strength.

The extremely high adsorption capacity of the 15% Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst, and, consequently, its high catalytic activity, also contributes to a decrease in the selectivity of the 1,2,4-TCB

hydrodechlorination reaction with respect to monochlorobenzene, as studies have shown [3, 4].

Table. Effect of the catalyst treatment temperature in a nitrogen flow on the apparent heats of 1,2,4-TCB adsorption

Catalyst	Catalyst Apparent heat of adsorption, kJ/mol			
	Temperature, K			
	573	653	723	773
15% Ni/ expanded clay	-	42,66 ± 4,2	38,23 ± 3,7	49,46 ± 4,5
15%Ni/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	20,78 ± 2,0	-	25,48 ± 2,2	14,46 ± 1,5

Due to the fact that during the hydrodechlorination of chlorobenzenes, the formed hydrogen chloride can play an important role in the course of the process, its adsorption-desorption capacity on the surface of the 15% Ni/expanded clay catalyst was studied.

It follows from the obtained data that with an increase in temperature, both during the treatment of the catalyst surface with hydrogen and nitrogen, the adsorption of hydrogen chloride decreases. However, a surface pre-treated with hydrogen retains more hydrogen chloride than a surface treated with nitrogen. As the temperature increases, the ratio of the volumes of HCl held by the surface treated with hydrogen and nitrogen increases, which probably indicates a strong interaction of hydrogen chloride with the surface treated with hydrogen. At the same time, the heat of adsorption of hydrogen chloride on the surface of the catalyst treated with nitrogen is almost two times higher than on the surface treated with hydrogen. This indicates a high strength, but a smaller number of sites adsorbing hydrogen chloride on the surface of the catalyst treated with nitrogen.

The strength of hydrogen chloride adsorption on the active sites of the 15% Ni/expanded clay catalyst is probably the reason for the hydrodechlorination of 1,2,4-TCB with the highest selectivity for monochlorobenzene than for benzene [3].

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Extraction and Clarification of Steviol Glycosides (Sweetener) from Stevia Rebaudiana Bertoni

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ABSTRACT

In the present study, the separation and purification of Steviol glycosides from the leaves of *S. rebaudiana* was carried out using physical separation techniques such as extraction and clarification. The extraction of the Steviol glycosides from the leaves of *S. rebaudiana* was carried out using hot water. The effect of Steviol glycosides to water ratio on extraction efficiency was studied. Higher percentage of recovery was obtained at the Steviol glycosides to water ratio of 1:35. The clarification of extract is an important stage as it imparts better visual quality to the final product, and this was done using decolouring and flocculating agent such as calcium hydroxide combing with filter aid followed by carbonation using carbon dioxide gas. Stoke law for setting solids was employed to work out sedimentation parameters such as settling time and settling velocity to understand the stevia clarification process. Subsequent to extract clarification, a new method for HPLC analysis has been developed for the analysis of Steviol glycosides. It was observed that clarification of Steviol glycosides with a recovery of 76% Steviol glycosides of high purity and a reasonably significant percentage of rebaudioside A in the clarified extract.

KEYWORDS: Stevia, Steviol glycoside, Clarification, Sedimentation, Carbonation, HPLC method

INTRODUCTION

Natural compounds derived from plants are the part of our daily diet. In recent years, there has been an increased focus on healthy way of life along with the search for new natural products. Amongst them are specific sweeteners, such as Steviol glycosides, now in great demand globally. Stevia rebaudiana, the nature's sweetest gift belongs to the family Asteraceae. The main source of sugar globally comes from cane sugar and beet. These sugars along with sweetening qualities contribute to high calories, which lead to obesity, a risk factor for some chronic diseases such as diabetes mellitus, hypertension, cardiovascular diseases and so on. Thus, craving for sweetness led man to discover several forms of alternative intense sweeteners, which have made possible to offer consumers sweet taste sans calories. Major Steviol glycosides such as stevioside and rebaudioside A are the major sweet components isolated from the leaves of *Stevia rebaudiana* (Figure 1).¹⁻³ It is about 300 times sweeter than sucrose and noncaloric⁴. Thus, it is gaining popularity as a sweetener in Asia and South America and has been used as a dietary supplement in the United States.² Steviosides can be degraded to its major metabolite, steviol, by intestinal bacterial microflora of human being.⁴⁻⁶ The chemical structures of steviol and major steviol glycosides such as stevioside and rebaudioside A are shown in Figure 1. Stevioside is formed by attaching glucose molecules to the steviol structure. The diterpene as steviol is the aglycone of stevia's sweet glycosides, which are constructed by replacing steviol's carboxyl hydrogen atom (at the bottom left of figure) with glucose to form an ester, and replacing the hydroxyl hydrogen (at the top of the figure) with combinations of glucose and rhamnose to form an ether. The two

primary compounds, stevioside and rebaudioside A, use only glucose: Stevioside has two linked glucose molecules at the hydroxyl site, whereas rebaudioside A has three, with the middle glucose of the triplet connected to the central steviol structure.

Figure 1. Molecular structure of Steviol glycosides: (a) Steviol (b) Stevioside (c) Rebaudioside A

Steviol glycosides have been reported to possess therapeutic value as an antihypertensive or antihyperglycemic agent.⁷⁻¹¹ The available data indicate that Steviol glycosides are nontoxic, non-mutagenic and noncarcinogenic in various mammalian species.^{12,13} It has been reported that, the leaf has several sweetener glycosides such as stevioside, rebaudioside A, B, C, D, E and dulcosides A and B. Those present in larger quantity are stevioside (5-10%), rebaudioside A (2-4%) and the others are present in smaller concentrations.¹⁴ Several methodologies have been illustrated for herbal extraction such as ultrasonic extraction,¹⁵ microwave assisted extraction,¹⁶ pressurized hot water extraction.¹⁷ However, these techniques were found to be relatively expensive and tedious. Keeping these points in mind, the present study focused to develop an effective and industrially feasible method for the extraction of steviol glycosides from the leaves of *Stevia rebaudiana* using hot water as an extractive agent. Several processes of extraction of stevia leaves presented in literature follows approximately the same methodology. The separation and clarification were carried out in two stages. Firstly, the extraction of the leaves of *S. rebaudiana* was carried out with water or alcohols (ethanol or methanol). The obtained extract was in the form of a solution loaded with colloidal particles of dark brown colour, containing all the active principles, pigments of the leaf, soluble polysaccharides, and other impurities. Except these processes, some of the processes has been stated on the removal of greases from the leaves with solvents, such as chloroform or hexane, a preliminary elimination of essential oils, chlorophyll and other a polar principles.^{17,18} The second stage consist of the clarification of the extract, which was usually carried out using chromatography; especially, the high-speed counter-current chromatography, resins, metallic ions, ultrafiltration and organic solvents has been widely used for the clarification of the steviol glycoside extract and various impurities complex natural Products.¹⁹⁻²¹ The impurity of these solution has been removed by either extraction process modified to yield products with higher clarity using organic solvents products or aqueous extraction purified with specific methods involving two phases aqueous extraction,¹⁹ consecutive utilization of metallic ions and organic solvents,²⁰ nano and ultra-filtration and membrane technology.²¹ Both approaches were proven to be effective in increasing clarity of the extract. However, utilization of organic solvent in the extraction required the separation of organic solvent from the extract which would cause an increase in manufacturing cost and more importantly these solvents are harmful to human health even if they remained in solution in trace amounts. Among these, chloroform used in extraction can be given as an example. These chemicals had previously been classified as group 2B carcinogen.¹⁹ Membrane technology is highly effective in clarification. However, this is

an emerging technology still coping with clogging problems and operational costs to actuate this process are extremely high. Health problems could be reduced by utilization of water as the solvent in the extraction and increase in clarity of the extract could be maintained using defecation by liming, carbonation.^{22,23} The extract clarification is a particularly important stage because it results into a better visual quality of the final product. However, usual clarification processes have some disadvantages: organic solvents and metallic ions residues which are harmful to health and thus are forbidden according to ICH guidelines. Ultra-filtration membranes and other advanced technologies are associated with high capital as well as high operating cost. The present study focused to develop cost effective, economical feasible process of extraction and clarification of Steviol glycosides. The techno-commercial aspects are expected to be in the favour of the proposed separation and clarification technology.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Chemicals

Steviol glycosides (Stevioside and Rebaudioside A) ($\geq 98\%$) were kindly provided by Scope Ingredients Pvt Ltd. Mumbai, India. Chemical reagent and solvent such as calcium carbonate, hydrochloric acid, filter aid was procured from S.D. Fine Chemicals, India.

Extraction Methodology

Leaves of *S. rebaudiana* were purchased from the local market in Mumbai. Stevia glycosides are freely soluble in water and hence water have been chosen for extraction. The leaves were ground to coarse powder and extracted at 55°C temperature of water for 2 h at 110 rpm. The extraction of Steviol glycosides from the ground powder was carried by mixing coarse powder and water using glass jar reactor equipped with baffles and a stirrer. The solvent was removed, and the process was repeated for one more time to remove the final traces of Steviol glycosides from the ground powder of stevia leaves. The extracts were then combined and concentrated by evaporating the water, that gives dark greenish brown extract. The obtained extract was used for further studies. The effect of Steviol glycosides to solvent ratio on the extraction efficiency was also studied by varying the quantum of the Steviol glycosides with water as a solvent.

Clarification and Purification of Extract

Clarification of crude dark greenish brown extract was carried out by adding calcium hydroxide till the pH was attained to 10-12 and stirred for 20 minutes at 50°C temperature, to remove unwanted plant colouring matters such as chlorophyll and carotenoids. It is known that Steviol glycosides remains stable over a wide range of pH and heat.²⁰ Then 50 ppm of Hyflo Supercel Celite® was added while stirring in the whole volume of extract furthermore limed juice leave it for sedimentation at detention time for 30 min to 2 hr, that reduces the concentration of suspended particles, pigments in the extracts, reducing the load on the filters. Stoke law for setting solids was employed to calculate to sedimentation parameters such as settling time and settling velocity to understand stevia clarification process. Subsequent to sedimentation, the supernatant, which was obtained in the above sedimentation process, then decanted and collected in separate glass jar. The supernatant was again filtered out to remain all suspended particles. Filtrate was collected and cake was subjected to the washing with fresh water to recover the glycoside effectively. The washings were added to the filtrate (supernatant) followed by carbonation treatment using Carbon dioxide gas. Carbonation was carried for 20 min by CO₂ gas till the pH was attained to 7 to 8. This leads to the precipitation of residual salt along with colouring matters thus leading to the further removal of impurities.

$$V = \frac{g \left(\frac{\rho_1}{\rho} - 1 \right) d}{18\nu} \quad (1)$$

Where V is settling velocity of the lime and filter aid; G is acceleration of Gravity; ρ_1 is the mass density of the lime and filter aid; ρ is mass density of the stevia extract; d is the diameter of the solids (assuming spherical) and ν is kinematic viscosity of the fluids

The carbon dioxide gas was obtained by reacting hydrochloric acid with calcium carbonate. During the carbonation process, pH was meticulously monitored since Stevia glycosides starts degrading below pH 4.0. The precipitate was removed by filtration and the process was repeated for one more time until the clear off-white solution was obtained. The filtrate was used for further study. Steviol glycosides content in each of the recovery process was quantified. The solid content, pH, chlorophyll, and carotenoids were estimated to examine the level of purity of Steviol glycosides extract. The total solids content of the sample was measured gravimetrically by heating the extract in a hot air oven at $104 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ until the difference in the weight of the extract becomes constant at successive intervals.²⁴ Total solids were represented in terms of gram per 100ml of Stevia extract.

Extraction of Chlorophyll

100 ml of sample was taken and extracted with 150 ml of 80% acetone. It was then centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 8 min. The supernatant was transferred, and the procedure was repeated till the residue becomes colourless. The volume make up has been done up to 100 ml. The absorbance of the solution was taken at 470 nm, 645 nm, and 663 nm against the solvent (80% acetone) blank. The process was followed for all the plant samples.

Estimation of Chlorophyll Content: The concentrations of chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b and total chlorophyll were calculated using the following equation)^{25,26}:

$$\text{Chlorophyll a} \left(\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{gm}} \text{ tissue} \right) = [12.7(A_{663}) - 2.69(A_{645})] \times \frac{V}{1000} \times W \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Chlorophyll b} \left(\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{gm}} \text{ tissue} \right) = [22.9(A_{645}) - 4.68(A_{663})] \times \frac{V}{1000} \times W \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Total Chlorophyll (a + b)} \left(\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{gm}} \text{ tissue} \right) = [20.21(A_{645}) + 8.02 (A_{663})] \times \frac{V}{1000} \times W \quad (4)$$

Where, A is absorbance of specific wavelength; V is final volume of Chlorophyll extract in 80% Acetone and W is Fresh weight of Tissue extract

Estimation of Carotenoids: The quantum of Carotenoids was estimated by using Lichtenthaler and Wellburn method.²⁷ The same chlorophyll extract was measured at 470 nm in spectrophotometer to estimate the Total Carotenoid (xanthophylls + carotene) content.

$$\text{Total Carotenoids} \left(\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{gm}} \text{ tissue} \right) = C_a + c = (1000A_{470} - 1.82a - 85.02C_b)/198 \quad (5)$$

Where, A is the absorbance at respective wavelength, C_a = Chlorophyll a, C_b = Chlorophyll b

HPLC Analysis of Steviol Glycosides

The Agilent (Germany) HPLC system, consisting of a model G1329A standard auto-sampler, model G1316A thermostat column, model G1322 A vacuum degasser, quaternary pump, model G1314B variable wavelength detector, were used. The separation was achieved on a stainless-steel silica based Zorbax Eclipse XDB-C18 column ($\phi 4.6 \text{ mm} \times 150 \text{ mm}$, $5 \mu\text{m}$). The column temperature was maintained at 30°C . Steviol glycosides were eluted using mobile phase consisting of methanol and 0.1% v/v H_3PO_4 (70:30) at the flow rate of 1 ml/min. The eluent was monitored at 219 nm. The standard curve was obtained by analysing known concentration of Steviol glycosides. The standard

curve was plotted between the concentration of stevioside and the area under the curve. This plot was used for the determination of concentration of the Steviol glycosides in the unknown solution. All the samples were prepared in the methanol of 10 mg/l concentration and filtered through 0.22 μm filter to remove any suspended particles. The amount of sample injected in the column was kept constant at 10 μl . The filtered solvents were sonicated for 10 min to remove any dissolved gases.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Extraction of Glycosides

The extraction of glycoside from the leaves of *S. rebaudiana* was carried out using hot water as a solvent and varying glycoside to different water ratios. The effect of glycoside to solvent ratio on the extraction efficiency was studied by varying these ratios. Figure 2 shows the plot of extracted Steviol glycosides verses dry feed to solvent ratio. The extraction increases until the feed to solvent ratio of 1:35 (w/v), there after; there is no significant effect of increasing the amount of solvent on the extraction efficiency. Similar observations have been reported by Abou-Arab et al.¹⁴ who obtained 93-98% of extraction efficiency using the equivalent quantity of water. Figure 3 shows the reduction in soluble solids when excess solvent is used during the process. This is interesting observations which tell us about the preferential solubilisation of Steviol glycosides as compared to other soluble matter which consists of polysaccharides and other such impurities. From these two figures, it can be said that the 1:35 ratio would be an ideal from the process economic point of view as illustrated by extraction of about 7.5% (w/w) concentration of total Steviol glycosides in the aqueous solution.

Figure 2. Effect of dry feed to water ratio on the percent yield of Steviol glycosides

Figure 3. The percentage of solids extract

Clarification and purification

The crude leaf extract was deep green to dark brown in colour due to the presence of pigments, chromospheres, and other soluble components. Figure 4 is the chromatogram of the crude extract showing several peaks along with two major peaks, viz., stevioside at the retention time 7.1 min and rebaudioside A at the retention time 6.97 min. However, Figure 5 represents the chromatogram shows the pigments such as chlorophyll and caretonoides present in the crude

extract, that affects to a great extent the purification process and the purity of the Steviol glycosides. The crude green extract was treated with flocculent such as calcium hydroxide along with Hyflo Supercel Celite® filter aid till the pH was attained to 12. This resulted into substantial removal of caretonoides and chlorophyll from the crude mixture as was seen by the lighter colour of the solution. The solution was then further treated with bleaching agent such as CO₂ until the pH reaches to about 8. Here, a transparent light colour was attained. It is known that the light is absorbed by certain chromophore present in the plant. C=C and C=O are essential building blocks which absorbs the UV and visible light thus producing the colour in organic matter. The carbonation treatment essentially converts double bond by reduction process and converts the coloured matter into colourless. More precisely, carbon dioxide gas reacts with water to liberate nascent hydrogen. The nascent hydrogen so formed, then adds to the coloured matter. As a result, discoloration takes place to add the aesthetic value to the final desired product, as shown by eq. (6).

Figure 4. Chromatogram of initial extract of *S. rebaudiana* leaves

It is usually assumed that, in juice clarification, any colour removal is due to adsorption of colorants on the nascent crystals of calcium carbonate and other sparingly soluble anions. Table 5 shows the extent of decolourization takes place during clarification processes. Almost 50% reduction in pigments obtained after the calcium hydroxide and Hyflo Supercel Celite® treatment. Thereafter, a substantial reduction could be seen when treated with the carbonation treatment. The pigment content was reduced by about 90% both in terms of chlorophyll and caretonoides as shown in Figure 5. Clarification was carried out in the two steps. In the first stage, flocculation with adding of filter aid was conducted. Furthermore, sedimentation was carried out in next step in conventional filtration process, which significantly enhance the filtration rate by removing suspended particulates from the stevia extract along with the colouring matter by means of gravity or physical separation. Evaluating the effect of flocculation in settling rate as per stock law, it was verified that settling rate of 2.0 cm/min for flocculating agent combine with filter aid and detention time of 2 h was noticed. Some of the batch studies of efficient clarification process were conducted on sedimentation, employing in the first stage. In the first stage, the pH of a succession of aqueous stevia extract solutions was adjusted to the required value by the addition of concentrated flocculating agent (pH = 12). The maximum clarification was observed by treating with 50 ppm Hyflo Supercel Celite® filter aid, that enhance the settling rate in sedimentation of 2 h. It was observed that the settling rate increased 2 times by increasing settling velocity and reduce settling times from 4 h to 2 h. In the second stage, the treatment of Carbonation (pH = 8.0) was employed. The supernatant was collected from the first stage and carbonation was employed at 50°C under stirring condition. Carbon dioxide gas was passed to the solution till the pH reached to 8.0. Subsequently, the filtration was carried out using whatman filter paper no.1; the supernatant was

collected and kept into second beaker and initial extract which is untreated was in first beaker marked as before studies. Figure 6 shows the obvious difference in the initial stevia extract and after clarification. Figure 6 (a) and (b) show that the best results for the overall process, either for colour removal or pigment removal were obtained at pH values below 8. Clarification of stevia extract was high after sedimentation/flocculation, whereas the highest clarity was obtained with treatment of carbonation, this because the more than 90% pigments and other colouring matter were removed significantly. This result indicated that carbonation had been effective in the clarification of Stevia extract.

Figure 5. Removal of Pigments during clarification steps

Figure 6. Stevia extract before and after clarification

HPLC analysis

The chromatograms of Steviol glycosides obtained from the leaves of *Stevia rebaudiana* were compared with standard Steviol glycosides and the percent purity of Steviol glycosides was found to be 76% with significant percentage of rebaudioside A and stevioside. Figures 4 and 7 shows the chromatogram of the clarified extract and initial extract of *S. rebaudiana* leave Steviol glycosides obtained in this study, respectively. The presence of stevioside was estimated at 6.97 min retention time and rebaudioside A at 7.1 min retention time, clearly illustrated the similarity in retention time and intrinsic advantage of clarification in attaining more sweeter component as a substantial fraction in the extracted purified product and impurity elimination.

Figure 7. Chromatogram of Clarified Steviol glycosides Extract

In conclusion, the extraction of Steviol glycosides from the leaves of *S. rebaudiana* using water as solvent was carried out. The optimized ratio of dried *S. rebaudiana* leaves to water was found to be 1:35. Followed by conventional extraction, the extract clarification was successfully carried out using flocculation and Carbonation. Stoke law for setting solids was employed to work out on sedimentation parameters such as settling time and settling velocity to understand stevia clarification process. The simple and novel approach based on extraction followed by clarification of extract in the present work can be the most promising techniques for this kind of natural sweetener extraction and clarification which is the pivotal process in stevia extraction technology.

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Economic Sciences

Improvement of the organizational structure of management of state programs of youth policy at the regional level

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Annotation. The relevance of the study is due to the fact that today youth is one of the most central topics among all topics discussed by politicians, scientists and journalists. Young people today are becoming a kind of sign of the era, various phenomena of youth culture are beginning to cause a fairly wide public resonance. In recent years, interest in youth and youth policy has grown so much that experts are already beginning to talk about a "new youth era" - an era when young people are able to change the nature of world culture itself, and the "idea of youth" is becoming the most popular product of the global market.

Key words: youth policy, state programs, program, society.

Introduction. Changes in modern society and the state, which are caused by the advent of the era of the global economy, as well as global mutual influence, require completely new approaches to the content of state youth policy, including taking into account the real needs of young people, refusing to perceive it as only a resource for the future state of society and a passive object of influence from the state, as well as other subjects of social relations.

The increased interest in the younger generation reflects one of the objective patterns of the current stage of world development, associated with the awareness by society and the state of the specific role and status of youth in political, economic and socio-cultural reality.

Large-scale transformations in the foundations of the life of our society have caused dynamic and profound changes in the social characteristics of the new generation, led to the emergence of large and multifaceted youth problems that deepen and determine the decline in youth potential. An effective state youth policy today is not only a factor of social stability, but also a guarantor of the security of the state as a whole.

It is up to the younger generations to implement the reforms started in our state and develop them to the level of systemic socio-economic transformations, which is impossible without building a transparent and open mechanism of public administration, creating favorable conditions for the full-fledged process of socialization of young people, involving them in making socially important decisions, becoming effective public communications and democratic standards in the provision of youth services.

Given this, there is an objective need for a scientific analysis of the state youth policy as a political and administrative phenomenon, as well as the search for effective mechanisms of public administration aimed at solving the problems of integrating young people into society in conditions of social instability, by studying and adapting foreign experience.

Paying tribute to the scientific and practical significance of the considered works of domestic and foreign scientists, it should, however, be noted that in the works insufficient attention was paid to a comprehensive study of the mechanisms of public administration in the field of youth policy. The need to identify management tools and new approaches aimed at conducting an effective youth policy of the state, theoretical substantiation of directions and development of practical recommendations for improving the mechanisms of public administration in the field of youth policy is the main goal of this article.

Based on all of the above, it should be noted that the term "state youth policy" is quite popular today. Having entered into scientific circulation back in the nineties of the twentieth century, today it has already become commonly used. The state youth policy is a system of state priorities and measures that are aimed at creating conditions and opportunities for successful socialization, as well as for the most effective self-realization of the young generation, for developing its potential in the interests of Kazakhstan and, thus, for cultural and socio-economic development state, ensuring its competitiveness and strengthening national security. The main means of developing the potential of the younger generation is the involvement of young people in the socio-economic, socio-cultural and socio-political life of our society. In general, the state youth policy is understood as such activity of the state regarding the implementation of the organizing functions of social development of youth, and an increasingly significant place belongs to the multilateral interaction of full participants in the processes of development, adoption and implementation of decisions that relate to socialization and, first of all, self-realization of youth, then there are - youth associations and other partners of the state represented by interested structures of civil society. The modern understanding of youth can be characterized by a certain transformation, the main trends of which are:

- approval of the concept of self-worth of youth, which replaces the idea of youth as about "inferior" adults;
- a departure from the paternalistic attitude towards the younger generation;
- a shift in emphasis towards supporting the independence of young people;
- rejection of the instrumental understanding of youth as a "resource";
- defining as the main goal the formation of conditions for the development of the young generation's own initiatives.

Today, youth policy, being an integral part of the internal policy of the state, more and more requires authors to comprehend and in the context of interaction between the state and society as a whole. This problem is one of the most urgent for Western authors, who mainly analyze in their works the ways and methods of interaction between state institutions and society.

Results and discussion. As for the youth policy in our state, the value, although significant, is still unstable. Laws are adopted and repealed, and state bodies for the implementation of state youth policy are established today and liquidated tomorrow, funding is opened and immediately closed.

Such facts mean that the state youth policy at the moment is still peripheral for Kazakhstan. Both from a legal and a practical point of view, it continues to be an inferior area of state activity that requires constant and careful study.

The situation of young people in the Republic of Kazakhstan is characterized as quite complex and accompanied by a significant number of problems, many of which are typical for the latest period of development of our country.

On the one hand, young people in our country make up over 20% of the population, are actively involved in the processes of public administration, young people are appointed to responsible positions in administrative, industrial and other fields of activity, which is consistent with modern long-term approaches and trends in the formation and development of personnel policy modern state.

On the other hand, there is a clear dissatisfaction of a significant part of Kazakhstani youth with their place in the socio-economic, political and cultural life of society, as well as potential opportunities for further personal development. The stratification of the population of the Republic of Kazakhstan in terms of economic indicators, the impoverishment of the population, also affects young people, creating catastrophic differences in “starting” opportunities and depriving them of a significant part of their life prospects. Insufficient attention of the state to the problems of youth as a social group, imitation by officials of vigorous activity to create unviable youth projects and movements, a changing system of values, youth demands, dissatisfaction with the real opportunities provided by the state and society to young people, pushing some young people to look for a better life outside their own. Fatherland (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Dynamics of indicators of the migration balance in Kazakhstan, 2015-2019

Note: built by the author

A high dynamics of migration among young people is recorded in the republic. So, if in 2015 the migration balance was -1,456, then in 2019 it reached -5,301.

Another part of the youth, trying to somehow compensate for these problems, often find themselves in extremism, other types of illegal behavior, or show apathy for active social activity and go into parallel subcultures, alcoholism, drug addiction, virtual reality.

The problem of the professionalization of youth, the replenishment of young personnel in industries critical for the existence of the state, as well as the problem of uneven distribution of the population, including youth across the territory of the Republic of Kazakhstan, loss of control over labor migration processes, which makes it impossible for the harmonious and purposeful regional development of the Kazakh village, becomes chronic.

The presence of these problems is confirmed by the data of the study, which was conducted, according to which about 30% of the young people surveyed noted dissatisfaction with modern life in Kazakhstan. Given the current economic crisis, as well as the socio-economic consequences of many events, these figures may change upwards.

15% of the young people surveyed doubted the possibility of getting a good education or did not set themselves such a goal at all. The same indicator was revealed when assessing the opportunity to get a prestigious job, to achieve material prosperity. 55% assessed their ability to create their own business in the same way. 33% doubted their ability to make a professional, political or public career, and two-thirds of them did not set such a goal. These indicators, on the one hand, indicate that most of the youth hope and count on their own strength, on the other hand, a significant part of them do not believe in the opportunities and prospects that society and the state offer them.

A different picture is obtained when evaluating the efforts of the state to form an optimal state youth policy, which also indicates the expectations of Kazakhstani youth. 72% of the young

people surveyed did not believe or did not show confidence that the reforms in Kazakhstan are being carried out in the interests of youth and the future of the country. A third of the respondents did not show confidence that Kazakhstan would become a prosperous country, a powerful power with high international prestige during their lifetime.

17% of respondents showed dissatisfaction with their financial situation. 23% of the respondents denied "an honest life" as their target. At the same time, 47% did not see anything wrong with getting rich at the expense of other people.

About 10% of the young people interviewed admitted to occasional drug use or did not want to answer the question. 17% of the respondents allowed the use of drugs or treated this phenomenon indulgently. Even more tolerant attitude the respondents showed to drunkenness and alcoholism - 40%. About a third of the respondents admitted that they drink hard liquor. 16% expressed a tolerant attitude towards animal cruelty. A quarter of the respondents admitted that they had experience of giving bribes or did not want to answer the question. At the same time, two-thirds of the respondents showed a tolerant attitude towards this phenomenon.

E-cigarette use has also increased among young people and these trends are likely to continue as e-cigarettes continue to gain popularity. The attitude of young people to family values and family life, the state of morality in this area is characterized by the fact that the proportion of persons in unofficial marital relations has doubled. 20% of respondents admitted to using sexual relations to achieve selfish goals or did not want to answer the question. 46% admitted or showed tolerance towards this phenomenon. Half admitted adultery, 65% considered it acceptable to have an abortion. 32% tolerated homosexuality.

The state of morality among the youth is also evidenced by the fact that 38% of the young people surveyed did not see anything wrong with showing hostility towards representatives of other nationalities. 75% of the respondents allowed evasion from military service duties or showed a condescending attitude towards this phenomenon. 21% - allowed treason under certain circumstances, or treated this phenomenon indulgently.

70% of the respondents considered it possible to resist the police, 72% - embezzlement of found money, 83% - stowaways in public transport.

All the above data testify to the subjective attitude of the young people surveyed to the important, basic phenomena and values of everyday household and social life, which in a certain way can correlate with the behavior of young people and often really manifests itself in the youth environment, confirming the data obtained. All this forms the guidelines that state authorities and Kazakhstani society should be guided by in the process of improving the organizational structure for managing state youth policy programs at the regional level.

Modern society with its information technologies and huge flows of information, on the one hand, provides young people with significant opportunities for self-realization, at the same time, exposes young people to strong information pressure, which leads to far-reaching negative psychological, sociocultural and political consequences.

The main ways to improve the organizational structure of the management of state youth policy programs at the regional level, we consider the preparation of an action plan for the implementation of the foundations of the state youth policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan for the period up to 2025.

An analysis of the structure of the Plan indicates that the state's efforts are concentrated around several areas of activity:

- improvement of the normative legal base of the state youth policy;
- increasing the efficiency of upbringing and development of youth;
- education of youth in various fields;
- introducing young people to a healthy lifestyle, physical education and sports;
- formation of correct ecological behavior and culture of safe life activity;

- improving the socio-economic situation of the youth of the Republic of Kazakhstan and increasing the degree of their involvement in the socio-economic life of the country;
- creating favorable conditions for young families aimed at increasing the birth rate, forming the values of family culture and the image of a successful young family, supporting young families;
- information support for the implementation of the Fundamentals of the State Youth Policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan for the period up to 2025.

A factor that amplifies these threats, as well as influencing almost all aspects of public life, are unfavorable demographic processes in Kazakhstani society that directly affect young people (Figure 2).

Figure 2 - Adverse factors affecting young people

Note: built by the author based on the source.

The planned measures to improve the legal regulation of the sphere of state youth policy should be aimed, first of all, at the development of methodological tools for statistical observation, the implementation of various areas of state youth policy, the development of student sports, as well as the introduction of a program-target principle for the implementation of state youth policy . This is important for increasing the specificity of the planned activities and developing mechanisms for the implementation of the goals and objectives of the Fundamentals of the State Youth Policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan. However, a certain problem is the rather low status level of the legal framework governing the state youth policy in the Republic of Kazakhstan. Until now, in our country there is no full-fledged law that summarizes the various areas of the state youth policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan (for example, the law "On Youth"). At the same time, in other countries, such regulations have long been adopted and, to a certain extent, implement the functions assigned to them. So in the Federal Republic of Germany, several similar laws have been adopted: "On the Protection of Youth" (2003), "On the Protection of Youth at Work", "On the Juvenile Court", the law "On Assistance to Children and Youth" (1991), which replaced the previously existing law of 1961 "On charitable assistance to youth", as well as other regulatory legal acts. Also in Germany, there is a state agreement of the federal lands "On the protection of human dignity and on the protection of young people in the field of broadcasting and telecommunications carriers" . Therefore, the development and adoption of such a law in Kazakhstan could well form the basis of measures to improve the legal regulation of the sphere of state youth policy.

There is also a need for active implementation of a public audit of the adopted and currently in force, as well as the normative legal acts being developed in the field of state youth

policy.

Activities of the Plan for creating conditions for the upbringing and development of youth contains 4 points aimed at conducting educational activities, as well as the development of youth tourism. A positive aspect of the content of this section of the plan is the emphasis on the education of patriotism and identity, knowledge about one's country and native land, interethnic and interfaith harmony.

However, the very small volume of the section of the plan raises questions. Also, the proposed activities themselves are not specific enough and poorly developed. There are no measures to form infrastructure for development, organization of leisure, sports of youth.

A serious shortcoming is still the complete absence of mention of labor education, involvement in the labor activity of students of secondary educational institutions, the need to teach simple basic specialties and skills. The same applies to the creation of infrastructure for the implementation of labor education.

Also, a lot of questions are caused by the lack of attention to the formation of a system of subjects that should implement the goals and objectives of the state youth policy.

The activities of the Plan for the development of educational work with youth are aimed at forming elements of self-government in educational institutions, raising the level of humanitarian, legal, financial knowledge, as well as knowledge about the history and traditions of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

The proposed activities of this section cause a feeling of lack of integrity of the approach to the formation of the worldview of young people, as well as their insufficiently close relationship with the content of the educational process.

The activities of the Plan for the formation of healthy lifestyle values, the creation of conditions for the physical development of young people, the formation of an environmental culture, and the improvement of the culture of life safety of young people do not sufficiently take into account the latest challenges of the modern information society, and also do not contain measures to prevent such widespread problems among young people as drunkenness and drug addiction, the formation of computer addiction, the growth of sexually transmitted diseases, the involvement of minors in socially dangerous destructive groups and the formation of ideals and models of socially dangerous behavior in adolescents and young people, etc.

The activities of the Plan to create conditions for the realization of the potential of youth in the socio-economic sphere are aimed at promoting youth employment and supporting young professionals, reviving the development of student groups, expanding opportunities for self-realization and development of young people living in rural areas, as well as developing international youth cooperation.

At the same time, events for the development and popularization of student sports would look more appropriate in the section under the title. "Formation of the values of a healthy lifestyle, creation of conditions for the physical development of young people, the formation of an ecological culture, and an increase in the level of a culture of safety for the life of young people".

Also, the ways of solving the tasks set in this section of the plan should contain measures to overcome the significant discrepancy in the starting conditions of young people, due to various factors, primarily social and material. In addition, the tasks in this area require serious measures aimed at changing legislation, providing serious benefits for young people entering the labor force for the first time, which, of course, will require significant material and financial support.

Perhaps we could also talk about the creation of special youth labor protection bodies, which should operate at the regional level and be formed from representatives of employers, workers, regional employment and health services, representatives of youth organizations, as well as youth affairs bodies.

The activities of the Plan for creating favorable conditions for young families aimed at increasing the birth rate, forming the values of family culture and the image of a successful young family, supporting young families contain only 2 points to improve the living conditions of young families and young professionals living in rural areas, as well as to stimulate the birth of the 2nd and subsequent children in families. It should be noted that all young specialists need to improve their living conditions, especially those who get a job outside their permanent place of residence, i.e. where they are needed. Without this, it is impossible to ensure the uniform development of remote Kazakhstani regions in the light of recent tasks to shift the priority of socio-economic development from the center to the regions of the Republic of Kazakhstan. In accordance with this task, other sections of the Plan should contain measures aimed at strengthening the family, introducing family values into the public consciousness, forming a system for preventing threats to the reproductive health of young people, and introducing parental universal education. The solution to this problem has a complex solution - from using the capabilities of educational institutions to attracting resources from electronic media.

Many tasks in the field of supporting a young family, which should be set in the content of the Fundamentals of the State Youth Policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan for the period up to 2025, were not reflected in the Action Plan.

The activities of the Plan for information support for the implementation of the Fundamentals of the State Youth Policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan for the period up to 2025 can be assessed as quite relevant and corresponding to the meaning of the tasks for information support of the state youth policy. At the same time, the means of mass communication should play a leading role in shaping the consciousness of citizens and, above all, young people. In the difficult conditions of the modern, rapidly changing world, as well as the growing dangers of a global scale, it is necessary to radically increase the importance of public interests regarding individual egoistic needs, which are actively cultivated in the media and mass culture today.

Speaking about the information support for the implementation of the goals of youth policy, in addition to the introduction of traditional family values, it is necessary to focus on highlighting and introducing the values of labor creative activity in the interests of one's family, Kazakhstani society and the state. There is a need to implement the restrictions and self-restrictions of the propaganda of values that destroy national and state identity, causing obvious harm to social stability, opposing various social groups of the population, introducing destructive life scenarios into the minds of Kazakhstani citizens, including youth, destructive life scenarios (dependency, unrestrained consumption and the desire to get rich quick). We are talking about the purposeful formation of mechanisms for both state and public control, as well as state and public regulation of this sphere, especially in those information segments that are financed from the state budget or use the material, political, informational capabilities of the state.

You can also generally note the complete absence of references to the volumes and mechanisms for financing state youth policy measures, which may be spelled out in the content of future federal targeted programs. However, since the financing of this sphere in the Republic of Kazakhstan has always depended on the action of numerous factors and has been a variable value, it would be quite a reasonable measure to legislate the quantitative framework for such financing.

The main principle of the state youth policy at the moment is the formation by the state and society of conditions for the free and most complete implementation and implementation of the creative potential of young people, providing the younger generation with the opportunity to become full-fledged citizens of their state not in the future, but today, to have real access to the adoption various kinds of responsible decisions that concern both young people and the whole society.

Thus, an effective model of the state youth policy is, first of all, the integration of ideas

about the conditions, goals, priority areas, forms and mechanisms, as well as the criteria for the effectiveness of the implementation of state policy regarding the younger generation. The effectiveness of the state youth policy in Kazakhstan is determined by the main parameters of the model of its implementation - the elaboration of the legal framework of the state youth policy, its most priority areas, the systematic organization of the activities of the main subjects of the state youth policy, as well as the adequacy of its resource support.

The main mechanisms for implementing the state youth policy at the regional level are as follows:

- program-targeted;
- regulatory and legal;
- financial and investment;
- structural and organizational.

Given the trends in the socio-political and socio-economic development of the Republic of Kazakhstan in the medium term, the state youth policy in Kazakhstan should be implemented in the following priority areas: development of the creative activity of the younger generation; involvement of young people in social practice, informing them about potential development opportunities; integration of young people who find themselves in a difficult life situation into the life and activities of modern society. At the same time, it is necessary to continue studying the best regional practices in the field of youth policy in order to implement their experience and correct existing shortcomings. In order to eliminate the current weaknesses in youth policy at the regional level, it is necessary to quickly adopt laws of the Republic of Kazakhstan on youth and youth policy, strengthen the current status of state youth policy as an independent direction of the state policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan, ensure a settlement in the field of state youth policy by the top political leadership of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

Conclusions. As you know, young people are the most active, mobile, open to innovation part of the population, which is a socially significant strategic resource for the development of a single city or the entire state, since the younger generation today is already becoming a kind of sign of the era, various phenomena of youth culture begin to cause quite a wide public response. In recent years, interest in youth and youth policy has grown so much that experts are already starting to talk about a “new youth era” - an era when young people are able to change the nature of world culture directly, and the “idea of youth” becomes the most sought-after product of the global market. But the youth policy in our state is a value, although significant, but still unstable. Laws are adopted and repealed, state bodies for the implementation of state youth policy are established today, and tomorrow they are liquidated, funding is opened and immediately closed.

So, the consistency, as well as the interdependence of these mechanisms, the systematic nature of their action ensures the effectiveness of the implementation of the state youth policy in our state.

Thus, we can say that the content of the Action Plan for the implementation of the Fundamentals of the State Youth Policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan for the period up to 2025 generally corresponds to the ideas laid down in the base document, but does not fully reflect the goals and objectives set in the Fundamentals of the State Youth Policy which in the future may lead to the emasculation of its content and will not bring the planned results.

Therefore, it is necessary to expand the scope of the Plan's activities, bringing them into line with the goals and objectives of the Fundamentals of State Youth Policy. In particular, it is necessary to pay attention to the following proposals that could increase the effectiveness of the policy of the Kazakh state in relation to youth:

- development and adoption of a federal law summarizing various areas of the state youth policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan;

- development of a mechanism for public audit of adopted and currently in force, as well as the normative legal acts being developed in the field of state youth policy;
- raise the status of the federal agency for youth affairs to the level of a ministry, transferring to its sphere of responsibility the functions of the federal agency for tourism and, possibly, tasks for the physical education of young people;
- development and implementation of a system of benefits, material, social and psychological support for young people from low-income families or those in circumstances that cause the need for social support in obtaining vocational education and employment;
- creation at the regional level of special bodies for the protection of youth labor, including representatives of employers, employees, regional employment and health services, representatives of youth organizations and youth affairs bodies;
- expand the scope of benefits, including housing, for young professionals in order to increase the motivation of young people for professional and personal self-realization in those areas and regions that today need an influx of young personnel;
- expand the range of measures aimed at strengthening the family, introducing family values into the public consciousness, forming a system for preventing threats to the reproductive health of young people, introducing a network of organizational structures for the implementation of the ideas of parental universal education.

First of all, it is necessary to concentrate all the efforts of the state around several areas of activity:

- improvement of the normative legal base of the state youth policy;
- increasing the efficiency of upbringing and development of youth; education of youth in various fields;
- introducing young people to a healthy lifestyle, physical education and sports;
- formation of correct ecological behavior and culture of safe life activity;
- improving the socio-economic situation of the youth of the Republic of Kazakhstan and increasing the degree of their involvement in the socio-economic life of the country;
- creating favorable conditions for young families aimed at increasing the birth rate, forming the values of family culture and the image of a successful young family, supporting young families;
- information support for the implementation of the foundations of the state youth policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan for the period up to 2025.

The planned measures to improve the legal regulation of the sphere of state youth policy are aimed primarily at developing methodological tools for statistical observation, implementing various areas of state youth policy, developing student sports, as well as introducing a program-target principle for implementing state youth policy. This is important for increasing the specificity of the planned activities and developing mechanisms for the implementation of the goals and objectives of the foundations of the state youth policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan. However, a certain problem is the rather low status level of the legal framework governing the state youth policy in our country.

The core of the problem of the expediency and effectiveness of the state youth policy is the contradiction between the intensification of practical actions of associations in this industry and the absence of certain changes in the position of the vast majority of the young generation of Kazakhstan. The effectiveness of the domestic model of the state youth policy is determined by the correspondence of its directions to the most urgent needs of the younger generation and the adequacy of their resource provision, as well as the impact of the policy being pursued on improving the position of the younger generation in the country, the dynamics and quality of its social and socio-economic activity.

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Prospects for the tenge as a regional currency in the EAEU space

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Abstract: The regional currency is a factor of the highest degree of integration of the EAEU countries, it is worth considering that against the influence of external factors, the possibility of transformation of the tenge from national to inter-regional currency status in the Eurasian Economic Union space increases. The article examines the opportunities and risks of the Kazakh tenge gaining the status of a regional currency, taking into account the state and competitiveness of the country's economy among the states of the Eurasian Economic Commonwealth and external factors.

Keywords: regional currency, EAEU, IMU, trade, exchange rate, supranational currency.

The relevance of the research topic stems from the following aspects. The geopolitical situation is such that Kazakhstan's largest trading partner is under economic sanctions, which have led to strong inflation and a depreciation of the tenge, putting great pressure on the interests of the national economy and complicating issues of diversifying its structure and transport communications. Payments within the EAEU are made either in roubles or US dollars.

And in the economic literature, experts raise the question of the feasibility of introducing supranational currencies or switching to bilateral cooperation. For example, in the article "Prospects of the ruble as a regional reserve currency: a theoretical aspect". [1], S. Narkevich considers the possibility of establishing the Russian ruble as a regional currency. Other economists refer to the positive aspects of this approach as reducing the cost of converting incoming foreign currencies, reducing currency risk, increasing the attractiveness of the economy and investment within the country, and confirming the country's position on the world stage as a regional currency [2].

According to third experts, the currency chosen as a regional (reserve) currency should at least have stability, backed by a correspondingly strong economy producing products with high added value [3]. This additionally means the presence in the country of qualified specialists, innovations and new technologies, high quality of life, which will be attractive to other states. Let us consider what opportunities Kazakhstan and its national currency, the tenge, have to become a regional currency in the Eurasian economic community.

First and foremost, it is worth defining a "currency area" as a geographically, politically or economically connected state which uses a single currency or a series of currencies whose exchange rates are invariably fixed in relation to one another. This exchange rate changes proportionally and synchronously with other world currencies. Two balances are considered in order to achieve an optimum currency area: the internal balance and the external balance of

each aspiring country. The internal balance is the ratio of inflation to unemployment. The external balance looks at many economic factors: the stability of the exchange rate; trade turnover; and the state of the country's current account, at the risks of solvency and reliability.

The theory of the optimum currency area was first shown in the 1960s in the work of Mandell and MacKinnon. Mandell supported the idea of a worldwide gold standard system. MacKinnon advocated a fixed exchange rate between the major industrialised countries - the US, West Germany and Japan.

By 2025, the EAEU plans to create a single financial market and a smooth transition to the settlement of trade transactions in Russian roubles. The shares of each national currency in trade with the EEU countries are presented below.

Table 1- Settlements within the EEU: shares of national currencies

Country-export/import EAEU	Predominant Settlement Currency by Decrease
Russian Federation	Russian Rouble - Dollar - Euro - Tenge - Others
Republic of Belarus	Russian rouble-dollar-euro-others-rouble RB
Republic of Kazakhstan	Rouble-dollar-euro-tenge
Kyrgyzstan	Dollar-rouble-tenge-euro
Note: Compiled by the authors on the basis of the source- [4]	

Today, about 70% of trade transactions are conducted in the national currencies of the participating countries (mainly the Russian rouble - 71.6% in 2022, whereas in the tenge - 1%) [4]. In the structure of the external balance, the Russian rouble also has a high share in settlements.

Table 2 - Currency structure of payments for exports and imports of goods and services between EAEU member states (in %)

Reciprocal payments by EEU member states	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
in Armenian drams	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,0	0,0
in Belarusian roubles	0,4	0,3	0,5	0,4	0,4	0,3	0,3	0,4	0,2
in tenge	0,4	0,5	1,1	0,7	0,9	0,7	1,0	1,4	1,4
in catfish	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,1	0,1	0,0	0,0
in Russian rubles	61,8	67,4	68,0	74,1	74,9	72,7	72,4	71,6	71,5
in US dollars	30,3	26,3	25,0	19,3	18,3	19,2	19,4	20,0	19,5
in euros	6,8	5,2	5,1	5,2	5,2	6,8	6,6	6,4	6,7
in other currencies	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,6
Note: Compiled by the authors on the basis of the source- [4-7]									

In the context of sanctions, Kazakhstan's neutrality in controversial political issues is an advantage when considering the promotion of the tenge as a single means of payment in the EAEU countries. The Republic of Kazakhstan has the economic and financial potential to develop domestic market diversification, to actively attract investment, and to build a financial system that is integrated into the global community.

With all the positives, there are also significant disadvantages of Kazakhstani currency. They are as follows:

- 1) The dependence of the economy on world energy prices and the impact on inflation;
- 2) A rather low level of production of high value-added goods. The share of manufacturing in GDP according to 2021 is 13% (an increase of 3.9%) [8];
- 3) there was insufficient control over the process of capital export from the country, which did not work for the country's economy.

There is no getting around the issue of state regulation of the national currency, as suggested by Kazakh economists it is not entirely effective, where the main instrument of regulation is the management of the base rate.

Below is a parallel to the relationship between the base rate and the inflation rate.

Figure 1: RK base rate 2015 - 2022 [9-10]

The similar trend of these indicators shows the weakness and dependence of the country's economy on energy resources. Monetary policy reacts more to external factors rather than preventing them, leading to inflation and depreciation of the national currency.

The dynamics of the exchange rate of the tenge against the US dollar are discussed below.

Figure 2: Dollar/Tenge exchange rate [11]

Generally, the establishment and process of integrating one currency as a reserve currency requires preparatory work and compliance with international criteria

The theory of optimal currency zones does not deny the possibility of establishing two currencies (in our case, the tenge and the ruble) that are maximally connected and synchronous to each other. Consider the possibility of conducting all payments and relations in tenge or ruble. Next, let us consider the basic criteria according to Mandel:

Figure 3: Basic criteria for a currency area

1) *Relative economic size, degree of openness and trade integration.* Russia's GDP for 2021 was \$1,771.9 billion. Kazakhstan's GDP as of the same date is \$191.3 billion. Trade between the countries is active, with the countries having leading exports of raw materials.

2) *The flexibility of economic structures.* In the short term, exchange rate volatility can affect changes in price levels. By adopting a common currency between the two countries, they will insure themselves against strong surges or a severe downturn. This would be done by a fixed ratio of the two currencies.

3) *The mobility factor.* It will be easier for the state to regulate relative prices if the three main factors of production (labour, land, capital) have sufficient mobility. Of the three factors, labour and capital have nonzero mobility. This is because if there is a crisis in any of the countries in the currency area, people and capital can move freely.

4) *Ability to absorb shocks.* For this criterion, it is better to consider a long-term perspective. When macroeconomic shocks occur, states that have more flexibility and mobility will have an advantage. In this case, if Russia and Kazakhstan are in the same currency area, there is more potential to successfully overcome and pass through these shocks. This criterion shows the stability of the exchange rate within the currency area.

5) *Homogeneity of the economy.* Kazakhstan and Russia have a more homogeneous economic structure. Both countries are oriented towards extraction and processing of raw materials, etc. Overall homogeneity in the transition to a common currency is important so that shocks from one country are not transmitted to the other.

6) *Access to support resources.* This is necessary to maintain the functionality of one

currency area state. If one has reduced flexibility or homogeneity to survive from this situation, support from the other state will be important, in terms of transferring resources to compensate for unemployment and others.

7) *Absolute stability*. This is expressed in terms of the stability of the underlying currency. Countries sharing a single currency will coordinate the same monetary policy, or as similar as possible, to ensure stability and movement in one common direction. If Kazakhstan agrees to the introduction of a single currency, Kazakhstan will most likely have to adopt the description of Russia's monetary policy model, but given the world situation, it is undesirable for Kazakhstan to aspire to a single currency area, which could adversely affect its economy.

In order to examine the sustainability of the economy in more detail, and hence the tenge, we consider the impact of key macroeconomic indicators on it.

Table 3 - Main Macroeconomic Indicators of Kazakhstan, million USD

	Y1	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	X6
Year	GDP	Import	Export	Inflation	Unemployment	Balance of payments	Currency
2011	192 630	36 905,8	84 335,9	8,30%	5,40%	14110	146,654
2012	208 000	46 358,4	86 448,8	5,10%	5,30%	1079,1	149,151
2013	236 630	48 805,6	84 700,4	5,80%	5,20%	-117,8	152,203
2014	221 420	41 295,5	79 459,8	6,70%	5,10%	5957,4	179,481
2015	184 390	30 567,7	45 955,8	6,70%	5%	-5463,7	222,902
2016	137 280	25 376,7	36 736,9	8,29%	4,90%	-8885	342,051
2017	166 810	29 599,6	48 503,3	7,22%	4,90%	-5389,5	326,222
2018	179 340	33 658,5	61 111,2	5,43%	4,80%	-51,7	345,05
2019	181 670	39 709,3	58 065,6	4,90%	4,80%	-8282,2	383,063
2020	171 080	38 929,1	47 540,0	7,50%	4,90%	-7589,8	413,671
2021	190 810	41 415,4	60 321,0	8,40%	4,90%	-7862,5	426,206

As might be expected, the volume of GDP clearly responds to all changes in production volumes both inside and outside the country.

Table 4 - Correlation matrix of RC indicators

	GDP	Import	Export	Inflation	Unemployment	Balance of payments	Currency
GDP	1						
Import	0,8553	1					
Export	0,8596	0,7910	1				
Inflation	-0,4137	-0,4262	-0,3325	1			
Unemployment	0,5873	0,4677	0,7878	0,0455	1		
Balance of payments	0,5283	0,2932	0,7819	0,0093	0,7909	1	
Currency	-0,6541	-0,3601	-0,7375	0,2198	-0,8812	-0,7611	1

But most of all, GDP depends on the country's export and import indicators. The indicator of imports and exports, the two variables X has a correlation coefficient of 0.79. This indicates multicollinearity. This is not good, as they do not have a separate effect on variable Y.

The impact of all indicators is presented in more detail in Table 5 below:

Table 5 - Regression analysis

<i>Regression statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0,986199
R-square	0,972588
Normalized R-square	0,93147
Standard error	7095,532
Observations	11

The R-squared coefficient is 0.97. Therefore, we can be more confident about the quality of the model.

Analysis of variance

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance of F</i>
Regression	6	7,1E+09	1,19E+09	23,6535503	0,004345429
Remains	4	2E+08	50346577		
Total	10	7,3E+09			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t-statistics</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Y-intersection	822274,4	184167,4938	4,4648184	0,01112	310943,49	1333605,36	310943,4853	1333605,359
IMPORT	3,908794	1,082523324	4,4648184	0,02254	0,9032278	6,91436101	0,903227845	6,914361012
EXPORT	0,000594	0,715815761	4,4648184	0,99938	-1,9868289	1,98801746	-	1,988017456
							1,986828873	
INFLATION	700212,2	302412,1375	4,4648184	0,08155	-139418,53	1539842,87	-	1539842,869
							139418,5283	
unemployment	-1,5E+07	3896103,589	4,4648184	0,01887	-	-4042648,4	-	-4042648,44
					25677284		25677283,92	
BALANCE OF PAYMEN	0,767323	1,065339635	4,4648184	0,51121	-2,1905336	3,72518045	-	3,72518045
							2,190533578	
Currency	-287,949	62,58759323	4,4648184	0,01003	-461,71991	-114,17788	-	-114,177877
							461,7199111	

Let's look at the Y and X coefficients of the intersection. With the first variable, the coefficient is 3.9. This is the level of dependence of GDP on imports. This coefficient is very high. The dependence on exports is much lower - 0.0005. That is, imports play the biggest influence than exports. The next indicator with a very strong influence is inflation - 700212.2. This is a huge indicator for this coefficient. The unemployment rate has a negative value. That is, it affects GDP in an opposite proportional way. If unemployment rises, GDP falls; if unemployment falls, GDP rises. The level of dependence on the balance of payments is also good - 0.76. And also the level of dependence on the exchange rate of tenge to dollar is negative. Exchange rate goes up - GDP goes down, tenge goes down - GDP goes up. The impact of the last variable is quite significant (-287.9).

In order to understand the trend of Kazakhstan's GDP and how volatile or stable it is, we used the moving average method.

Table 6 - Values of moving average analysis

№	Value
1	-
2	-
3	212 420
4	222 016,67
5	214 146,67
6	181 030
7	162 826,67
8	161 143,33
9	175 940
10	177 363,33
11	181 186,67

Figure 4: Graph and forecast of GDP by moving average

As the graph shows, the trend of the actual GDP indicator and its projected value correlate with each other. In order to determine the possibility of change in Kazakhstan's GDP indicator, a forecast for the next 3 years is given. The coefficient of approximation of the actual indicator shows a high result only by polynomial trend line - 0.293. And the forecast is positive, an upward trend is expected. If we talk about the forecast of the predicted data values, the situation is worse. The trend line here shows a decline, and has an approximation coefficient of 0.58, which suggests that the trend line is more reliable. Nevertheless, given the performance of recent years, and given that the actual value was higher than the predicted value, there are hopes for better results.

Thus, GDP is influenced by both exports and imports, which confirms the strong dependence of the economy on external factors. This requires a reorientation of the economy towards the development of industrial production.

Should the Tenge be recognised as a regional currency, it is possible to assess the positives and negatives of this decision.

Table 7 - SWOT analysis of the Kazakh tenge

Strengths- Tenge and RK	Opportunities-at a regional currency
Decreasing confidence in the Russian rouble,hence the outlook for the tenge	According to E. Abel and B. Bernanke - simplified movement of goods, labour and capital. Reducing currency risk (addressed in international treaties) Dependence on other countries is reduced.
Weaknesses-Tenge and RK	Threats-at a regional currency
Weak purchasing power of the population Weak share of economic diversification Dependence on other countries and oil prices	Foreign investment will seek to buy assets within Kazakhstan, which in the long term maylead to excessive foreign capital in the economy The single currency does not benefit all countries in the same way due to different levels of economies, often leading to balance
	sheet deficits in weaker economies, leading to commitments from more stable member states
Note: compiled by the authors	

The threats from becoming a reserve currency are most fully disclosed in the "Triffin Paradox" theory, which consists of threats of a long-term nature. That is, despite the fact that reserve currency is issued in large volumes to support transactions on trading floors without reference to the gold reserve-there is a real risk that over time the currency should lose a certain degree of confidence in it. If we consider the Jamaican monetary system, i.e. the detachment of the exchange rate from the gold reserve, the Triffin Paradox persists in image: to support international level transactions, the central bank issues more units of money into circulation, which in turn has the effect of raising inflation. The solution lies in exports exceeding imports to ensure stability - also an indicator of a leading economy, but this phenomenon cannot be ensured due to the rising value of the currency, which affects the attractiveness of domestic goods. In this case, the paradox is that a country with a strong economy, which allowed it to become a reserve currency issuer, suffers from the "advantage" of having its national currency recognized as a regional currency [12].

Japan, for example, has a policy of keeping the exchange rate under control, while also being one of the world's major reserve currencies.

The national currency is an attribute of state independence. The country's first president proposed the introduction of a supranational currency, Altyn. In fact, the transition to a single currency is an indicator of the highest degree of integration. Not all EEU countries are yet ready to give up some of their sovereignty, so this issue will be on the agenda for a long time to come.

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IMPACT OF DIGITALIZATION OF HEALTH CARE ON THE ECONOMY

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Abstract. The article considers and defines the concept of digitalization and the health system. The main goal of digital transformations has been formulated, the main sub-goals of healthcare digitalization have been identified. The main directions and activities already undertaken or still planned are listed. Their evaluation at the conference was made.

Key words: digitalization, healthcare system, cost minimization, accessibility of medical care, telemedicine, coronavirus infection, demographic crisis.

Over the past decades, the world has witnessed the global modernization of the usual forms of production, business, accounting, auditing, management, marketing and other major economic areas. This is due to the development of information technologies in all socio-economic spheres.

Digitalization, as a modern trend, is perceived by experts as the latest fashion. It is important to follow trends. And one of the main trends of recent times is the Digital economy, which contributes to the successful realization of the opportunities of both the state and society.

In simple words, economic digitalization is a process of transition from tangible media to intangible (digital), or the transition from offline to online. Most often, the digitalization of the economy is e-commerce or e-business, a characteristic feature of which is electronic payments.

In a relatively short period of time, digitalization has penetrated into the daily life of every person. It is difficult to imagine modern services and procedures that would be impossible to produce online.

Digitalization is a process that involves the use of digital technologies and digitized data to transform business processes, business models, and business operations. [1, p.150]

A characteristic feature of the 21st century is the global and full-scale digitalization of all sectors of society. The technological leap that has taken place over the past 50-60 years has significantly facilitated and improved everyday operations.

The healthcare system, not being an exception, is also subject to digital transformations, and, therefore, needs constant monitoring. Thus, since healthcare functions in close relationship with the economy, the relevance of the study is confirmed by its practical significance.

Healthcare is part of the health protection system, one of the branches of the social sphere that ensures the realization of citizens' rights to provide them with adequate medical care (medical prevention, treatment, medical rehabilitation).

"The health system is a set of interrelated activities that promote health and are carried out at home, in educational institutions, in the workplace, in communities, in the physical and psychosocial environment, as well as in the health sector and related sectors" (WHO definition).[2]

Within the framework of this work, the processes of digitalization of the healthcare sector will be described, as well as the degree of influence of these processes on the country's economy will be revealed.

Despite the fact that digitalization is a process characteristic of the vast majority of spheres of modern society, its main goal is the same in every sphere.

The goal of digitalization is to minimize the costs associated with the production of goods (services). In addition, by means of digital transformation, optimization of the provision of services

is achieved, as a result of which the level of service increases and the organization increases the degree of customer orientation.

The healthcare system has come a long way, which has been characterized by significant changes and improvements. Specialists in the field of medicine in the past could only dream that high technologies, most of which are digital, will be used to diagnose and treat certain diseases in the future.

If earlier, a person had to personally contact a large number of authorities in order to get this or that certificate, now almost any service can be obtained without leaving home.

Digitalization of the healthcare system pursues several goals, among which there are both purely medical and economic:

1. Improving the quality of diagnosis of diseases of various complexity.
2. Treatment of complex diagnoses, rare diseases.
3. Reducing the cost of operating the system.
4. Increasing the availability of medical care.

To assess the degree of influence of digital processes in the healthcare system on the economy, it is necessary to familiarize yourself with the main directions of digitalization in this area, and then formulate the main vectors of influence on the economic system of the state.

In the Republic of Kazakhstan, the process of digitalization of all spheres, including healthcare, proceeded somewhat slower compared to Western countries, which are leaders in the issue of digital technologies. This fact is natural, since the specifics of the socio-political system that existed in our country for a long time slowed down processes that went beyond the ideological views of the system.

The process of digitalization of healthcare began in the 10th years of the 21st century, when it became possible to electronically record patients for an appointment with a doctor. In addition, the appearance of electronic patient records can also be attributed to the first manifestations of digitalization of healthcare, which significantly facilitated the work of medical workers.

The above-mentioned fact from the point of view of its impact on the economy can be characterized by the following conditional provisions:

firstly, the motivation of medical personnel has increased, who have freed up the time previously needed to maintain patient records. Consequently, more time was devoted to examination, diagnosis and treatment.

secondly, thanks to digital technologies, the management process of the medical institution has been facilitated.

thirdly, the use of mobile applications and wearable gadgets will save patients their time, which they can use for self-development or increase income.

Fourth, new jobs will be created for the implementation of healthcare digitalization programs. I will need qualified specialists in the field of IT-healthcare, which will solve the problem of unemployment in the economy;

Fifthly, in the era of paid medical services, undoubtedly these processes will lead to an increase in the profits of commercial organizations. Probably, here we have come to the main direction of the impact of digitalization of healthcare on the economy. The profit received by commercial organizations is taxed.

If we evaluate the impact of profit growth of commercial organizations on the economy of the state as a whole, one of the main functions of the state, performed by it from time immemorial – fiscal, involuntarily comes to mind.

The fiscal function of the state is one of the most important activities of the state, which consists in the formation and replenishment of the state treasury - the state budget, at the expense of taxes, as well as statutory financial fees, duties and payments. [3]

It is important to mention that every citizen of the Republic of Kazakhstan has the right to receive qualified medical care, including using modern digital technologies.

In this regard, there is the fact that every year, the Government lays down certain amounts in the budget intended for the implementation of State programs for the digitalization of healthcare. Expenses in this area are directed to the purchase of expensive equipment, software development, its maintenance and improvement, training and other related products and services. All this leads to entrepreneurial activity of the population, an increase in intellectual capital and, consequently, to the economic growth of the country.

Returning to the issue of the main digital transformations in the field of healthcare, the following can be distinguished:

1. Development and implementation of modern medical equipment. This category is quite broad, but within the framework of this work on assessing the impact of digitalization of healthcare, there is no need to dwell on it in detail.

2. Online consultation and diagnostics.

The second point has become especially popular recently. This fact is due to the fact that over the past three years, humanity has faced a pandemic of coronavirus infection. Covid-19 forced to rebuild almost all spheres of human activity. In this light, online consultations have become popular. The effectiveness of this type of medical services was manifested due to the remote treatment of people with limited mobility, elderly patients, as well as those infected with coronavirus.

The above-mentioned digital transformations, to a greater extent, have a positive impact on the economy of the state. As mentioned above, the effectiveness of doctors is growing. In addition, online consultations, being a paid medical service, serve as a source of replenishment of the state budget through taxes and fees.

The state's interest in digital transformations in the field of healthcare is illustrated by the adoption in 2013 of the State Program "Information Kazakhstan – 2020", in which the term "electronic health care" (e-health care) was introduced for the first time, it identified ways for further development of health informatization. In accordance with this program, it was planned that the introduction of ICT into the healthcare system would bring the quality of medical care to a new level for the population. E-health technologies will make it possible to monitor the population at a distance, better disseminate information among patients, and improve access to health care, especially in remote areas, for the disabled and the elderly.

An additional fact confirming the trend towards digitalization of healthcare is the projects being developed and implemented. These include the creation of a patient information cloud, telemedicine, the use of artificial intelligence, and others.

It is assumed that the above-mentioned measures in the field of digitalization in the health care system should contribute to the elimination, perhaps, of one of the socio-economic problems of modern Kazakhstan concerning the demographic crisis.

Confirmation of the existence of demographic problems in Kazakhstan is open statistical data from both domestic and foreign sources. One of the estimates looks like this.

In the world, the average life expectancy at birth is: 71.0 years (68.5 years for men and 73.5 years for women) The country with the highest total life expectancy is: Japan — 84.3 years, followed by Switzerland — 83.4 years and South Korea — 83.3 years. Kazakhstan is in the list at 94 positions with an indicator of 74 years. [5]

The disappointing position of Kazakhstan characterizes the crisis situation in the domestic healthcare system. And it is not at all surprising that the leaders are countries with a high degree of development of digital technologies.

An important aspect demonstrating the relationship between digital transformations and the economic system is the tourism sector. When choosing a country for travel, travel agencies recommend paying attention to such criteria as: the cost and duration of a visa, security, crime rate and possible diseases.

Of course, the activity of tourists visiting countries with high viral morbidity will be low. In addition, attentive tourists will also pay attention to the level of health care of the state they are going to visit. After all, cases when a traveler may need medical assistance are not excluded.

Consequently, digitalization of the medical sphere will improve the country's international position and make the healthcare system more reliable. As a result, the flow of tourists will increase, which will also contribute to economic growth.

In addition, medical tourism is quite popular in the world. The leaders in this field are Israel, Germany, and Switzerland. Since 2020, when the COVID-19 pandemic began in the world, the numbers have decreased significantly. However, they are not indicative, and are primarily related to the restriction of border crossing. [6]

A set of measures, proposed or already implemented, are aimed at solving the demographic problem. Telemedicine, "Connected Patient", high-tech medical equipment, the use of electronic medical records - all these measures pursue the following main goals, the unifying criterion of which is overcoming the demographic crisis:

1. Collection, systematization of data and processing of information about patients who receive medical care.
2. Reducing the number of medical errors
3. Availability of medical services.
4. Cost reduction.
5. Improving literacy and people's interest in their own health.

The state, like no other, is interested in preserving the life and health of the population. This is due to the fact that the existence of the state is impossible without an economically active population working and replenishing GDP.

Summarizing the above, it can be concluded that by paying attention to the development of digital transformations in the healthcare system, the state achieves the implementation of several system-forming goals that contribute to long-term socio-economic development.

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SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPLICATIONS OF THE WAR IN UKRAINE FOR THE EUROPEAN UNION

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Abstract. The purpose of this study is to identify the key implications of the war in Ukraine for the EU's socio-economic situation in a globalised world. The study demonstrates that the war in Ukraine represents an alarming humanitarian crisis and a serious economic shock. Asymmetric effects between countries due to the war will also include higher inflation and a decline in international trade over the next two years. The consequences of war will weigh not only on the material level but above all on the social level, as war results in thousands of deaths and increased emigration. The diagnosed consequences may remain relevant after the end of the conflict and should be taken into consideration in the formation of reconstruction strategies and policies in the EU and Ukraine.

Key words: crisis, growth, inflation, refugee, supply chains, war

Russia's invasion of Ukraine has plunged Europe into extreme economic uncertainty, exacerbating existing problems and forcing the European Commission to revise its pre-conflict assessments and make new forecasts for the coming years (Spring Forecasts) for the global and EU economies. The extent of the economic impact of the war is highly uncertain and depends crucially on its duration. The central scenario in the forecast for the world and EU economy assumes that geopolitical tensions will not normalise until the end of 2023. In addition to the specific impact on the European economy, the war in Ukraine has caused a severe shock to the entire global economy. International financial markets have also seen a rise in general inflation. Higher commodity prices are causing a significant negative trade shock in other areas. The worsening trade situation is further weakening global demand and reducing growth potential, increasing inflationary pressures. This shaped the purpose of this study to identify the key effects of the war in Ukraine on the EU's socio-economic situation in a globalised world.

Russia's invasion of Ukraine has created new disruptions in value chains and shifts EU trade to less efficient routes. Delays in the supply chain are worsening again. Therefore, with the outbreak of war, growth prospects for the EU economy have weakened and global inflationary pressures are increasing (global stagflation). The effects of the war have led to a situation of stagflation, a general weakening of economic growth with rising prices in all EU countries, and also had a profound impact on other macroeconomic variables. Economic forecasts and trends that were assumed before the invasion were turned upside down after the outbreak of war (Brondoni, 2022).

The war in Ukraine presents an alarming humanitarian crisis and a major economic shock. Before the war, the global trend of recovery from the pandemic was expected to continue in 2022 and 2023, thanks to supportive country policies, progress in vaccination campaigns and favourable financial conditions. At the end of 2021, the economic outlook for the OECD (2022) projected global GDP growth of 4.5% in 2022 and 3.2% in 2023. National data and indicators at the start of

2022 remained in line with this forecast. But just when it seemed that some of the supply chain problems seen since the pandemic began were beginning to subside, the outbreak of war in Ukraine caused a new negative shock to the global economy.

Ukraine has a very important influence on the world economy in commodity markets, where it plays a significant role in the supply of a range of commodities, such as wheat, corn, metals, neon and others. With the outbreak of war, the prices of many of these commodities rose sharply. A complete halt to wheat exports from Ukraine would lead to economic crises in some countries as well as humanitarian disasters with a dramatic increase in poverty and hunger (Ben Hassen and El Bilali, 2022). The war and related sanctions against Russia are already causing global disruption to trade and financial relations. Prior to the conflict, the fiscal stance in most countries was expected to become more restrictive in 2022 and 2023 due to the phasing out of pandemic-related support measures and some fiscal consolidation measures. Due to the impact of the conflict, these plans are already being revised. Near-term spending priorities include funding for refugee assistance in Europe and mitigating the impact of shocks to household and enterprise commodity and food prices, while in the medium term an increase in clean energy investments is likely.

As mentioned and highlighted in the OECD Economic Outlook June 2022, the Russian invasion of Ukraine is above all a humanitarian crisis affecting millions of people; there are tens of thousands of deaths and injuries and almost seven million people have already been forced to flee Ukraine to other European countries. The decline in production in Ukraine because of the conflict reduces demand for products from other countries and also directly reduces global economic activity. Rising commodity and energy prices lead to external shortages in many countries (Orhan, (2022).

Disruptions in agricultural exports of grain and fertilizers from Ukraine increase the risks to food security if alternative suppliers cannot be found. Trade dynamics are reduced due to a ban on exports to Russia, delays and difficulties with international payments. The EU has already imposed several bans on energy imports from Russia, an embargo on coal, gas and oil imports from Russia has been agreed, and the Russian state has in turn stopped exporting gas to some EU countries. Early March. The closure of businesses in China and the war have increased delivery times for suppliers and waiting times for goods. Many air and sea shipments, as well as rail transport, were suspended.

Inflation has been rising globally for more than a year, albeit unevenly across states, given the varying severity of the pandemic, the policy response to Covid and the varying patterns of economic activity. Hopes of a rapid slowdown in the ongoing inflationary surge in 2021 and early 2022 have been dashed with the onset of conflict. Worsening supply problems and sharp rises in energy and food prices mean that consumer price inflation will reach higher levels and peak later than expected. Prices are rising faster than household incomes, leading to a deterioration in real disposable income. Core and core inflation have also been revised upwards in 2023. Due to the fact that inflation in most OECD countries will now be observed for a longer period, it is assumed that central banks will raise interest rates faster than previously expected.

High-frequency data also shows the negative impact of conflict on growth in almost all countries in 2022-2023. Global GDP growth is expected to slow to 3 per cent in 2022 and output is only expected to increase by 2 per cent in the period up to the fourth quarter of 2022. In the OECD countries, economic growth is estimated to slow to 2.7 percent in 2022 and 1.6 percent in 2023, with output in 2023 around 2 percent lower than previously assumed. Nevertheless, private consumption at the OECD level is estimated to increase by around 2% in 2022-2023 with a declining savings rate and sustained employment growth (Mariotti, 2022).

Russia's invasion represents a conflict with undeniable global economic and geopolitical consequences unlike any other conflict in the last 75 years. World GDP is expected to lose about

one trillion dollars in the next two years, according to the International Monetary Fund 2022, affecting mainly EU countries, to a greater extent Russia and Ukraine, but also the US. Other regions of the world, which are strong in commodities production, will, on the contrary, benefit in terms of GDP growth. Asymmetric effects between countries because of the war will also include higher inflation and a decline in international trade over the next two years. In developing countries, exports will fall by 3.2% and consumer prices will rise by 4.6%, while in developed countries they will rise by less than half. Although inflationary pressures are already being felt, lower growth rates will be noticeable in the longer term. We will also see an increase in public expenditure to help the people of Ukraine and other countries affected by the conflict and the rearmament process.

The consequences of the war will weigh not only on the material level, but above all on the human level, as the war results in thousands of deaths and the emigration of many people, which has serious consequences on the social level as well (Kyzym et al., 2022). Not to mention the pre-existing food shortages that the war exacerbates in a number of developing countries. Prior to the conflict, it is estimated that more than 800 million people worldwide were already facing hunger. With war, disruptions in agricultural exports from Russia and Ukraine could cause supply shocks in many developing countries, such as Africa, the Middle East and Central Asia, and exacerbate rising food prices. Coordinated action is needed to monitor and mitigate these risks by providing food and assistance to facilitate planting and transportation of crops, refraining from restrictions on exports of food and other agricultural products, and removing logistical barriers that limit food supplies to importing countries.

The effects of the war will persist and have an impact on the economy and human level for several more years, in addition to the immediate effects that can already be seen. Effective action is still needed to maintain open borders and provide technical and financial assistance, as well as to implement the necessary actions to address the problems arising from the war in Ukraine. Developing economies will be particularly exposed to these challenges caused by the war and the ongoing pandemic. In this case, it will be necessary to consider not only the timeframe in wartime, but also the period when the conflict is over and the economic impact in peacetime is observed.

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FACTORS SHAPING THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM SERVICES IN MOUNTAIN REGIONS

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ABSTRACT

When analyzing the concept of tourism, we come to the conclusion that every person who has this leisure time, as a social group or individually, as a traveler, or for the purpose of leaving the place of residence for not less than 24 hours in search of work (except for trips with a change of permanent residence), people contains the relations between In our opinion, a person who travels for leisure is called a tourist. In some cases, any person traveling abroad is registered as a tourist, regardless of the purpose of their visit. In our opinion, this should be considered a wrong approach. Non-leisure travelers cannot be included in this group. Therefore, serious consideration should be given to accounting for this at the border.

KEY WORDS: tourism, mountain, circulation, development

INTRODUCTION

In the economic literature, it is said that the demand for the tourism product directly depends on the motivation and behavior of the individual. This idea suggests that increasing the pleasure and interest in travel is the main factor driving the demand for tourism products [5, p. 19]. This concept was mostly created by P. Bernekker. According to R.M. Gasimov, buying goods related to tourism is an ordinary human need and is considered as an action performed during a trip.

A number of scholars pay attention to the theoretical and methodological elements of tourism, which should be specially noted. They are V.A. Kvartalnov, V.I. Azer, A.G. Alirzayev, R.M. Gasimov and other local researchers [2].

When studying tourism from a theoretical-methodological point of view, we will see the importance of a set of factors that influence its organization and development. There are two main points to consider here:

At the initial stage, socio-economic factors attract attention. Such factors include the production of different types of services, their volume and structure. The basis of the influence of socio-economic factors is the formation of personal and public demand. Production and sale of products (services) is carried out in the tourism sector as well as in other areas that ensure economic development. It goes without saying that this is also evaluated as a component of the circulation of total revenues and expenses during the analysis of the country's economy.

As a second point, a number of factors are included in the composition of psycho-physiological factors:

a) The general psychological state of buyers of products and services produced in the field of tourism;

b) Cultural development indicators of customers;

c) Buyer expectations formed in accordance with the requirements of the time, etc.

In general, various characteristic features of this group of factors can be determined:

- the relationship of the tourist (customer) with cultural issues;

- the tourist's awareness of products and services, as well as their availability, price changes. security of information on issues;

- the impact of the client's physiological development indicators on the tourist experience;
- behaviors based on cultural, environmental, customs and traditions that appear under the influence of various factors.

One of the most important points in the conceptual evaluation of the tourism field is the formation of products and services produced in this field. Tourism product refers to a number of product types:

- 1) Services means delivery of tourism products to potential buyers.
- 2) Industrial tourism. As in other sectors of the economy, enterprises and organizations offer specific products and services in this area. This in itself is the structure of the production mechanism, types of activities systemized with.
- 3) Population product. It ensures the production of products and services that combine historical, religious, cultural and regional qualities, as well as the introduction of traditions into the markets, and develops them and adapts them to the conditions of the time [8, p. 28].

It should also be noted that in modern literature, the concept of tourism, prospects for the development of tourism, as a result of a comprehensive evaluation of these prospects, their application possibilities and external factors shaping the process have begun to be investigated more precisely than in previous periods. When we say tourism development prospects, the volume of investments in this field, the resources of households (in terms of material and financial), the part of households as labor resources, etc. is intended [4, p. 104]. Operational mechanisms include costs, pricing, revenue (profit), taxes, special benefits and subsidies, and other payments. These are mechanisms that correspond to traditional economic models. Although both the tourism product and its production and sales prospects, as well as their implementation models, are based on external factors (it can be seen in the example of many IEOs), the tourism market in general is defined as an area that depends mainly on external factors.

The provision of natural resources can be considered as the basis for defining and developing the tourism industry as an independent field. For this purpose, many countries have adopted this area as one of the priority areas of their economic policies. The goals set by these countries are to form a competitive tourism market by increasing the quality of tourism services. Tourism forms a whole complex by connecting trade, public catering, transport and communication, hotels, advertising and information provision. Improving the quality of service in these areas could, in turn, contribute to increasing competitiveness in the tourism sector. At the same time, the relationships created in the fields listed above allow to justify the socio-economic characteristics and theoretical-methodological foundations of the tourism industry. In order to develop labor productivity in tourism, increase the quality of offered services, ensure safety during work organization, stimulate workers, and train qualified personnel in this field for conducting scientific research, it is important from the point of view of solving the problem. Therefore, it would be appropriate to focus on the listed issues from the point of view of the development of the tourism sector. Economic literature [89] groups the factors influencing the development of tourism. Such an approach acts as a leading locomotive in determining the socio-economic essence of tourism.

These factors can be grouped as follows:

1. Economic factors that ensure the development of the tourism industry.
 - a) Growth in the real income of the population.
 - b) Organization of distribution and redistribution of national income in an effective form.
 - c) Ensuring stability in the exchange rate.
 - d) Development of integration relations.
2. Economic factors hindering the development of tourism.
 - a) Rising of local problems for various fields to the global level.
 - b) Occurrence of decline in the sectoral structure of the national economy (in a number of countries, industry is considered an important sector in terms of ensuring the employment

of the population. For this reason, the negative situations occurring here spread to other sectors in a short time).

c) Inadequate level of state policy in the field of money-credit and currency relations.

As we mentioned before, the problems in the field of tourism should be considered from the socio-economic aspect. Therefore, not only economic, but also social issues should be in focus here. These include population location, migration, demographic factors, the influence they have on the formation of their customs and traditions, decision-making, production and employment habits, etc. we can relate the problems [4, p. 39].

It should be noted that the approaches to the development of tourism in different periods cannot fail to attract attention. From the middle of the 20th century, various organizations were created to regulate the tourism sector. During the World Tourism Conference held in the Philippines in 1986, some important points were examined and became the object of research [1, p. 162]. The Manila Declaration, which includes 120 countries, reflected the possibilities of tourism organized at the international level to influence the world market, cultural development, the level of well-being of the population, and the development of business relations. Later, international events related to the development of tourism were carried out from time to time. In turn, in these events, a number of conditions have been adopted in order for people to get permanent and more active leisure opportunities, spend their free time effectively, travel freely, develop human relations and, from this point of view, progress in management skills. They consist of:

- Active participation of local peoples in this process.
- Formation of human capital as a result of efficient use of human resources.
- Ensuring environmental protection and ecological safety.
- Effective use of tourism potential in terms of socio-economic development of regions.
- Compliance with competition rules accepted at the international level.
- Organization of awareness and propaganda work.

Ensuring economic security as a logical result of all this.

There is a unique system of indicators reflecting the economic essence of tourism. These indicators allow to assess the development dynamics of the field [6, p. 50]. Let's consider those indicators:

1. Cross-country tourist flow reflecting the circulation of arrivals and departures.
2. Evaluation of the material and technical base of the country's tourism at current prices.
3. Carrying out comparative analyzes with other areas of the national economy, comparing turnovers by areas and preparing recommendations accordingly.
4. The main macroeconomic indicators related to the tourism sector.
5. The number of people employed in this field.
6. Financial and economic indicators of tourism companies.
7. The level of provision of material and technical base of the field in comparison with other fields.
8. The position of the tourism sector in world rankings.

The development of tourism is also influenced by its improved legislative framework. Legislation on tourism consists of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Law "On Tourism" [5], relevant international agreements to which the Republic of Azerbaijan is a party, and other normative legal acts of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

The basis of the legal basis of the development of tourism in Azerbaijan was laid by the adoption of the Law "On Tourism" adopted on July 27, 1999. In view of modern requirements and global challenges, the bill was revised and adopted on December 27, 2021.

As a factor of the growth of the gross domestic product and a component of the socio-economic development of the regions, the regional directions of tourism are reflected in the state programs. According to the decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan regarding

structural reforms, on April 18, 2001, the Foreign Tourism Council was abolished and the Ministry of Youth, Sports and Tourism was established. In September of the same year, Azerbaijan became a member of the World Tourism Organization. By the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated January 30, 2006, the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Ministry of Youth, Sports and Tourism of the Republic of Azerbaijan, which were operating until that time, were abolished, and the Ministry of Culture and Tourism was established on the basis of the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Through the Ministry of Culture and Tourism (January 28, 2006), which is an organizational body that ensures the development of state tourism, it prepares the conceptual development directions of this field, the projects of creating its financial and material base, and implements a specific regulatory policy based on a single strategic plan.

In order to organize tourism within the country and to organize the successful use of tourism resources, the "State Program for the development of tourism in the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2002-2005" was approved by the Decree of the President dated August 27, 2002. At the beginning of the 21st century, modern residences and guest houses were opened in Baku, Ganja, Nakhchivan and other cities of the country. 149 hotel complexes are officially registered. The total number of places in these hotels is more than 5000. Today, private treatment and entertainment centers have been opened in places suitable for tourism. The number of foreign visitors to our republic has exceeded 1 million. President Ilham Aliyev's attention and concern for the organization of tourism in these regions was also reflected in the mentioned state programs. Therefore, there are a number of state programs approved by President Ilham Aliyev for the purpose of tourism development.

In addition, the "State Program on the development of tourism in the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2010-2014" was adopted on April 6, 2010. Issues of tourism development The President of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On improving the structure of the Ministry of Culture and Tourism of the Republic of Azerbaijan" dated March 29, 2016, "On additional measures related to the development of tourism in the Republic of Azerbaijan" dated September 1, 2016, "Accelerating the flow of tourists to the Republic of Azerbaijan" on additional measures related to" is also reflected in the orders dated February 20, 2017.

The State Tourism Agency of the Republic of Azerbaijan was established on the basis of the Ministry of Culture and Tourism of the Republic of Azerbaijan according to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated April 20, 2018 "On some measures related to the improvement of state management in the field of culture and tourism".

In accordance with the Regulation on the State Tourism Agency of the Republic of Azerbaijan, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated September 21, 2018, the State Tourism Agency of the Republic of Azerbaijan is a center that implements state policy and regulation in the field of tourism, as well as the protection of historical and cultural monuments located in the territories of state reserves under its jurisdiction. is an executive authority.

The Agency has powers to determine and actualize the interconnected state approach in the field of tourism, implement regulatory measures in the field of tourism, state administration, state control and management, and other state departments, activities and organizations related to the development of tourism.

Natural resources are one of the leading factors for recreational use of the territory. Although, according to A.A. Mints, "the effect of natural factors on production activity is carried out through certain techniques" [10], the nature of natural conditions has a significant impact on the formation and development of recreation complexes. Because natural resources play a major role in choosing a recreation and travel region by vacationers. Vacationers take into account the features of the landscape and climate, the richness and diversity of the flora and fauna, the opportunities

to engage in sports, hunting, and fishing. The organization of types and forms of recreational activities, the type of complex depends on the set of natural resources the area has. The diversity in the value of resources depends on one hand on their belonging to certain natural complexes, and on the other hand on the role they play in ERC.

Determining the initial conditions for the development of recreation areas requires studying the physical and geographical characteristics of the region. In this regard, foreign and local geographers have sufficient experience.

Assessment of natural resources takes an important place in the issues of interaction between nature and society. Any economic activity is based on the assessment of natural resources and conditions.

The works of many local and foreign researchers have been devoted to the evaluation of the territories for the use of sanitary-resort purposes. They include Y.M. Baybakova, G.A. Nevrayev and A.A. Chubukov [8], Y.M. Ilicheva [9], N.K. Kalitini [9], A. Meyer and V. Zeits [9], G.A. Nevrayev, A.A. Chubukov and Y.P. Maslov [10], L.P. Parfyonov. [102].] and we can give examples of others.

In recent years, the methodological approach to the principles of recreation evaluation of natural complexes has become widespread. Among them, it is interesting that V. Stauskas [5] tried to develop landscape evaluation criteria during the design of recreation areas. On the basis of this study, the author takes into account economic factors (forests, rivers, terrain, roads, etc.) along with natural factors. The results are evaluated using a five-point system.

In the work of M.G. Bojko [7], recreation regions are evaluated not only by their natural features, but also by the direction of economic development of the area. The authors conduct an engineering-construction assessment of the area and determine the feasibility of using the land for economic purposes.

The research work of Y.A. Veden and N.N. Miroshnichenko [8] on the methodology of recreation monitoring of territories is of interest. Here, the authors evaluate the recreation areas according to the system they prepared based on the physical-geographical atlas of the world, the climate atlas, and the climate handbook.

Assessment of natural conditions for recreation and tourism is very complex. In contrast to the evaluation of treatment resources, the attractiveness of landscapes, their unpredictability, exoticism, unrepeatability are of particular importance here [10].

According to the system developed by the British, typical English landscapes are evaluated with 18 points, and landscapes in the Himalayas with a 32-point system. According to M. Klaus (Germany), the design of recreation centers in the district of Rostock is carried out based on the assessment of natural-climatic conditions (in general, landscape, relief, climate, vegetation). Y. Warchinskaya (Poland) [11] proposes to carry out the assessment of natural resources for the purposes of recreation and tourism according to a model calculated on the basis of a mathematical function. This proposal was tested during the evaluation of the Kraków region for the purpose of mountain tourism. At that time, the main landscape features of the area (relief, hydrographic network, vegetation) were taken into account.

V. Reinhard (Germany) [11], after reviewing more than 20 methods of landscape recreation assessment, came to the conclusion that such an assessment should be based on the study of different types of capacity of the area: technical or output capacity (number of roads, parking lots, tourist trails and etc.), the economic capacity resulting from the load that may fall on the landscape, the psychological capacity measured by the amount of visitors who do not create an obstacle for normal recreation, and finally the financial capacity (financial capabilities of the land owner). Another German expert, Z. Günter, suggests using multiple criteria when evaluating the suitability of the area for recreation and tourism. The first criterion is the area of the area, the second criterion is the variability of the landscape within a recreation area, and the third criterion is the negative impact on the recreation area (noise, dust, odor, etc.).

When assessing the suitability of areas for recreation, both the comfort factor (favorable location of beaches, the presence of forests, mineral deposits, etc.), hygienic conditions (quality of river and sea water, etc.), as well as aesthetic (beauty and harmony of landscapes) factors should be taken into account.

We believe that when evaluating various factors, their importance for recreational activities should be taken into account. In our opinion, the main factors that form the basis of the assessment should include the following: the duration of favorable temperature conditions, the presence of sea coasts, the features of the relief, the presence of forests, rivers, lakes and reservoirs. On the other hand, the level of provision with transport highways should also be taken into account.

The development of tourism in mountain regions is more favorable at low and high average daily temperatures. Therefore, the days when the air temperature fluctuates between 10 and 22°C in such areas are considered favorable for tourism and recreation. In the mountain regions, the average daily temperature is observed from the second half of May to the middle of September in the hot season.

Taking into account the above, the following recreation regions are distinguished in Azerbaijan:

1. Shamakhi-Zagatala
2. Gusar-Shabran
3. Ganja-Mingachevir
4. Kalbajar-Karabagh
5. Kura plain
6. Absheron-Gobustan
7. Nakhchivan
8. Lankaran.

The following 56 recreation areas have been identified in the selected 8 recreation districts:

1. Shamakhi-Zagatala region: Gabala, Sheki, Bugur, Oguz, Ismayilli, Gakh, Ilisu, Zagatala, Korug, Shamakhi, Chukhuryurd, Pirgulu, Kaleybugurd, Lahij, Basgal.
2. Gusar-Shabran region: Yalama-Khudat, Guba, Laza, Afurcin, Gonaqkend, Gilgilchay, Galaalti.
3. Ganja-Mingachevir region: Goygol, Hajikand, Goygol-Maralgol, Gazanbulag, Naftalan, Gadabey, Tovuz, Agstafa, Mingachevir, Kura surroundings.
4. Kalbajar-Karabakh region: Sugovushan, Khankendi, Shusha, Lysogorsk, Istisu, Levchay, Lachin, Gubadli.
5. Kura plain region: Sabirabad, Ust-Kur.
6. Absheron-Gobustan region: northern shores of Absheron, Shikhov-Primorsk-Gobustan, Altyagaz.
7. Nakhchivan region: Bichenak, Shiran, Badamli, Nakhchivan, Ordubad, Sirab.
8. Lankaran region: Lankaran, Astara, Lerik, Masalli, Yardimli, Kurkosa.

The geographical location of the country or region plays an important role in the formation of territorial recreation complexes (RECs) and the formation of various recreational facilities. In other words, proximity to the sea, mountain and forest massifs, convenient location in relation to the main stream of vacationers, and important transport hubs are of great importance. Thus, the geographic position was a decisive factor during the formation of numerous resorts in the Mediterranean Sea (especially the Black Sea) and Caribbean Sea basins. The combination of picturesque mountains, valleys and lakes, as well as its location in the center of Europe, have attracted tourists to Switzerland since the past. So, in the early days of tourism in 1914, 80% of European tourists went here. The favorable position of the cities of Nalchik and Vladikavkaz in Russia also turned them into tourist centers. In general, the peculiar climate of the North

Caucasus, mountainous terrain, healing mineral waters turned it into a health resort center of the Union level.

The relief of this or that area is of great importance for the development of recreational farms. It should also be noted that this is a contradictory idea. On the one hand, areas with complex topography, including mountainous areas with frequently changing landscapes, are more attractive for tourists in terms of scenic landscapes, mountain air, mountaineering, and hunting. On the other hand, the complex terrain creates difficulties due to the construction of various facilities and communications and the associated additional costs (these costs are quickly removed).

It should be noted here that the mountain relief has led to the creation of many tourist centers. We have already mentioned Switzerland. The same can be said about the Alpine regions of Austria, Italy, France and the Carpathian mountains of Poland, Romania, Valdai, North Caucasus, Altai, Kamchatka.

The diversity and diversity of the structure of the territory of Azerbaijan, favorable physical and geographical conditions allow easy monitoring of the influence of natural factors on recreation complexes. This can be seen from the scientific works of H.A. Aliyev [5], M.M. Huseynov [9], A.D. Ayyubov [11] and others.

RESULTS

The location of Azerbaijan, a South Caucasian country, is attractive for Europeans and those living in the north in terms of climate and terrain. Its geographical location, its border with Russia in the north, Iran in the south, Georgia in the northwest, brotherly Turkey in the west, Turkmenistan in the east, and Kazakhstan in the northeast can be considered important in terms of organizing joint tourism routes. In general, it is possible to think about the organization of joint tourism routes with Central and Central Asia.

As we mentioned, the relief of Azerbaijan is colorful. In the north, there are the Bazar Düz (4466 m) and Shahdag (4243 m) mountain ranges of the Greater Caucasus, covered with eternal snow and glaciers, and in the west and south-west, there are smaller heights than the Greater Caucasus, the absence of permanent glaciers, and the Lesser Caucasus, which differs in the structure of its complex relief. The Talysh mountains stretch along the shores of the Caspian Sea in the southeast of Azerbaijan. The Kura-Araz lowland forms the major part of the republic.

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THE ROLE OF INNOVATION IN ENSURING SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF AZERBAIJAN

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ABSTRACT

The current state of the world economy shows that countries in which innovative activity is developed receive significant competitive advantage, which is manifested in the fact that the intellectual products they produce, as well as ordinary goods and services, are in high demand on the part of those states in which innovative activity underdeveloped and which specialize in the production of material goods. In modern Azerbaijan, which is the most dynamically developing country in the region, increased attention is paid to the development of innovation. The innovation policy pursued by the Azerbaijani state implies the creation of the necessary conditions for production, the dissemination and implementation of new knowledge and technologies. One of the most important features characterizing the development of the national economy in the modern period is the rationalization of innovative activities of entrepreneurs. And this, among other things, depends on the effectiveness of innovation management.

Key words: innovation economy, activity, management, competitiveness.

INTRODUCTION

Innovations, at the current stage of formation, play a significant role in ensuring the competitiveness of the national economy. This conclusion is confirmed by the experts of the World Economic Forum (WEF). When compiling the index of prospective competitiveness, calculated by the WEF since 2000. and reflecting the possibility of sustainable formation of the country in the medium term, three levels were taken into account [9, p. 98]:

- technological (innovative) index;
- index of public institutions;
- macroeconomic environment index.

To study the technology (innovation) index, WEF specialists divided all countries into main innovative countries (core innovators) and auxiliary innovative countries (noncore innovators). In the main innovative countries, technology accounts for 50% of the share, and 25% each for the index of government organizations and the index of the macroeconomic environment. In auxiliary innovative countries, all indices occupy 1/3 of the share.

Thus, the share of innovations in the general competitiveness index of states ranges from 1/3 to 1/2. At present, the closer the state is to become the main innovator, or, according to M. Porter's classification, to reach the innovative stage of development, at which domestic companies not only improve foreign technologies, but also form their own, the greater the weight of innovations in supplying competitiveness [4, p. 56].

It seems possible to single out innovations as a separate factor of competitiveness also for the following reason, which follows directly from the theory of international competitiveness by M. Porter. In accordance with the theory, the stages of economic development of each country can be shown as a series of stages in the development of competitiveness. Porter identifies four such stages:

- factorial stage;

- investment-driven stage;
- the stage driven by innovation;
- stage of wealth.

If in the first three stages there is an increase in the competitiveness of the national economy, the fourth stage means a gradual slowdown in growth and, ultimately, a recession. If at the investment stage of formation, national competitiveness “is based on the readiness and ability of national companies to aggressively invest”, then competitive preference at the innovation stage is based on the ability and readiness of companies to innovate, or, in other words, on innovative activity. Technologies are transferred in both commercial and non-commercial ways. The dissemination of technologies in the broad sense is implemented, as a rule, in non-commercial forms, such as: scientific and technical publications; holding exhibitions, symposiums; migration of specialists; activities of specialized international organizations, etc.

Licensing agreements are the main form of technology transfer in TNC networks. It consists in the fact that the licensor (owner of the technology) transfers to the licensee (person or organization) the rights to use the patented find or technology as know-how. The licensor usually receives a reward (or other compensation) for the use of technology or these services [8, p. 93].

A distinguishable role in international practice is played by franchising agreements. Franchising (from English, franchise - a privilege) is a business activity carried out in accordance with the terms of a commercial concession agreement. In the last decade, the world economy has shown that innovations play a significant role in the development of the competitiveness of enterprises and countries, providing strategic preference to the leaders of innovation processes. This makes it an urgent task for every country to choose priority areas for innovation.

The world market of innovative experts estimates about 1 trillion. USD In the middle of the 21st century, the United States supplied \$690 billion worth of innovative products. United States, Japan - \$680 billion US, China - \$138 billion USA, while countries with transformational economies lagged behind, for example, Russia supplied innovative products for only \$3.9 billion. USA. The dependence of competitiveness on innovation is often declared, but the relationship between them is not simple and unambiguous. The study of this dependence reveals that, despite the close organizational and economic relations of managerial, technological product innovations as economic target functions of entrepreneurial activity, the mutual influence of elements in the chain has not been fully established: innovation-innovation activity - competitiveness of the business structure [7, p. 38].

Innovation is often defined as the result of research and development (R&D), although today this concept is interpreted much more broadly. M. Porter, in his famous works on the theory of competition, notes that most changes in production are evolutionary rather than radical. At the same time, the accumulation of minor changes brings more than a significant technological breakthrough. Innovation is the result of research and development, as well as the result of organizational improvements. Innovation is associated with investment in research. Development, marketing. Innovations lead to a change in leadership in rivalry, provide competitive preference for the firm. Among the main reasons for innovation, Porter emphasizes: new technologies; new or changed customer requests; the emergence of the newest segment in the region; changes in the price or availability of assigned resources; modifications in state regulation, etc. [10, p.74].

Technology modification can create new opportunities for product development, new ways of marketing, production or after-sales service. The modification of technology precedes the emergence of new industries. Typically, competitive preference is passed on when old leaders fail to grasp changing customer requirements and therefore fail to create a new value chain. The emergence of a new segment may come as a surprise to the former leaders, which cannot quickly and significantly change the old value chain, and this is used by other competitors. Changes in prices for energy, raw materials, transport, communications, equipment can lead to a decrease in

the competitiveness of former leaders and gaining competitive preference for new leaders. Existing market leaders are adapted to certain forms of government regulation and do not always have time to respond to regulatory changes. New environmental policies, commercial restrictions, requirements for new industries can lead to innovations that entail new competitive preferences for firms that have managed to adapt to these new policies.

Some economists point out that the most important impact of innovation on competitiveness is the increase in the duration of competitive advantage. The degree of sustainability of competitive advantage is determined by the sources of competitive preference and the opportunities for their sustainable improvement and expansion. In this regard, it is possible to determine the degree of sustainability of the company's competitive advantages (PPC) [2, p. 45]:

- GDP with a low degree of stability. This type of competitive preference is readily available to competitors. For example, competitive preference in the cost of labor or raw materials, economies of scale from the use of technology, equipment, etc.;

- GDP with an average degree of stability. To do this, it is advisable to attribute the preservation to longer competitive preferences. For example, patented technology, differentiation based on unique products or services, company reputation, established product distribution channels. To achieve these benefits, intensive and long-term investment in production facilities, SIC and marketing research, as well as special training of personnel are required;

- GDP with a high degree of stability. This type of competitive preference requires a combination of high investment in innovative projects with high quality implementation.

It is known that you can acquire access to innovations in the market economy by buying them in the market. However, this path was doomed to the so-called catch-up development, since, as a rule, the most advanced novelties do not appear in commercial circulation. The buyer of the latest technology acquires a number of preferences: does not spend money on the development of a discovery, avoids the risk of introducing R&D, reduces the time for introducing an invention into production. At the same time, such an approach, as indicated above, reduces the time for maintaining competitiveness and does not provide high profits [8, art. 91].

The greatest preference is given to enterprises that prefer the method of financing their own internal development or establish control over developments outside the company (contracts with research institutes, universities).

Several companies can finance their own development, and the Western market is characterized by a significant concentration of R&D costs for enterprises. R&D goals vary. This may be the development of the latest product, the development of the latest technology, or the improvement of the product. The main share of R&D costs of firms is spent on the first direction, but for certain purposes there are national and industry specifics.

For firms in a transformational economy, funding sources are limited for R&D. Western firms spend a small percentage of their turnover on research, but their turnover is a billion dollars. The volume of internal funds of domestic firms does not allow sufficient financing of innovative activities. Thus, the acquisition of licenses for new products for our market, leasing operations for the purchase of equipment, is becoming more common. Borrowed funds, bank loans are also a significant source of financing for the company in the implementation of their innovative activities.

When developing an innovation policy, enterprises should proceed from the fact that innovation is not so much an advanced scientific development, but an advanced introduction to mass production. In relation to this object of scientific analysis is the innovative activity of the enterprise. Financing the creation of innovations does not guarantee innovative activity. Funding for R&D is more of a preventive measure. There are many examples in the economics literature of famous firms with strong market positions taking a defensive standpoint in scientific and technological competition. Part of the active science and technology policy is carried out by firms whose R&D expenditures are quite modest. High activity in the introduction of innovations is

distinguished by small firms, new competitors compared to already known ones, since for them such activity is often the only way to penetrate the market, create and maintain competitive preferences. The basis of low activity is, first of all, the risk of introducing innovations. According to US researchers, 40% of all new product offerings fail in the consumer goods market, 20% in the industrial goods market, and 18% in the services market. Another reason is the amount of funding for implementation. A ratio of 1:10:100:1 is generally considered the cost of scientific research, 10 times more money should be spent on prototyping, and 100 times more money should be spent on organizing mass production of goods. Therefore, it is understandable why most of our studies do not go beyond the first stage, only a small number reach the second stage. Lack of sufficient funds to finance R&D, lack of demand from buyers (saturation of the market with many well-known products in other countries) and high risk of innovation make it difficult to increase the competitiveness of enterprises based on innovation. For the normal functioning of the company's innovation cycle, it is necessary to search for ideas for production.

Income from the sale of new products, at least, covered the costs of further development. Therefore, the dilemma facing enterprises, whether to develop a novelty or to receive low, but relatively guaranteed profits by using goods and technologies already known on the world market, is often decided in favor of the latter. Among the factors delaying innovation processes, researchers note:

- weak level of research base, the fact that enterprises are not ready to study new scientific and technological achievements, the lack of information about the latest technologies and markets;
- lack of own funds, high economic risks, long-term return on innovative projects;
- incomplete level of development of legal and regulatory documents;
- insufficient innovative development of the technological market.

Innovative activity in a transformational economy is complicated by another problem. In connection with the growing role of innovation in ensuring competitiveness, the need for specialists in the company is increasing. In order to provide themselves with a competitive workforce, Western organizations enter into agreements with universities and specialized colleges, open their courses for retraining and advanced training, apply new methods of motivation and payment, etc. One of the forms is to attract specialists from other countries, in particular from countries with economies in transition, which poses a threat to the competitiveness of the latter [7, p.78]. In a number of studies, insufficient attention was paid to factors of competitiveness, such as personnel. In the circumstances of the innovative economy, the innovative activity of the organization's personnel becomes the basis that establishes the innovative formation and competitiveness of the enterprise. It follows that in order to manage the competitiveness of an organization, it is necessary to abandon outdated methods and indicators and, first of all, evaluate the main intellectual and creative potential of the company, on which further levels of competitiveness of the business structure depend: in technology, goods and finance.

In the modern world, there have been significant changes in the role of factors and sources that determine the economic development of the country. The depletion of traditional resources that determine economic growth requires the formation and development of a system of innovative processes, scientific knowledge, new technologies, and, as a result, new goods and services. An integral feature of the modern economy of countries is innovation, which will remain a priority for its development in the near future.

The main (basic) resource in an innovative economy is not the material factors of production, as in the industrial economy, but labor factors, in the structure of which the share of intellectual labor of researchers and developers increases sharply.

The current state of the world economy shows that countries in which innovative activity is developed receive significant competitive advantage, which is manifested in the fact that the intellectual products they produce, as well as ordinary goods and services, are in high demand on the part of those states in which innovative activity is underdeveloped and which specialize in the production of material goods.

In modern Azerbaijan, which is the most dynamically developing country in the region, increased attention is paid to the development of innovation.

Today, when oil prices are falling on world markets, the issue of reducing the dependence of the country's economy on oil exports becomes relevant. In order to ensure the sustainable development of the non-oil sector of the country's economy, create alternative sources for the development of the Azerbaijani economy, increase the investment attractiveness of local markets for foreign investors, it is necessary to ensure the development of the information technology sector, the creation of a network of innovative structures such as innovation centers, technological complexes, technology parks and business incubators, improving the management of their future activities. The Development Concept "Azerbaijan - 2020: a look into the future" states: "The expansion of innovation will be one of the main directions for ensuring long-term sustainable economic development, building a knowledge economy, accelerating the creation of science-intensive technologies and products (work, services). In this regard, the development of science will be prioritized on the basis of its history in our country and trends in the world, and the process of effective integration into progressive world science will continue. The scientific infrastructure will be improved, the material and technical base of science will be modernized and the transition of information support systems in this area to electronic form will be ensured." In the concept, also, one of the main tasks for ensuring the sustainable development of the country in the near future is considered to be the strengthening of ties between science, education and production, the development of mechanisms for managing this process and innovation activity [1].

The innovation economy is based on the production of high quality human capital, which provides a high basic level of development of education, and its improvement in the field of research and development. The result of this process is the replacement of traditional material and natural capital with human capital. Such substitution is a defining feature of the innovative orientation of the economy [2].

The innovation policy pursued by the Azerbaijani state implies the creation of the necessary conditions for production, the dissemination and implementation of new knowledge and technologies. This policy is primarily aimed at ensuring economic security, using the possibilities of new technologies in international economic relations, and creating jobs for all types of the country's labor potential, incl. for highly qualified personnel, restoration of the culture of knowledge-intensive production. It is interesting that the innovation policy in Azerbaijan is carried out as one of the forms of investment activity aimed at introducing the achievements of science and technology into production and the social sphere.

This includes the implementation of long-term scientific and technical programs, the financing of fundamental research to implement qualitative changes in the state of productive forces in order to improve the structure of the economy. One of the most important features characterizing the development of the national economy in the modern period is the rationalization of innovative activities of entrepreneurs. And this, among other things, depends on the effectiveness of innovation management.

Innovative activity, first of all, is the activity of creating, mastering, disseminating and using innovations. In addition, innovation activity is understood as a complex of scientific, technological, organizational, financial and commercial activities aimed at commercializing the accumulated knowledge, technologies and equipment. At the same time, the range is expanding and updating and the quality of products (goods, services) is improving, their manufacturing technologies are

being improved, and the result of such activities is new or additional goods and services, with new qualities that will ensure their competitiveness in domestic and foreign markets [3].

The management of innovative activities is dealt with by a special direction of management - innovation management.

Innovation management is an independent area of economic science and professional activity aimed at the formation and achievement of innovation goals by any organizational structure through the rational use of material, labor and financial resources [4].

The essence of innovation management lies in the management of innovation activities using the principles, functions and methods of management. The goals of innovation management are: diversification of the economy, development and implementation of new technologies and industries, modernization and improvement of traditional industries, creation of conditions for more efficient operation and increasing the competitiveness of the country's economy.

Innovation management includes the development of plans and programs for innovation, project evaluation, coordination of structures involved in innovation, financial and material support for innovation, creation of conditions for a comprehensive solution of innovation problems.

At the present stage of development of innovative activity, in order to increase its efficiency, it is necessary to create unified complexes of research, development and production in corporations and large firms. When forming and implementing the innovation policy of large enterprises and corporations, there is a reorientation of the directions of scientific, technical and production marketing activities towards an increase in the share of science-intensive products. This increases the competitiveness of products not only in domestic but also in international markets. Innovation management includes:

1. Market research to determine the need for innovation.
2. Forecasting new innovations and necessary activities for the development, creation, production and marketing of these innovations.
3. Analysis of the conditions for providing the resources necessary for the implementation of these innovations.
4. Evaluation and analysis of costs and benefits of innovation options and their implementation, taking into account real and predicted market conditions.
5. Evaluation of the effectiveness of investments in specific innovations and planning of innovation as an investment project, taking into account alternative options for investing in other projects.
6. Analysis of expected risks and uncertainties. Determination of means and methods for their minimization and management.
7. Study of the technological level of a specific innovation and the possibility of transferring (borrowing) technologies in the process of creating, mastering, placing and maintaining the minimum required level of sales on the market.
8. Determination of the organizational form of work on the creation, development and production, as well as the marketing of a new product [2].

The study of the experience of innovative development of leading enterprises in the developed countries of the world showed that the effectiveness of innovation management in them is associated with the introduction of integrated innovation management systems. The creation of integrated innovation management systems begins with the creation of an innovation structure in which the creation of new products is integrated into the overall strategic plan for the development of the company. Companies can implement both their own innovative developments and those acquired from outside. The company is developing an innovation management system, the purpose of which is to introduce innovations into the work of the enterprise in order to improve its economic performance. Since the innovative activity of an

enterprise is associated with an increase in the level of risk, the innovative strategy should also take into account measures to combat them. With the development of economic relations in society, the importance of innovations increases, which have become one of the first tools for conducting competition. The innovation system is usually understood as the elements of the organization that accompany innovation, as well as the relationship between them, which are fixed in the regulatory documents of the enterprise (charter, regulations on divisions, job descriptions). The creation of an innovation system pursues the following goals:

- increase the competitiveness of products and the enterprise itself;
- to ensure the economic security of the enterprise;
- to create an innovative base for the sustainable development of the enterprise.

To do this, the innovative system of the enterprise performs the following functions:

- predicts the innovation market;
- evaluates innovative ideas;
- develops an innovative strategy;
- plans innovative activities at the enterprise;
- introduces innovations;
- evaluates and corrects already implemented innovations.

There are offensive, defensive, imitation innovative strategies. An offensive innovation strategy is aimed at conquering new markets, a defensive strategy is aimed at maintaining its position in the market, and an imitation strategy is aimed at copying new technologies that have been developed by other companies. Innovations are a factor in the competitiveness of an enterprise, increase the ability of an enterprise to adapt to the conditions of the external environment, ensure the efficient use of production resources, increase the ability of an enterprise to find and conquer new product markets, and increase the stability of an enterprise's development. For the successful operation of the innovation system, financial support is important. In accordance with the economic ideology of the twenty-first century, one of the urgent problems is the formation of a development strategy based on innovation, analysis of the existing innovation potential and effective regulation of the activities of innovation structures.

RESULTS

The main trends in the development of the advanced countries of the world are aimed at developing the economy of these countries, based on information, knowledge, information technology, and innovation. The process of forming such an economy made it necessary to create innovative structures, including technology parks. And this, in turn, requires the organization of innovative activity and its management. In the further development of the Azerbaijani economy, the creation of technology parks is also one of the priority tasks. Therefore, the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Special Economic Zones" provides for the possibility of regulating relations related to the creation and management of technology parks, as well as the rules for organizing business activities there. Along with this, the "National Strategy for the Development of Science in 2009-2015 in the Republic of Azerbaijan" sets the task of developing the infrastructure for innovation and expanding the scope of the research network in this direction. In order to ensure the sustainable development of the country's economy and increase its competitiveness, expand industries based on innovation and ICT, create modern complexes for conducting scientific research and developing new information technologies, a High Technology Park (HTP) was created. The High Technology Park will provide research in the field of information and communication technologies, telecommunications and space, energy, and the development of new high technologies. The creation of the HTP and the innovative development of the country's economy will allow developing the non-oil sector of the country's economy, increasing its export potential, employment level, modernizing the economy, forming an innovative and knowledge-

intensive economy, expanding the production of competitive products, increasing the country's investment attractiveness, and developing innovative entrepreneurship.

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FACTORS INDICATING HUMAN RESOURCE UTILIZATION AND ITS DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

The changes taking place in the world under the name of globalization, the displacement of professional and creative people taking into account the impact on socio-economic development and international competition, as a result, the increase in migration rates at the international level, the steps taken in the direction of the formation of a knowledge society, require the re-evaluation of all theoretical approaches and practical measures in the management of human resources. So, from the beginning of mankind until now, research has been conducted in the direction of improving the forms and methods of regulating the use of people at both the micro and macro levels in order to develop the skills and knowledge of people, to gradually increase the areas of innovation and to form new competencies in employees, to reveal and develop the potential of people. makes it important. In an era of strong domestic and foreign competition, maintaining the primacy in production, service and other fields is related to how human resources are managed. For this reason, states and large companies attach great importance to the issue of the use of human resources, and constantly improve regulatory mechanisms in this direction.

KEY WORDS: human resources, enterprises, production, macro and micro economics

INTRODUCTION

In many economic literatures, the term "human resources" refers to one of the resources that a person uses to achieve the goal of an enterprise in the production of products and services. The human factor is the main component of the manufacturing and service sector. Human resources includes everyone from the highest to the lowest position in the enterprise. On the other hand, human resources management is a formal management design of an organization that effectively uses human knowledge, skills, and talents to achieve goals. In other words, human resources means the collection of knowledge, experience, habits, abilities, and minds of people working in an organization. The ultimate goal of human resource management coincides with the ultimate goal of the organization. This ensures sustainable and stable development of the organization in the long term.

The direct goal of human resources management is to provide the enterprise with the necessary personnel, to create a team with closely related aspects, to achieve a worthy achievement of the planned goal. Human Resource management is a process organized by organizations to maximize the performance of employees in accordance with the strategic goals of the employer. The concept of Human Resource management emerged in the early 1980s. As a process by which the human resource needs of an organization or company are assessed, the human resource needs are met and the necessary incentives and work environment are provided to get the most out of the new hire.

We can also consider the concept of Human Resources as a business function that helps to achieve organizational goals such as production, marketing and finance. In other words, human resources management has weakened the accounting part of traditional personnel management, but human resources management has been brought to a broader concept. Classical personnel management was a concept limited to registrations of entry and exit from work, salaries, personal

information of employees and registrations of disciplinary sanctions. Human Resource management is a more dynamic process.

Human resource management represents a specific function of management. Recently, this function has gained a lot of meaning, as the effectiveness of the organization, its competitiveness depends on the effectiveness of its main human resources. In connection with this, the demand for employees increases, the value of creative approach to work and high-level professionalism increases. The function of human resources management is becoming more difficult, the role and place of the head of personnel service is changing. He becomes the main manager of it.

The content of the human resource management function has changed along with the production conditions and goals of management. From the 19th-20th centuries to the 20th century, the management of human resources was limited to their stimulation and training, and the creation of a discipline system, so the main concern of management is to increase labor productivity and increase the work capacity of each employee, and the efficiency of production in general.

In the 50s and 60s of the 20th century, the main issue of management was the creation of human relations in the organization. Therefore, the main goal in management was to create a pleasant environment in the collective, and the creation of cooperation in the group was the main thing. For this purpose, accurate, sensitive, tactically trained managers were trained.

In the 1960s and 1970s, the main problem of "Participation" emerged. Therefore, the focus is on participative management, where employees participate in the decision-making process. The "participation" challenge required highly qualified staff, which necessitated the development of a new curriculum, retraining and staff development.

In the 70s and 80s, the main issue was taking ideas and opinions from subordinates in complex, creative work. During this period, the labor evaluation program is developed and a special team is established.

In the 1980s and 1990s, as a result of job cuts, economic recession, development of technology, and international competition, the overcrowding of workers led to the problem that workers had to be laid off. To mitigate the stress of losing a job, it is necessary to take measures, these measures include providing various compensations, organizing special seminars, retirement, and retraining for a new sphere.

In the 1990s and 2000s, the main problem was the change in the workforce and the labor shortage in general. Human resource management strategy, implementation of employee rights, extension of rights, availability of flexible work schedule and provision of benefits and also computerization process are the leading functions of management. While in the past the HR department saw employees as "assets", today's HR department is seen as a "resource to be developed" and strives to increase their knowledge, skills and abilities.

In the period before our independence (when we were part of the Soviet Union), human resources management functions were carried out by employment agencies and personnel departments in enterprises. They dealt with the issue of a single state, providing the national economy with the necessary personnel, fulfilling the labor rights of citizens (ensuring their employment). In most enterprises, the activities of personnel departments (to date) were mainly limited to solving issues of hiring and firing employees and processing personnel documents. This does not correspond to new requirements in personnel policy, new functions in human resources management. There is no single system in human resources management. First of all, there is no single management system that determines what the employees are capable of and their direction in accordance with their professional activity and personal quality. In most enterprises, the urgent task is to increase the role of the restructuring and personnel departments, the creation of the human resources management department, which is related to the changes in the economic and social conditions of the enterprises.

The main goal of human resources is to increase productivity, increase the quality of work life, gain a competitive advantage, and legal compliance. The human resources management system is formed based on the basic rules of the organization, which are determined by the personnel policy. The elements of personnel policy can be approached as follows:

- 1) goals and issues of the enterprise
- 2) approval of employees' rights
- 3) formation of jobs
- 4) payment principles and labor evaluation
- 5) working conditions
- 6) social guarantee

Based on these basic rules, it is possible to distinguish the goals and issues of people management in the organization. In order to realize the goal, the following main issues must be resolved:

- 1) staffing - equipping the organization with employees of the right quality at the right time, in the right place
- 2) organizational work - creation of a working environment to help the effective work of the staff
- 3) training, development - equipping employees with knowledge and skills, necessary for effective work, behavioral models
- 4) rewarding - creation of a staff motivation system, involvement in achieving personal, group, organizational goals
- 5) creation and maintenance of an effective system of labor relations - provision of a social environment that helps the effective work of the staff and increases the efficiency of the organization's economic activity.

Strategies, tools, techniques and operations for solving the problems listed in the human resource management system, which make people work according to the results, which are necessary for the organization and take into account the interests of the employee. In order to increase the productivity of employees, companies or organizations organize additional trainings and courses for each employee. At the same time, these trainings have an effect on the quality of work life.

Functions of human resources:

- Business analysis and business design
- To plan
- Employee selection and recruitment
- Training and development
- Performance evaluation
- Career development
- Business evaluation
- Salary management
- Discipline
- Worker health and worker safety
- Legal aspects of human resources management
- Human resources information system and electronic human resources
- International human resources management

Business analysis is the design and study of a particular business along with its smallest components. The main functions of business analysis are to collect information about the characteristics of each task, the general state and characteristics of the work, the environment and working conditions in which the work is carried out, to systematically check and evaluate the collected data, and to write information about them. Business analysis helps to plan human

resources, determine the need for training, prepare career plans, determine the monthly amount to be paid to the employee. In human resources planning, three main goals are considered, which are the right place, the right time and the right person. The main motto of planning in general human resources is "the worst plan is no plan". Human resource planning is a conscious activity aimed at achieving the productivity of employees in the right place and time, in the right number and quality, in order to realize the goals of the organization in a productive way. Estimating human resource needs both qualitatively and quantitatively is among the tasks of the human resource planning function. Human resource planning period:

- Determining the supply of human resources
- Determining the demand for human resources
- Determination of supply and demand of human resources

Aspects such as organizational chart and job description, general labor inventory, labor skills inventory, staff turnover rate, and continuity rate play a key role in determining human resources provision. A general labor inventory is an examination of the existing labor force in terms of quantity and quality to determine future labor movements. The rate of labor capacity is calculated as a percentage of the number of employees who leave work in a certain period. The absenteeism rate is the absenteeism of programmed personnel.

Determining the demand for human resources consists of some requirements:

- Real labor requirements: the amount of human resources that perform the work that needs to be done. It is the equalization of the current amount of workers with the amount of workers that should be.

- Reserve staff requirement: the staffing requirement is determined to fulfill the demand arising from the attendance.

- Additional worker demand: is the demand arising from those who leave work for various reasons. The staff turnover rate is an important source for this.

- New employee requirements: new employee requirements that arise during new investments, new technologies, production or sales growth, organizational structural changes.

In general, human resource planning refers to supply and demand management. Human resource plans make different decisions when there is excess supply or excess demand. In human resources, two different sources are used during the recruitment process. These are internal and external sources. Again, positive and negative aspects emerge when employees are recruited from internal and external sources. Job changes are made based on requests from employees within the company to internal sources. The upside of an insourced employee is the possibility of promotion, motivation, intra-company cultural cohesion and commitment to the company. The negative aspects that may arise when hiring an employee from an internal source is the decrease in motivation of other candidates, except for the candidate selected from several applications for the same position. There are positive aspects such as external sources, new change, development, the need for differently qualified people with the creation of a department, the idea that new participation will be highly motivated for psychological reasons, the opportunity to add new ideas and dimensions to the organization of various thought structures, and finding employees under more comfortable conditions. Ways to recruit new employees:

Notification to the Ministry and Directorate (public institution)

- Internal announcements (bulletin board, general meetings, department meetings)
- Business announcements (web page, newspaper)
- Human resources companies
- Suggestions and advice from employees
- Trade unions, professional organizations, universities, compulsory services, those in the internship program

When selecting an employee, education, work experience and personal qualities are the main factors to be considered. The application and selection process begins with the creation of a demand due to a shortage of personnel. Curriculum vitae and CVs of candidates for the required position are collected and refined. The next step is to hold the first meetings. Candidates who pass the first meeting can be tested. The next step is the interview. After the stage, which continues with the reference screening of the candidates who passed the interview, the candidate is required to undergo a health examination. The next stage is the candidate's starting work. There are several types of candidate interviews.

- Free interview: questions are not limited, they can be on any topic, even the candidate can ask questions. In total, this accounting form can take 20-40 minutes. In some cases there may be more than one interviewer. Questions that are not directly related to the job or do not reflect on the job performance cannot be asked. Ask open-ended questions as much as possible. In this form of accounting, there is no need to inquire into the details of the candidate's past successes or failures.

- Boundary interview: Questions are prepared in advance and answers are recorded in a form. Interviewer and candidates cannot get extensive information about each other.

- Situational interview: It is examined whether the candidate can cope with the critical situations that he may face through example situations.

Orientation training: Providing information to the newly hired employee about the company, managers, human resources practices, and workplace rules and practices. There are 2 types of orientation training.

1. General orientation: conducted by the head of the department or the head of the human resources department.

2. Job-centered orientation: can be conducted by the supervisor or other employees.

There are some methods used in orientation, the first of which is business publications. Another method is holding conferences or meetings. This step is carried out in human resources when hiring not one but several employees at the same time. During the orientation method, which is in the form of an interview, the questions are answered with a one-on-one interview. The last orientation method is on-the-job orientation training. In human resources, this method is the most common method, and in this method, the orientation of the employee is carried out by the position holder. Problems that a failed orientation program can cause include:

- Waste of time: Inadequate training prevents timely completion of work.
- Loss of performance: insufficient information about work and feeling alienated from the workplace lead to loss of performance.

- Cost loss: time and performance loss directly leads to cost loss.

- Loss of trust: as a result of inefficiency and reduced commitment, the employee's trust in the enterprise decreases, or the opposite of this situation can happen.

In addition to the newly hired employee, the current employee of the company also undergoes orientation training. The main purpose of this training is personal development, professional development and technical skill development. It is carried out in 2 ways: at work and outside of work.

During on the job training, the employee is trained to be more competent while working on the job. This method of training has positive and negative aspects. Employee productivity is maintained, training is standardized, and costs are low because there is no need for a dedicated trainer, which are positive aspects of this training method.

A positive aspect of off-the-job training is that employees pay more attention to training. The downside may be the failure to adapt off-the-job training to the workplace. Performance evaluation: It is a concept that expresses quantitatively and qualitatively what an individual, a group or a company doing a job can achieve and provide in the direction of the intended goal. Performance appraisal is done in order to improve the performance and to make decisions such

as pay, promotion, dismissal based on the results. Performance appraisal can be done not only for employees but also for managers and executives to evaluate themselves. Performance appraisals reveal the training needs of employees. The purpose of performance evaluation should be determined in advance. Performance planning is done in two ways:

1. Company performance planning: Mission, vision, strategic goals, objectives and strategies are defined and communicated to employees. Action plans, programs, budgets and targets are prepared.

2. Personal performance planning: Performance criteria are defined. Criteria for personality traits include truthfulness, honesty, intelligence, and speed. Behavioral criteria include working together, having a sense of team spirit, and taking initiative. Competence-based criteria include leadership, problem-solving, and decision-making.

Factors affecting the formation of human resources management can be divided into two places: internal and external factors. Internal factors are a type of main factors affecting the organization. Internal factors are more important: type of organization, management style and methods, organizational structure of the enterprise, social-labor relations in the enterprise. External factors are factors that cannot be determined in advance by the organization: state regulation, market pressure (competition), socio-demographic trends, trade union activity, etc. Although there are different forms of human resource management systems, they have common features:

- 1) The main goal of the human resource management system coincides with the goal of the organization.

- 2) Staff management is the first layer of management in any organization, as it is the people who unite around common goals, who form this organization, and through them the flow of information, material, and finance is influenced.

- 3) Staff management is involved in all functional spheres of the organization's activity: production, marketing, finance, accounting, innovation

- 4) Personnel management has common features in all systems; related to human collectives: the need for communication, the possibility of conflicts, etc.

There are many factors that affect the use of human resources. Among them, the most influential in our time are the following:

1. Global competition. Today it is difficult for companies to maintain their reputation. The advantage in competition is related to the correct and efficient use of human resources. It is known that the economic results of organizations are related to the activities of the staff of those companies and institutions.

2. Technological progress. No matter how new technological services are, it should not be forgotten that they depend on the human factor. The use of new technologies in enterprises and the innovations created by them also affect the use of human resources and create a number of changes.

3. Labor force structural changes. Correct observation of such structural changes increases the objectivity of management. When we think of structural changes, the first thing that comes to mind is demographic change. It is necessary to observe all the changes in time and take the necessary measures.

4. Development and growth of enterprises and organizations. Already, large enterprises and organizations are trying to make management from a single center by creating a special system.

5. Legal norms in the workplace. The enterprise regulates the relationship with its employees in accordance with legal norms. The picture of determining the duties for which both the employer and the employees are responsible has changed. The hiring process has become more systematic, and labor wages have increased.

6. Increasing the level of education. From the past to the present, the characteristics, features, and in short, the demand for employees have changed. This is related to the social and economic revolution taking place in the world. Technological development, in turn, has led to the acquisition of new knowledge, the rise and development of the level of education.

Proper planning of human resources, therefore, conducting job analyzes and determining vacancies, issuing job announcements for the purpose of selecting human resources, holding meetings with applicants, work adaptation, education and career work, ability measurement, job change and promotion, dismissal it covers work such as release, wages, social-cultural activities and medical care.

The biggest investment of the state is people. Because the political, economic and social well-being of every state depends on its citizens. That is why the concept of human capital was born. If we look at developed countries, we will see how much capital is invested in the personal development of their employees. The development of people depends on the country's education system and the correct and efficient management of Human Resources at work. For the development of Human Resources, the trainings carried out with the aim of obtaining the maximum performance from the employed person during his working life are important. That is why the interest in local and international courses and seminars has been quite large recently.

The most important factor in the development of Human Resources is education. In enterprises that do not give due importance to education, the ability of that enterprise and organization to increase the success and work efficiency of employees or to compete in the presence of strong competition is very low. As a result of technological changes, the ability of people to work with new modern equipment depends on the new knowledge and practical experiences gained.

If we look at well-known, high-profit companies, we will see that the Human Resources department is the backbone of the company.

The purpose of trainings carried out by Human Resources:

- Providing the employee with the skills, knowledge and behaviors appropriate to their duties
- Preventing errors that may occur in enterprises
- Improving product and service quality
- Reducing the number of staff resignations
- Shortening the time of adaptation of personnel to innovations
- Increasing the self-confidence and motivation of the staff.

Correct identification of the need for education and training is the most important step. This need is related to the gap between existing performance and desired performance.

Training Need=Outcome Required - Outcome Available

Among the factors affecting the development of human resources, the most important are technological progress, economic revolution and global competition. Thus, the main goal of competitive companies is to create innovation. Because often companies repeat the most basic strategies of their competitors with some changes. In order to create innovation, the company tries to train its staff as professionals as much as possible. Trainings aimed at the social, cultural and scientific development of personnel also lead to the recognition of the company. Thus, the participant in the training also represents the enterprise or organization where he works.

If everyone in the enterprise does their work at the highest level and efficiently, there will be no need for additional employee potential. This means saving both money and time. That is, it is appropriate to apply the principle of quality, not quantity, in human resources.

The technological progress brought along with the economic progress in the world has already caused a change in the characteristics sought in people. In our computer-supported industrial era, the ability of people to use technological equipment correctly and efficiently is more prominent. For this, the trainings conducted by specialists are of great importance.

The system established by persons responsible for human resources should be professional. Because this system should meet both the company's own welfare and interests, as well as the interests of the staff. The development of human resources management strategies should be considered as a broad project. It is very important to involve human resources specialists and modern information technology professionals in such a project. This is due to the fact that the main resource of the organization is people, it is the correct management of human resources that creates the competitive advantage of the enterprise. This role is realized through the following types of activities; influence the process of human resources planning, legal issues related to people management, study of workforce turnover, solving acquisition and merger issues, downsizing and restructuring of the enterprise; reward management. Strategic management of human resources provides a planned strategy for the development of human resources of the organization, which allows to create a trained staff according to the needs of the enterprise.

Operational approach – corresponds to the traditional view of human resource management. This is a managerial and short-term role, concerned with various current people management activities and generally focused on the implementation of developed strategies. This role is carried out with the following types of activities: recruitment and selection of staff for the purpose of filling available vacancies, determination of professional and social orientation, as well as implementation of job adaptation; discussion of reports on technical safety during accidents, management of additional benefits programs; creation of pleasant labor relations between management and staff in the collective; processing of complaints; evaluation of labor activity.

Stages of human resources management:

- 1) Planning of human resources - development of a plan to fulfill the demand for human resources in the future.
- 2) Recruitment of staff - creating a pool of potential candidates for all positions (departments).
- 3) Selection - evaluation of candidates in workplaces and selection of the best ones from reserve candidates.
- 4) Determining wages and providing additional benefits in order to retain the necessary employees and create interest in their remaining at work.
- 5) Social adaptation and professional direction - the employee hired by the enterprise must understand what the enterprise expects from the employee and what his work will be evaluated.
- 6) Training - development and implementation of a program of learning work habits that are important for the effective performance of work.
- 7) Evaluation of labor activity - development of methods of evaluation of activity and delivery to employees.
- 8) Promotion, demotion, transfer to another job, dismissal - development of methods of placing employees in high and low responsibility positions, development of professional practices.
- 9) Training of managerial personnel, career management - Development of a program aimed at increasing the efficiency and ability of managerial staff.

Human resources planning in Azerbaijan is based on the change of the external environment of the enterprise and the change of the enterprise's goals. The enterprise must operate in unstable conditions, in a competitive environment and in an environment where threats are expected. Such cases place special demands on employees. Being able to take risks, introduce new products, propose new ideas, show initiative, creative approach, and business skills that can survive in conditions with marketing skills are valuable.

RESULTS

During the research, we found that human resources occupy a very important place in the development and activity of the state, enterprises and organizations. It is very important to choose the right steps by considering both negative and positive factors affecting the development of this

field. As we mentioned before, the principle of right place, right time, right person should be constantly monitored. Motivating employees, understanding their goals and tasks, correct division of work and hours will help to increase their labor activities and productivity. Also, the further expansion of experience and work opportunities for our young people entering the new job field, and the increase of paid internship programs should be among the most important tasks of human resources. In order for them to acquire not only theoretical, but also practical knowledge, appropriate work should be carried out. This will have a positive effect on their individual development and future activities, and will also stimulate the development of the country's economy. The training of local specialists and their development will be beneficial for our country and will reduce the demand for foreign specialists. At a time when individual entrepreneurship is developing, the productivity of employees and the correct calculation of time management are very important both in terms of increasing income and improving the lifestyle, as well as in terms of increasing the quality of the work done. has been revealed as an important issue. This, in turn, is directly related to the development of the economy, the reduction of the cost of the manufactured product and the reduction of idle time during the process. These, in turn, are one of the main conditions for raising the standard of living of the population. In general, each of these processes has a positive effect on the system as a whole and increases overall productivity.

Thus, in contrast to the traditional personnel department, which considers its activity to be completed mainly with the functions of accounting and the preparation of documents necessary for the recruitment and release of employees, the organization of the perfect work with the staff of the enterprise requires a completely new approach to the formation of this service area.

In the conditions of market relations, the elimination of planned management by the state in personnel training makes it necessary to take into account supply and demand in the labor market. Therefore, the indicators affecting the determination of employee needs must be taken into account. Here, the employee's world view, familiarity with constantly developing techniques and technologies, knowledge and skills, as well as the desire for self-development are the main criteria.

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THE ROLE OF AGRICULTURE IN ENSURING ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Accelerating commercial and economic relations, increasing international trade turnover, creating a healthy competitive environment in the demand market, and other such factors, most countries of the world consider the globalization of their economic systems as the most optimal solution for solving a number of problems. In this context, economic subjects should be represented in world markets on equal terms, regardless of their material and technical conditions, and competition laws should act as the main regulatory role.

KEY WORDS: agriculture, provision, implemented, policy

As we mentioned, the agricultural sector stands out from other sectors of the economy due to a number of its aspects. The uniqueness of this field comes from the fact that agricultural production is highly dependent on a number of objective and subjective factors. Intensification of erosion processes of water and land resources, crisis and recession, disproportionate change in the production-consumption ratio of agricultural and food products, disparity in the agricultural sector, etc. creates additional difficulties for the agricultural sector. Each of the mentioned requires the implementation of a flexible agrarian policy in modern conditions.

In order to ensure the continuous and sustainable development of the agricultural sector, to form reliable bases for food security in the country, and also to adapt the national economic subjects to the increasing competition in the global markets, the modern agrarian policy should be able to create a solid basis for the competitiveness of the agricultural sector in the global markets.

In order to keep pace with the dynamics of globalization and changes in the structure of the global consumer market, the adaptation of both production relations and the legal-normative framework in the agricultural sector to global requirements and norms, thereby ensuring the competitiveness of national production is the most important part of the policy implemented in agriculture in the country. should be the main goal. In order to achieve this goal, in our opinion, good results can be achieved by taking the following areas as the main priorities of the policy and forming them into a single strategy:

- improvement of the national legislative framework for the agricultural sector;
- putting the issue of food safety in the foreground;
- implementation of food safety measures;
- reduction of import dependence on agricultural products;
- supporting scientific researches in the sector;
- organization of efficient use and protection of land and water resources;
- reducing the urbanization process;
- deployment of qualified personnel in villages;
- expansion of export potential.

Each of the mentioned provisions of the policy implemented in the agricultural sector is of great importance and requires the development and consistent implementation of a strict system

of measures. As it has been emphasized, currently production relations depend on how competitive economic subjects are. In particular, the growing demand for agricultural and food products has intensified the competition in the consumer market. From this factor, it is clear that manufacturers should benefit from modern technologies and achievements of ETT, and produce products according to the conditions of international standards and norms. The application of innovations, scientific and technical innovations to production and the formation of production spheres in accordance with technical norms that meet modern standards will create suitable conditions for the production of competitive products in the globalized world economy.

The policy implemented in the field of food products market development - stimulation of domestically produced agricultural products market; stimulation of export processes; restricting free market entry and exits to protect the internal market. As it is known from the above, the currently used practice is to actively use the methods of legal regulation in the agricultural sector in order to stimulate local producers and protect the local market.

However, the issues facing the regulation of the agricultural sector in Azerbaijan and other post-socialist countries are somewhat specific and complex. Because, in the mentioned countries, they are faced with the obligation to simultaneously solve the three basic problems grouped below:

Implementation of the transformation of the existing system. For more than half a century, radical reforms should be carried out for the formation of free market relations in transition economy states living in the administrative-empire system.

Reshaping the structure of the economic system. The states in question were excluded from the effects of the international division of labor because they were in a closed economy during the socialist period. It is for this reason that the current structure of the economic systems of the mentioned republics was established not under the influence of the international division of labor and because of their competitive advantages in the market, but on the basis of the interests of the unified national economic complex of the former USSR. In other words, in the states implementing the transformation policy, there is an incomplete economic system with an incomplete structure and a failed, imperfect structure from the point of view of national economic development, as well as the existing economic potential. For this reason, systematic structural changes should be implemented by determining the competitive areas of the economic systems of the mentioned countries.

Effective and successful integration of the existing economic system in the country into the world economy. Along with the creation of a successful economic system based on the principles of the free market and the comparative advantages of the post-socialist countries, the integration of those countries into the global economic system in this context is also of great importance.

Noting these fundamental issues, it can be concluded that the goals of the policy implemented in the agricultural sector of countries like Azerbaijan should mainly include three directions:

1) Achieving the formation of market economic relations in the agricultural sector by implementing a number of reforms and creating a system of economic and legal regulation of this sector based on market principles;

2) creation of an advanced structure of the agricultural sector proportional to the national potential, local demand and advantages of the international division of labor;

3) ensuring successful integration into the international agricultural market. From the point of view of the target in the first priority, the following can be attributed to the goals and tasks of the policy implemented in the agricultural sector, based on the results of existing scientific and experimental studies:

a) by carrying out reforms, to ensure the formation of an economic system based on the development of private property in the agricultural sector and market economic relations as a whole;

- b) to save the production of agricultural products from recession;
- c) create an abundance of food products in the country.

In connection with the above, the tasks to be implemented can be given as follows:

- reconstruction of the agricultural sector, denationalization of land and reorganization of production units of the sector.
- organization of new market relations in the agricultural sector, privatization of production companies, establishment of free market relations.
- increasing the level of payment of the country's demand for agricultural products, as well as food products, at the expense of local production.

After realizing the stated goals and objectives, the next major problem for countries with transition economies is the creation of a system of regulating the agricultural sector based on market relations. From this point of view, the following can be indicated as the main tasks:

- creation of a normative-legal base in accordance with the conditions of the market economy;
- creation of a healthy competitive environment in agricultural markets;
- stimulation of sustainable and sustainable development of the agricultural sector;
- implementation of the correct protectionism policy, ensuring the food safety issue with the help of customs regulation, duties on the import of food products;
- formation of favorable investment environment for international investments;
- financing of the main scientific and technical directions on problematic issues of the agricultural sector.

The objectives of the policy implemented in the target agricultural sector in the second priority are broader and comprehensive. For this reason, researching the theoretical and practical issues of legal regulation from the point of view of successful use of competitive advantages and increasing competitiveness is an important issue.

In order to better understand and increase the impact of the policies currently implemented in the agricultural sector, there is a need for a more serious study of the specific characteristics of this sector and the role it plays in the national economy. Based on various sources, it is possible to show the specific characteristics of the agricultural sector and the role it plays in the national economy as follows:[19]

- The agricultural sector provides most of the daily necessities for the life of the population. A significant part of these products is food products produced in the agricultural sector. From this point of view, taking into account that the food supply system is formed on the basis of geographical environment and cultural factors, and that providing people with food products is of strategic importance, the existence of a specific, independent agricultural system of each country emerges as a public task;

- products produced in the agricultural sector are the main raw material resource of industrial enterprises. Since the main raw materials produced in a number of industrial enterprises such as textiles and food are provided by the agricultural sector, this sector is also of special importance from the point of view of sustainable and sustainable industrial development;

- is a large market for agricultural sector as well as industrial products. The products of many industries, especially engineering and petrochemicals, are widely used in the agricultural sector;

- the agricultural sector is the main sector in which the population is engaged in developing countries. Currently, 3-4% of the employed population in the EU, 1.5-2% in the USA, 55-60% in the CIS, and 40% in Azerbaijan work in the agricultural sector;

- capital accumulation available in the agricultural sector is an investment resource for industrial enterprises. One of the important research objects of development economics after World War II is related to the successful use of added value in the agricultural sector to make the country an industrial country;

- the agricultural sector is an efficient sector from the point of view of environmental cleanliness. The great possibilities of using waste-free technology in this field make it ecologically efficient;

- since a significant part of the goods produced in the agricultural sector are exported, they play the role of a source of currency for the country. One of the factors that encourage industrialization in republics at the initial stage of development is the attraction of foreign capital to the country. Capital resources obtained from the export of the agricultural sector are the main source in fulfilling this factor import;

- the agricultural sector is one of the sectors most affected by scientific and technical development. Currently, the share of employment in the agricultural sector in developed countries is only 2-4%, which is an indicator of scientific and technical development, and this facilitates the orientation of the economically active population to other fields. On the other hand, scientific and technical development helps to lower prices and further improve the social condition of the population by creating an abundance of products;

- the production process in the agricultural sector is more dependent on the natural environment. Since land is the main factor of production in the agricultural sector, production in this area cannot be fully controlled by producers. That is, force majeure events beyond the producer's control - natural disasters such as floods, droughts, floods, unexpected frosts, and the spread of harmful insects directly affect the level of production;

- The policy implemented by the state in the agricultural sector is closely related to a number of policy directions implemented at the national level, such as regional policy. It is clear that the activities of the agricultural sector on an international scale are located in certain areas and are carried out by the population located in the villages. From this point of view, the policy implemented in the agricultural sector should be coordinated and implemented with a number of measures related to regional development;

- incomes and prices in the agricultural sector are highly differentiated. inelasticity of demand for agricultural products, dependence of production conditions on natural factors and seasonality, high competitiveness are the main factors that intensively change incomes and prices in the agricultural sector;

- more competition in the agricultural sector, the environment is healthier. Since there are a large number of producers, there are ample opportunities for a healthy competitive environment, but sometimes the difficulty of predicting production decisions, such as determining the amount of land cultivated by competing producers, does not allow for a correct assessment of the market structure;

- the quantitatively large production areas in the agricultural sector create additional costs. A large amount of additional costs are required to control workers who do not participate in the distribution of special incomes

- the issue of incorrect information in the agricultural sector leads to the creation of an imperfect insurance and credit market. Because frequent changes in income affect the conclusion of insurance and credit contracts, which weakens the interests of financial markets in this sector;

The role of the agricultural sector in the economic development mentioned above and the agricultural policy formed by taking into account some of its characteristics today, being a part of the policy implemented at the national level, includes different directions, and at this time the agricultural sector and agricultural sector producers are constantly subjected to special protective measures of the state. principle is expected.

Development concepts, tactical and strategic goals of agriculture, settlements in villages, agro-industrial complexes in general, justification of concrete measures and mechanisms for implementation, as well as the implementation of economic, social, organizational and legal measures agricultural policy has a different meaning from the point of view of the goals and

objectives set in the market economy. The agricultural policy, whose strategic goal is to provide agricultural producers with a proper and necessary standard of living, the population with low prices and the necessary amount of food products, and industrial enterprises with the necessary raw materials, also includes a number of sub-goals:

- Orientation and development of production according to market requirements, in the direction of foreign and domestic consumption demand;
- Ensuring the food security of the Republic;
- Integration of the agricultural sector into the market economic system as a whole;
- Increasing productivity and quality in the production of agricultural products;
- Protection of political and economic balance in society and the state;
- Increasing the volume of exports and adapting them to the international trade system;
- Stabilizing the income of agricultural producers and raising their living standards;
- Creation of balanced and environmentally friendly infrastructure in order to protect and efficiently use natural resources.

If, in addition to the above, the agricultural policy measures carried out in the market economy conditions increase the efficiency of existing economic relations and serve for their further development, in the market economy conditions they serve to completely eliminate the previous relations and replace them with new ones and are carried out by forming new ones. Against this background, in the conditions of a stable economy, the agricultural policy is to maintain the volume and price of products at the appropriate level, ensure their insurance, protect water and land resources, provide raw materials to agriculture, expand scientific research in the field of agriculture, stimulate the sale of products in the world markets, farmers. Although it carries out tasks such as solving lending problems, in the market economic system it faces the following goals:[15]

1. Liberalization of the agricultural market: It involves the transfer of this function to liberal markets by eliminating the state monopoly inherent in the planned economy in the distribution of processed products and consumed resources in the agricultural sector. The main measures are the restriction of subsidies and grants to agricultural producers and consumers, trade and price liberalization. In such a case, changing prices, incomes and other monetary quantities become the main factor determining the choices of producers and consumers, causing intensive changes in the volume and structure of production, consumption, and trade of agricultural products in the republic;

2. Creation of new economic-property relations in the agricultural sector: In this direction, identifying municipal and state-owned objects, carrying out land reform and, as a result, changing the ownership relations of municipal, land reclamation and water management institutions, determining the forms of their more correct use, state and private it concerns the allocation of land belonging to ownership, the creation of new economic relations in social infrastructure facilities, the privatization of agricultural production enterprises and infrastructure facilities, etc.;

3. Reconstruction of agricultural systems: Measures such as privatization and land reform are intended to change ownership relations, organization, production type and management forms in agricultural systems, thereby increasing efficiency. At this time, the formation of privately owned economic subjects, joint farms, joint-stock companies, cooperatives and state-owned agricultural firms and joint-stock companies based on state ownership on the basis of state farms and collective farms and on new lands involved in circulation is one of the main problems;

4. Formation of commercial and trade infrastructure in the agricultural sector: consists of the formation of public and private institutions and organizations or services that meet the requirements of a market-oriented, successful agricultural economic system. This includes issues such as the formation of agrobanks, insurance, credit and other financial institutions, information

and information systems in the market, distribution, supply and sales systems, legal infrastructure regulating the relations between market subjects;

5. Formation of the state guarantee mechanism in the agricultural sector: It involves the formation of an economic management mechanism that incorporates the state guarantee mechanism of the agricultural sector, which is based on market economy principles, from the strict administrative-empire management mechanism belonging to the socialist republic in the agricultural sector. . In such a case, issues such as the development of agricultural infrastructure companies, the existence of a number of tax and financial regulations, the regulation of the agricultural market, the social protection of the population living in villages, the training of qualified personnel working in the agricultural department, and the scientific and technical support of the sector are among the main issues.

As a rule, the functions and tools of the state in the economic system change depending on the specific historical and economic-political conjuncture. In the market economic system, the possibilities of legal regulation of the economy of the state depend on the level of economic development of these countries and the specific nature of the reforms carried out in them.

One of the main aspects determining the importance of legal regulation of the agricultural economy is determined by its inability to reduce the adverse effects of low-income, intersectoral and foreign competition. That is, the fact that the agricultural sector has its own characteristics makes it necessary to effectively regulate this sector by the state.

One of the most important goals facing the agricultural economy in the near future is the implementation of fundamental social changes in the village along with other organizational and economic measures. These changes are related to the creation of production and social infrastructure in villages, raising population incomes to the level of developed countries, and in general, creating favorable working and living conditions in villages. Consequently, in order to achieve the mentioned goals, it is necessary to revise the inter-sectoral proportions.

It is known that it is necessary to systematically implement reforms in the agricultural sector in order to create a healthy competitive environment. It should be noted that this approach is generally calculated to bring the economy of the republic to the standards of conformity existing in developed countries. The following results were obtained and proposals were made regarding the analysis and improvement of the current level of sustainable and sustainable development of the agricultural sector, the current state of its legal regulation.

1. During the past period, a number of normative-legal acts on the regulation of the general entrepreneurship environment, especially in the agricultural sector, have been adopted in our country, and in the adopted programs, a number of measures have been planned in this sector for the next years. However, the problem in our country is not in the preparation of these documents, but in the implementation of the requirements arising from them. The main reason for this is the unorganized nature of the relevant management bodies, which requires the implementation of serious measures. It should be noted that although the implemented agricultural reforms have been able to prevent the decline in the sector and achieve certain positive results in meeting local demand, serious lags are still evident in the republic's export opportunities and the production volume is at a low level from the point of view of the current potential. . In order to solve the mentioned problems, the policy implemented in the agricultural sector in the coming years should address a number of tasks, such as expanding the use of high technologies, increasing the efficiency of production according to international standards.

2. It should be noted that increasing the number of regulated prices, as well as including industrial sectors engaged in the production of material and technical resources for the agricultural sector and processing the final product of this sector, can create conditions for increasing the efficiency of price regulation in the agricultural sector. Because the agricultural sector is under the control of the means of production and processing areas. Although there is no

large-scale price regulation in the country in modern conditions, the prices of a number of products are regulated by authorized institutions. However, the category of regulated prices includes only products and services of state monopoly, natural monopoly and monopolistic subjects, therefore the scope of application of price regulation by the state is limited.

3. Expanding the scope of application of the anti-monopoly policy, preventing regional and field monopolistic tendencies, forming the Anti-monopoly and Competition Improvement Committee to increase the effectiveness of the policy in this area, weakening monopolies in other areas along with existing monopolies in the agricultural sector, systematizing the legislation on monopolies, and It necessitates the adoption of the Competition Code.

4. The formation of the Export Assistance Fund for the purpose of increasing the export potential in the agricultural sector, providing channels for the producers to access the international market, as well as the formation of the Import-Export Bank, which deals with more convenient financing of exports, is of particular importance.

5. As a result of the assessment of the development opportunities of the agricultural sector in our country, it is clear that our country has wide opportunities in this sector, but there is a need to systematically implement measures for the full and effective implementation of this potential and the formation of a competitive agricultural sector in the country.

6. Although legal regulation in the agricultural sector is necessary, the scope, methods, means and tools of this regulation may have unpleasant consequences if they do not take into account the characteristics of the sector's current opportunities and development directions. Among the main tasks of the sustainable development strategy of the agricultural sector, global problems such as ensuring sustainable economic growth in the agricultural sector, optimizing the supply and demand structure in this sector, and strengthening environmental measures should be included. In addition to road maps for the main sectors of the national economy, including the agricultural sector, sustainable development programs should be adopted based on the concept of sustainable development.

7. As one of the main conditions for ensuring the sustainable development of the agricultural sector in modern conditions, one of the main tasks of the policy implemented in the agricultural sector is the regulation of the negative impact that production can have on the disturbance of the ecological balance. For the protection of the environment and the efficient use of natural resources, educational measures should be carried out among the population.

8. It is appropriate to establish Agrarian Development Banks by the state in order to solve the issue of providing credit resources to business entities in the agricultural sector, to finance scientific researches aimed at the development of the sector, to provide credit to exports, and to provide significant support for solving social problems in villages.

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DEVELOPMENT DIRECTIONS OF THE PRODUCTION INFRASTRUCTURE IN THE COUNTRY UNDER A MARKET ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

In order to increase the volume of the gross domestic product in the country and achieve sustainable economic development, it is required to implement complex measures in the direction of development and improvement of all areas of the production infrastructure. From this point of view, it is necessary to ensure the development of important production infrastructures, especially production infrastructures such as fuel and energy, transport, communication.

In the "State Program for the Socio-Economic Development of the Regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2014-2018" it is envisaged to develop infrastructure areas in the following directions:

- creation of advanced information and communication infrastructure in the regions, further expansion of information and communication services;
- raising the level of knowledge and personnel training of the population in the field of ICT in the regions;
- further improvement of the quality of television broadcasting in the regions;
- continuation of the creation of new forces in the country's energy system, construction and reconstruction of new stations and transmission networks;
- expanding the use of alternative and renewable energy sources;
- construction of new thermal and hydropower plants in the regions, continuation of modernization of existing power units;
- continuation of measures to further improve gas supply in the regions;
- construction of modern heating systems in the regions, continuation of restoration, modernization and reconstruction of existing heating systems;
- continuation of measures in the direction of reconstruction and improvement of the water supply and sewage system in the regions;
- continuous development of the transport system in the regions, further improvement of the transport sector, including the competitive environment in the market of transport services;
- further development of the country's inter-regional, city and intra-regional road transport infrastructure;
- continuation of measures related to the construction and reconstruction of highways in the regions, especially the construction and major repair of rural roads.

Development of the energy sector is one of the most priority directions of the state's economic and social policy. The energy sector has always been of strategic importance for the country's economy and will continue to be so in the future. The analysis shows that the demand for electricity will increase by 5 percent every year due to the transition of the republic to market relations and the creation of new enterprises. Therefore, measures are being taken to restore the power of existing power plants and build new ones. Irregularity in the daily load schedule is constantly increasing due to the increase in the demand for electricity of the population and sectors of the economy operating in intermittent mode. Due to insufficient hydraulic power of HPPs, thermal stations are involved in load regulation, which leads to lower efficiency and lower reliability of the energy system. Therefore, hydropower plants should be one of the main

directions of energy development. The existence of economically efficient hydropower potential, which is not sufficiently used in Azerbaijan, allows to form a large-scale program for the construction of more effective facilities.

Plans for the reconstruction of high-voltage overhead power lines and the construction of new substations are also on the agenda to increase power transmission capacity. The project of ensuring the parallel operation of the energy systems of Turkey, Georgia, Russia, Azerbaijan and Iran also looks attractive.

After the implementation of the projects listed above, the Republic of Azerbaijan will have the opportunity to export electricity to neighboring countries.

The development of transport in the country is of great importance from the point of view of economic development. When transportation services are high, the cost of products is low. From this point of view, the need to develop the transport system in parallel with other areas of the economy and effectively, in accordance with the conditions of the market economy, is of special importance for the state. For this purpose, it is necessary to increase attention to the creation of effective conditions for the subjects in the transport sector to reduce their dependence on the state and to work profitably. With the passage of the North-South international transport corridors through the territory of the republic, the increase of the country's transit opportunities, the fact that a significant part of the transportation, i.e. 61.6 percent, is carried out by road transport necessitates the development of the road network in accordance with international standards and the implementation of relevant measures in this field. The measures implemented in the field of development of the transport system in the conditions of market economy relations created real foundations for the country's economic progress. Over the past years, the transport services market has been formed in Azerbaijan, state-owned motor transport enterprises have been privatized, and state management in the field of transport has been established in accordance with market economy relations. In addition, there are many problems in the highway network, which is an important component of the country's transport infrastructure. Thus, the compliance of the highway network with international standards, the growth rate of the country's motor vehicles and the intensity of the flow of traffic, the lack of operational condition of the road facilities is not sufficient to satisfy the demand of the country's economy and the population for high-level transport services, to use the country's transit potential at the appropriate level, and creates obstacles to the connection of the road network to the international highway network and requires their elimination in the near future. The pioneering development of the Europe-Caucasus-Asia TRACEKA international corridor, the "North-South" international corridor covering the Northern Europe-Russia-Caspian Sea-Azerbaijan-Iran-Iranian Gulf-India route, as well as the transcontinental export energy corridors are at the heart of the future development of Azerbaijan's transport system. stands

Reconstruction of 6-42 km and 89 km - Russia border sections of the "North-South" corridor of the Russian Federation state border-Gusar-Baku-Astara-Islamic Republic of Iran state border highway in the territory of the country, Baku-Russian Federation state border highway, Baku-Construction and reconstruction of projects for the reconstruction of 28-89 km of the Samur highway, the Alat-Masalli highway and the Masalli-Astara-Iran border highway, as well as the construction of the Baku Ring Road connecting the "North-South" and TRASEKA international corridors without entering the center of Baku. investment projects are expected to be realized. In a number of regions, as well as in the city of Baku, it is planned to create transport logistics points and build bus stations for the purpose of harmonious transportation of goods and timely delivery to their destination.

Within the framework of the "Trade and Transport Facilitation" project funded by the World Bank, the railway transport support project includes restoration and reconstruction of the country's railways, renewal and modernization of railway vehicles, purchase of electric

locomotives and diesel locomotives, freight wagons, especially oil cargo tanks, and passenger wagons. The future development directions of the country's transport complex are reflected in the institutional and technical assistance projects to be held with the support of the World Bank and the Asian Development Bank. The project consists of components such as support for reforms in border and customs services, support for the transport sector and restructuring of state-owned transport enterprises, integrated transit management, improvement of key North-South and East-West corridors, as well as a number of selected national road and rail infrastructure. Within the framework of the project, the restructuring of the transport sector through the separation of commercial and regulatory functions and the reduction of relevant state assets is envisaged, with the gradual management reform of the transport complex.

Each of the TRACEKA, North-South and Kars-Akhalkalaki-Tbilisi-Baku transport corridors has its own importance for the Republic of Azerbaijan.

On the whole, the TRACEKA corridor can be considered more efficient in a relative sense, as it covers more modes of transport and more countries. In any case, in order to increase the country's transit capabilities and effectively use the existing potential, it is necessary to rebuild the relevant infrastructures and improve them according to international standards. In order to expand the transit opportunities of the Republic of Azerbaijan, to create a competitive transport-transit system that meets modern international standards, and at the same time to use the existing potential as efficiently as possible, it is necessary to implement a number of measures in a complex manner. Of course, the proposed measures will cover several directions, referring to different types of transport. Research has shown that in any case, within the framework of the "TRACEKA" project, in order to ensure the use of the transport transit potential of the Republic of Azerbaijan at an optimal level in terms of its national and economic interests, the creation of a common market for transit transportation, simplification of customs and transit processes, transit transportation elimination of illegal freight transportation, simplification of administrative procedures, improvement of the structure of taxes, duties, and other various charges in transit cargo and passenger transportation, ensuring flexibility of transit transportation tariffs according to market conditions, introduction of free permit (entry) system examining its capabilities, adopting long-term complex State programs in the direction of increasing the transit capabilities of our country, as well as carrying out structural changes in the national transport complex by taking advantage of world experience, as well as national In order to increase the competitiveness of public organizations, it is necessary to implement the following measures:

- creation of a common legal framework for transit transportation;
- simplification of border-customs technologies to speed up transit transportation;
- implementation and improvement of integrated border management, modernization of border crossing points;
- to mutually agree on taxes and tariffs related to transit with neighboring countries;
- to mutually agree and harmonize the working regime with the border-customs checkpoints of the neighboring states;
- to mutually agree and harmonize taxes and tariffs related to transit with the neighboring countries located along the transport corridors;
- to consistently develop and improve the transport and transit infrastructure of the country;
- to apply transit guarantee and transit insurance system;
- computerization of relevant workplaces operating at border-customs checkpoints for the purpose of prompt registration, documentation and preliminary data processing of transit shipments;
- increasing the transparency of transportation of transit cargo, publishing joint manuals describing the procedures and rules applied to import, export and transit cargo in cooperation with neighboring countries on transport corridors, opening a website;

- modernization of transport infrastructure in order to ensure the development of transit transport in international transport corridors;
- Technical modernization and improvement of the control regime in the transit corridors using the airspace of Azerbaijan;
- the process of simplifying the border-crossing procedures, which is one of the main components of the transit strategy, their adaptation to procedures at the international level, and increasing transparency during their application;
- apply one-time processing of documents, including phyto-sanitary and veterinary control documents, at border crossing points;
- issuing transit visas at the border, recognizing international certificates for food and livestock products;
- to revise the railway tariffs for passenger and cargo transportation and align them with the unified tariff system of TRASEKA member countries;
- create free economic zones to expand and develop the scope of transit and trade services;
- to organize transport-logistics centers in order to increase the efficiency of transit services and reduce the cost of transportation;
- to mutually harmonize the application of transit and transport related business practices and taxes and fees with neighboring countries;
- to create and develop a regulatory mechanism to resolve any disputes between the participants in the transit process, in accordance with the requirements of the developing market economy.

In our opinion, the mentioned proposals will have a positive effect on increasing the competitiveness of the transport-trade transit sector of Azerbaijan. In the medium-term period, the transformation, denationalization, and privatization of the enterprises with various fields, including the main and auxiliary activities within the transport companies, will be carried out.

The "State Program on the development of the railway transport system in the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2010-2024" approved by the decree of the President of the country dated July 6, 2010 was approved. This program includes restoration and reconstruction of the country's railways, renewal and modernization of railway vehicles, purchase of electric locomotives and steam locomotives, cargo and passenger cars, etc. designed. The construction of the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway line will allow the country's railway network to be included in the European railway network. In addition, the development of the railway line in the North-South corridor is also planned in the medium-term perspective.

The priorities of the development of the transport sector in the medium term are as follows:

- pioneering development of transport, which is the infrastructure of the national economy;
- equal and consistent development of different types of transport of the road-communication complex;
- equal development of freight transport, which realizes inter-farm commodity exchange, and passenger transport, which provides one of the main social needs of the population;
- equal development of international and transit corridors and roads, as well as the country's interregional, urban and intraregional road transport infrastructure;
- Rapid integration of the national transport and road system into the world communication space based on the modernization and modernization of the transport and communication traffic passing through the territory of Azerbaijan and the main means of transport according to world standards;
- Maintaining and strengthening Azerbaijan's leading position in the international and transit transportation of energy carriers during the delivery of hydrocarbons produced in the Caspian region to world markets;

- Leading implementation of TRASEKA, North-South, INOGEYT Programs during the strengthening of Azerbaijan's international transport system;
- Broad diversification of oil and gas export routes produced in Azerbaijan and creation and joint use of new transregional energy corridors with the participation of other Caspian producer countries.

In the XXI century, due to the transition to the information society and its establishment, the formation of electronic government and the development of intellectual potential, increasing socio-economic development has become one of the priority issues. The importance of ICT in the modern era and for future prospects has come to the fore, and it has formed the main provisions of the programs in the field of national activity and electronic strategy of the country. The development of the ICT sector has been identified by the country's leadership as the second priority area after the oil and gas industry.

In our opinion, the measures implemented in the field of development of information and communication technologies and communication should be in the direction of the implementation of necessary technical and technological changes for the performance of electronic document circulation, electronic commerce, provision of electronic services and other such activities. Increasing the speed of providing information and reducing its volume will have a positive effect on the country's competitiveness.

The following tasks are ahead in the field of ICT development:

- = creating an appropriate environment for ensuring the rights of citizens and social institutions to receive, disseminate and use information;
- creation of Electronic Government for implementation of effective, transparent and controllable state administration and local self-government;
- creation of advanced information and communication infrastructure, formation of a single national electronic information space, expansion of information and communication services;
- ensuring the country's information security and creating basic components of the Electronic Government infrastructure;
- integration of the country into the global electronic information space;
- creation of national software tools, development of production of information and communication technologies products (ICT industry);
- increasing the level of training of civil servants on information technologies.

Implementation of the "Electronic Government" State Program in the center of ICT development, implementation and development of the DVB-T digital television broadcasting system in the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan, creation of high-tech regional economic zones, expansion of the provision of banking and financial services in the post offices of "Azerpocht" DM, next generation mobile, wireless, data and more. speeding up the introduction of telecommunication services and granting licenses taking into account the principles of competition, establishing an independent regulatory body under the authority of the state in the field of communication and information technology activities, forming effective market competition on the liberalization of tariff regulation.

Privatization of the state share in joint enterprises operating in the field within the framework of the development of communication and information technologies, improvement of the pre-privatization restructuring and management structure of enterprises declared open for privatization, expansion of the application of international standards, complete digitization of the transmission network and complete electronicization of the switching network within the framework of the modernization of the telephone network, TAE optical line the completion of the construction of the underwater part, the organization of fiber-optic cable communication between the city and district centers of Nakhchivan MR, the creation of an information exchange network of state administration bodies, the organization of digital television broadcasting in the

regions of the country within the framework of the improvement of radio and television broadcasting, the development of new cable television, the broadcasting of programs effective use of satellites, radio and television programs of Nakhchivan MR measures such as the organization of the evacuation have been planned. At the same time, it is planned to create a free economic zone for information technologies - IT Technopark, to apply information communication technologies in the improvement of the education system.

At the same time, in order to improve the supply of electricity, the construction of new thermal and hydropower plants in the country's electric power system, the modernization of existing power units, and the acceleration of work towards increasing power due to alternative energy sources, as well as the commissioning of high-voltage distribution lines to ensure the transmission and distribution of electric power, and it is planned to be equipped with distribution systems and transformer substations for all administrative regions of the republic.

In order to establish a management system in accordance with market economy principles in the production, transmission and distribution of electricity, restructuring measures will be continued in this area.

In order to strengthen financial discipline in the gas supply sector, to create a transparent management structure in accordance with the market economy in the areas of natural gas transportation, gathering and distribution, it is planned to carry out reforms in the relevant directions. So that:

- effective use of natural gas, increasing the level of accounting for its distribution and consumption, and completing the provision of gas meters to the gas consumer population;

- reduction of losses;

- in the direction of the development of the natural gas supply system, improvement of the material and technical base of farms, restoration of main and distribution pipelines, reconstruction of underground gas storages;

- reconstruction of the transportation system of natural gas produced from new fields and increase of receiving capacities, in order to ensure the development of the heat supply sector in stages based on market economy principles, the following goals have been set by "Azeristiliktehzat" JSC:

- restoration, modernization and reconstruction of existing heating stations; - construction of new boiler houses;

- restoration of indoor heating networks;

- implementation of measures for transformation from centralized heat sources to autonomous boiler houses;

- increasing the production capacity of boiler houses by carrying out reconstruction and construction works based on the prepared action plan.

In order to achieve the mentioned goals, it is planned to continue reforms in the following directions in this area.

- improvement of norms, rules and standards on heat supply, taking into account the experience of the countries of the world;

- creation of a favorable environment for investment in the field by implementing institutional measures and wider involvement of the private sector;

- reconstruction of the system by involving ecologically clean, modern effective technologies;

- provision of hot water to consumers along with heat supply; - use of alternative and renewable energy sources, energy saving and environmental protection;

One of the serious problems in the water industry is the poor state of the sewage system. Thus, despite the fact that the sewage system of Baku city has been in use for more than 70 years, during this period no major reconstruction works have been carried out in the area. The same situation can apply to the material and technical base of the water industry. Thus, most of the

main funds and technical equipment have already passed their depreciation period. All these factors create the basis for the frequent occurrence of serious accidents in the water and sewage system and the low level of the quality of the services provided. A similar complex situation prevails in the field of waste water discharge in Azerbaijan, which seriously stimulates the emergence of another problem, as in many cases the existing water resources throughout the country are exposed to extreme pollution. Domestic and industrial waste water from many residential areas of the country is discharged into the surrounding water bodies without undergoing any level of treatment (mechanical, biological, chemical). In order to meet the increasing demand for water and to solve the problems of providing the population with drinking water according to international standards, and to ensure the development of the water sector as a whole, the following goals have been set by "Azersu" SC:

- commissioning of facilities built with a state-guaranteed loan within a specified period;
- Completion of the Oguz-Gabala-Baku water pipeline project;
- Reconstruction of water pipelines, reservoirs, pumping stations, distribution networks, indoor water systems and sewage treatment facilities in Baku city;
- completion of the installation of meters for the purpose of recording the used water;
- raising the collection level to 100% for the services rendered. Regarding the implementation of these measures, it is planned to implement the appropriate policy in the following directions in the sector:
 - continuation of restructuring measures in order to attract investments to the water sector;
 - ensuring payment of the specified service fees with electronic carriers through any bank and post office;
 - provision of sustainable water supply according to world standards;
 - restoration of water and sewage systems in all cities and regional centers of the republic, especially in rural areas, and involvement of the private sector and municipalities in the construction of new lines and facilities.

An important issue is related to production costs in production service areas. In the current environment, such enterprises are trying to reduce production costs by increasing the scale. However, in our opinion, this should be based on the application of the achievements of scientific and technical progress to production. In the medium term, the priority directions of the development of the transport sector will consist of the following:

- improvement of the competitive environment of the transport sector, including the market of transport services;
 - the development of various types of transport in the road-communication complex;
 - development of international and transit corridors and roads in the country, as well as the country's interregional, urban and intraregional road transport infrastructure;
 - Integration of the national transport-road system into the world communication space based on the modernization of transport and communication traffic passing through the territory of Azerbaijan and the main means of transport according to world standards;
 - Creating a reliable multimodal transport system in the Caspian Sea, designing and implementing attractive logistics schemes and the shortest transcontinental routes based on preferential tariffs in the port, marine merchant fleet and railways;
 - Creation of special economic zones on the territory of Azerbaijan, especially in ports, organization of transport and logistics centers with high information and communication security.

RESULTS

Based on a comprehensive study of the current state of production infrastructure development in Azerbaijan, the following conclusions and proposals were put forward:

- Production infrastructure means a single system consisting of a set of energy-fuel, transport, communication-information, water supply, sewage, warehousing, wholesale trade and other areas that serve the efficient operation of individual production areas and make up the external environment of these areas. It is understood. Infrastructure influences output growth by facilitating the division of labor, spreading technology and introducing new organizational methods, or by providing access to larger markets and access to new resources and intermediate products.

- The ability of enterprises providing production services to meet the demand of the main production determines the demand for production services. Demand for production services 1) from the level of income of material production areas; 2) in mutual replacement of used production services; 3) from the number of enterprises producing material goods; 4) depends on the application of innovation.

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MARKETİNQ KOMMUNİKASIYA SİSTEMİNİN TƏKMİLLƏŞDİRİLMƏSİ İSTİQAMƏTLƏRİ

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Qeyd etmək lazımdır ki, bütün firmalar tərəfindən marketingin kommunikasiya sisteminin ənənəvi metodlarının tətbiq edilməsi olduqca baha başa gəlir və lazımı səmərə vermir. Bunun isə bir sıra səbəbləri vardır:

1. Marketingin kommunikasiya tədbirlərinin həyata keçirilməsi zamanı əksər firmalar tərəfindən eyni metodların tətbiq edilməsi istehlakçılarını yorur, onlarda informasiya axınına qarşı marağı azaldır. Təsəvvür etmək çətin deyildir ki, rəqib firmaların oxşar məhsullarının yerüstü şitlərdə, televiziya, radioda təkrar olunan reklamları artıq firmalar, məhsullar haqqında yayılan informasiyaların istehlakçılar tərəfindən qavranılması dərəcəsini xeyli azaldır.

2. İstehlakçı psixologiyasının dəyişməsi. 1990-cı illərdən başlayaraq cəmiyyətdə güclü dəyişikliklər baş verir və bu dəyişikliklərə uyğun olaraq istehlakçıların tipləri, onların psixologiyası, reklam informasiyalarına münasibətləri də dəyişməkdədir. Müasir istehlakçı artıq istehsalçı ilə ikitərəfli interaktiv təmasda olmağa can atır, onun haqqında daha çox məlumat əldə etməyə çalışır. Bu tip istehlakçılar güclü sosial mövqeyə malik olan firmalara üstünlük verirlər. Belə istehlakçılar daha çox fərdi və səmərələşdirici xarakterə malik olurlar və istehlakı dəyərli fəaliyyət növü hesab edirlər, ideya liderlərinə xüsusi diqqət yetirirlər.

3. Ənənəvi kommunikasiya metodları istehlakın baş verən fərdiləşməsinə uyğun gəlmir.

4. Televiziya reklamının baha olması və effektivliyinin azalmağa doğru meyl etməsi. Video dövründə yaşayan istehlakçılar televiziya informasiyasının şifrə açmasını öyrənmişlər və bu cür məlumatlara əvvəllərdə olduğu kimi reaksiya vermirlər. Çoxlu sayda telekanallar və istənilən anda onları dəyişmək imkanı yaranmışdır. Bununla yanaşı, maraqlı televiziya verilişlərində və filmlərin nümayişi zamanı reklamların həddən çox uzunmüddətli olması və çox tez-tez təkrarlanması da tamaşaçılarda reklama olan marağı azaldır. Bütün bunlar tamaşaçıda istədiyi anda telekanalı çevirmək və reklama baxmamaq, reklam dövründə digər kanalda hansısa maraqlı bir verilişdən xəbərdar olmaq fikrini formalaşdırır. Televiziya reklamının dəyəri durmadan artır və bunun əksinə olaraq onun effektivliyi getdikcə aşağı düşür. Kütləvi reklamın effektivliyinin kəskin sürətdə aşağı düşməsi bir vaxtlar qərb ölkələrinin reklamçıları üçün gözlənilməz olmuşdu. Görünür, televiziya reklamının xüsusi, yüksək rola malik olduğu Azərbaycanın reklam bazarı da yaxın dövrlərdə belə bir şəraiti yaşamaq olacaqdır.

5. Ənənəvi kommunikasiya metodları yeni informasiya kanallarını nəzərə almır. İnternetin və digər informasiya texnologiyalarının təsiri altında Kütləvi İnformasiya Vasitələrində (KİV) ciddi dəyişikliklər baş vermiş, informasiya yayımının yeni kanalları meydana gəlmiş, interaktiv mediya yaranmış, ixtisaslaşmış KİV inkişaf etməyə başlamışdır.

6. Ənənəvi kommunikasiya sisteminin çox xərc tutumlu olması. Son onilliklərdə beynəlxalq bazarlarda, xüsusən də yeni bazarlarda marketing məsələlərinin az xərc tutumlu üsullarla həll edilməsi zəruriyyəti yaranmışdır.

Bütün bu qeyd olunan problemlərin və məsələlərin həll edilməsi məqsədilə inteqrasiya olunmuş marketing kommunikasiyası sistemi meydana gəlmişdir.

İnteqrasiya olunmuş marketing kommunikasiyası (İOMK). Bu kommunikasiyaya görə, firma özü və məhsulu haqqında istehlakçılarda dəqiq, ardıcıl və inamlı təsəvvür yaratmaq məqsədilə özünün çoxsaylı kommunikasiya kanallarını - reklam, şəxsi satış, satışın həvəsləndirilməsi, ictimaiyyətlə əlaqə, birbaşa marketing, malların qablaşdırılması və s. bu kimi məsələləri təhlil edir, əlaqələndirir.

İOMK-köhnə problemlərə yeni baxış, yeni yanaşma konsepsiyasıdır. Bu konsepsiya:

- birincisi, vahid maliyyələşmə üsulu kimi tətbiq edilir ki, bu da kommunikasiyanın ayrı-ayrı istiqamətləri üzrə fərdi büdcə hesablanmasını və bu sahədə yaranan mübarizələri aradan qaldırır;
- ikincisi, əmtənin irəlilədilməsini təmin edən kommunikasiya tədbirlərinin həyata keçirilməsi üzrə vahid idarəetmə mərkəzi yaratmağa imkan verir;
- üçüncüsü, kommunikasiya tədbirləri üzrə kampaniyanın həyata keçirilməsində vahid planlaşdırmanın tətbiq edilməsini nəzərdə tutulur ki, bu da məhsul haqqında cəmiyyətə, istehlakçılara müxtəlif, bəzən də yanlış məlumatların ötürülməsinin qarşısını alır;
- dördüncüsü, ən vacibi odur ki, kommunikasiya sisteminin yaradılması və həyata keçirilməsində bu yanaşma ənənəvi metodlara nisbətən təqribən 2 dəfə ucuz başa gəlir. Bu zaman xərclərin azaldılması reallıq təşkil edir, çünki, İOMK sistemi, reklamın birbaşa televiziyada yerləşdirilməsindən imtina etməyi nəzərdə tutur.

Bu gün tələbatın formalaşması və satışın həvəsləndirilməsində İOMK-nın rolunu yüksək qiymətləndirirlər. Əksər mütəxəssislər İOMK-nı marketing məsələlərinin həll edilməsinin ən səmərəli üsulu kimi qiymətləndirirlər. Çox güman ki, yaxın 25 il müddətində bu konsepsiya qorunub saxlanacaq və daha da inkişaf edəcəkdir.

Eyni zamanda, qeyd etmək lazımdır ki, marketingin kommunikasiya tədbirlərinin vahid sistem halında, inteqrasiya olunmuş şəkildə tətbiq edilməsi ideyası heç də yeni ideya deyildir. Hələ keçən əsrin 50-ci illərində «Martsteller İnc» kompaniyası İOMK-dan istifadə etməyə başlamışdır. O zaman bu konsepsiya «total kommunikasiya» adlandırılırdı. Kompaniyanın müştərilərinin demək olar ki, yarısı onun PR, reklam və malın irəlilədilməsi üzrə həyata keçirdiyi xidmətlərdən istifadə edirdilər. Lakin həmin dövrdə inteqrasiya olunmuş marketing kommunikasiyası geniş tətbiq olunmadı və bu ideya yaşamadı.

Ənənəvi kommunikasiya sisteminin həyata keçirilməsində yeni yanaşma lazım olmadı. Çünki özünün ilk illərində televiziya reklamı yüksək effektivini göstərməyə başladı. Keçən əsrin 50-ci illərində məhz televiziya reklamı sayəsində istehlakçı tələbi durmadan, sürətlə artmağa başlamışdı. O zaman çoxlu pul xərcləmək düzgün sayılırdı. Məhz televiziya reklamı istehlakçıların şüurunda inqilab etdi, onları çoxlu pul xərcləməyə həvəsləndirdi. İOMK ideyası yalnız 2000-cı illərdən aktualıq kəsb etməyə başlamışdır.

Qeyd etmək lazımdır ki, İOMK-nın mahiyyətini nəzəri cəhətdən dolğun izah etmək olduqca çətinidir. Lakin bu konsepsiyadan istifadə etməklə işləməyi öyrənmək daha çətinidir. Bu zaman yol verilən əsas səhvlərdən biri də ondan ibarətdir ki, İOMK bəzən reklamı da nəzərdə tutan «Pablik Rileyşnz» proqramı ilə eyniləşdirilir. Əlbəttə məhsulun istehlak xüsusiyyətlərini və digər xarakterik cəhətlərini istehlakçılara çatdıran reklamlarla istehlakçıların imicini yüksəltməyə xidmət edən PR

proqramının əlaqəli şəkildə tətbiq edilməsi ümumilikdə istehsalçı və məhsul haqqında təsəvvür yaradır və müəssisənin marketing fəaliyyətinə müsbət təsir göstərir. Lakin bu, heç də İOMK demək deyildir.

Müasir kommunikasiyaların əksəriyyətində bu cür inteqrasiya artıq baş verməkdədir. İnteqrasiya olunmuş kommunikasiya sisteminin həyata keçirilməsi, reklam, ictimaiyyətlə əlaqə, satışın stimullaşdırılması və s. bu kimi istiqamətlər üzrə ayrı-ayrı şöbələr, agentliklərlə işləməkdən daha asandır. İOMK modelində hər il üzrə planlaşdırma yenidən aparılır və bu zaman köhnə ilin kommunikasiya və büdcə planlarından istifadə edilmir. Bu model üzrə planlaşdırmanın fərqləndirici xüsusiyyəti ondan ibarətdir ki, ilk növbədə kommunikasiyanın məqsədi müəyyənləşdirilir. Sonra isə həmin məqsədə uyğun gələn kommunikasiya tədbirləri hazırlanıb həyata keçirilir. Planlaşdırmanın bu səviyyəsində ictimaiyyətlə əlaqə İOMK-nın digər istiqamətləri ilə eyni səviyyədə həyata keçirilir. Onların hər birinin güclü tərəfləri mövcuddur və onlar müxtəlif kommunikasiya problemlərinin həllində səmərəli şəkildə istifadə oluna bilərlər.

Azərbaycanda fəaliyyət göstərən kompaniyalar, müəssisə və firmalar hal-hazırkı dövrdə satış konsepsiyasından marketing konsepsiyasına keçid dövrünü yaşayırlar. Onların əksəriyyəti hələ ki, ənənəvi marketing nəzəriyyəsindən istifadə etməklə ictimaiyyətlə əlaqənin ənənəvi metodlarını tətbiq edirlər. Respublikada kütləvi kommunikasiya tədbirləri bu gün daha çox ənənəvi marketing konsepsiyası çərçivəsində həyata keçirilən tədbirlərə uyğun gəlir. Bütün bunlara baxmayaraq artıq Azərbaycanın spesifik xüsusiyyətləri yeni ideyalar irəli sürməyə, müasir kommunikasiya metodlarını tətbiq etməyə, yeniliklərə meyilli olmağa imkan verir.

Dünya bazar sistemi, o cümlədən, sahibkarların kommunikasiya fəaliyyəti daima inkişaf etməkdə, təkmilləşməkdədir. Bu proses öz növbəsində marketingin kommunikasiya sisteminin dəyişməsinə, durmadan təkmilləşdirilməsinə tələb edir. Artıq istehlakçılar öz maddi ehtiyaclarını ənənəvi üsullarla, mağazalara gedib mal almaq qaydasında ödəməklə kifayətlənmirlər. Onlar üçün kompüter arxasında əyləşib hər hansı bir mağazanın saytını açmaqla lazım olan malı almaq daha maraqlı görünür.

Kommunikasiya sisteminin müxtəlif elementləri üzrə informasiya axınının güclənməsi, yeni informasiya yayımı formalarının meydana gəlməsi, xüsusilə də internetin bu sistemə daxil olması kommunikasiya sisteminin dəyişməsi meyllərini gücləndirmiş, yeni, işgüzar kommunikasiyanın müasir sisteminin yaranmasına və tətbiq edilməsinə ciddi təkan vermişdir.

Bu gün internet marketingin kommunikasiya sisteminin ayrılmaz hissəsinə çevrilmişdir. Əlbətdə, bu, başadüşüləndir. Çünki məhz internet marketşünaslara məqsədli auditoriyaya daha yaxın olmağa, hər bir istehlakçının evinə daxil olmağa imkan verir, daha effektiv kommunikasiya tədbiri kimi çıxış edir. Mütəxəssislər yaxşı bilirlər ki, istehlakçılarla əlaqə nə qədər yaxın, birbaşa olsa, onun effektivliyi də bir o qədər yüksək olar, informasiya ötürülməsi yolunda mövcud olan xətlər xeyli azalar. Ən vacibi odur ki, internet məqsədli auditoriya barədə lazım olan zəruri informasiya əldə etməyə imkan verir.

Hal-hazırda bir çox firmalar internet-bizneslə məşğul olmağa, elektron ticarəti metodlarını tətbiq etməyə çalışırlar. Lakin bunu hansı formada tətbiq etməyi müəyyənləşdirmək olduqca çətinidir.

Biznes fəaliyyətinin formalaşması və inkişafı baxımından internet-layihələrin bütün növlərini şərti olaraq iki qrupa bölmək olar.

Birinci qrup korporativ biznesin bütün internet-layihələrini aid etmək olar. Korporativ layihələr adlandırılan bu layihələr artıq mövcud olan və ənənəvi marketing konsepsiyası əsasında həyata keçirilən biznes fəaliyyətinin elektron sistem tətbiq edilməklə genişləndirilməsini nəzərdə tutur.

İkinci qrup internet-layihələrin əsas xüsusiyyəti onların qeyri korporativ xarakterə malik olmasıdır ki, bu halda layihənin əsasını artıq mövcud olan biznes fəaliyyəti deyil, yeni yaranan, yalnız internet-layihələrdə mövcud olan biznes fəaliyyəti təşkil edir.

İnternet kommunikasiya sistemində çox maraqlı, yeni bir istiqamətdir və satıcılar ondan istifadə etməklə öz məhsullarını satmağa, real alıcı kütləsini çoxaltmağa çalışırlar. Kommunikasiya sistemində internetdən istifadə yeni layihələr tətbiq edilməklə getdikcə təkmilləşir və sürətlə inkişaf edir.

Müasir dövrə kommunikasiya mütəxəssisləri məqsədli auditoriyaya təsir göstərməyin yeni, təkmilləşdirilmiş, daha səmərəli yollarını axtarırlar. Əvvəllər istehsalçılar birbaşa reklamın həyata keçirilməsinə əsaslanan ATL kommunikasiya texnologiyasına üstünlük verirdilər. Bu gün isə məqsədli auditoriyaya təsir etmənin yeni texnologiyası-BTL texnologiya (Belov The line Technology) məqsədli auditoriyaya təsir etmə metodlarının inteqrasiya olunmuş sistemi kimi izah edilir. Bu sistema birbaşa reklam metodlarından başqa digər təsir metodları da daxil edilir.

BTL texnologiya sisteminə daxil olan metodlara marağın yüksəlməsi onunla izah edilir ki, artıq istehlakçılar əmtənin irəlilədilməsinin ənənəvi metodlarına getdikcə daha az inanırlar. Adi reklam lazımı səviyyədə əks əlaqə yaratmağa imkan vermir və kommunikasiya əlaqələri birtərəfli xarakter daşıyır. Müasir istehlakçı dialoqa girməyə, satıcı ilə təmasda olmağa ehtiyac hiss edir və məhz BTL texnologiya tədbirləri bu cür qarşılıqlı əlaqənin yaradılmasına imkan verir.

Hal-hazırda BTL texnologiyasının bir sıra metodları tətbiq edilir. Onlardan ən geniş istifadə edilənlərindən biri bazara yeni brendin çıxarılması, özgənin məhsul markasının alınması, məhsul çeşidinin genişləndirilməsi, malın qablaşdırılmasında dəyişiklik edilməsi və s. ibarətdir. Bu metodun ən effektiv üsullarından biri mal alışına görə hədiyyə verilməsidir.

Yeni məhsul bazara çıxarılanda istehsalçılar məqsədli auditoriyaya malın nümunəsinin pulsuz paylanması metodundan da tez-tez istifadə edirlər. Bu metodun mahiyyəti ondan ibarətdir ki, istehlakçıya yeni məhsulu yoxlamaq imkanı verilir.

Bu gün uduşlu oyunların (müsabiqələr, lotoreyalar, mükafatların oynanılması və s.) həyata keçirilməsi üsullarından da aktiv surətdə istifadə olunur.

Satışın stimullaşdırılmasının effektiv metodları arasında kütləvi-əyləncəli tədbirlərin həyata keçirilməsini xüsusi qeyd etmək olar. Lakin bu cür tədbirlərin həyata keçirilməsi böyük xərc tələb edir və yalnız böyük kompaniyalar belə tədbirləri həyata keçirmək imkanına malik olurlar. Odur ki, əksər firmalar satışın güzəştli şərtlərlə həyata keçirilməsinə daha çox üstünlük verirlər.

Beləliklə, qeyd etmək lazımdır ki, marketinqin kommunikasiya sistemi daima təkmilləşir, onda ciddi dəyişikliklər baş verir. Bu dəyişikliklər firmalara bazarda rəqabət üstünlüyü əldə etməyə, kommunikasiya tədbirlərini effektivliyinin yüksəltməyə, ümumilikdə malın irəlilədilməsini təmin etməyə imkan verir.

Müasir dövrdə marketinq yalnız keyfiyyətli məhsul yaradılması, ona cəlbedici qiymət müəyyənləşdirilməsi, səmərəli bölgü və satış kanallarından istifadə edilməsi ilə kifayətlənmir. Firmalar istehsal etdikləri məhsulların müvəffəqiyyətli satışını təmin etməli, onlara olan istehlakçı tələbatının hər vasitə ilə artırılmasına nail olmalıdırlar. Bunlar isə öz növbəsində marketinqin kommunikasiya sisteminin tətbiq edilməsini, onun elementləri üzrə kompleks tədbirlərin həyata keçirilməsini tələb edir.

Əmtələrin irəlilədilməsinin ümumi büdcəsinin hesablanmasında müxtəlif metodlardan istifadə edilir:

1. Mövcüd vəsaitlərdən hesablama metodu.
2. Satışın məbləğinə nisbətən faizlə hesablama metodu.
3. Qarşıya qoyulan məqsədlərdən və vəzifələrdən asılı olaraq hesablama metodu.
4. Rəqiblərə əsaslanan hesablama metodu.
5. Xərclərin planlaşdırılması əsasında hesablama metodu.

Qeyd etmək lazımdır ki, beşinci hesablama metodu adətən ikinci yanaşma zamanı, yeni ayrı-ayrı stimullaşdırma tələbləri üzrə büdcə hesablanıldıqda daha çox istifadə edilir.

Ümumiyyətlə isə nəzərə almaq lazımdır ki, qeyd olunan metodlar əsasında əmtənin irəlilədilməsinin ümumi büdcəsinin hesablanması nisbi xarakter daşıyır, olduqca çətin və mürəkkəb

bir məsələdir. Firmaların rəhbərləri heç bir zaman dəqiq müəyyənləşdirə bilmirlər ki, əmtəənin irəlilədilməsinin ümumi büdcəsinin optimal həcmi nə qədər olmalıdır. Ümumiyyətlə isə sahənin və məhsulun xarakterindən asılı olaraq stimullaşdırma xərclərinin səviyyəsi müxtəlif olur. Əmtəənin irəlilədilməsi üzrə ümumi büdcə hesablandıqdan sonra firma həmin vəsaitin ayrı-ayrı stimullaşdırma tədbirləri üzrə bölüşdürülməsini həyata keçirir. Bunun üçün isə əmtəənin irəlilədilməsinin proqramını işləyib hazırlamaq lazım gəlir. Eyni bir sahədə fəaliyyət göstərən firmalar əmtəənin irəlilədilməsinin kompleks-proqramını müxtəlif cür hazırlayırlar. Bəzi firmalar vəsaitlərin əksər hissəsini reklama xərclədikləri halda, digərləri şəxsi satışa və birbaşa marketingə daha çox üstünlük verirlər.

Əmtəənin irəlilədilməsi üzrə stimullaşdırma vasitələri proqramda çox diqqətlə, düşünülmüş şəkildə, ardıcılıqla əks olunurlar. Bu vasitələrin hər biri üzrə həyata keçirilməsi nəzərdə tutulan kompleks tədbirlər proqramı da ardıcılıqla qeyd olunur, onların həyata keçirilməsi vaxtı, müddəti və dövrü, icraçıları müəyyənləşdirilir, xərcləri hesablanır. Bu tədbirlər bəzən vaxt baxımından üst-üstə düşür, bəzən isə biri digərini tamamlayır. Ona görə də proqram tərtib olunarkən orada nəzərdə tutulan müxtəlif istiqamətli tədbirlər bir-biri ilə əlaqələndirilir və uzlaşdırılır.

Firmalar daima əmtəənin irəlilədilməsi üzrə hazırladıqları proqramları təkmilləşdirməyə, bir stimullaşdırma vasitəsinə digərilə əvəz etməyə çalışırlar. Stimullaşdırmanın effektivliyini yüksəltməyin yollarını və üsullarını axtarırlar.

Bu və ya digər stimullaşdırma vasitələrinin seçilməsinə çoxlu sayda amillər, təsir göstərdiyindən, onlar əmtəələrin irəlilədilməsinin kompleks proqramının işlənilməsində hazırlanmasında nəzərə alınırırlar.

F. Kottler bu cür amilləri dörd müxtəlif qrupa bölür:

1. Bazarın və ya məhsulun tipi.
2. Əmtəənin irəli itələnməsi strategiyası və yaxud alıcıların məhsula cəlb edilməsi strategiyası.
3. Alıcıların hazırlıq dərəcəsi.
4. Məhsulun həyat dövrünün mərhələləri.

Bazarın və ya məhsulun tipi. Bazarın və ya məhsulun xarakterindən asılı olaraq müxtəlif stimullaşdırma vasitələrinin effektivliyi də dəyişir və məhz buna görə, firmalar müxtəlif xarakterli məhsullar üzrə bu və ya digər stimullaşdırma vasitələrinə daha çox üstünlük verirlər. Bunu aşağıdakı şəkildən daha aydın görmək olar:

Şəkil 1. İstehlak malları və istehsal təyinatlı məhsullar bazarında stimullaşdırma vasitələrinin nisbi effektivliyi.

Şəkildən göründüyü kimi istehlak mallarının stimullaşdırılmasını həyata keçirən firmalar reklama daha çox üstünlük verirlər, nəinki satışın həvəsləndirilməsinə və şəxsi satışa. Kütləvi istehlak mallarının xüsusiyyətlərindən, onların istehlakçılarının sayının çoxluğundan asılı olaraq bu bazarlarda reklam daha böyük rol oynayır və güclü təsirə malik olur. İstehsal təyinatlı məhsullar istehsal edən firmalar isə stimullaşdırma vasitələrindən şəxsi satışa daha çox üstünlük verirlər, daha sonra satışın həvəsləndirilməsinə, ondan sonra reklama və nəhayət ictimaiyyətlə əlaqəyə vəsait xərcləyirlər. Şəxsi satış az sayda alıcıları olan bahalı malların satışında daha səmərəli hesab olunur.

Əmtənin irəli itələnməsi strategiyası və yaxud alıcıların cəlb edilməsi strategiyası. Firmalar iki müxtəlif strategiyadan istifadə etməklə məhsullarının satışını və onun stimullaşdırılmasını həyata keçirirlər. Birinci halda satışın həvəsləndirilməsi tədbirlərindən istifadə etməklə istehsalçılar məhsullarını topdan tacirlərə, onlar isə pərakəndə tacirlərə, pərakəndə tacirlər isə istehsalçılara satmağa çalışırlar. İkinci halda isə istehsalçılar reklam tədbirlərindən istifadə etməklə məhsullarına tələbat formalaşdırmağa və bununla da istehlakçıları məhsula cəlb etməyə səy göstəririlər. Bu halda istehlakçılar məhsulu pərakəndə tacirlərdən, pərakəndə tacirlər topdan tacirlərdən, onlar isə istehsalçılardan almağa çalışırlar.

Alıcıların hazırlıq səviyyəsi, mal alışına hazır olmaları onların məlumatlılıq səviyyəsindən çox asılıdır. Məlumatlıq səviyyəsinin və məhsul haqqında biliyin artırılmasında isə reklam və ictimaiyyətlə əlaqənin təsiri olduqca böyükdür. Mallara üstünlük verilməsində və istehlakçıları mal alışına inandırmaqda şəxsi satış daha böyük rol oynayır.

Məhsulun həyat dövrünün mərhələləri. Əmtənin irəlilədilməsi üzrə stimullaşdırma tədbirləri məhsulun həyat dövrünün mərhələləri ilə sıx əlaqəlidir və onlardan hər hansı birinin seçilməsi məhsulun hansı mərhələdə olmasına uyğun olaraq həyata keçirilir. Məhsulun həyat dövrünün bazara çıxarılma mərhələsində reklamdən istifadə etmək daha səmərəli hesab olunur. Həyat dövrünün inkişaf mərhələsində reklam və ictimaiyyətlə əlaqə öz güclü təsirini qoruyub saxlayır. Yetkinlik mərhələsində isə satışın həvəsləndirilməsi tədbirlərindən istifadə etmək daha məqsəduyğun hesab olunur.

Beləliklə, qeyd etmək lazımdır ki, əmtəələrin irəlilədilməsinin ümumi büdcəsinin və proqramının işlənilib hazırlanması müəssisənin marketinq fəaliyyətinin daha səmərəli həyata keçirilməsində olduqca mühüm rol oynayır və firmalar stimullaşdırmanın kompleks proqramının işlənilib hazırlanmasında istifadə edilən metodları və üsulları daima təkmilləşdirməyə cəhd göstərirlər.

Digital Marketing: Key Strategy in Global Economy

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The paper analyses the importance of digital marketing at the global market. The aim of the paper is to show the importance of digital marketing for modern organizations who are operating at Georgian and international market. Also, how digital marketing is able to influence decision making process and how it can affect buying decision. The paper also includes research, that shows how digital marketing can affect the decision making process. Moreover, the international practice is shown according to the survey conducted by “PwC Total Retail Report”. For better understanding and proper evaluation of digital marketing the case of TeliaSonera Company is discussed, the paper analyses the net sales and net incomes of the company during 2002-2017 years.

Key words: Digital Marketing, International Business, Globalization.

In the conditions of modern globalization, technological development is gaining more and more importance. Modern technologies have changed the whole world, contributed to the development of business connections, the realization of scientific potential and the deepening of political-economic relations between nations. Information technologies, including the Internet, have changed people's lives, relationships and, accordingly, business [1, p. 7]. In recent years, the attitude of companies to new technologies, especially the Internet, has changed significantly, because it has a great impact on the activities of companies [2, p. 7]. The Internet has become an important means of creating, offering and selling products. Modern organizations actively use the Internet because it has many positive aspects. Organizations save time and money by using interns. Marketing activities of many modern organizations are related to the extensive use of the Internet. They create their own website, organize promotions and contests on the Internet, have representation in various social networks, communicate with customers and get their opinion. Internet is becoming more and more attractive for modern organizations as an effective means of public relations.

In Georgia, as in the whole world, the future belongs only to those companies that will adapt to the changing economic environment. One of the tools for adapting to such an environment is the Internet. Digital marketing is created through the Internet, which offers different opportunities to businesses and allows to use completely new ways and means for marketing. It can be considered the largest and cheapest informational resource. Internet space allows business to reveal its potential with minimal costs, namely to create a product, offer it to customers, sell it, etc. [3, p. 7]. It can be said freely that XXI is the century of digital marketing because most of the population of the earth is connected to social network and internet. Internet and social media allow you to connect with the desired person from anywhere in the world, understand and share the current news in the world. Today, digital marketing has become one of the most powerful tools in business. The reason for this is its flexible features, in particular, the fact that organizations have a two-way communication with the customer. In Georgia, digital marketing, namely Facebook and Instagram, is currently being used, which allows Georgian business to develop and implement various strategies in the Internet space. This is one of the effective means of increasing awareness and contact with the target audience.

A company working on the Internet market must identify target groups of customers that it can satisfy better than others, and then offer its products in such a way that the image of its company becomes recognizable to the target audience. Digital marketing has many advantages that are very flexible and help companies to do business:

- Low cost - web space and social media allow reaching a wide audience with low costs.
- Measurability - allows to determine the size of the potential audience. It's also easy to measure whether an ad has resulted in an increase in sales or traffic.
- Format - it can be image, video, audio, link, presentation and others. Unlike traditional media, the web provides a unique opportunity to create interactive advertising.
- Targeting - through the social network it is easy to select and segment the target audience by demographic, geographic, interests. It is possible to count how many times a specific user saw this or that advertisement and in what order.
- Coverage - With the web it is possible to cover global and local markets. It is accessible and universal for everyone.
- Speed - once the communication design is prepared, it can be published immediately. In addition, the customer on the web can at any time change the course of his campaign, the design of the advertisement or other details, which traditional advertising media does not have.

Forms of Internet communication have individual characteristics, the effectiveness of which depends on such factors as: the company's goal, tasks and financial capabilities, characteristics of goods, consumer behavior, and others. Therefore, the optimal form of communication should be selected after a purposeful analysis of the external and internal world of the company. There are various social media platforms: Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, Twitter, Pinterest, Youtube and Wikis. For companies that use social media, the most popular are: Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and blogs, which are actively used in digital marketing. Facebook is the world's most widespread social network. In fact, it has no competitor. The platform helps companies to have continuous contact with customers. Many businesses today find advertising on Facebook quite profitable. In order to better study modern approaches, we used the company Geocell, because it is one of the innovative companies in the Georgian market that actively uses digital marketing, in particular - social media. The company appeared on the Georgian market in 1996 and in a short time completely changed the daily life of people.

Geocell is one of the first companies that started using digital marketing for marketing activities. For this purpose, I conducted a study, the purpose of which was to determine the impact of digital marketing on the company's customers. A total of 120 respondents were interviewed. User demographics were analyzed and the following table shows how the results were distributed:

Results or respondents' Demographic Data

		quantity	%
sex	Female	60	50
	Male	60	50
	sum	120	100
age			%
	18-25	30	25
	25-35	34	28
	36-45	29	24
	46-55	25	21
	55+	2	2
	sum	120	100
Frequent of internet use			%
	everyday	88	73
	Once a week	17	14
	Twice a week	13	11
	Once a month	2	2
		sum	120

The purpose of this study was to understand the impact of digital marketing on the consumer's decision-making process, as well as the areas that the company should pay attention to and where there is a need to use more digital media. 33% of respondents report that digital marketing has a major impact on their purchasing decisions. In particular, reviews and comments on this or that product in social media influence their purchase. And 41% of respondents say that thanks to digital marketing, the attitude towards the brand has changed. To see the role of digital marketing more clearly, let's take a look at Teliasonera's sales. In the early 2000s, when the social revolution began and the world became familiar with digital marketing, Teliasonera Group did not lag behind in innovation and started promoting its product through digital marketing. Below is the company's net sales data since 2002.

According to Teliasonera data, when the company started actively using digital marketing after around 2002, it had a positive impact on the company's sales. The company was particularly

active in Georgia in 2002-2009. Now the market has become more competitive and the company is experiencing a decrease in sales. It is necessary for him to focus more on digital marketing, which allows him to understand the opinion of the customer and try to satisfy their demands, needs and desires.

Also, according to the data presented by the company, blue marketing after 2002, in particular social media, had a positive impact on the customer. Both sales and revenues have increased as a result of using digital marketing. The company was quite active and innovative in Georgia in 2002-2009. Today, the market has become much more competitive and the company must spend more energy on digital marketing to attract customers and not lose existing customers. It is necessary for the company to understand the customer's opinion and take into account its future activities in order to be competitive in today's environment.

Based on the presented Teliasonera reports, initially there was a drop in net profit, i.e. the company went into losses, and when it started using digital marketing, the company's revenue increased. Digital marketing has a significant impact on a company's revenue, especially social media. Social media has developed a lot and today it is quite a powerful tool, it is the main component of marketing strategies of organizations[8]. According to the PwC total retail survey 2016, 45% of global respondents believe that reading reviews and comments influences their decision. If a blogger shares a post on social media, be it Facebook or Instagram, and reviews what a good and affordable product is, his visitors are largely interested in this product and buy it. As mentioned in the research, social media is a great influencer and it provides more information to the user. According to a study conducted by PwC, 78% of respondents have been influenced by social media at least once. 43% say that communication with their favorite brand had a positive effect on their attitude towards the brand. And 68% indicated that two-way communication led to their greater respect and loyalty to the brand.

As research shows, digital marketing offers many benefits and most importantly, with minimal costs. Today, when the majority of the world's population is hooked on social media and uses the Internet on a daily basis, the role of digital marketing has also increased significantly due to this factor. Therefore, it is necessary for modern companies to pay great attention to digital marketing and use it as one of the important marketing tools. It is useful for all types of businesses as it has a flexible working environment. Thanks to its positive characteristics, it is possible to reach the maximum result with small measurements. Due to the many positive features of digital marketing, it is even vital for modern companies to use it.

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Pedagogical Sciences

МАССОВЫЙ ОТКРЫТЫЙ ОНЛАЙН КУРС — ДИНАМИЧНО РАЗВИВАЮЩАЯСЯ ФОРМА СОВРЕМЕННОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

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Эффективным показателем инновационной экономики обозначены тренды развития вузовской науки. Совершенствование системы образования рассматривается как одна из стратегически важных направлений стратегий Казахстана.

Развитие и наращивание ресурсного потенциала образования и науки становятся возможными благодаря осознанию руководством страны значимости развития системы образования путем всесторонней поддержки и проведении реформ [1].

Современное общество информационных (цифровых) технологий, так называемой постиндустриальной цивилизации, отличается от индустриального общества конца XIX—середины XX века в большей степени заинтересованностью в том, чтобы его граждане были способны независимо самостоятельно действовать, принимать решения, быть готовыми к изменяющимся условиям жизни [2].

Сейчас все большую популярность получает онлайн образование. С появлением материально-технической и информационной базы образование начало приобретать открытый характер. Ведущие мировые вузы стали выкладывать свои учебные ресурсы в открытый доступ, что привлекает людей, не имеющих возможности обучаться в престижных вузах, но желающих получать качественные знания. Одни лишь лекции не способны должным образом структурировать поставляемые знания, поэтому разрабатываются полноценные интерактивные курсы по различным предметам, которые включают лекции, практические занятия и проверку полученных знаний, навыков.

Всемирная конференция по открытым образовательным ресурсам (OER), состоявшаяся с 20 по 22 июня 2012 года, приняла Парижскую декларацию об OER, призывающую правительства поддержать разработку и использование открытых образовательных ресурсов. В декларации, принятой Генеральной Ассамблеей, указывалось, что одним из наиболее важных результатов является то, что официальные представители стран-участниц согласились с необходимостью принятия законодательства, обеспечивающего широкое внедрение «открытой лицензии» на практике, таким образом материалы, размещенные на различных порталах OER, должны быть бесплатными с возможностью доступа для всех желающих.

Распространение массовых открытых онлайн курсов привело к формированию новой и уникальной образовательной парадигмы, с использованием дистанционных технологий, создавая единую многонациональную информационную среду в образовании. С развитием MOOK, происходит модернизация онлайн-курсов за счет развития и улучшения информационных технологий. За последнее десятилетие появилось множество разнообразных приложений и платформ, помогающих создать общую виртуальную среду, интуитивно понятную пользователям.

Современная высокотехнологичная жизнь с постоянно возникающими новыми вызовами во всех сферах человеческой жизнедеятельности диктует необходимость постоянного и непрерывного личностного и профессионального развития каждого члена общества. Развитие информационных технологий, представленное в соответствии с рисунком 1, способствует модернизации образовательных технологий и системы образования в целом. В этой связи достаточно перспективным направлением является самообразование в рамках массовых образовательных онлайн-курсов [3].

Рисунок 1. Развитие образовательных технологий

Массовый открытый онлайн курс представляет собой интернет-курс, изучать который может неограниченное количество участников. MOOK-и включают как традиционные материалы, такие как заснятые видео-лекции и теоретический текстовый материал, вместе с тем многие из них предоставляют интерактивные формы подачи и закрепления материала, а также включают в себя средства общения между студентами, и преподавателями. MOOK-и представляют собой относительно новый подход в образовании, выделенный в отдельное понятие в 2008 году и получивший популярность в 2012 [4]. Проанализируем понятие «массовый открытый онлайн курс». Массовый означает, что курс не рассчитан на определённое количество людей, проходить его может любое количество пользователей. Самые популярные курсы собирают по миллиону студентов [5].

Открытый подразумевает, что курс открыт для любого желающего, для его прохождения не требуется сдачи каких-либо дополнительных экзаменов и собеседований. Не важно, в какой стране проживает человек, в каком социальном и общественном статусе он находится. Отдельные курсы могут быть ограничены в связи со спецификой предмета по религиозному принципу или по возрастному. Обязательным условием является открытая регистрация. Стоит заметить, что ранние MOOK распространяли свои курсы под открытой лицензией, что позволяло на бесплатной основе использовать их для своих целей. Многие современные MOOK используют закрытые лицензии, сохраняя при этом бесплатный доступ для обучающихся [6].

Онлайн означает, что курс проходит посредством интернета технологий. Все действия пользователя происходят реальном времени.

Курс предполагает комплексное, целенаправленное изучение определённого материала, с его закреплением и проверкой. Во многих курсах предоставляются сертификаты.

Разобрав основные понятия, можно перейти к основным концепциям массовых открытых онлайн курсов, которые отражают специфику MOOC.

Открытые образовательные ресурсы, OOP (Open Educational Resources, OER) - это ресурсы, предназначенные для преподавания, обучения и научных исследований, они являются общедоступными и выпускаются под открытой лицензией, которая позволяет неограниченный или минимальный доступ, использование, преобразование, повторное использование и распространение материалов ресурса[7].

Коннекционизм моделирует мыслительные или поведенческие явления процессами становления в сетях из связанных между собой простых элементов. Основным принципом коннекционизма является предположение, что психологические явления могут быть описаны сетью простых элементов, связанных друг с другом. Отношения и формы элементов могут варьироваться от модели к модели. Например, элементы в сети могут представлять нейроны, а соединения могут представлять синапсы[8].

Открытые данные - это концепция, отражающая мнение о том, что определенные данные должны быть свободно доступны для использования и последующего выпуска без ограничения авторским правом, патентами и другими механизмами контроля.

"Игрофикация - применение подходов, характерных для компьютерных игр в программных инструментах для неигровых процессов с целью привлечения пользователей и потребителей, повышения их вовлеченности в решение прикладных задач, использование продуктов, услуг" [9].

Коннекционизм определяет структуру взаимодействия пользователя с ресурсом. В MOOC необходимо определить специфику подачи материала, его закрепление и проверку. Определённые курсы делают под разные платформы, хотя правильней выбирать платформу в соответствии от типа материала. К примеру, если курс посвящён изучению иностранного языка нет нужды встраивать в платформу редактор кода, когда он будет более уместен в технических курсах.

"Классическое, принятое в англоязычной литературе определение MOOC таково: «бесплатные (free), без получения степени онлайн-курсы, открытые, с неограниченным глобальным охватом всех людей, кто желает учиться, независимо от их текущего уровня образования». Степень финансовой свободы и открытости может быть разной от предоставления курсов даром до оплаты обучения, но, как правило, ценой на порядок меньшей, чем традиционные дистанционные курсы. Для монетизации MOOC характерным является предоставление доступа к курсу бесплатно, но введение платы за дополнительную функциональность:

- верификация сертификата путем идентификации обучающегося;
- дополнительные занятия с преподавателем или индивидуальные консультации;
- оплату образовательными организациями использования курсов в собственном учебном процессе" [10].

Одна из проблем MOOC связана с мотивацией обучающихся и преподавателей.

Мотивация обучающихся. По статистике менее 10% людей, записывающихся на курсы, доходят до последнего урока, при этом ещё меньше получают удовлетворительные оценки в финальных тестах. Курсом с самым высоким процентом завершения был "Функциональные принципы программирования в Scala" из Швейцарии, базирующийся на платформе courser, его выполнило 19,2% учащихся из более чем 50000 человек. При этом в

той же coursera есть курс "История мира с 1300 года" Принстонского университета, его выполнили до конца всего 0,8% из более 83000 человек. Проблема удержания учащихся является самой большой и актуальной в MOOK. Через несколько занятий курсы становятся более сложными, время, которое надо тратить на каждое занятие, увеличивается, и обучаемому просто надоедает учиться, и он забрасывает курс.

У данной проблемы есть комплекс решений. Наличие аутентичного, живого тематического контента заметно увеличивает процент завершивших курс, другая проблема — где его взять, ведь не каждая научная область в изобилии содержит интересный контент. Из этого можно вывести несколько общих правил, которые применимы к любой научной области.

После каждой смысловой части приводить наглядные примеры, будь то кусок кода в курсе по программированию или предложение в языковом курсе.

Разбивать курсы на как можно более маленькие уроки, при этом каждый урок должен разделяться логическим или физическим переходом на новую страницу. Материала в каждом уроке не должно быть много, нужно понимать, что человек не робот и за раз может усвоить только определенное количество информации, а искать, где в прошлый раз остановился, гораздо удобней, когда заканчиваешь на структурной единице курса.

Из вышеописанного правила вытекает, что лучше добавлять ссылки на дополнительные источники, чтобы обучающийся смог найти дополнительные материалы, не затратив много времени. При этом это будет одним из поводов вернуться на сервис и посмотреть интересующую ссылку.

Комбинировать контент. Восприятие информации у различных людей различается, есть люди, кому более удобно читать текст, есть те, кто предпочитает смотреть видеозапись, стоит по возможности комбинировать эти два подхода в подаче материала, и если есть лекция, то подготовить по ней текст не составит труда, тем более, что быстрый интернет ещё не пробился во все уголки планеты и многие люди просто не могут увидеть, что записано на видео.

Вторым решением проблемы может стать игрофикация процесса обучения. К текущему времени это уже состоявшееся концепция, которая позволяет удерживать пользователя от занятия к занятию [11].

Мотивация преподавателя. Мотивация преподавателей создавать и запускать свои массовые открытые онлайн-курсы зависит от многих факторов, опишем основные 4 направления, развитие которых влияет на процесс внедрение MOOK:

- роль массовых открытых онлайн-курсов в традиционных системах образования и конкретных учебных заведениях;
- модернизация работы преподавателей, путем внедрения их в глобальную систему электронного обучения, однако возникает проблема их "ухода" (переобучение) от устаревших методов обучения;
- перспективы внедрения онлайн-образования напрямую зависят от скорости и темпов развития информационных технологий;
- влияние онлайн-обучения на реструктуризацию традиционного образования.

Следует отметить, что анализируя литературные источники и публикации, посвященные вопросам внедрения массовых открытых онлайн курсов, можно сделать вывод, что авторы обеспокоены ролью электронного образования и его влиянием на традиционные тенденции, однако все подчеркивают значение в этом вопросе информационных технологий.

На основе анализа литературных источников была разработана концептуальная модель, содержащая групповые стимулы. Данная модель представлена в соответствии с рисунком 2.

Личностный и профессиональный рост	Обязательства	Образовательная стратегия
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "выход" на международный уровень • материальное вознаграждение • пример коллег • распространение собственных идей и исследований • стремление "выгодно" отличиться от коллег 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "задание руководства с целью:" <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • повышения престижа кафедры • повышения престижа университета • шанс удержаться на должности 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • полный "вывод" курса в онлайн-среду • онлайн-курс как образовательная инновация • повышение востребованности курса среди студентов

Рисунок 2. Факторы, косвенно влияющие на решение преподавателя создать MOOK

На данный момент наблюдается смешанная образовательная модель, где традиционное образование остается основным, наряду с ним, стремительно развивается онлайн-образование. Однако, за счет отсутствия у преподавателей мотивации, они не спешат "в больших масштабах" переносить свои дисциплины в онлайн среду. Автор считает, что модернизация законодательной базы и локальных нормативных актов университетов коренным образом изменит данную ситуацию, и "легализует" разработки и внедрения массовых открытых онлайн курсов [12].

Чтобы бесплатно обучать миллионы людей и при этом приносить прибыль аукционерам и инвесторам фирмы чаще всего делают условно-бесплатную концепцию, по которой на первое место ставится обучение, а потом получение денег. Концепция работает уже продолжительное время и вполне зарекомендовала себя.

Самый популярный сервис по обучению английского языка в России LingvaLeo предоставляет основной функционал (изучение слов, просмотр обучающего видео, изучение текстов) бесплатно. Но платить приходится только за профильные курсы, при этом в некоторых происходит онлайн-взаимодействие с преподавателем. Самый популярный сервис массовых онлайн курсов в мире Coursera предоставляет полностью бесплатные курсы, но при этом просит деньги за дополнительные услуги: персональную поддержку, репетиторство, рекламу на сайте, продажу сертификатов и тестирование с определением личности.

По мнению критиков, возрастание популярности MOOK приводит к большей доступности качественного высшего образования, что грозит монополией от ведущих университетов, которые в будущем могут вытеснить с рынка менее престижные университеты. С другой стороны, создания качественных MOOK менее престижными вузами даёт шанс на возрастания популярности вуза [13].

Платформа Dulaty University MOOCS. DULATY.KZ

В соответствии с «Концепцией обучения в течение всей жизни (непрерывное образование)» Таразский региональный университет им.М.Х.Дулати уделяет особое внимание разработке и имплементации массовых онлайн курсов в учебном процессе.

Платформа Dulaty University moocs.dulaty.kz – это платформа для создания и размещения массовых открытых онлайн курсов преподавателей и сотрудников Таразского регионального университета им. М.Х.Дулати. На конец 2021 года на платформе размещено 54 массовых открытых онлайн курсов. Платформа Dulaty University moocs.dulaty.kz представлена на рисунке 3.

Рисунок 3 – Платформа Dulary University moocs.dulatory.kz

Курсы представляют собой структурированную подачу авторских видео и текстовой информации. Общее количество разработанных видеозанятий - более 560. При разработке видео занятий используются инновационные видео инструменты, такие как: скринкаст, хромокей и неоновая доска. Для проверки знаний используются тестовые вопросы разных типов: с одним/несколькими правильным(и) ответом (ми), выпадающий список, вопросы типа Drag and Drop, на соответствие и другие [14]. Вопрос типа «Выпадающий список» на платформе moocs.dulatory.kz на рисунке 4.

Рисунок 4 – Вопрос типа «Выпадающий список» на платформе moocs.dulatory.kz

Платформа создана на базе открытого кода Edx, что позволяет импортировать созданные курсы на Национальную платформу открытого образования. Страница экспорта онлайн-курсов представлена на рисунке 5.

Рисунок 5 – Страница «Экспорт»

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MODERN AZERBAIJANI LITERARY LANGUAGE: NORMS, FORMS AND STYLES

Sevda islam gizi Abbasova

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The state language of the independent Republic of Azerbaijan is Azerbaijani. Its advantages are determined by its lexicon, richness of synonyms, diversity of word formation methods, mobility of stress and intonation, and wide syntax.

The concepts of Azerbaijani national language and Azerbaijani literary language are different - the first of them is wider. It covers all areas of speech activity and includes functional styles, dialects, professional slang, and vernacular and literary language. Azerbaijani literary language is a narrower concept. This is the language used by prominent wordsmiths: writers, public figures, scientists.

The modern literary language is a strictly standardized and codified form of the national language. A language norm is usually understood as a set of the most stable, traditionally consecrated language means and rules of their use accepted in a certain society at a certain time. According to the structure of the language, orthoepic, lexical, grammatical (word creation, morphological, syntactic), orthography, and punctuation norms are distinguished. All these norms are important to ensure the functioning of the Azerbaijani language as a state language.

Forms of Azerbaijani literary language. Modern Azerbaijani literary language exists in two forms: oral and written. The main feature of the oral (daily-speech) form is spontaneity. In addition, the following features are noted: the composition of the vocabulary and the abundance of phraseology; use of simple and incomplete sentences; rare use of participles and adverbial phrases; dialogue form; extensive use of paralinguistic tools: mimicry, gestures, pauses, intonation, repetitions.

The written (standardized) form is distinguished primarily by initial reflection and editorial processing. The following are typical for written speech: complex graphics, spelling and punctuation system; strict adherence to literary norms; special selection of vocabulary, phraseology; use of complex and mixed complex sentences; special role of word order and monologue form.

Communicative qualities of speech. The addressee's speech addressed to the addressee should be selected with communicative appropriateness so that the addressee can decipher it correctly. The main communicative characteristic of speech is accuracy, that is, the ability to express one's thoughts clearly and correctly.

Other important communicative properties of speech are comprehensibility, i.e. understanding, accessibility for the addressees. Clarity is determined by the accurate selection of speech means, the use of words known to the listeners. It should be noted that the dictionary of the Russian language is divided into two groups: the dictionary of unrestricted use (generally used); limited vocabulary: specializations, dialectics, slangs, terms, foreign words.

Important communicative qualities of the speech are its richness and variety, which indicates the speaker's erudition, broad outlook, and high intelligence.

The richness of the language lies in the richness of its vocabulary. Researchers believe that the active vocabulary of a modern person is no more than 7-8 thousand words, while others think that it is 11-13 thousand words.

New words - neologisms are constantly appearing in the language. It is impossible to track their creation, because it is an individual process. Famous people can be the authors of new words.

Unfortunately, in the speech of native speakers, so-called parasitic words are often found, which reflect the uncertainty of the speaker and irritate the listener. For example, concretely, as it is, practically, in principle, largely, such words are sufficient. The task of every literate person is to strengthen his linguistic immunity by developing language intuition or linguistic awareness, preventing parasitic words from entering his speech.

The need to pay constant attention to the word is reflected in proverbs and proverbs of the Russian people: The word is not a sparrow, it will fly - you will not catch it; What is written with a pen cannot be cut with an ax; The word is pain, not bullets; A good rope is long, speech is short;

Maintaining the language culture at a high level, observing the norms in the use of the literary language is the most important task of the state's language policy.

Styles of Azerbaijani literary language. Modern Azerbaijani literary language is multifunctional. It has several functional styles: scientific, official business, journalistic, literary-artistic, and conversational.

Sometimes the boundaries between styles are blurred. Some styles allow you to use an expressive color dictionary to create a specific style effect.

When working with dictionaries, special attention should be paid to stylistic signs. For example, the label spoken language is not the same as the concept of spoken language. So, the word *kakkildama* refers to the colloquial form of the literary language, and the word *neighbor* refers to the vernacular.

Speech culture - the ability to clearly and correctly express one's opinion, the ability to speak correctly, the ability to attract the attention of the audience not only with the content of one's speech, but also with an emotional impact on the listeners. Speech culture includes the following: observing the rules of oral communication; to know the norms of oral and written forms of the literary language; the ability to select and organize language tools that help achieve certain communicative goals in a given communication situation. Thus, speech culture includes three aspects: normative, communicative and ethical.

The normative aspect is the most important aspect. It reflects the correctness of the speech, that is, its compliance with the norms of the literary language. Speech culture cannot be included in the list of prohibitions. It is necessary to have the skills to choose and use language tools according to communicative tasks. This is the basis of the communicative aspect of speech culture. In order to make the optimal choice of language tools, native speakers must be proficient in a variety of functional styles.

The ethical aspect involves knowledge of the ethical norms of speech behavior and includes greetings, requests, questions, thanks, apologies, etc. involves the correct use of speech formulas.

Colloquial speech culture is characterized by the non-distinction of the stylistic layers of the vocabulary, incompetence in monologue speech, and the non-distinction between you and the speech sphere.

The science of personal names is called anthroponymy. The choice of personal name is determined by the national-mental stereotype. A personal name has several conceptual supports: animacy, gender, age. Azerbaijani personal names live an active social life and form an important layer of the linguistically cultural vocabulary.

Communicative qualities of speech. The addressee's speech addressed to the addressee should be selected with communicative appropriateness so that the addressee can decipher it correctly.

The main communicative characteristic of speech is accuracy, that is, the ability to express one's thoughts clearly and correctly.

Other important communicative properties of speech are comprehensibility, i.e. understanding, accessibility for the addressees. Clarity is determined by the accurate selection of speech means, the use of words known to the listeners.

The richness of the language is also reflected in the paraphrases. A paraphrase is the replacement of a one-word name of an object or event with a descriptive statement that shows one or more of the main characteristics of the object or event. Paraphrasing is an important tool to make speech more varied. For example: Sumgait - youth city, Maiden's Castle - impregnable fortress, Baku city - a city on the coast of the Caspian Sea. The content of paraphrases is constantly updated.

Important communicative qualities of the speech are its richness and variety, which indicates the speaker's erudition, broad outlook, and high intelligence.

The richness of the language lies in the richness of its vocabulary. Researchers believe that the active vocabulary of a modern person is no more than 7-8 thousand words, while others think that it is 11-13 thousand words.

The richest source that fills the vocabulary of a language is synonyms. Synonyms that differ in shades of meaning and stylistic color make it possible to form an idea with extreme precision, to give speech a conversational or book character, and to express a positive or negative attitude to what is said.

An important communicative advantage of speech is the skillful use of phraseological units. The Russian language is rich in phraseology, which attracts with expressiveness, the potential to evaluate a phenomenon positively or negatively, figuratively express approval or condemnation, mockery or mockery.

Synonyms, phraseological units, paraphrases allow avoiding tautologies and diversifying speech. The richness of the speech is proved by the presence of proverbs and proverbs, winged words and phrases. Proverbs and proverbs reflect the multifaceted life of the people and are considered examples of folk wisdom: They cut down the forest - chips fly; The leopard changes its spots; The stock pocket is not drawn; Happiness and hard work go together.

Winged words and expressions are widely accepted, figurative expressions of the author: I will be glad to serve - to serve is disgusting.

An important characteristic of the communicative aspect of speech is its purity, which implies the absence of redundant words and parasitic words

An integral characteristic of the communicative aspect of speech is its expressiveness. Expressiveness is a speech that can keep the listener's and reader's attention and interest. The linguistic basis of expressiveness of speech is the presence of pictorial and expressive means.

The source for the creation of tropes and figures is polysemy, which is closely related to the imagery of language.

Tropes - metaphor, metonymy, epithet, simile, hyperbole, litota, personification, paraphrase - are formed on the basis of meaning transfer. Paths give speech uniqueness, visibility, attractiveness. There are two types of trope: 1) common language: metaphor - hot time; metonymy - eating a plate; hyperbola - fatal fatigue; Litota - they pay pitiful pennies, a little man with a hoof, two inches from the pot, two steps away, one second; personality - the sun has set; 2) original: marmalade mood.

Figures of speech are special forms of syntactic constructions that enhance their impact on the addressee. Figures of speech include antithesis (He complains morning and evening, night

and day), gradation (They will think that I am angry, I am cruel, I beat you, I am maiming you.), repetition, rhetorical question, appeal, etc.

Means of expressive speech also include phraseological units, proverbs, proverbs and catchphrases.

We will talk about this in our next articles.

Ақпараттық білім беру ортасында биолог студенттердің цифрлық мәдениетін қалыптастырудың құрылымдық-мазмұндық моделі

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Ақпараттық білім беру ортасында биолог студенттердің цифрлық мәдениетін қалыптастыру моделінің компоненттері: педагогикалық жүйе туралы білім беру, цифрлық мәдениетін қалыптастырудың ерекшеліктері туралы жан-жақты білім, ақпараттық кеңістік туралы білім, ақпараттық-коммуникациялық технологиялар және олардың дидактикалық мүмкіндіктері туралы, ақпараттық білім ортасы туралы, ақпараттық ресурстар және оларды білім беруде тиімді қолдану әдістері туралы білім мазмұны - болашақ биолог оқытушыларды кәсіби дайындауда олардың білімі мен дағдыларын жаңа сапалы деңгейге көтереді.

«Модель» термині «үлгі» мағынасын береді. Бұл нысан және оған қатынасқан мәндерді көрсететін көрнекілік құралдардың бірі. В.А. Штофф модельдеу мәселелері бойынша «модель деп зерттеу объектісін бейнелеу немесе ол туралы ақпаратты жаңарту негізінде қайталап зерттеуге мүмкіндік беретін, ойша ұсынылатын немесе материалдық тұрғыдан іске асатын жүйе», - деп анықтама береді [1]. Педагогика ғылымында жалпы методология негізінде модельге У.Э.Эшби: «модельдеу оқып, үйрену әдісі ретінде – жеңілдету логикасы». Жеңілдету үдерісінің өзі жеткілікті дәрежеде күрделі, себебі олардың көмегімен зерттеу пәні, мақсаты мен міндеттері анықталатын, жұмыс гипотезасы жасалатын, зерттеу нысаны мен оның қасиеттерін сипаттап, бағалайтын әдіс-тәсілдерді таңдау шараларымен байланысты.

Ақпараттық білім беру ортасында биолог студенттердің цифрлық мәдениетін қалыптастырудың құрылымдық-мазмұндық моделі көздеген мақсатына қол жеткізуі үшін шешілуі тиіс бірқатар міндеттер айқындалды. Олардың қатарында келесі міндеттер белгіленеді:

- біріншіден, ақпараттық орта құру мотивтерін, жетістік мотивтерін және инновациялық технологияны игеру жағынан өзін-өзі дамыту дағдыларын қалыптастыру;
- екіншіден, ақпараттық орта құру және оны тиімді қолданудың педагогикасы мен психологиясы бойынша идеяларды кеңейту;
- кәсіби педагогикалық дағдыларды (гностикалық, жобалау, зерттеушілік, ұйымдастырушылық шығармашылық, рефлексивтілік) қалыптастыру.

Модельдің әдіснамалық құрамдас бөлігі зерттеп отырған тақырыптың негізінде жатқан әдістемелік тәсілдер жиынтығын (жүйелілік, құзыреттілікке және білім алудағы белсенді қабілетке негізделген) ұсынылған; ұстанымдарды, олардың сақталуы болашақ кәсіптік оқыту педагогтарының кәсіби шығармашылық құзыреттілігін қалыптастыру үдерісін реттейді. Педагогика ғылымындағы әдіснаманың алатын орны ерекше. Білімдік түсініктер

шеңберіндегі әдіснама – ғылымның таным парадигмасын зерттеу аясында қолданылатын жалпы тәсілдері мен ұстанымдарын негіздеуді ұсынады.

Әдіснама - қағидалар жүйесі және тәжірибелік іс-әрекетті ұйымдастыру және құру тәсілдері, ғылыми таным әдістері туралы оқу, қандай да бір ғылымда қолданылатын әдістердің жиынтығы дегенді білдіреді. Әдіснаманың негізіне белгілі бір білімдер (ұғымдар, заңдылықтар) жүйесі жатады. Философиялық тұрғыдан әдіснама таным және объективті шынайылықты өзгерту үрдісінің тәсілдері мен жолдары жөніндегі ғылым. Әдіснама кең мағынада барлық ғылыми пәндерге ортақ бастапқы философиялық позиция ретінде қабылданады [2].

Ақпараттық білім беру ортасында биолог студенттердің цифрлық мәдениетін қалыптастыру шеңберіндегі ғылыми зерттеулерде, тәжірибелік деңгейде әдіснамалық категорияларды негізге алу келесі себептерді анықтайды. Олар:

- ғылымдардың арасындағы нақты шектің жойылуы, объективті әлемнің кешенді талдаулар арқылы өтуі, бір заттың бірнеше ғылымдар үшін зерттеу пәніне айналуы ақпараттық білім ортасы әдіснамалық сипатындағы ғылыми тұтастығын, жүйелілігін, кешенділігін, интегративтілігін, кәсіби бағытталуын айқындайды;

- жобалауды жүзеге асыруды ғылыми зерттеулердегі зерттеу нысанының, зерттеу пәнінің жаңа қырларының ашылуына байланысты әдіснама, бұл - ақпараттық білім ортасын құру, жобалау, ал олар өз кезегінде зерттеудің іргелі мәселелерін шешуге бағыттайды;

Ақпараттық білім беру ортасында биолог студенттердің цифрлық мәдениетін қалыптастыруда төмендегідей әдіснамалық тұғырлар басшылыққа алынады, олар: жүйелілік тұғыр, іс-әрекеттік тұғыр, ақпараттық тұғырлар.

- жүйелілік тұғыр ақпараттық білім ортасы жобалаудағы жүйелер (білім алушы, түлек, оқытушы) мәселесін зерттеудің жалпы ғылыми негізі ретінде қарастырылады;

- іс-әрекеттік тұғыр білім алушы мен оқытушының қызметінің негізгі компоненттерін бірыңғай әдіснамалық тұрғыдан қарастыруға мүмкіндік береді.

Ақпараттық білім беру ортасында биолог студенттердің цифрлық мәдениетін қалыптастырудың құрылымдық-мазмұндық моделін жасауға негіз болатын бірнеше қағидаларды пайдаланамыз: білім берудің үздіксіздігі қағидасы, гуманистік қағидасы, интеграция қағидасы, ашықтық қағидасы, ақпараттық мәдениет қағидасы, білім берудің іргелілігі мен тұтастығы қағидасы. Бұл қағидалар студенттерге педагогикалық жүйе туралы білім беру, жобалау ерекшеліктері туралы жан-жақты біліммен қамтамасыз ету, ақпараттық кеңістік туралы білімді меңгерту, ақпараттық орта туралы түсініктерін кеңейту, ақпараттық-коммуникациялық технологиялар және олардың дидактикалық мүмкіндіктері туралы білім беру, ақпараттық білім ортасы туралы түсінік қалыптастыру, ақпараттық ресурстар, цифрлық ресурстар және оларды білім беруде тиімді қолдану әдістері туралы білім мазмұнын негізге алуды көздейді.

Үздіксіз білім беру, қоғамның әлеуметтік-экономикалық дамуының қоры, ғылыми-техникалық прогрестің, мемлекеттің тіршілік әрекетінің көптеген салаларының негізі, тұлғаны, соның ішінде болашақ биолог оқытушыларын қалыптастыру, дамыту және өзін-өзі бекіту құралы болады. Ол қоғамның жалпы кәсіпқойлығына қол жеткізуге, жеке тұлғаның сараланған білім беру қызметтеріне деген қажеттіліктерін қанағаттандыруға бағытталған.

Үздіксіз білім беру тұжырымдамасы ақпараттық қоғамның қалыптасу үрдісімен тығыз байланысты. Бұл ретте И. Масуда көзқарасын қолдаймыз және білім беру жүйесін өзгертудің неғұрлым келешегі зор бағыттары - бұл: жабық білім беру жүйесін ашық білім беру ортасымен ауыстыру; білім берудің жекелендірілген сипаты; өз білімін жетілдіруді білім берудің жетекші функциясы ретінде бекіту; тереңдетілген білім беруге бағыттау; өмір бойы білім беру жүйесін қалыптастыру деп санаймыз.

Үздіксіз білім беру жүйесінің маңызы зор, өйткені ол әлеуметтік білім беру ортасы мен факторларының, ақпараттық-коммуникативтік желілердің, қаржылық және материалдық ресурстардың жиынтығы болып табылады; ол тұлғаның әлеуметтік-мәдени және білім алу қажеттіліктерін қанағаттандыруға бағытталған.

«Гуманистік» қағидасы – білім берудің адамға бағытталуынан, шығармашылық даралықты дамыту үшін жағдай жасаудан тұрады. Н.В. Бордовскийдің анықтамасы бойынша, «білім беруді гуманизациялау бұл – білім беру жүйесі мен барлық білім беру үрдісін әр адамның құқықтарын құрметтеуге негізделген студенттер мен оқытушылардың өзара сыйластық қарым-қатынасын қалыптастыру мен дамытуға; олардың денсаулығын, жеке басының қадір-қасиетін сақтау мен нығайтуға және жеке басының әлеуетін дамытуға бағытталуы» деп көрсетіледі [3]. Гуманистік білім адамға өзін табуға, өзін-өзі ортада көрсетуге, өзін-өзі айқындауға, өзін дамытуға деген құқығын қорғауға көмектеседі, оның мәдени өрісін құрады, яғни тұлғаның дүниетанымдық, жалпы мәдени, рухани және интеллектуалдық дамуы мәселелерінің жүгін өзіне алады.

Білім берудің «іргелілігі мен тұтастығы» қағидасы бұл – білім алушылардың теориялық, жоғары білім беру, жалпы ғылыми дайындығын тереңдету, ол жалпы мақсатты функциямен біріктірілген және жеке тұлғаның даму мүдделеріне бағытталған іргелі пәндердің бірыңғай циклдарын енгізуді көздейді. Дәл осы білім берудің іргелілігі дайын өнімдерді қолдануды ғана емес, тұлғаның өздігінен жасай алатын шынайы еркіндігінің қажетті шарты болып табылады.

Қоғамды ақпараттандыру қарқыны тұлғаның ақпараттық мәдениетін арттыру мәселесінің өзектілігіне негізделеді. Ақпараттық мәдениет ақпараттық білім ортасының құрамдас бөлігі болып табылады, адамның әлеуметтік табиғатымен байланысты және оның әртүрлі шығармашылық қабілеттерінің өнімі болып табылады. Жеке тұлғаның ақпараттық мәдениетінің тұжырымдамасы адамның ақпаратты құрушы, қабылдаушы және өндіруші ретінде түсіндірілуіне негізделген, ал жеке тұлғаның ақпараттық мәдениеті сыртқы ортаның жағдайына бейімделу және игеру құралы ретінде және әлеуметтік-маңызды ақпараттың барлық көлемін игеру барысында адамның ішкі әлемін үйлестірудің тәсілі ретінде қарастырылады [4].

«Ақпараттық мәдениет» қағидасы бұл – ақпаратпен мақсатты түрде жұмыс істей білу және оны алу, өңдеу және беру үшін ақпараттық үдерістер мен қарым-қатынастар табиғатын түсінудегі сауаттылық пен құзыреттілікті; ақпараттық тұрғыдағы шығармашылық және әлеуметтік-экономикалық белсенділікті қамтитын компьютерлік ақпараттық технологияларды, қазіргі заманғы техникалық құралдар мен әдістерді қолдана білу. Бұл контексте білімге оның қатысушыларының өзін-өзі мәдени дамыту мақсаттарына қол жеткізудегі жеке ойы, диалогы және ынтымақтастығы қозғаушы күш болып табылатын, білім беру мекемесі біртұтас ақпараттық-білім беру кеңістігі ретінде қарастырылатын, мәдени үрдіс ретінде қарым-қатынас жасау маңызды болып табылады.

«Ашықтық» қағидасы бойынша ашық жүйеде жеке пікір білдіру, өз өмір жолын таңдау, өз мансабын құру мүмкіндігі бар. Мұндай таңдаудың еркіндігін қамтамасыз ету-адамға сыртқы мәжбүрлеу және шектеу қоюсыз білім алуға мүмкіндік береді. Ашық білім беру қағидасын іске асыру педагогикалық жүйенің барлық элементтеріндегі сапалық өзгерістерге әкеледі, оның ішінде білімнің сипаты, білім беру ұйымдарының түрлері мен әдістері, оқу үрдісінде оқытушылар мен білім алушылардың рөлі. Білім беру жүйесінің ашықтығы мен оның білім беру мекемелерінің көп функциялылығы сипаттамасы өзара тығыз байланысты. Көп функциялық білім беруде оқытудың әртүрлі бағыттары мен бейіндерін бөлуге, әртүрлі деңгейлі білім беру бағдарламаларын және оқу - тәрбие үрдістерін ұйымдастыру моделін құрастыруға мүмкіндік беретін оқу-тәрбие үрдісін саралауға негізделеді.

Ақпараттық білім беру ортасында биолог студенттердің цифрлық мәдениетін қалыптастырудың моделін жасауда мотивациялық-мақсаттылық, мазмұндық-іс-әрекеттік және бағалаушылық-рефлексиялық компоненттер алынды.

Мотивациялық-мақсаттылық компоненттің мазмұнын анықтау және іске асыру үшін болашақ биолог оқытушысының ақпараттық білім ортасын жобалаудағы белгілі бір түрткінің әрекетке итермелеуін мотивация десек, ол – әрекетті реттеп (ізденушілік, ақпараттық динамикаға қызығушылық), түрткі үшін арнайы мақсатты күйлерге жетуге бағыттайтын үрдіс болады (кесте 1).

Кесте 1 – Ақпараттық білім беру ортасында биолог студенттердің цифрлық мәдениетін қалыптастырудың компоненттері, өлшемдері мен көрсеткіштері

Компоненттер	Өлшемдер	Көрсеткіштер
Мотивациялық-мақсаттылық	Білім алушылардың ақпараттық білім ортасына мотивациялық-құндылықтық қатынасының болуы	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - цифрлық мәдениетті қалыптастыруда ақпараттық ізденушілік пен танымдық қызығушылықтың болуы; - ЖОО-да цифрлық мәдениетті қалыптастырудың ғылыми-ақпараттық маңызы мен педагогикалық қажеттілігін түсіну; - цифрлық мәдениетті қалыптастырудағы ынта; - ақпараттық технологияларға қызығушылық
Мазмұндық-іс-әрекеттік	Цифрлық мәдениетті қалыптастыруда білім мен біліктіліктің болуы	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - әдістемелік пәндерді оқытудағы цифрлық мәдениетті қалыптастырудағы жүйелі білімі; - цифрлық мәдениетті қалыптастырудағы әдістемелік білігі; - ақпараттық білім беру ортасында жұмыс жасау іскерлігі; - ақпараттық білім беру ортасында шығармашылық белсенділігі
Бағалаушылық-рефлексиялық	Білім алушылардың ақпараттық білім ортасы арқылы кәсіби біртұтастылығы	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - цифрлық мәдениетті қалыптастырудағы тиімді әдістемелерді таба алады және астарлы мағынаны ажыратады; - ақпараттық дамуда өзінің танымдық қызығушылығы арқылы қол жеткен нәтижеге баға береді; - цифрлық мәдениетті қалыптастыру бойынша жаңа теория, идея құра алады және ұсынады; - ақпараттық білім ортасын шығармашылық істерде орындау әрекеті

Мазмұндық-іс-әрекеттік компоненті білім алушылардың цифрлық мәдениетін қалыптастырудағы жүйелілік тұғырға сәйкес, тұлғада қалыптасатын іскерліктерді қамтамасыз етеді. Ақпараттық білім беру ортасындағы цифрлық мәдениет және оны қалыптастырудағы білімі мен біліктері бойынша алынған көрсеткіштер, мұндағы әдістемелік

пәндерді оқытудағы ақпараттық білім ортасын жобалаудағы жүйелі білімі, ақпараттық білім ортасын жобалаудағы әдістемелік білігі, ақпараттық білім ортасында жұмыс жасау іскерлігі, ақпараттық білім ортасын жобалаудағы білім, білік, дағды сапалар жиынтығы және ақпараттық мәдениетте кеңес берудегі шығармашылық белсенділігі болады.

Бағалаушылық-рефлексиялық компонентінде білім алушылардың цифрлық мәдениетін қалыптастыру арқылы кәсіби біртұтас дамудың болуы интеграциялық қағида мен ашықтық қағидасына сай жиынтықтарда өзін-өзі дамытуға, кері байланыс арқылы ақпараттық білім ортасының тиімді болатын тұстарын таңдауға, рефлексиялауға мүмкіндік туғызады.

Бағалаушылық-рефлексиялық компонентіндегі ақпараттық білім беру ортасы арқылы кәсіби біртұтас дамуының болуы өлшемі бойынша ақпараттық білім ортасын жобалаудағы тиімді әдістемелерді таба алады және астарлы мағынаны ажыратады, ақпараттық дамуда өзінің танымдық қызығушылығы арқылы қол жеткен нәтижеге баға береді, ақпараттық білім ортасын жобалау бойынша жаңа теория, идея құра алады және ұсынады деген көрсеткіштер түзіледі.

Ақпараттық білім беру ортасында биолог студенттердің мәдениетін қалыптастыруға даярлаудың компоненттері, өлшемдері мен көрсеткіштерінің негізінде жоғары, орта, төмен деңгейлері анықталды.

Төмен деңгейі – ақпараттық білімге мән бермейді, ол тұрақсыз қызығушылықпен сипатталады және ақпаратты іздеу қабілеттілігі төмен, ақпараттық білім ортасын жобалауда тиімді тұстарын шеберлікпен таба алмайды, яғни ақпараттық бойынша өзін-өзі білімдендіруге білімі жеткіліксіз деңгейде. Цифрландыру туралы теориялық түсінігі, ақпараттық білім ортасы жағдайында педагогикалық білім жүйеленбейді және оны жүзеге асыруды қажет деп санамайды, педагогикалық рефлексиялық әрекеттер қалыптаспаған.

Орта деңгейі – ақпараттық білім беру ортасында цифрлық мәдениетті қалыптастыруға тұрақты қызығушылық пен ақпараттық-техникалық ізденушілік көзқарасымен сипатталады; ақпаратты іздеу қабілеттілігі бар, жаңа іскерлік дайындығы бар, алайда өзін-өзі білімдендірудегі тапсырмалар арқылы өздігінен дайындауда, топта жұмыс жасаудағы ақпараттық білім ортасының қажеттілігін түсіну жеке емес; педагогикалық рефлексиялық ұстаным жобалаудағы өзіндік үлесін білумен байланысты, жалпы мағынада көбірек назар аударумен, тұрақтылықпен, ақпараттық білім беруді жүзеге асырудың тәсілдері мен оларды таңдауды, цифрландыруды инновациялық түсіну, ендіру білігі орташа сипатталады; ақпараттық білім беру ортасында цифрландыру ниеті саналы және жеке мағынасы бар; оны өз тәжірибелерінде қолдау терең педагогикалық білімге негізделген, бірақ шығармашылық тұрғыдан ойлау арқылы қолдамайды.

Жоғары деңгейі – білім алушылардың цифрлық мәдениетті қалыптастыруға қажеттілігінің сенімділігімен сипатталады. ЖОО-ғы білім беру үдерісінің тиімділігін арттырып, студенттер ақпараттық білім ортасында цифрландыру арқылы педагогикаға негізделген білім мазмұнын модельдеуді, жоғарғы білім мазмұнында тапсырмалар арқылы цифрландыру әрекетін жүзеге асырады, ақпараттық білім ортасында өзінің де кәсіби білімін үзбей жетілдіріп отырады.

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Электрондық кітапхана: Тұжырымдамалық негіз

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Электронды кітапхана және оның қызметтері туралы елімізде зерттеулердің жоқтығын ескере отырып, негізінен шетелдік ғалымдар жазған 70-тен астам басылымдарға талдау жасалды.

Ақпараттық технологиялардың қарқынды дамуы және ХХ ғасырдың соңында біздің ғаламшардың миллиондаған тұрғындарына қолжетімді болған ғаламтор (интернет) коммуникацияны жаңа деңгейге шығарды және жаһандану үдерістерінің жеделдеуіне алып келді. Атап айтқанда, бұл электрондық қызметтердің жаңа түрлерінің [1], ашық еңбек нарығының, бұқаралық ынтымақтастықты (mass-collaboration) және ұжымдық ақыл-ойды пайдалануға негізделген жаңа өндірістердің (peer-to-peer production), пайда болуымен, материалдық игіліктерді шерингтік иеленудің және зияткерлік меншікті иеленудің бірлескен жаңа мүмкіндіктерімен (Creative Commons (CC), General Public License (GPL) GNU лицензиялары) [2] көрініс берді. Осы қатардан краудсорсинг және краудфандинг құбылыстары ерекше орын алады. Олар ғалымдардың ерікті негізде адамдарды, жобаларды, өндірісті, өнімдер мен көрсетілетін қызметтерді ілгерілету, тарату және тұтыну үдерістеріне тарту туралы ұғымын түбегейлі өзгертті [3]. Экономика экономиканың жаңа типінің ерекше нышандарына ие бола бастады: on-demand economy, бірлесіп тұтыну экономикасы (sharing economy), ынтымақтасу экономикасы, викиномика (wikinomica) [4, с. 104], жоғары технологиялық тарту экономикасы (the hi-tech gift economy).

Ғылым мен білім саласын дамытудың перспективалық бағыттарының бірі – бизнеспен орнықты серіктестік қатынастар орнату және электронды платформалар жасау мақсатындағы коллаборация. Ұшан-теңіз ақпарат ағынымен бірге оны жинау, іріктеу және талдау үдерісіне жұмсалатын еңбек көлемі де қатар артып отырған қазіргі замандық жағдайлардағы өзекті міндет ақпараттың ғылыми және тағы басқа түрлерінің қолжетімділігін қамтамасыз ететін жаңа буын электронды кітапханасының эталондық үлгісін қалыптастыру болып табылады. Осы орайдағы қолжетімділік қажетті ақпаратты жылдам да жеңіл табу мүмкіндігімен ғана емес, онымен жұмыс істеудің қолайлылығымен айқындалады. Мысалы, көпшілік тұтынуға бағдарланған заманауи ақпараттық жүйелерге қойылатын басты критерий – мобильділік, яғни қазіргі замандық портативтік мобильдік құрылғыларға – смартфондар мен планшеттерге арналған жүйелерді іске қосу және олармен жұмыс істеу мүмкіндігі болып табылады. Заманауи электронды платформалар сапасына қойылатын басқа маңызды критерий ақпаратты семантикалық іздестіру механизмдерін қамтамасыз ететін құралдардың, мысалы, онтология мен нейрондық желілердің болуы болып табылады. Ал, әрине, осындай ақпараттық-анықтамалық жүйелер қазіргі замандық сандық форматтарда: мәтін, сурет, бейне, дыбыс, 3D және т.б.үлгілерде ұсынылған әртекті ғылыми ақпаратқа жетімділікпен қамтамасыз етуі тиіс.

Электронды кітапханаларды зерттеу және әзірлеу — оңай міндет емес. Олар ақпаратты индекстеу, іздестіру, топтамаларды дамыту, дерекқорларды басқару, анықтамалық қызметтер, адам мен компьютердің өзара байланысы, интерфейс дизайны, цифрлау және сақтау, зияткерлік меншік, желілерді қалыптастыру және функционалдық үйлесімділік сияқты кітапханалық, ақпараттық және компьютерлік ғылымдардың көп санын қамтиды.

Сандық кітапханалардың эволюциясы және сақталуы — бұл тек технологиялық шешімдер қабылдау мәселесі емес, егер олар бірін-бірі өзара толықтыратын үш өлшемді ықпалдастыру сипатында қарастырылса (ақпараттық, технологиялық және әлеуметтік салалар негізінде), олар туралы түсінігіміз жақсы болады. Осы параметрлер бірге сандық кітапхананың бүкіл тұжырымдамасын сипаттауға лайықты тұжырымдық негіз болып қалыптасады.

Соңғы бірнеше жыл жүзінде электронды кітапхана үлгісін әзірлеуге қатысты бірнеше зерттеу жобалары болды. Мысалы, e-Dvara негізгі сәулеттік ерекшеліктерінің бірі болып табылатын XML негізінде құжатты сақтау бұрын Greenstone жобасында ұсынылды [5], яғни ол – кітапханашыларға мәтін, кескіндер, бейне және электронды кітаптар сияқты ғаламторда сандық мәнмәтінді құрастыру және әртекті топтамалар жариялау мүмкіндіктерін ұсынуға арналған сандық кітапхана.

Электронды кітапхананың эталондық үлгісін қалыптастыру үшін электронды кітапхана көрсететін қызметтер сапасын қарастыру қажет болды.

Әдістеме негізіне біз электрондық қызмет сапасының ықпалдастық индексіні өлшеу әдістемесін / e-SQMSU платформасын әзірлеген профессор Л.В. Лapidусты алдық [6]. Ол 12 электрондық қызмет сапасын келесідей сипаттады:

1. Сезімталдық қабілеті.
2. Ақпараттық жүйелердің сенімділігі.
3. Қауіпсіздік (яғни, ақпараттық).
4. Кепілділік.
5. Қолжетімділік (іздеу үшін, физикалық).
6. Пікір ашықтығы, эмпатия.
7. Юзабилити – қарапайымдылық/қолайлылық.
8. Жүйеге жауап беру шапшаңдығы және жедел көмек.
9. Кері байланыс, сатылымнан кейінгі қатар алып жүруді қоса.
10. Ақпарат (мәнмәтін/оқылымдылық).
11. Көріністеу (дизайн/инфографика).
12. Қызметпен қамту уақыты.

Электрондық қызметтерді келесі критерийлер бойынша жіктеу мақсатқа сай:

- кешенділік [6, 7];
- үдерістер жиынтығы (тізбек);
- адам факторына (мамандар құрамына) тәуелділік дәрежесі;
- нысаналы сегменттер.

Электронды кітапханалар көрсететін қызметтер сапасын бағалау, олардың күшті және әлсіз жақтарын анықтау үшін сезімталдық қабілеті, қолжетімділігі (іздеуге арналған, физикалық), юзабилити, жүйеге жауап беру шапшаңдығы, кері байланыс, көріністеу (дизайн/инфографика) сияқты критерийлік топтар таңдап алынды, сонымен байланысты келесі қосалқы индекстер жағдайы бағаланды:

- PPB Index (сезімталдық индексі) – тұтынушының электрондық қызметті тұтыну сезімінің дәрежесін көріністейтін көрсеткіш;
- FB Index (кері байланыс индексі) – электрондық қызмет көрсету кезінде кері байланыс сапасын көріністейтін көрсеткіш;
- VMI (visual memory index) – жадыда сақтап қалу дәрежесін көріністейтін көрсеткіш;
- EPI (emotional & psychological index) – эмоциялық және психологиялық әсер ету дәрежесін көріністейтін көрсеткіш;
- VimgQ (visual image index) – көріністік қатар сапасын көрсететін көрсеткіш;
- VH (visual helper index) – көріністеу көмекшілерінің болуын көрсететін көрсеткіш;

- T (time visual index) – көріністік қабылдауға жұмсалатын уақытты көрсететін көрсеткіш;
- RVC (real visual content index) – көріністік мәнмәтіннің ақталуын көрсететін көрсеткіш;
- EU (ergonomics and usability of user interface index) – пайдаланушы интерфейсінің эргономикалық және юзабилити деңгейін көріністейтін көрсеткіш;
- UMV (usability of mobile version index) – е-кітапхана мобильдік нұсқасының эргономикалық және юзабилити деңгейін көріністейтін көрсеткіш.

Осы көрсеткіштер бойынша ірі шетелдік оқу орындарының үздік электронды кітапханалары зерттелінді. Зерттеу нәтижелері 1 кестеде көрсетілген.

1 кесте. Ірі шетелдік оқу орындарының үздік электронды кітапханалары

Кітапхана	EU	UWV	FB	PPB	VMI	EPI	VImgQ	VH	T	RVC
Кембридж университетінің кітапханасы (Англия)	10	8	1	8	9	10	10	9	8	10
Оксфорд университетінің кітапханасы (Англия)	9	9	6	7	10	9	8	8	8	9
Индиана университеті кітапханасы	7	7	8	9	7	6	8	7	7	8
Миннесота университеті кітапханасының каталогы	9	9	1	8	8	7	7	7	7	8
Эдинбург университетінің кітапханасы (Шотландия)	9	8	3	7	7	7	9	9	7	9
Австралия ұлттық кітапханасының каталогы (Австралия)	8	8	9	8	7	5	5	6	5	6
Ресей Ғылым академиясының кітапханасы (Ресей)	5	4	1	8	8	7	4	4	5	5

Алайда, барлық электронды кітапханалардың ерекшеленген детерминанттар бойынша ұсынылатын электрондық қызмет сапасына қатысты кемшіліктері бар. Жасалған талдау нәтижелері тексеруден өткізілетін электронды кітапханалардың бір де бірінің эталон бола алмайтынын көрсетеді.

Электронды кітапханаларға эталондық үлгі жасау талап етіледі, өйткені пайдаланушы мен дерекқор, пайдаланушы мен ақпараттық материалдар авторы, әкімші мен электрондық

кітапхана, басқару жүйесі және дерекқор және т.б. арасында бірыңғай құрылымдарға байланыстар жүйесінің қажеттілігі болады.

Электронды кітапхана е-SQMSU әдістемесі бойынша электрондық қызметтер сапасына аудит, негізгі критерийлік топтар бойынша және электрондық қызметтердің сапа детерминанттарымен өзара байланыста индекстік және қосалқы индекстерді бағалау үдерісінде анықталған критерийлер негізінде құрылуы тиіс, олардың арасында мыналар бар:

1. Ғаламтор желісіне қосылу мүмкіндігі бар кез келген заманауи құрылғыдан (компьютер, смартфон, планшет және т.б.) әртүрлі мәнмәтін қолжетімділігі.
2. Пайдаланушы үшін қолайлы және дағдылы интерфейс.
3. Мәнмәтіннің кез келген түрімен мұрағаттарды сақтаудың сенімді және қауіпсіз жүйесі.
4. Сұрауларды тез түсінетін және нақты ақпаратты табуға көмектесетін нейрондық желілер негізінде ақпаратты семантикалық іздестірудің «ақылды» жүйесі.
5. Пайдаланушыға арналған толық және сапалы ресурстар.
6. Ақпараттық ресурс туралы нақты мета-деректер.
7. Мәтіндердің әмбебап бейімделген үлгісі (epub/html негізінде).
8. DOI алу және дерекқорларға арналған жарияланымдарды және цитаталық индекстерді автоматты түрде даярлау.

Электронды кітапхананың эталондық үлгісі дегеніміз не?

- Эталондық үлгі – бұл қандай да бір ортаның субъектілері арасындағы елеулі өзара байланыстарды түсіну үшін және осы ортаға қолдау көрсететін бірізді стандарттар немесе спецификацияларды әзірлеу үшін абстрактілі негіз.

- Эталондық үлгі біріктіретін тұжырымдамалардың шағын санына негізделген және оны маман емес адамға стандарттарды жасау және түсіндіру үшін негіз ретінде пайдалануға болады.

- Эталон іске асырудың қандай да бір стандарттарымен, технологияларымен немесе басқа нақты бөліктерімен тікелей байланысты емес, бірақ ол әртүрлі жүзеге асырулар арасында екі мағынасыз пайдалануға болатын жалпы семантиканы қамтамасыз етуге ұмтылады.

Эталондық кітапхананың электронды үлгісінің мақсаты мен құрылымы зерттеулердің ықпалдасуын оңайлатып және тиісті жүйелерді әзірлеудің үздік тәсілдерін ұсына отырып, негізін қалайды және ғаламдық электронды кітапханалардың өңірлік-түкпірлік тұжырымдамаларын айқындайды.

Үлгі мынадай функцияларды қамтамасыз етуі тиіс:

- нысанды тіркеу, атау беру, аңдатпа-парақ жазу және айқындау рәсімін қамтитын ресурстарды жариялау;
- ресурстарды талдамалық өңдеу;
- динамикалық қалыптастыру функциясын қоса, жарияланған ресурстарға қолжетімділік;
- ресурстарды автоматтандырылған мониторингтеу және олардың мета-сипаттамаларын өзектендіру;
- жаңа ресурстардың пайда болуы және ағымдағы ресурстардың жаңартылуы жөнінде пайдаланушыларды хабарландыру;
- диспетчерлік қызметпен қамту.

Әлемде әртүрлі эталондық электрондық кітапханалардың үлгілері бар:

- *CIDOC CRM (The International Committee for Documentation of the International Council of Museums, <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/>)* дүниежүзілік мәдени мұра саласында және онымен байланысты салаларда ықпалдастыққа, аралық делдалдыққа және ақпарат алмасуға арналған;

- *FRBR (Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records, ИФЛА әзірлеген)* – «түпнегіз – байланыс» тұжырымдамалық үлгісі кітапханалық каталогтар мен библиографиялық дерекқорларды ғаламторда іздестіру және оларға қол жеткізу мәселесін шешеді [8];

- DELOS DLRM (Digital Library Reference Model) бағдарламалық жүйелерді кейіннен іске асыруға арнаған нақты сәулеті бар өрісі тар үлгілерді әзірлеуге арналған [9];

- 5S үлгісі – Streams, Structures, Spaces, Scenarios, Societies (ағындар, құрылым, кеңістіктер, сценарийлер, қоғамдастықтар).

Жоғары оқу орнына арналған электрондық кітапхана құруға ең лайықты үлгі – DELOS DLRM, өйткені ол дерекқорлар, зерттеу журналдарындағы мақалалар, рецензиялар, тезистер мен ғылыми еңбектердің сандық нұсқалары, академиялық қоғамдастықтың басқа сандық активтері сияқты материалдарды шоғырландыратын білім беру ұйымының электронды кеңістігін қалыптастыруға мүмкіндік береді.

DELOS сандық кітапханасының эталондық үлгісі

Digital library ұғымы Delos электрондық кітапхана манифестінде (Digital Library Reference Model, DLRM) – Еуропалық комиссия Ақпараттық қоғам технологиясының бағдарламасы шеңберінде [10] және Кітапханалар мен ақпараттық ресурстар кеңесі америкалық ұйымы [11] құрған Электрондық кітапханалар федерациясы [12] атауымен негізін қалаған Электрондық кітапханаларды жетілдіру желісі (Network of Excellence on Digital Libraries).

Жоба мақсаты – электрондық кітапхана әмбебаптық ерекшелігін құрайтын фундаменталдық ұғымдарды, маңызды объектілерді және олардың қатынастарын, стандартты функционалдық және құрылымдық бөгеттер мен үдерістерді жүйелеу. Эталондық үлгі бағдарламалық жүйелерді кейіннен іске асыруға арналған нақты сәулеті бар өрісі тар үлгілерді әзірлеуге арналған. Электронды кітапхана үшін негіздік түсініктер (нақты электрондық кітапхана, электрондық кітапхана жүйесі жүйесі, электрондық кітапхананы басқару жүйесі) айқындалды, осы ұғымдар үшін пайдаланушылар санаттары (әзірлеуші, пайдаланушы, әкімші) белгіленді. Алты негізгі жоғары деңгейлі ұғымдар/салалар белгіленді:

1. мәнмәтін,
2. пайдаланушы,
3. функционалдық мүмкіндіктер,
4. сапа,
5. саясаттар,
6. сәулет.

Осы стандартқа тән маңызды ерекшеліктер электрондық кітапхананың логикалық та, сондай-ақ, талассыз, физикалық та үлгісі болып табылады, сондықтан стандартты қолдану нәтижесі айрықша өзгешеленуі мүмкін [13].

Электрондық кітапхана мазмұны мета-деректер жинақтарын және оларды тасымалдау мен сақтау барысында ұсыну тәсілдерін көріністейтін жекелеген стандарттармен сипатталады. Бұл стандарттар DELOS DLRM байланыссыз әзірленеді және электрондық кітапхана мазмұнын сипаттау міндетін шешеді.

Мета-деректердің осы немесе өзге стандартын пайдалану тақырыптық бағдарлауға қарай әрбір нақты электрондық кітапхана үшін бөлек анықталады.

Мәнмәтін саласы олар туралы ақпарат кітапханада қолжетімді болатын және тұтынушылардың ақпараттық қажеттіліктерін қанағаттандыру үшін пайдаланылатын барлық объектілер түрінде болады. Ақпараттық объектілер, өз кезегінде, электронды кітапхана ресурстары болған кітапхана мәнмәтінінің тікелей құрамдас бөліктері болып табылады. Ресурс ұғымы, өз кезегінде, жалпы сипаттамаларды қамтиды және ақпараттық объектілер таралымдық даналары болатын жүйеде мазмұндалған ресурстардың барлық типіне тән

байланыстардың болжамды типтерін айқындайды. Ресурстар мен олардың даналарын топтамада ұсынудың барлық деңгейлерінде біріктіруге болады. Ресурсты бұлтартпай түсіндіру үшін оның сипаттамасын мейлінше күрделі болуы мүмкін және және онда ресурстар өте ұсақ ыдырап кетуі мүмкін онтология түрінде ұсынуға болады және олардың арасындағы байланыс айқындалады.

CIDOC CRM (CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model, CIDOC тұжырымдамалық эталондық үлгісі) CIDOC комитетінің (Халықаралық құжаттау комитеті (International Committee for Documentation)) құжатты стандарттау жөніндегі жұмыс тобы және CIDOC CRM әзірлеу жөніндегі арнайы жұмыс тобы әзірлеген. Үлгі кеңейтілетін семантикалық делдал-үлгі ретінде ойластырылды, ол мұражайлар, мұрағаттар және кітапханалар жариялайтын мәдени мұра жөніндегі әртекті ақпаратты біріктіруге арналған құрал болуы тиіс.

Үлгі материалдық және материалдық емес объектілерді уақыт пен кеңістікте байланыстыратын «оқиғаға» бағдарланған. Үлгі орталығында – уақыт ұғымдары – кезеңдер, оқиғалар, қызмет – ол тіршілік еткен кезеңде объектімен болған нәрсенің бәрі – идеяның пайда болуы, физикалық нысан өндірісі, нысанды модификациялау, ыдырау және т.б.

CIDOC CRM базасында бірқатар ірі жобалар құрылған. Олардың арасында – сандық кескіндердің, үш деңгейлі үлгілердің және толық мәтіндік сипаттамаларымен және мета-деректерімен бейнематериалдардың ауқымды топтамалары бар 6 еуропалық мұрағатты қамтитын SCULPTEUR жүйесі бар. Жүйе пайдаланушыға CIDOC CRM мәтінін, мета-деректерін және тұжырымдарын біріктіру бойынша топтаманы іздестіруге мүмкіндік береді.

CIDOC CRM әзірлеушілері машинамен өңдеу үшін да жарамды, адамның түсінуіне де оңай үлгінің стандартын жазуды өзіне мақсат етіп қойды. CIDOC CRM үлгілері 87 кластан және 148 ерекшеліктен тұрады, олар нысандарды, ұғымдарды, адамдарды, оқиғаларды, орынды, уақытты және олардың қатынастарын сипаттайды. CIDOC CRM мазмұндарын және олардың байланыстарын сипаттайтын жоғары деңгейлі ұғымдарды ғана ұсынады және осындай жүйелерді құжаттаумен немесе оларды жүзеге асырумен ешқандай байланысы болмайды.

FRBR және FRBRoo үлгісі

CIDOC CRM үлгісіне байланыссыз 1991-1997 жылдары Кітапханалық қауымдастықтар мен мекемелердің халықаралық федерациясы (International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, IFLA) қандай да бір каталогтандыру кодына немесе іске асырылуына байланыссыз библиографиялық универсумның жинақталған ұғымы ретінде «Библиографиялық жазбаларға қойылатын функционалдық талаптар» (Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records, FRBR) ER-үлгісін әзірледі.

FRBR тұжырымдамалық үлгі сипаттамасын (мәндері, олардың қатынастары мен атрибуттары) қамтиды, барлық материалдар типтерін және пайдаланушының каталогтарда, библиографияларда және басқа библиографиялық құралдарда сипатталған библиографиялық ресурстармен байланысты міндеттерін ұсынады [14, 15].

Сонымен, FRBR үлгісі материалдардың барлық типтеріне және библиографиялық ресурстармен байланысты пайдаланушы міндеттеріне арналған әмбебап библиографиялық жазбаларды; атрибуттар мен қатынастардың мол жинағын ұсынады; *шығарма және суреттеме* нысандары арасындағы шекаралар жойылған; қатынастар небәрі он, бұл кітапханалық қосымшалардың басым көпшілігіне анық жеткіліксіз.

Жобаланған электронды кітапханаға арналған ақпараттық жүйе ресурстарының ойластырылған үлгісін әзірлеу барысында біз сыртқы жүйелермен ықпалдасу мүмкіндігімен ресурстардың әртүрлі типтерін ықпалдастырудың ыңғайлы жүйесіне қол жеткізуді көздедік. Жүйені әзірлеу барысында кітапхана ресурстарын үлгілендіру стилін айқындаудың негізгі идеялары деректердің икемделген үлгілерінің тұжырымдамасынан алынды.

Жоғарыдағы баяндауға сүйеніп, онда сақталуы мүмкін және осы орайда оның терминологиялық сипаттамасына қолдау көрсетілетін белгілі бір ғылыми тақырыптық сала

ресурстарының әртүрлі типтерінің сан алуандығын есепке алуға болатын кітапханаларға арналған ақпараттық жүйе құру міндеті тұжырымдалды. Жүйенің мәнмәтінінде негізгі шешілетін міндеттердің бірі – бұл деректер үлгісінің семантикалық сипаттамасы сақталатын көздерден алынған деректерді ықпалдастыру мүмкіндігін қамтамасыз ету. Іс жүзінде, осындай жүйе кез келген бағыттағы сандық кітапхананы жасауға арналған және сақталатын деректер мәнмәтінінің бейімделген үлгісімен жарақтанған конструктор түрінде болады. Деректердің бейімделген үлгісі тақырыптық саланың терминдермен бекітілген тезаурус шеңберіндегі кітапхана мәнмәтіні деректерінің ерікті үлгісін сипаттауға мүмкіндік береді.

Осы жүйені жүзеге асыру үшін аталған жұмысты да іске асыратын мына міндеттер белгіленді:

1. кітапханада қамтылатын ресурстардың кез келген типтерін сипаттауға мүмкіндік беретін кітапхана мәнмәтінінің онтологиялық ұсынымын әзірлеу;
2. әзірленген ұсыным моделі кез келген тақырыптық саламен оңай ықпалдасуы тиіс, оны ұсыну оның кейбір терминдерін таксономия түрінде (желілік сөздік, классификатор, тезаурус) түрінде жинаумен шектеледі;
3. ғылыми білімнің күрделі құрылымдалатын салалық тезаурустарын қолдау үшін тезаурус ұсынудың кеңйтілген ұғымдық үлгісін жасау;
4. деректер үлгісінің негізіне кітапхана мәнмәтінінің әзірленген онтологиялық үлгісі қойылған кітапхананың ақпараттық жүйесін әзірлеу;
5. кітапхананың әзірленген ақпараттық жүйесінің деректерін ұсыну LOD шеңберіндегі мәліметтер мен дереккөздерге қойылатын талаптарға сай болуы тиіс;
6. тақырыптық саладағы тезаурус көмегімен кітапхананың мәнмәтін сипаттамаларын семантикалық белгілеп қоюды жүзеге асыру тақырыптық саланың тезаурусы көмегімен кітапхананың мәнмәтін сипаттамаларына қолдау көрсетуді іске асыру;
7. кітапхананың ақпараттық жүйесі пайдаланушыларға өз мүдделерінің шеңберін айқындау мүмкіндігіне, тақырыптық тезаурусты оны пайдаланушыны қызықтыратын бағытта терминологиялық кеңейту мүмкіндігімен бірге қолдана отырып, қолдау көрсетуі тиіс.

Ойластырылған шешімнің негізгі мақсаттарының бірі – бұл кітапхана деректерін әртүрлі көздерден алынған деректермен ықпалдастыру және байланыстыру. Осы сатыда шешілетін негізгі міндеттер – деректер деңгейінде де, деректер сызбалары деңгейінде де әртүрлі көздерден алынған деректерді біріктіру барысында туындайтын мәселелерді қалпына келтіру. Сонымен қатар семантикалық үлгідегі кітапханалар қарастырылды.

Семантикалық кітапханалардың негізгі ерекшелігі олардың әр алуан мәнмәтінін құрылымдау мүмкіндігі және әртүрлі көздерден алынған деректерді байланыстыру мүмкіндігі болып табылады, өз кезегінде, бұл талассыз осы мәнмәтін сапасынан көрініс береді.

Қарастырылатын жүйенің анықтауыштары болып табылатын семантикалық кітапханалардың негізгі ерекшеліктерін атап өтеміз:

- семантикалық кітапхана әртүрлі дереккөздердің деректер жинағын молайтатын және толықтыратын ықпалдасу түйіні түрінде болады;
- кітапхана мәнмәтіні семантикалық деңгейде сипатталады, бұл дереккөздер арасындағы үздік өзара байланысқа қол жеткізу мүмкіндігін береді;
- кітапхана мәнмәтінінің, кітапхананы құру барысында қарастырылатын бастапқы шарттарға қарай, құрылымның сан қырлы таралымының әртүрлі дәрежесі болуы мүмкін;
- семантикалық сипаттама және оның әр қырлы деңгейі кітапхананың ақпараттық жүйесін іске асырудың техникалық сипаттамаларына байланысты емес және нақты іске асырудан тыс айқындауға болады;

- кітапхана мәнмәтінің ұғымдық сипаттамасы оны кітапхана ресурстарының терминологиялық тұрғыдағы тақырыптық саласын шектейтін тезауруспен қолдауға ие болады.

Қорытынды

Электронды кітапханалар эталондық үлгі құрылуын қажет етеді, өйткені пайдаланушы мен дерекқор, пайдаланушы мен ақпараттық материалдар авторы, әкімші, басқару жүйесі және дерекқор және т.б. арасындағы байланыстардың бірыңғай құрылымданған байланыстар жүйесінің қажеттілігі болады. е-SQMSU электронды қызметтерінің сапа әдістемесі негізінде кітапханаларға және ірі шетелдік жоғары оқу орындарының каталогтарына, ұлттық кітапханаларға, электрондық кітапханаларды қолданудың ресейлік тәжірибесіне талдаулар жасалды. Талдау барысында әрбір электронды кітапхананың артықшылықтары анықталды. Тек кешенді талдау ғана университеттер мен тұтынушылар арасындағы серіктестік келісімнің арқасында ауқымды аумақтануға және тұрақты дамуға бағдарланған электрондық кітапхананың эталондық үлгісін ұсынуға мүмкіндік береді.

Жасалған эталондық электронды кітапхана әртүрлі нысандарда (мәтін, дыбыс, бейне) ұсынылған қазіргі замандық кітапханалық қордың бірыңғай платформасын қалыптастыру қажеттілігін қанағаттандыруға мүмкіндік береді. Ғалымдар мен оқытушылар жүргізілген ғылыми зерттеулер мен жобалар бойынша қажетті ақпаратты жылдам іздеу жүргізе алады, осы орайда оларға пәнаралық жобалар әзірлеу үшін командалар құру мақсатында пәнаралық салаларда басқа факультеттерден серіктестер іздеу мүмкіндігі ұсынылады.

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Таңғажайып жеті саны

Шарип Риза

Қазақстан республикасы Ақмола обылысы Целиноград ауданының Ынтымақ ауылы
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Жердің жүзін мекендеген халықтардың көбісі ерте кезден-ақ жеті санында сиқырлық күш бар деп санаса, оны киелі, қасиетті деп ұғатын да ұлттар бар. Біздің ата-бабаларымыз да жеті санын қастерлеп, бірқатар таным-түсінігі мен табиғат құбылыстарын, аспан денелері мен заң, жүйелерді жеті санымен атайды. Аллаһ Тағаладан пенделеріне түскен қасиетті кітаптардың бірі – Тауратта жеті саны 500 рет қайталаанады. Қазақтардың таным – түсінігінде.

Жеті ата. Бұл – Қазақ халқының дәстүрлі салт-санасында адамның ата жағынан тегін таратудың нақты жүйесі. Әрбір Қазақ баласы өзінен бастап жеті атасының аты жөнін білуге міндетті. Мұны әке-шешесі, ата-әжесі үйретіп, жаттатуға тиіс. Өйткені қазақта жеті атаға дейін қыз алыспайды, оған дейінгі ұрпақ бір атаның баласы – туыс саналады.

Қазақтар негізінен жеті атаны былайша таратады: 1. Бала. 2. Әке. 3. Ата. 4. Үлкен ата. 5. Баба. 6. Түп ата. 7. Тек ата. Сондай-ақ, адамдар атасынан төмен қарай атағанда былайша ататек жалғасады: ата, әке, бала, немере, шөбере, шөпшек, немене. Мұнан соң туыстың атаулар әрі қарай: жүрежат, туажат, жұрағат, жат жұрағат, жегжат, жамағайын болып кете береді. Жеті аталық ұстаным әрбір қазақтың, бүкіл халықтың бабалар рухы алдында іштей жауапкершілік сезімін оятатын күшке ие. Ол – этникалық тұтастықтың қуатты арқауы, темірқазығы. Сол себепті ата-бабаларымыз: «Жеті атасын білмеген: жетесіз», «Ата – тегін айтқанның айыбы жоқ» деп ұрпақтарына жеті атасын білуді өсиет, аманат етіп айтып кеткен. Қазақтар бала, немере, шөбере, шөпшек, немене, туажат, жүрежатты «Жеті пұсты» деп те атайды.

Жеті қазына. Ол жөнінде пікір таласы көп. Алайда қазақтар ертеде жеті қазынаға мыналарды жатқызған: 1. Ер жігіт. 2. Сұлу әйел. 3. Ілім-білім. 4. Жүйрік ат. 5. Құмай тазы. 6. Қыран бүркіт. 7. Берен мылтық. Қазақтар жеті қазынаны «жеті ырыс» деп танып, оған мыналарды жатқызған: 1. Адамның ақыл-ойы, санасы. 2. Денсаулық. 3. Ақ жаулық (ердің жары). 4. Бала (өмір жалғасы). 5. Көңіл (көңіл мен пейіл кең болса, ынтымақ, береке орнайды). 6. Жер («Жерсіз – ел тұл, ерсіз – жер тұл»). 7. Ит. Жігіттің жеті қазынасы Жүрдек аты –жігіт қаны, қанаты Қыран бүркіт – қарым күші, қуаты. Құмай тазы - бастан берік сенімі, Ақ мылтығы – сөнбес оты, серігі Алмас кездік – жігіт сусы, һәм мысы ау жылымы – амал, айла, әдісі Қара қақпан серті себі тірліктің Осы жеті қазынасы жігіттің.

Ал, Ислам аңызы бойынша, **жеті қазынаға мыналар жатады:** 1. Қыдыр (қызыр). Қыдыр дарыған адам бай болады. 2. Бақ. Ол ерекше жаратылған құдірет иесі. Бақ дарымайды, қонады. 3. Ақыл (Байлық пен бақыттың тірегі). 4. Денсаулық. 5. Ақ жаулық. 6. Тұз (Ол – Алланың адамдар мен жан-жануарларға берген несібесі, таусылмайтын кені). 7. Ит. (Адам Ата мен Хауа Ананың алғашқы серігі).

Қазақтардан басқа халықтарда да жеті қазына туралы өзіндік таным, түсінік бар. Мысалы, грек аңыз - әңгімелерінде жеті қазынаға мыналар жатады: 1. Көк аспан. 2. Күн (барлық зат оның шуағынан нәр алады). 3. Ай (түнгі тіршілік нәрі). 4. От (От – Күннің жердегі сүлдесі. Оны пайдалану арқылы адамдар дүниенің төрт бұрышына тарады). 5. Су. (сусыз тіршілік жоқ). 6. Жер (тіршілік анасы). 7. Ит. Жеті қат көк. Ол – аспан әлемі туралы мифологиялық түсінік. Оның үш мағыналық сипаты бар. Біріншісі: Аллаһ Тағала аспанды жеті қабатты етіп жаратқан. «Алланың жеті аспанды қабат-қабат етіп жаратқанын көрмедіңдер ме?» (Құран Кәрім, 72 сүре, 14 аят). Екіншісі: жеті жұлдызға байланысты атау. Олар: Ай, Меркурий (Ғұтрад), Шолпан (Зуһ-ра), Күн, Марс (Миррих немесе Қызыл жұлдыз),

Юпитер (Мүштары), Сатурн (Зұхал). Үшіншісі: ежелгі түркілік мифологиялық түсінік негізіндегі мағына. Ол мұсылмандық ұғыммен сіңісіп, ұмытылып кеткен.

Жеті қат жер. Ежелгі наным-сенім бойынша олар мынандай: 1. Тұңғыық. 2. Жылан. 3. Су. 4. Қос балық. 5. Қара тас. 6. Көк өгіз. 7. Жер. Жаратылыстың сегізінші қабаты – тағдырдың талайы жазылған «лайық» атты жазу тақтасынан, тоғызыншы қабаты – «күрсі», «мінбер» және «тақ» орнатылған тәңірлер әлемінен тұрады.

Жетіқарақшы. Ол – аспанның солтүстік жарты шарындағы шоқжұлдыз. Оның 1, 8 көрінерлік жұлдыздық шамаға дейін жалтырап көрінетін ең жарық жұлдыздары – Алиот пен Дубке. Жетіқарақшының жарық жеті жұлдыздың сыртқы пішіні шөміш тәрізді. Оның шеткі екі жұлдызы бойынша Темірқазық жұлдызын табуға болады. Жетіқарақшы наурыз, сәуір айларында жақсы көрінеді. Темірқазықты айнала қозғалатын жетіқарақшы арқылы жер тараптары мен түнгі мезгілді айыруға болады.

Аптаның жеті күні. Олар: дүйсенбі, сейсенбі, сәрсенбі, бейсенбі, жұма, сенбі, жексенбі. Кемпірқосақтың жеті түсі. Жарық мынандай жеті түстен тұрады: қызыл, қызғылт-сары, сары, жасыл, көгілдір, көк және күлгін. Күн сәулесі жаңбыр тамшысына түскенде, жарықтың жеті түсі сынып, тамшы арасынан көрініп, кемпірқосақ пайда болады.

Жеті жарғы. Ол – Тәуке хан (1678-1718) тұсында қабылданған Қазақ халқының дәстүрлі әдет-ғұрып заңдарының жинағы. Тәуке хан «Қасым ханның қасқа жолы» мен «Есім ханның ескі жолын» одан әрі жетілдіру арқылы осынау заң жүйесін өмірге әкелген. Ол 20-ғасырдың басына дейін қолданылып келді. «Жеті жарғы» деп аталуы Тәуке ханның бұрынғы заңдарға енгізген жеті өзгертуіне байланысты» дейтін тұжырым бар.

Ол жеті өзгеріс мынандай: 1. «Халықтың ханы, сұлтаны, пір -әзіреті қастан өлтірілсе, олардың әрқайсысы үшін жеті кісінің құны мөлшерінде құн төленсін». 2. «Төрелер мен қожалардың жай қатардағы біреуі өлсе, олардың әрқайсысына екі кісінің құны төленсін». 3. «Сырттан кірген адам үйге кірерде мініп келген атын босағаға байлағандықтан, біреуді теуіп өлтірсе, бүтін құн, үйдің жапсарына байлаған ат теуіп өлтірсе, жарты құн, ал үйдің артына байлаған ат теуіп өлтірсе, тек ат-тон айып тартады». 4. «Ата-анасын туған баласы ренжітіп, қарсы келіп, қол жұмсаса, онда ол баланы ата-ана өлтірсе де ерікті, сұраусыз болады». 5. «Кәмелетке жеткен баласы туған ата-анасына тіл тигізіп сөккені үшін (қол тигізбесе) қара сиырға не қара есекке теріс мінгізіп, мойынына құрым іліп, ауылды айналдыру керек». 6. «Құйрық – бауыр жесіп, құда болған соң ақ баталы жесір басқаға кетсе, оған берілген қалыңмал жесір иесіне түгел қайтарылып, оның үстіне қалыңсыз қыз немесе бір қыздың қалыңмалы беріледі». 7. «Ұры айыр түйеге нар, атқа аруана, тайлаққа, атан, тайға ат, қойға тана төлейді. Оның үстіне үш тоғыз айып төлейді». Әрине, бұл жеті

өзгерістен басқа да «Жеті жарғыда» жер дауы, отбасы, неке заңы, қылмыс пен құн дауы, куәлік ету, ант беру, тонаушылық және тағы да басқа жағдайларға, рәсімдерге байланысты әдет-ғұрып, заң шаралары өз көрінісін тапқан.

Жеті жұт. Бұлар: 1. Құрғақшылық. 2. Жұт (мал қырылу). 3. Өрт. 4. Оба (ауру). 5. Соғыс. 6. Топан су. 7. Зілзала (жер сілкіну).

Жеті жоқ. Ол былай: 1. Жерде өлшеу жоқ. 2. Аспанда тіреуіш жоқ. 3. Таста тамыр жоқ. 4. Тасбақада талақ жоқ. 5. Аллаһта бауыр жоқ. 6. Аққуда сүт жоқ. 7. Жылқыда өт жоқ.

Жеті жетім. Бұл жөнінде мынандай даналық сөздер бар: Тыңдамаған сөз жетім, Киюсіз тозған бөз жетім. Иесіз қалған жер жетім. Басшысы жоқ ел жетім. Аққу, қазсыз көл жетім. Жерінен айырылған ер жетім. Замандасы қалмаса – Бәрінен де сол жетім.

Жеті ғашық. Халықтың ән – жырында жеті ғашық мынандай екі нұсқада кездеседі: а) Ләйлі – Мәжнүн, Жүсіп – Зылиха, Фархад – Шырын, Тахир – Зухра, Арзу – Қамбар, Уәлик – Ғарра, Уәки – Күлшаһ. ә) Ләйлі – Мәжнүн, Жүсіп – Зылиха, Фархад – Шырын, Баһрам – Күләнда, Сейпілмәлік – Бәдіғұл, Бозжігіт – Анула (кей нұсқада Қарашаш), Зияда – Хорлы (Хорлы - Ғайын).

Әлемдегі жеті санымен аталатын кереметтер Вавилондықтардың түсінігінше, әлемде жеті планета бар. Сол себепті олардың ғибадатханалары да жеті деңгейлі. Бірқатар діндерде де жеті саны киелі: еврейлердің балауыз қойғышы, шырағандары, менорлары жетіден.

Ислам дінінде.

Жеті аспан: күміс, алтын, меруерт, ақ алтын, жақұт, анартас және ғажайып жарық.

Жеті шәріп: Мекке шәріп, Мәдина шәріп, Бұхар шәріп, Шам шәріп, Қатым шәріп, Құддыс (Мысыр) шәріп, Кәләм шәріп (Құран).

Жеті тозақ: 1. Сағир. 2. Лазо. 3. Сақар. 4. Жахим. 5. Жаһаннам. 6. Хауия. 7. Хатома.

Христиан дінінде

Жеті саны: сенім, үміт, қайырымдылық, әділеттілік, сабырлық, ақылдылық және рухтың күші.

Таурат кітабы бойынша: Құдай 1 – күні жарықты, 2 – күні аспанды, 3 – күні жерді, 4 – күні Күн, ай және жұлдыздарды, 5 – күні балықтар мен құстарды, 6 - күні аңдар мен адамдарды жаратқан, 7 – күні дем алған. Бұл әлемді жаратуға арналған жеті күн деп аталады.

Өлімге себепкер жеті күнә: 1. Тамақсаулық. 2. Жалқаулық. 3. Нәпсіқұмарлық. 4. Өркөкіректік. 5. Ашу. 6. Қызғаншақтық. 7. Сараңдық. Бұл жеті күнәні XV ғасырда суретші Иероним жоғарыдағы суретте тамаша бейнелеген.

Әлемнің жеті кереметі

Алғашқы жеті керемет: 1. Египет пирамидасы. 2. Вавилонның аспалы бағы. 3. Ертедегі Артемида храмы. 4. Олимпиядағы Зевстің мүсіні. 5. Галикарнастағы Мавсол патшаның табытханасы. 6. Жерорта теңізі аралығындағы Гелиостың (Күн Құдайы) қолдан жасалған мүсіні. 7. Александрия маягі.

Бесінші ғасырдан бері танылған 7 керемет: 1. Рим колизейі. 2. Александрияда жер астында жол пішінде қазылған мазарлар. 3. Қытайдың ұлы қорғаны. 4. Англиядағы алып тас қорған. 5. Италиядағы Пиза қисық мұнарасы. 6. Қытайдың Нанжин қаласындағы фарфор мұнара. 7. Ыстамбұлдағы әулие София ғибадатханасы.

Жеті континент. Олар: Африка, Антарктида, Австралия, Еуропа, Солтүстік және Оңтүстік Америка.

Гептатлондағы (жетісайыс) спорттың жеті түрі. Олар: тосқауылдармен 100 метрге жүгіру, биіктікке секіру, 200 метрге ату, ұзындыққа секіру, 800 метрге найза лақтыру. «Жеті саны – бақытты сан, ол - адамзаттың сүйікті саны». Көп халықтың түсінігі осындай.

Жеті ішекті қазақтың музыкалық аспаптары Сылдырмақ. Қазақ ерте заманда көшпенді халық болғандықтан, түрлі музыкалық аспаптарды тұрмыста кеңінен қолданған. Ағаш, қыш, темір, мүйіз сияқты күнделікті өмірде пайдаланатын шикізаттан алуан түрлі аспаптарды жасап шығарған. Алғашында ол шаруашылыққа қажет бұйым болса, кейіннен ырғақты ұстап тұратын музыкалық аспапқа айналған. Соның бірі сілкімелі аспап – сылдырмақ. Әрбір ұрып ойнайтын аспаптың өзіндік ерекшеліктері бар. Олардың сыр-сипаты мен ерекшелігі тембрлік және динамикалық дыбысталуына қарай айқындалады.

Сондай-ақ Орта Азия халықтары мен латын америкасы елдерінде бір-біріне ұқсас аспаптар көп кездеседі. Соның бірі - маракас аспабының қазақи формасын музыканттар өзі ойлап тапқан. Халқымыз төрт түлік малдың етін жеп, көлік ретінде пайдаланудан бөлек, оның сүйегін де кәдеге жаратқан. Соның бірі - ат тұяғының дүрсілі сияқты малдың жүрісін білдіретін аспап - мүйізше. Ол ерте заманда әуенді сүйемелдеуші аспап ретінде қолданылған. Шеберлер немесе музыканттар аспаптың дыбысталуына қарай оның санын қасиетті 7 санына дейін жеткізген. Ал оларға қолданылған шикізатты Қазақстанның әр аймағындағы және әр түрлі жастағы ірі қараның сүйектерінен жинайтын болған. Жетіген - Қазақ халқының көп ішекті шертпелі аспабы. Жалпы тұрқы ұзынша, жәшік тектес етіп жасалады. Бетіне жұқа тақтайдан қақпақ жабылып, үн беретін ойықтары салынады.

Музыкалық аспаптарға да жеті саны тараған баолатын. Мысалы: Жетіген — жасалуы да, айналу әдіс-тәсілі де өте күрделі аспап. Ертеректе ел арасында сақталған көне Жетігеннің ішегі аттың қылынан тағылып, тиектің орнына асықтар пайдаланылатын болған. Аспаптың құлақ күйі осы асықтарды әрлі-берлі жылжыту арқылы келтірілген. Ішек сандары жетеу болғандықтан, аспап Жетіген аталған. Жетігеннің ноталық жүйесін анықтаған ғалым - зерттеуші Б. Сарыбаев болды. Жетіген аспабына байланысты оны ертеде жеті ұлынан айырылған күйші - өнерпаз жасап, “Жетігеннің жеті күйін” шығарыпты дейтін аңыз бар. Аспаптық-фольклорлық музыкамызда ерекше орын алатын бұл аспап 1970 жылдан бері Т. Сарыбаев, Е. Құсайынов, С. Мерекеев, т. б. музыкашылардың орындауында жаңаша сипатқа ие болды. Жетіген аспабының қазіргі шеберлер жасаған үлгісінің дыбыс ауқымы 2 — 2, 5 октаваға дейін жеткізілді. Қазақ халық музыка аспаптары мұражайында Жетіген аспабының этнографиялық сипаттамалар бойынша жасалған көне үлгісі мен жетілдірілген үлгілері сақталған.

Негізгі бөлімде біз Фибоначчи сандарын табиғаттағы үйлесімділігі мен 7 санының табиғат пен ырымдармен байланысын қарастыратын боламыз.

WORK ON SPELLING IN MORPHOLOGY TRAINING

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The main purpose of the mother tongue, which is a powerful educational tool, is to form correct writing and speaking habits, which is impossible to achieve without mastering language rules and norms at the appropriate level.

The level of grammar knowledge given to students in grades V-VII differs from the elementary school level, and each rule and definition is relatively complicated, adapted to the age and meaning capabilities of the students. In the understanding of the scientific essence of the language, the principle of consistency and inheritance is expected, and its being a means of thinking, learning and speaking is put in the spotlight.

Through this subject at the primary level, students who acquire expressive and conscious reading, correct written and oral speech habits, are familiar with the lexical, phonetic, grammatical and stylistic richness of speech, and are able to get to the essence of practically necessary language rules, improve their knowledge, skills and habits at the secondary school level also deepens, their cognitive activity and speech skills develop further. Students develop a conscious love and respect for their mother tongue.

The grammatical laws and rules of the language operate on the basis of certain linguistic regularities, and the language as a whole system has a mechanism of action as precise as the natural sciences.

The teaching of language rules on the basis of comprehensible regularities turns it into a system that specifies the directions of experience and application of the acquired knowledge, as well as ensuring the cognitive activity and awareness of the students. The teacher should approach the mastery of language rules seriously, and should take into account succession and perspective when providing scientific information.

The internal regularities operating in the language system regulate it and ensure the existence of the language. At one end of this system is the phoneme, which is the smallest language unit (meaningful sound), and at the other end is the sentence, which is the most perfect construction of language units. Within this system, each section and subsection, each language unit has its own task. It is impossible to study the language in a scientific way and to understand it as a whole system without knowing the laws of combination of sounds in words and words in sentences and the reasons for various language phenomena that occur at this time.

One of the sections, rules, prepares the ground for the other, it plays the role of a key for the section and rule to be understood in the future. From this point of view, after the rules related to phonetics, lexis, and word creation, the study of language rules related to morphology is a language regularity, and this section to be studied also acts as a basis for learning the language rules related to syntax.

The systematic study of the language rules related to morphology will serve both to remember the language rules that have been mastered at first, to understand the theoretical knowledge of the section itself on a scientific basis, and to effectively learn the rules related to syntax in the future.

The initial assimilation of the language rules related to morphology, the provision of basic concepts, is started from the primary classes, and it is at that stage that the ground is created for the provision of further in-depth information. Already in elementary grades, students master the

minimum knowledge of the morphological structure of the language in the form of simple, clear rules and comments, while mastering the rules of the language, mastering the important speech skills and being able to apply it in practice.

Morphology training can give more efficient and effective results when its teaching is coordinated with other sections. When teaching all topics from morphology, the teacher should try to connect them as much as possible with phonetics and lexicology passed before morphology, and with syntax to be taught after that. More precisely, the discussion of morphology should be connected with phonetics and lexicology, and should create a basis for teaching syntax. When we say connection, it should not be meant to simply artificially compare any topic with a topic that will be discussed today. Both old knowledge and skills should be remembered, and new ones should be mastered in a conscious way by using these connections and similarities of related and similar topics.

In particular, it is impossible to do without phonetics when giving information about orthography and spelling or doing practical work. It is pointless to try to master the rise, fall, and change of sound without taking into account the phonetic phenomena and laws, and without memorizing them.

It is impossible not to remember the information about the lexical and grammatical meaning while learning the grammatical meanings of the words, and the lexical meanings of the words while passing the separate parts of speech. When teaching nouns and adjectives, one should not forget the knowledge and skills of students about word groups such as homonyms, synonyms, antonyms. It is impossible to determine the boundaries of complex verbs without remembering the knowledge and skills of phraseological units. All such comparisons are not related for the sake of relatedness, but related to the requirements of the principle of interrelatedness. The teacher should identify this need while preparing the lesson and be prepared for such comparisons.

Trying to create a foundation for syntax during the training of morphology both facilitates the work of teaching syntax in the future and provides a scientific basis for the exact separation of morphological concepts and syntactic concepts.

Therefore, during the teaching of morphology, contrasting a number of morphological concepts with syntactic concepts helps to master the morphological concepts themselves. In this regard, while going through all the parts of speech, it is very necessary to teach their role in the sentence. Special attention should be paid to teaching not only the main, but also the role of auxiliary parts of speech in a sentence. By learning the role of the noun, adjective and other parts of speech in the sentence, the student will be able to accurately master the similarities and differences of the concepts of the part of the sentence and the part of speech, and will not confuse them in the future. However, it is not possible to achieve this by studying the role of parts of speech in a sentence only in the teaching of morphology.

During the teaching of syntax, the work started in the subject of morphology is completed by teaching the means of expression of all sentence members. In this regard, special attention should be paid to teaching the role of parts of speech in a sentence. For example, an adjective is not always defined. Because an adjective can become a noun in a sentence and become a member of another sentence. Although this noun can be used at the beginning of another noun and become its definition, it does not come out of the noun. When paying attention to such issues, students are able to distinguish morphological and syntactic concepts, morphological and syntactic questions, which is of great importance.

The knowledge and skills to be imparted on morphology have an important role in mastering a number of literary language norms. The Azerbaijani language teacher should be able to use these possibilities of morphology training in the acquisition of speech development habits of students.

First of all, the conscious delivery of grammatical concepts greatly helps students to master common grammatical norms in their speech. A person who is not able to solve the word correctly and change the verb correctly according to the tense, he cannot acquire normal speech habits because he cannot even expect normal grammatical norms in his speech. Therefore, the teacher should provide students with the most necessary knowledge about grammatical concepts and concepts, and also take care of their acquisition of the skills specified in the program for individual sections.

Morphology training can also play an important role in students' acquisition of pronunciation norms. In this respect, the work started in phonetics on acquiring orthoepic habits is completed in morphology training. Teaching students the rules of pronunciation of all morphemes should be one of the main tasks of morphology education. For example, the teacher should teach the students how to pronounce the infinitive suffix -maq, -mæk, as well as how to pronounce them correctly. It is necessary to learn that the consonant Q should be pronounced as ğ, and the consonant k as y. It is important to work on pronunciation rules for all morphemes.

Morphology training also plays an important role in students' acquisition of orthographic norms. In parallel with the pronunciation of all morphemes, writing should also be taught practically. For example, in addition to teaching the pronunciation of the infinitive suffix -mag, -mak, the teacher is also obliged to teach its spelling. Students are taught that when a vowel is added to the suffix -maq, -mæk, the consonant q becomes ğ, and the consonant k becomes y and is written. In the subject of morphology, it is the teacher's main task to conduct practical work on their pronunciation and writing rules while teaching all word-correcting and word-modifying suffixes. This plays an important role in their acquisition of orthographic and orthographic norms.

Morphology training can play an important role in mastering a number of stylistic norms and enriching students' speech with style. The teacher is also obliged to carry out concrete work on the assimilation of stylistic norms. For example, when teaching the cases of nouns, when the teacher works on the possibility of giving the same idea in several forms, when expressing the work of one time form of the verb with another time, the students acquire stylistic norms and can have a sensitive stylistic attitude towards speech.

The main purpose of teaching the mother tongue in high school is to inculcate high speaking skills in students, to teach forms of information exchange, and to provide them with the ability to express their ideas freely, creatively, critically and logically based on written and oral communication at various points of communication. What does the teacher do? What does the student do? It is difficult to respond to the requirements of the modern lesson without establishing teaching-learning activities in the form of education, without creating sources of motivation and conscious "scientific conflict", without giving the student the opportunity to put forward his own idea, hypothesis, and take away his conclusions.

Of course, in the teaching of separate parts of speech, more attention should be paid to the morphological principle, which is one of the main principles of spelling. The essence of this principle is determined by providing a stable expression of the meaningful parts of each word that can be divided. The morphological principle regulates the uniform pronunciation and uniform spelling of words. For example, in pronunciation we find the suffix form nan, nan, mennan, atamnan, etc. In such a case, we should accept the suffix of speech in two ways -dan,-dan and -nan,-nan. However, such a fixed rule has been adopted that the case suffix of the noun is pronounced as nan, nen after the words ending with the consonants -dan, -dan, -m, -n. The morphological principle is also based on the pronunciation of the word. Or, when polysyllabic words ending in vowels a and a are joined by a suffix with a connecting consonant y at the beginning, according to the law of harmony, those vowels become one of the sounds и, и, y, y and are pronounced: kosyaye-meshiya, anaya-anyiya, kayaya-kaiyaya, etc.

Therefore, in the teaching of the cases of the noun, it is impossible to pass without touching these orthographic and orthoepic rules. In school practice, there are many methods and means to ensure the expectation of the application of spelling rules in the teaching of morphological categories. Let's talk about these methods briefly.

Of course, in order to effectively use this type of analysis, first of all, it is necessary to set up phonetic-orthoepic analysis examples correctly. It is the phonetic-orthoepic analysis that is the foundation and cornerstone of correct spelling and pronunciation rules. Students will encounter difficulties in morphological analysis if they cannot analyze the spelling and pronunciation norms here.

Morphological analysis means analysis both according to the composition of the word and according to the parts of speech.

During the analysis according to the composition of the word, the dependent parts of the word, lexical (word correcting), grammatical (word modifying) suffixes, the initial form of the word should be mastered accurately, the analysis according to the composition should be carried out with existing conventional signs. In this case, root, word-correcting, word-changing suffixes should be used.

During morphological analysis, the pronunciation of words and suffixes should be focused. For example, if the word is analyzed from the baskets, the word must be analyzed in the correct order in the baskets. When words are analyzed based on pronunciation, it becomes easier to remove the defects from dialects and dialects. For example, I come, I see, I see, I see, etc. both incorrect and correct pronunciation norms of the words are written on the board, during the analysis the student feels that the difference is in the pronunciation of the present tense.

Morphological analyzes are carried out in complete and incomplete form. Analyzes conducted on separate parts of speech and their separate categories are incomplete, analyzes conducted on all parts of speech and categories are considered a complete analysis example. For example, an analysis of the case of a noun can be considered as an example of an incomplete analysis. If the teacher wants to conduct a full analysis of nouns, first of all, their concrete and abstract, structural types, general and specific, affiliation, change according to the person, cases should be mastered in sequence.

Conducting such analyzes within the possibilities of interactive training will attract students to more independent thinking and activity. For example, a specific piece of poetry may be given to separate groups or pairs, and it may be required to determine the orthographically characteristic words related to the topic and determine the spelling order.

This rule creates conditions for cooperation in training, exchange of ideas, mutual trust.

Analyzes and practical exercises on morphology are of great importance in their acquisition of correct pronunciation and correct writing habits by creating a wide opportunity for independent activity of students.

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Azərbaycan dili dərslərində nitq inkişafı və üslubiyyatla bağlı məsələlər

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Açar söz: üslubiyyat, nitq inkişafı, ana dili

Üslubiyyatla bağlı orta məktəblərimizdə aparılan işlər şagirdlərin nitq inkişafı istiqamətində görülən işlərdən ən başlıcasıdır. Azərbaycan dili təliminin qarşısında duran başlıca vəzifələrdən biri də şagirdlərin nitq vərdişlərini inkişaf etdirmək, onların ədəbi dilə mükəmməl yiyələnməsinə nail olmaqdır. Üslubiyyat üzrə işlərin şagirdlərin nitq inkişafında mühüm roluna aid ilk tədqiqatı prof. H.Balıyev aparmış, Ə.Kəlbəliyev və başqaları da bu mövzudan bəhs etmişlər. Onlar üslubiyyat üzrə aparılan işlərin təcrid olunmuş şəkildə deyil, lüğət üzrə, ədəbi tələffüz vərdişləri, cümlə qurmaq və rəbitəli nitq vərdişlərinin inkişafı üzrə aparılan işlərin məktəblərimizdə hələ də günün tələbləri səviyyəsində olmadığını nəzərə alaraq, üslubiyyat məşğələlərindən daha geniş şəkildə bəhs etməyi zəruri hesab etmişlər. Üslubiyyat məşğələlərinin məzmununa isə Azərbaycan dili leksik və qrammatik üslubi imkanlarının praktik şəkildə öyrədilməsini, nitqin dəqiqliyi, yığcamlığı və bədiliyi üzrə işləri daxil etmişlər.

Ümumiyyətlə linqvistika termini latınca "lingua" (dil) sözündən və yunan mənşəli "istika" şəkilçisindən əmələ gəlmişdir. Dünya dilçilik ədəbiyyatında linqvistika beynəlxalq elmi termin kimi qiymətləndirilir. Xüsusən ingilis və fransız dillərində dil haqqında elm anlayışını bildirmək üçün müəyyən fərqli variantda linqvistika termini işlədilir.

Nəzəri linqvistika dilçiliyin ayrı-ayrı bölmələri üzrə dil qaydalarını, fonetik, leksik, qrammatik məfhumları, onların funksiyasını, qrammatik quruluşu və s. araşdırırsa, tətbiqi linqvistika alınmış nəzəri biliyin tətbiq edilməsini, nitqdə nə cür reallaşmasını və s. araşdırır. Bir sözlə, fonetik məfhumlar, sözlərin leksik-semantik mahiyyəti, qrammatik məfhumlar və anlayışlar, sintaktik vahidlər bütövlükdə linqvistikanın araşdırdığı predmetlərdir.

Linqvistik təhlil də məhz tətbiqi linqvistika termini ilə bağlı olub, Azərbaycan dili fənninin tədrisində istifadə edilən çox mühüm spesifik təlim metodudur. Linqvistik təhlil termini Azərbaycan dili tədrisi metodikasına aid metodik ədəbiyyatda ilk dəfə Ə.Əfəndizadə tərəfindən "Azərbaycan dili təliminin metodları və onların təkmilləşdirilməsi haqqında" məqaləsində işlədilmişdir. Ə.Əfəndizadə linqvistik təhlili çalışmaları üzərində iş, dil faktları üzərində müşahidə və imla metodları ilə bir sırada dili nəzəri-praktik cəhətdən öyrənməyə xidmət edən şagirdlərdə ancaq müvafiq bacarıq, vərdişlər aşılayan, verilmiş biliyi möhkəmləndirən metod kimi qəbul edirdi.

Leksikologiyada sözü aşağıdakı cəhətlərinə görə öyrənirlər: Sözü dilin lüğət tərkibindəki rolu, mövqeyi, sözlərin mənşə qruplarına görə və işlənmə dairəsinə görə növləri, sözlərin mənə qruplarına görə növləri, sözlərin dilin lüğət tərkibindəki aktiv və passiv roluna görə qrupları və s. Bu sadaladığımızı müəllim dərslərində müxtəlif resurslara söykənərək öyrətməyə çalışmalıdır.

Linqvistik təhlilin metod, üsul, vasitə, priyom, yol və s. adlandırılması ilə bağlı Azərbaycan dili tədrisi metodikasında zaman-zaman müxtəlif fikirlər söylənilmişdir. A.Abdullayev linqvistik təhlili Azərbaycan dili təlimində istifadə olunan yollar sırasına daxil etmiş, onu dərslərində asılı olaraq "vasitə", "məşğələ növü", "çalışma növü" adlandırmışdır.

Linqvistik təhlil həm metod kimi, həm də üsul, priyom kimi istifadə oluna bilər. Bu hər şeydən öncə dərslərində asılıdır. Əgər müəllim yeni bilik verən dərslərini (deduktiv) linqvistik təhlillə tədris edərsə, bu zaman linqvistik təhlil metodudur. Fikrimizcə, bu daha səmərəlidir. Deduksiya (lat.

deductio - izah etmək, nəticə çıxarmaq) əqli nəticənin bir növüdür. Deduksiya elə bir əqli nəticədir ki, verilmiş predmet və hadisələrə əsaslanaraq yeni nəticə hasil edilir. Burada fikir ümumidən konkretə doğru gedir. Deduksiyada müəyyən hökmlərdən istifadə etməklə predmet və hadisələr haqqında yeni bilik əldə olunur. Əlbəttə, lingvistik təhlillə aparılan deduktiv dərslər tipində digər pedaqoji üsullardan da (müqayisə, müsahibə, diskussiya və s.) məqsədyönlü şəkildə istifadə edilir. Leksikologiya təlimi “Söz və onun leksik mənası” mövzusunun tədrisi ilə başlayır. Sözü leksik mənası dərindən dərk edilməsə, digər mövzuların da (qrammatik məna, həqiqi və məcazi məna, təkmənalı və çoxmənalı sözlər, omonim, sinonim və antonimlər və s.) tədrisində və qavranılmasında çətinliklər yaranacaq. İbtidai sinif şagirdlərinə izah edilməlidir ki, sözü leksik mənası onun əsas və həlledici mənasıdır. Dilin leksik tərkibinə daxil olan sözlərin vasitəsilə təklidə ifadə olunan konkret məna leksik məna adlanır. Şagirdlər çox vaxt leksik şəkilçi ilə qrammatik şəkilçini qarışıq salırlar. Leksik məna sözü ilk və başlıca mənasıdır. Bir sözü leksik mənası digər sözü leksik mənasından konkret və müəyyən bir əşya ilə əlaqədar olmasına görə fərqlənir. Məsələn, “qələm” sözü tələffüz etdiyimiz zaman onun ifadə etdiyi ilkin məna leksik mənadır: yəni, yazmaq üçün istifadə edilən əşya. Bu sözü leksik mənası ilə yanaşı, qrammatik mənası da vardır: ümumi qrammatik mənasına görə isimdir, nə sualına cavab verir, sadədir, ümumidir, konkretidir və s.

Dilçiliyin digər bölmələrinin tədrisinə nisbətən orta məktəbdə leksikologiyanın müstəqil bir bölmə kimi öyrənilməsinə bir qədər gec, ötən əsrin 70-ci illərindən başlanılmışdır. Bu vaxta qədər leksika məsələləri fonetika və qrammatikanın təlim problemlərinin daxilində əridilir, hətta bəzi tədqiqatçılar qrammatikadan sistemli kurs tamamlanmadan leksika və frazeologiya təliminin qeyri mümkünlüyündən danışdılar. Nəhayət, 1992 və 2002-ci il tədris proqramlarında leksikanı müstəqil bir bölmə kimi V sinifdə tədris etmək nəzərdə tutuldu. Dilimizin leksikasının sistemli öyrənilməsinə isə XX əsrin 50-ci illərindən etibarən başlanılmış, S.Cəfərov, A.Qurbanov, H.Həsənov, N.Xudiyev, B.Xəlilovun onlarla dərslük və monoqrafiyası bu sahənin tədqiqinə həsr olunmuşdu. Kurikuluma görə leksikanın əsas elementləri (sözü leksik və qrammatik mənası, məcazi mənalıma, çoxmənalılıq, omonim, sinonim, antonim, arxaizmlər və frazeoloji birləşmələr) V sinifdə “Niyə belə deyirik” bölməsindəki mətnlər kontekstində tədris olunur. Dərslükdəki söz ehtiyatı istiqaməti üzrə işlər isə birbaşa şagirdlərin lüğət fondunun zənginləşməsinə və leksik bacarıqların formalaşmasına gətirib çıxarır.

Hər hansı sözü ilk mənasından əmələ gələn yeni mənalara onun məna çalarlığı adlanır. Biz məfhumun müxtəlif məna çalarlığını ifadə edən sözlərə çoxmənalı sözlər deyirik. Dilimizdə isə sözlərin çoxmənalılığı böyük əhəmiyyət kəsb edir. Çoxmənalı sözlərdə onun daşdığı mənalardan biri öz konkret mənası daxilində ehtiva edir, söz ilk mənasından ayrılıb çoxmənalılıq kəsb edəndə məcazi mənaya malik olur. Sözü çoxmənalılığı söz yaradıcılığı prosesinin ayrılmaz hissəsini təşkil edir. Şagirdlərin sözləri qeyri-dəqiq mənada bilmələrinin bir səbəbi də sözü çoxmənalılığını bilməməkdən irəli gəlir. Çoxmənalı sözlər vahid bir sözü sonrakı inkişafının nəticəsidir ki, bu cəhət də dilimizin üslubi imkanlarını artırır və söz üçün mətnin nə dərəcədə böyük əhəmiyyətə malik olduğunu göstərir.

Çoxmənalı sözlərin bütün məna çalarları eyni hüquqa malik deyil. Bu mənalardan biri həmin sözü ilk həqiqi, müstəqil mənası, qalanları isə törəmə-məcazi mənalardır. İbtidai sinif şagirdlərinin səhvi məhz bu fərqi ayıra bilməməkdir. Ona görə də aşağı siniflərdən başlayaraq şagirdləri sözlərin çoxmənalılığı ilə tanış etmək vacibdir. Bu işi aşağıdakı qaydada əyaniləşdirib başa salmaq olar:

Göz – bədənin bir üzvü; stolun gözü; bulağın gözü; iynənin gözü; uşaqların gözü (fərqləndirmə); bir göz otaq.

Burada birinci məna əsas, qalanları isə törəmə mənalardır. Sözü ikinci mənası adətən məcazi olur. Lüğət ehtiyatının zənginləşdirilməsi nöqtəyi-nəzərindən diqqəti cəlb edən cəhət ikinci mənanın yeni emosional eksspressiv çalarlığa malik olmasıdır. Sözü həqiqi mənası konkret

surətdə əşya, hadisə, proses və s. bildirirsə, məcazi mənə əşyanın əlamətlərinin tutuşdurulmasına əsaslanır.

Ana dili dərslərində şagirdlərin ən çox çətinlik çəkdiyi məsələlərdən biri də omonimlərlə çoxmənalı sözlərin ayırd edilməsi məsələsidir. Çoxmənalı sözlərə dilimizin demək olar ki, bütün əsas nitq hissələrində təsadüf edilir. Bunların içərisində kəmiyyət etibarilə isimlər və feillər çoxluq təşkil edir. Fikrimizcə, fəal dərstdə müəllimin seçdiyi metoddan asılı olaraq şagirdlərə omonimlərlə çoxmənalı sözlərin fərqli xüsusiyyətlərini özündə əks etdirən cədvəl və ya slayd mümayiş etdirilməlidir. Ənənəvi təlim zamanı dərslərində daha çox Venn diaqramından istifadə olunurdu. Fərqli və oxşar xüsusiyyətləri bir cədvəldə görən şagird mövzunu yaxşı mənimsəyir, hafizəsinə həkk edir.

Hər hansı sözün ilk mənasından əmələ gələn yeni mənalar onun mənə çalarlığı adlanır. Bu məfhumun müxtəlif mənə çalarlığını ifadə edən sözlərə çoxmənalı-polisemantik sözlər deyilir. Müasir Azərbaycan dilində çoxmənalı sözlərin olduqca böyük əhəmiyyəti vardır. Bu onu göstərir ki, sözlərin çoxmənalılıq kəsb etmə prosesi dilimizdə ən qədim dövrlərdən fəal şəkildə mövcud olmuşdur. Çoxmənalı sözlərdə onun daşdığı mənələrdən biri də öz konkret ifadəsini ancaq mətnin daxilində alır. Söz öz ilk müstəqim mənasından ayrılıb çoxmənalılıq kəsb edəndə məcazi mənə bildirir.

Nitq inkişafı üzrə işin başlıca istiqamətlərindən biri üslubiyyət üzrə işlərdir. Ümumtəhsil məktəblərində üslubiyyət ayrıca tədris olunmasa da, fonetik, leksik və qrammatik üslubi imkanları şagirdlərə öyrətmədən onların nitqinin inkişafına nail olmaq mümkün deyildir.

Üslubiyyət bəhsində bu və ya digər dilin üslubi imkanları öyrənilir. Dilçilikdə “üslub” dil vasitələrindən məqsədyönlü istifadə üsuludur. Dil vahidlərinin vəzifə əlaqələri, qarşılıqlı əvəzlənmə imkanları, sinonim münasibətləri və bunların müxtəlif nitq hissələrinə paylaşması, ifadə vasitələrinin sistemi üzrə formalaşan üslublar – üslubiyyətin mövzusunu təşkil edir.

Məhz burada səslərin, sözlərin, ifadələrin, cümlələrin mənə və təsir qüvvəsi cəhətdən seçilməsi, hansının məqsədə daha çox uyğun olmasını müəyyənləşdirmək yolları araşdırılır. Dilçiliyin bir sahəsi kimi üslubiyyətə dilin ifadə vasitələrinin məqsədəuyğun olaraq istifadə qaydalarından, müxtəlif üslubların əlamətdar cəhətlərindən bəhs edən bir elm kimi tərif verilmişdir.

Eyni zamanda üslubiyyətin mövzu və vəzifəsi, onun həcmi və quruluşunu daha da müəyyənləşdirmək üçün şərait yaradır. Belə ki, üslubiyyət dilin bütün vahidləri ilə, xüsusən də dilin lüğət tərkibi və qrammatik quruluşu ilə daha sıx bağlıdır.

Şagirdlərin istər yazılı, istərsə də şifahi nitq vərdişlərini inkişaf etdirmək məsələsi ana dili təlimi qarşısında duran əsas vəzifələrdən biridir. Qrammatikanın tədrisində lüğət üzrə leksik çalışmalara geniş yer verilir. Belə çalışmalar lüğət-qrammatik və lüğət-orfoqrafik olmaqla iki qismə ayrılır. Birinci növ çalışmalar sözün hansı nitq hissəsinə daxil olmasını müəyyənləşdirməyi, sözə qohum sözlər, sinonim, antonim tapmağı, çoxmənalılıq üzrə məşq etməyi, sözləri qruplaşdırmağı, növ, cins əlaqələrini aydınlaşdırmağı və s. tələb edərsə, ikinci növ çalışmalar heç bir qayda ilə yoxlanmayan, yaxud qrammatik əlamətlərin mürəkkəbliyinə görə yazılışı çətin sözlərin yazılması üzrə işləməyi tələb edir.

Şagirdlərin ibtidai siniflərdən lüğət üzrə və ya leksik bilik və bacarıqlara yiyələnmələri zərurəti özünü göstərir. Ətrafdakılarla ünsiyyət, oxu, müşahidələr və praktik işlər şagirdlərin lüğət ehtiyatını yeni sözlər və terminlərlə zənginləşdirir. Bu prosesdə onların nitqi həm kəmiyyət, həm də keyfiyyətə zənginləşir.

Tədqiqatçılarımız nitq vərdişləri üzrə aparılan işlərdə ilk növbədə lüğət ehtiyatı üzrə işləri ön plana çəkir. Bu məqsədlə dərslər vəsaitlərinin və eləcə də məktəbdənkənar sinifdən xaric oxu materiallarının xüsusi rolu vardır.

Orta məktəbdə lüğət ehtiyatının zənginləşdirilməsi işi müxtəlif istiqamətlərdə aparılır ki, bura lüğətin genişləndirilməsi, dəqiqləşdirilməsi, fəallaşdırılması və eləcə də lüğətin təmizliyi üzrə

aparılan işlər daxildir. Bir çox hallarda şagirdlərin nitq mədəniyyəti onların dilimizin leksik zənginliklərinə necə yiyələnmələrindən, şəxsi lüğət ehtiyatının həcmindən və keyfiyyətindən asılı olur. Dilin elə bir sahəsi yoxdur ki, sözlə bağlı olmasın. Söz üzərində işi düzgün və səmərəli təşkil etmək üçün onun xarakteristikasını bilmək lazımdır. Yəhya Kərimov yazır ki, “sözün səslərdən ibarət olması onu fonetika ilə, varlığın hər hansı hadisəsini, əşyasını adlandırması, başqa sözlə, məna kəsb etməsi onu leksika ilə, müəyyən qrammatik formada olması onu qrammatika ilə əlaqələndirir” [2, s.471].

Şagirdin lüğət ehtiyatının genişləndirilməsi zamanı yeni sözlərin izahından, danışıda obrazlı ifadələrlə bağlı işlərdən istifadə olunmalıdır. Lüğət ehtiyatını genişləndirmək üçün bədii mətnlər, eləcə də çalışma üzrə işlər daha məqsədəuyğundur.

Sözlərin mənalarnı bütün incəlikləri ilə izah etmək də bu işin həyata keçməsinin əsas yollarından biridir. İbtidai sinif müəllimi eyni zamanda sözlərin həqiqi və eləcə də məcazi mənalarnın şagirdə öyrətmək üzərində çalışmalıdır. Bu yolla da, müəllim şagirdin lüğətinin dəqiqləşdirilməsinə nail olur.

Lüğət ehtiyatının zənginləşdirməyin bir istiqaməti də lüğətin fəallaşdırılmasıdır. Bu zaman bir sıra vasitələrdən istifadə olunur. Bunlardan biri də sözləri müxtəlif mənalarda işlətməkdir. Bu tapşırıqlar üzərində işləməklə şagirdlərin lüğəti fəallaşır. Daha sonra onlarla bir və ya bir neçə sözü cümlədə işlətmək, frazeoloji vahidləri nitqdə olduğu kimi işlətmək məqsədəuyğundur. Şagird lüğətini fəallaşdırmağa kömək edən vasitələrdən biri də onları xalqımızın şifahi yaradıcılığının nümunələri olan atalar sözlərindən, zərb məsəllərdən danışıda istifadə etmək, onlardan yerli yerində işlətmək bacarığı aşılamaqdır.

Şagirdin lüğətini fəallaşdırmağa verilmiş hər hansı bir şəkil üzərində nağıl etmək də kömək edə bilər. Məsələn, savad təlimi dövründə şagird şəkil əsasında öz fikrini ifadə edir. Şəkil üzərində danışmaq zamanı şagird lazımı söz ehtiyatına malik olmaq üçün formalaşmalı, eyni zamanda həmin sözləri yerində işlətməyi bacarmalıdır. Bu da müəllimdən, həqiqətən də böyük zəhmət və ustalıq tələb edir.

Nitq inkişafı üzrə aparılan işlər zamanı şagirdlərin yazılı və şifahi rabitəli nitqində müxtəlif üslub səhvləri müşahidə olunur ki, bunları leksik-üslubi və qrammatik üslubi səhvlərə bölürlər. Bəzən şagird yazısında sözlər öz yerində işlədilmir. Belə sözlər şagirdin sinonim seçmək bacarığının düzgün formalaşmadığından irəli gəlir. Yaxınmənalı sözlərdən hansını işlətməyin doğru, dəqiq olduğunu şagirdlər fərqləndirə bilmirlər. İstər yazılı, istərsə də şifahi nitqdə bu qəbildən olan üslub səhvlərinə tez-tez yol verilir. Bunun qarşısını almaq üçün müəllim şagirdə həmin səhvin öz düzgün məqamında işlədilmiş sözdən fərqi izah etməlidir. Bunun üçün eyni sinonim qrupunda birləşən müxtəlif leksemləri tapmalı, işlətmə məqamına görə müqayisə etməyi bacarmalıdır. Üslubi səhvlər dedikdə, məsələn, nitqdə rus sözlərinin tez-tez işlədilməsidir. Təcrübəli və peşəkar müəllim nitqində rus sözlərindən istifadə etməməlidir.

Müəllim müxtəlif məzmunlu çalışmalar üzərində şagirdləri çalışdırmaqla yazılı və şifahi nitqdə olan belə üslub səhvlərinin aradan qaldırılmasına nail ola bilər. Nitq inkişafı üzrə aparılan iş zamanı rast gəlinən digər üslubi səhv cümlədə artıq, lüzumsuz sözlərin işlədilməsidir. Burada əsas məsələ həmin sözlərin cümlədə artıq olduğunu şagirdə izah etmək və onun nitqinin səlisliyi üzərində ardıcıl iş aparmaqdır.

Bəzən şagird nitqində, müxtəlif mövzularda yazılan inşa yazılarda, ifadə yazılarda, habelə yazıya hazırlıq zamanı şagirdin şifahi cavabında dialekt sözləri eşidir. Belə qüsurlar da leksik-üslubi səhvlərə aid edilir. Bu tip səhvlərin aradan götürülməsi üzrə iş apararkən, həmin dialektlərin ədəbi dil qarşılığını şagirdlərə öyrətmək məqsədəuyğundur.

Şagirdlərə nitq inkişafı üzrə aparılan işlərin əsas istiqaməti kimi onlara öz fikir, hisslərini, duyğu və düşüncələrini düzgün, səlis, ardıcıl şəkildə ifadə etmək vərdişləri aşılamaq müəllimin öhdəsinə düşür. Sintaktik-üslubi səhvlər kimi ifadə və inşa yazılarında cümlədə fikrin dəqiq ifadəsini şərtləndirən üzlərin, məsələn, tamamlığın, zərfliyin buraxılması müşahidə olunur ki, bu da fikrin

dəqiq başa düşülməsini çətinləşdirir. Nitqdə bu növ üslub səhvlərinə yol verilməsi əsasən, ona görə baş verir ki, yazı və danışiq zamanı şagirdlər ayrı-ayrı cümlələrin üslubi dəqiqliyinə nəzər salmırlar. Cümlədə buraxılmış hər hansı bir üzvün ondan əvvəlki cümlələrdən başa düşüldüyü hesab olunur.

Nitqin əsas keyfiyyətləri haqqında yığcam bir şəkildə aşağıdakıları qeyd etmək olar:

Nitqin aydınlığı. Aydınlıq dinləyici və oxucunun asanlıqla anlaması, başa düşülməsidir. Nitq zamanı aydınlığın pozulmasının bir səbəbi də dili, sözlərin mənasını, işlənmə məqamını və s. yaxşı bilməmək, zəngin söz ehtiyatına sahib olmamaqdır. Nitqin aydınlığını yaradan amillərdən biri də diksiyadır. Natiqlik praktikasında nitqin diksiya baxımından aydınlığı və düzgünlüyü böyük əhəmiyyət kəsb edir.

Nitqin yığcamlığı. Burada yığcamlıq dedikdə, müxtəsərlik, fikrin qısa və aydın, lakonik şəkildə ifadə olunması nəzərdə tutulur.

Nitqin təmizliyi. Mədəni nitqə verilən əsas tələblərdən biri də onun təmizliyidir. Bu o deməkdir ki, ədəbi dilin normalarına uyğun gəlməyən dil vahidləri (sözlər, ifadələr, frazeologizmlər, cümlələr və s.) nitqdə işlədilməməlidir. Nitqin təmizliyi digər mədəni keyfiyyətlər kimi, danışanın təhsili, mədəniyyəti və tərbiyəsi ilə bilavasitə əlaqədardır.

Nitqin düzgünlüyü. Nitqin bu keyfiyyətindən bəhs olunarkən çox zaman göstərilir ki, düzgünlük həm yazılı, həm də şifahi nitqdə qrammatik qaydalara əməl etməkdir.

Nitqin zənginliyi. Bu nitqdə işlənən dil ünsürlərinin müxtəlifliyi, rəngarəngliyi və çoxluğu. Nitqin zənginliyi və emosionallığını təmin edən amillərdən biri də intonasiyadır. Nitq zənginliyinin başlıca əlamətlərindən biri də onun məzmun cəhətdən dolğunluğudur.

Nitqdə ifadəlilik, emosionallıq müxtəlif vasitələrin köməyi ilə yaranır. Bura daxildir: intonasiya (melodiya, temp, tembr, vurğu, pauza, ritm, səsin gücü, səsin diapazonu), leksik vahidlər: sinonim və antonimlər, frazeoloji birləşmələr, atalar sözü, məcazi mənalı sözlər, təkrarlar, emosional nidalar və s.

Lüğət ehtiyatının zənginləşdirilməsində antonimlər də mühüm rol oynayır. Əlbəttə, ibtidai sinifdə əvvəlcə yaxınmənalı, əksmənalı kimi sözlər şagirdlərə öyrədilir.

Lüğət ehtiyatı üzrə aparılan işin digər bir tərkib hissəsi kimi əhəmiyyətli olan lüğət ehtiyatının təmizliyinə ibtidai siniflərdən etibarən çalışmaq lazımdır. Bu işə bütün sinifdənkənar və məktəbdənxaric işlər zamanı da diqqət yetirməli və orta məktəbin XI sinfinədək aparılmalıdır.

Lüğətin təmizliyi dedikdə, şagirdlərin leksikonuna daxil olan sözlərin ölçülüb-biçilməsi, ədəbi dilin normalarına uyğun olması nəzərdə tutulur. Ədəbi dilin leksik, qrammatik, orfoqrafik, fonetik və orfoepik normaları yerli şivələrdə pozulduğundan ibtidai mərhələdə dialektizmlər daha çox mühafizə olunur.

Nitq inkişafı üzrə aparılan işin digər bir əsas istiqaməti də şagirdlərin ədəbi tələffüz vərdişlərinin inkişaf etdirilməsi ilə bağlı aparılan işlərdir. Bu sahədə görülən işlər arasında orfoepiya üzrə işlər xüsusi yer tutur. Ədəbi tələffüz üzrə aparılan işlərə daha sonra intonasiya və fasilə, ritmik bölgülər və vurğu, habelə nitq sürəti və tonu üzrə işləri də aid etmək olar.

Dilimizdə başqa dillərdən keçmiş bəzi sözlərin vurğusunu müəyyənləşdirməkdə şagirdlər çətinlik çəkirlər.

Şagirdlərin ədəbi tələffüz vərdişlərinin inkişafı üçün müntəzəm iş aparılmalı, xarakterik bədii və ya elmi mətnləri şərti işarələrlə qeyd etməyə də onlar alışdırılmalıdırlar. Orfoepiya üzrə aparılan işlərdə şagirdlərə qəbul olunmuş orfoepik qaydalar öyrədilməli, həmin qaydaların oxuya tətbiqinə nail olunmalıdır.

Saitlərin tələffüzü ilə bağlı qaydalar ayrı, samitlərininki də ayrıca öyrədilməlidir. İntonasiya, fasilə və ritmik bölgülər üzrə işlər ədəbi tələffüz vərdişlərinin inkişafı üzrə aparılan işlərin mühüm tərkib hissəsidir. Müəllim sual və hiss-həyəcan ifadə etməyin fərqlərini şagirdlərə izah etməklə yanaşı, dilin bu rəngarəng vasitələrindən istifadə bacarığını önə çəkməlidir. Nitq inkişafı üzrə aparılan işlərin bir mühüm istiqaməti də cümlə qurmaq vərdişlərinin inkişaf etdirilməsidir. Nitq vərdişlərinin inkişafı üzrə aparılan işlərin digər istiqamətlərinə nisbətən, məktəblərimizdə cümlə

qurmaq vərdişlərinin inkişafı üzrə işlərin vəziyyəti lazım olan səviyyədə sayıla bilər. Həm şifahi, həm də yazılı nitq vərdişlərinin inkişafında mühüm rol oynayan bu vərdişlərin yaranması üçün müəllim rəngarəng yollardan və vasitələrdən istifadə edirlər.

Rabitəli nitq vərdişlərinin inkişafı nitq inkişafı üzrə işlərin xüsusi rolunu təşkil edir. Düzgün nitqə verilən üslubi tələblərin praktik şəkildə öyrədilməsi şagirdlərin nitqini üslubca zənginləşdirir.

Rabitəli nitqin inkişafına Azərbaycan dili proqramlarında geniş yer verilməsində məqsəd, şagirdlərə öz düşüncələrini düzgün şəkildə, aydın və səlis bir formada ifadə etmək vərdişlərini aşılamadır. Bu da şagirdin nitq mədəniyyətinin səviyyəsini yüksəltməyə xidmət edir. Nitqin üslubca səlis bir şəkildə olması məsələsi yalnız müəllimin ciddi səyi nəticəsində öz həllini tapa bilər. Lakin rabitəli nitqin inkişafı üzrə aparılan sərbəst imla, yaradıcı imla, ifadə və inşa yazılarda, habelə şifahi nitqdə şagirdlərin yol verdikləri üslub səhvlərinin aradan qaldırılmasına Azərbaycan dili müəllimlərimiz ciddi səy göstərirlər. Halbuki üslub səhvlərinin növünü, nə üçün baş verdiyini şagirdlərə başa salmaq, onların xarakterini izah etmək tələb olunur.

Şagirdlərdə nitq mədəniyyətini yüksəltmək kimi mürəkkəb bir işdə Azərbaycan dilinin leksikası üzrə aparılan üslubiyyət məşğələlərinin xüsusi rolu var. Təcrübə göstərir ki, nitq vərdişlərinin formalaşmaması, yaxud da düzgün qayda da inkişaf etməməsi şagird nitqində bir sıra çətinliklər törədir. Belə ki, söz ehtiyatının az olması, şagird leksikonu tərkibinin zəngin olmaması, fikrin ifadəsi zamanı sözlərdən yerli-yerində istifadə etmək vərdişlərinin olmaması onların danışıqında müxtəlif növ üslub xətlərinin əmələ gəlməsinə səbəb olur.

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UPBRINGING TOLERANCE AND CULTURE OF INTERNATIONAL DIALOGUE AMONG STUDENTS

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Abstract. Development of tolerance and culture of international dialogue among students, the awareness of the younger generation of their belonging to a particular ethnic group. Pedagogical conditions of the university intended to provide not only professional knowledge, but also to form a number of professionally significant and socially desirable qualities related to the interaction of human and social environment.

Keywords: tolerance, culture, interethnic communication, ethnos, ethnocultural, student environment, education

At the present stage of development of society, when not only adults, but also children are drawn into the sphere of interethnic conflicts, it is very important to combine in training and education the highly humanistic principles of spiritual culture such as religious tolerance, tolerance, national and universal values, not to lose the humanistic orientation of educating a growing personality, consider as much as possible ethnopedagogical and ethnopsychological characteristics. The modern conditions of ethnic diversity, in which the younger generation of multinational Kazakhstan grows and forms, are one of the sources of serious problems for society as a political, economic, religious, cultural space, as well as the education of ethnic tolerance.

The problem of interethnic communication has always been and will be relevant, it has always been of interest to scientists from many countries. Communication is a specific interpersonal interaction of people as members of society, representatives of certain social groups, cultures, and as an important component of a person's social existence, it is the source of his life, a condition for the formation of both society and personality. The need for communication is one of the basic needs of a social individual since a person cannot exist without communicating with other people.

The student environment is one of the most intense areas of interethnic contacts. Young people from almost all regions of Kazakhstan, countries of near and far abroad come to study in large cities. It is in higher educational institutions that representatives of a wide variety of ethnic groups meet, and various systems of world perception and worldview come into contact. As a result of these contacts, stereotypes of interethnic perception and behavior are fixed in many students. Student age, according to I.S. Kon, S.V. Saltsev and others, act as a special, completely independent stage of a person's life, during which he has and forms his own development environment, participates in such activities that today are as personally forming factors and

determine the model of his social behavior [1]. This is the stage of individualization, associated with the search for one's identity in the world, with the development of one's own worldview, with the definition of one's originality and uniqueness, with the development of one's own outlook on life. However, this is the period of the most active development of moral feelings, increased interest in moral problems. In general, student age from 18 to 22 is a decisive period in the development of ethnic identity, its strengthening and consolidation. During the period of study at a university, the ethnic identity of a young person expands the system of his ideas about the world and strengthens his place in it. Student age is a crisis transition between youth and adulthood, during which multidimensional, complex processes take place in the personality: the acquisition of an adult identity and a new attitude to the world.

In everyday life, the ethnicity of most students is not updated, and ethnic self-identification does not occupy a leading position. Despite this, students show a rather lively interest in various ethnic issues. At the same time, the existing elements of bias and negativism in national relations should be noted. Although many students have among their friends and close representatives of other nationalities, quite a significant number determine their attitude towards a person based on his ethnicity. A huge mobilizing factor for most students is an insult on a national basis or a negative assessment of the people to which a person belongs. It is this that most often leaves a deep imprint on a person's memory and makes them take any action. Another powerful factor in ethnic mobilization is involvement or empathy with some common success or achievement.

All this increases the responsibility of higher education for the future of the state, for which path it will take, and how the processes of interethnic interaction will develop. But, unfortunately, today in this direction this work is poorly carried out. And the modern education system does not guarantee the formation of positive interethnic attitudes. And the negative perception of one or another ethnic group that has taken shape in the student environment or the exclusivity of one's national group is doubly dangerous. After all, the future intellectual elite, which will determine life in the future, may become the carrier of negative attitudes in interethnic interaction.

In the conditions of communication, a communicative process is carried out, interaction, mutual influence of individuals occurs, mutual understanding arises.

The leading position in intercultural communication is occupied by the culture of interethnic communication of representatives of various ethno-national communities, where the determining factor is the ethnic tolerance of the individual. [2].

Ethnic tolerance is understood as a complex attitudinal formation of a personality. It is expressed in tolerance for someone else's way of life, other people's customs, traditions, mores, other feelings, opinions, and ideas. In accordance with the Declaration of the Principles of Tolerance adopted by UNESCO, tolerance is defined as a value and norm of civil society, manifested in the right to be different for all individuals of civil society; ensuring stable harmony between different confessions, political, ethnic and other social groups; respect for the diversity of the world's different cultures, civilizations and peoples; willingness to understand and cooperate with people who differ in appearance, language, beliefs and beliefs.

Ethnic tolerance of a person manifests itself in various critical situations of interpersonal and intrapersonal choice when ethnic stereotypes and norms for solving problems facing a person, developed in a different socio-cultural way of life, do not work, and new norms or stereotypes are in the process of their formation. Ethnic tolerance of an individual is revealed and, in a certain sense, arises in problem-conflict situations of interaction with representatives of other ethnic groups. Ethnic tolerance of a person cannot be studied in isolation from the processes of ethnic identification, since all ethnopsychological phenomena are facets of one holistic phenomenon - ethnic variability of a person [3].

Comparative and comparative consideration of the folk-pedagogical knowledge of different peoples, excludes the imposition of certain values, interethnic intolerance, contributes

not only to identifying the commonality of the spiritual origins of different ethnic groups, but also clearly illustrates that it is in the dialogue of cultures that the spirituality of an ethnic group, its humanistic values, is manifested. Such knowledge allows students to understand the relationship of national spiritual cultures, the ability to think analytically, comparing the categories of “private” and “general”, the relationship of “national” and “international”, which contributes to the adoption of a general humanistic position.

The education and upbringing of the younger generations, while providing a mechanism for transmitting ethnic heritage to new generations, is also called upon to ensure integration processes, lay the foundations for understanding and communicating with other cultures, and aim at the ability to maintain and develop a dialogue of cultures. These tasks are best met by the process of ethnopedagogization of the university, during which the tasks of forming a culture of interethnic relations and fostering interethnic tolerance are optimally solved.

One of the main directions in solving the problems of educating a culture of interethnic communication can be an increase in the role of ethnopedagogy and ethnopsychology in educational programs. It is these disciplines that can vividly demonstrate and explain the specifics of the differences that lie in interethnic differences. Showing the unique essence of the most diverse cultures and demonstrating that the bearers of these cultures cannot think and feel in the same way can greatly contribute to increasing interethnic tolerance (tolerance). At the same time, special attention should be paid not only to theoretical training, but also to practical contacts between representatives of different cultures, both at the interstate level and within the country, where interethnic differences often turn out to be even more vivid.

In general, it is in the student environment that interethnic politics should be formed and disseminated. It is here that a common system of values and attitudes should be formed, ensuring the unity of the multinational Kazakh society. Modern students as the future intellectual elite of the country can become an active guarantor of the stable development of society.

When working with students, it must be remembered that many of them are future teachers who will have to pass on the acquired knowledge and formed attitudes to future generations. And modern research shows that we can talk about the presence of social and psychological factors that, to one degree or another, violate the adequacy of children's behavior in groups in which teachers work with inadequate forms of expression of ethnic self-consciousness. Children studying with teachers with an adequate positive form of expressing ethnic self-consciousness are better adapted in the microcommunity, their behavior is characterized by more flexible and harmonious ways of interacting with others. The educational system plays a special role in this process. The education system is designed to correct the negative manifestations of various kinds, to create conditions for the formation and dissemination of those value orientations that are preferable for both the individual and society.

The development of tolerance in education should take place through a dialogue of cooperation between the teaching and learning parties, the humanization of the educational process. It is necessary to enrich the content of training courses and programs of the humanities, social and natural sciences with multicultural topics, as well as to improve the teaching methods of all types of disciplines.

Based on invariant universal values, national and international values, paradigms of convergence and integration of spiritual values, the basic culture of the individual, its correspondence to the realities of the changing world should be formed and supported.

In multicultural educational institutions, more flexible, softer pedagogical systems and learning and development operations should be tested that contribute to the adaptation of the individual to culture through education. The special characteristics of pedagogical technologies during educational operations of multicultural education are cooperation, dialogue, activity-creative nature, focus on supporting, protecting the individual development of a person, providing

him with a free, protected space for making independent decisions, a variety of ways, forms, and techniques of creative self-expression of the individual in its cultural identification [4].

In an open multicultural educational space, a process is being implemented, the main goal of which is to create conditions that provide protection and support for the development of everyone. In accordance with this, it is advisable to introduce methods and technologies into the practice of work that contribute to an individual-personal approach to social development, adaptation of a person to an intercultural educational environment through various types of activities: activating the processes of self-knowledge, self-development, contributing to the development of reflection mechanisms; aimed at identifying the subjects of education, their most important needs and problems in organizing the process of pedagogical interaction, in which everyone has the opportunity to identify personally significant goals of life activity (individual sphere of self-realization); aimed at finding means and forms of adaptation, protection and support of a person of a consultative, informational and practical nature.

The components of a multicultural educational space are value and content; student-oriented; operational and activity; regional integration. They reflect a complex of relations: to the individual as the highest value in pedagogical interaction, as the subject of life, capable of cultural self-determination and self-change; to the teacher as an intermediary between a person and culture, able to introduce him into the world of culture and provide assistance and support to each person in individual self-determination in the world of relations, values and activities; to education, its content as a cultural process based on personality, personal meaning, universal and national values, dialogue and cooperation; to an educational institution as a holistic, multicultural educational space, where cultural values live and are recreated, intercultural communication, interethnic education of a person of culture is carried out [5].

The introduction of elements of multiculturalism into education can contribute to the education of tolerance. The main thing in solving this problem can be considered, first of all: comprehensive mastery of the culture of their own people by students, as an indispensable condition for integration into other cultures; teaching students human rights and peace; formation of ideas about the diversity of cultures in multinational Kazakhstan and the world; fostering a positive attitude towards cultural differences that promote the progress of mankind; formation of skills and abilities of effective interaction with representatives of different cultures; education in the spirit of peace, tolerance, humane interethnic communication.

In addition, the effectiveness of pedagogical support and protection of students in multicultural education depends on the reasonable introduction of new pedagogical technologies of multicultural education, as well as the appropriate level of position of teachers. The introduction of innovative technologies in multicultural educational institutions with a multi-ethnic composition of students will provide each individual with the opportunity to self-identify as a representative of a particular national culture; create conditions for an equal dialogue with the ethno-cultural environment; will involve students in the global processes of modernity for the assimilation of national and universal values based on the principles of equality and the importance of cultures [6].

A true culture of interethnic communication, interaction and cooperation of peoples can only arise based on the disclosure of the spiritual and moral potential of each nation, the exchange of experience in social and cultural creativity, based on the implementation of the ideals of freedom, justice, and equality. And it is education that is designed to provide a combination of international and national education for students.

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Бұқаралық ақпарат құралдары шет тілі сабақтарында тілдік емес жоғары оқу орындары студенттерінің сөйлеу дағдыларын дамыту құралы ретінде

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Бұқаралық ақпарат құралдары өздерінің үлкен ақпараттық және дидактикалық мүмкіндіктерімен шет тілін оқытуда, студенттердің өзіндік танымдық іс – әрекетінде, қашықтықтан оқыту курстарымен жұмыс жасауда, сабақтарда оқу процесінде және т.б. баға жетпес пайда әкелуі мүмкін.

Бұқаралық ақпарат құралдары оқушылардың оқу процесінде мұғалім қолдана алатын жаңа, үнемі өзгеріп отыратын және толықтырылатын ақпарат көздеріне деген қызығушылығын қолдайды. Бұқаралық ақпарат құралдарын бір мезгілде оқыту ортасы ретінде (білім беру сайттарындағы интерактивті тапсырмалар, нақты уақыт режимінде жаңалықтарды қарау және т.б., қашықтықтан оқыту) және оқу материалдарының сапасы, түрі мен формасы бойынша әр түрлі ақпарат көзі ретінде қарастыруға болады. [5]

Ұсынылған мақалада біз ағылшын тілді интернет Жоғары мектепте ағылшын тілін оқытуда, атап айтқанда "Халықаралық қатынастар", "Саясаттану", "Аймақтану" салаларында және олармен жұмыс істеудің кейбір әдістерінде қолдану үшін ұсынатын материалдардың түрлеріне толығырақ тоқталамыз.

Интернет-ресурстармен жұмыс істеу әдістемесі мақсатқа байланысты: сіз сабақтарда желілік материалдармен жұмыс жасай аласыз; студенттер оларды жоба бойынша жұмыс жасау кезінде ақпаратты іздеу үшін — жеке немесе топта, сондай-ақ кез-келген мәселені өз бетінше зерттеу немесе білімді жетілдіру үшін пайдаланады. Осы міндеттердің барлығы оқытудың бірыңғай мақсаты – коммуникативтік құзыреттілікті қалыптастыру арқылы біріктірілген.

Электрондық ақпарат құралдары студенттер үшін ерекше қызығушылық тудырады. Біріншіден, бұл ақпараттық агенттіктердің сайттары және газеттердің Онлайн нұсқалары, онда халықаралық оқиғаларға шолу жасалады, ақпараттық және аналитикалық мақалалар ұсынылады. Жаңалықтар сайттары сонымен қатар бейнежазбаларда немесе тікелей репортаждарда жаңалықтарды тыңдауға немесе көруге, ақпараттық хабарламалар материалына негізделген тілдік тапсырмаларды орындауға мүмкіндік береді.

Бұқаралық ақпарат құралдарында "жаңалықтар" ақпараты бар көптеген сайттарды табуға болады, бірақ, өкінішке орай, олардың барлығы мазмұны жағынан да, тілі жағынан да сапалы материал бермейді. Сондықтан мұғалімге сапалы интернет-ресурстарды таңдау маңызды.

Негізгі ақпарат агенттіктерінің бірі- BBC. BBC веб-сайтының басты бетінде (<http://news.bbc.co.uk>) әлемдегі соңғы оқиғалар туралы хабарламалар орналастырылған, оқиғалар орын алатын аймақтар көрсетілген, әр түрлі қызығушылық салаларының тізімі бар (бизнес, ғылым, спорт, ойын-сауық), ауа-райы және т. б. "елге шолу" бөлімінде аймақ туралы тарихи ақпарат бар, Экономика, кез келген проблема, сондай - ақ Би-Би-си мұрағаттарынан

аудио және бейнеклиптер. "Ағылшын тілін үйрену" беті сөздік қоры мен сөз тіркестерінің түсіндірмелері бар саяси және экономикалық мақалаларды ұсынады, ағылшын тілінің грамматикасын талқылайды, мұғалімдерге тесттер, ресурстар ұсынады (газет мақалалары мен радиобағдарламаларға негізделген сабақ жоспарларын басып шығару, бақылау жұмыстары және т.б.).

Сайттың жоғарыда аталған бетінде студенттерге ұсынылатын мақалалардың материалы келесідей ұйымдастырылған: ақпараттың негізгі мазмұнын қысқаша баяндайтын кіріспе, есте сақтауға арналған сөздер мен сөз тіркестері бар мақала (мақаланы бір уақытта оқуға және тыңдауға болады) және одан кейін мақала, олардың мағыналарын түсіндіретін сөз тіркестері. Тыңдаушылардың білім деңгейіне байланысты бұл материалды әр түрлі ретпен қолдануға болады: сөздермен жұмыс жасаудан бастаңыз, мақаланы тыңдаңыз, оқыңыз, аударыңыз, мазмұнын ұсыныңыз. Жоғары деңгейлі топтарда тақырып бойынша мақаланы қарап шыққаннан кейін сіз аймақтағы соңғы оқиғалар туралы ақпаратты көре аласыз, олардың мазмұнын ұсына аласыз және талқылауды ұйымдастыра аласыз. Үй тапсырмасы ретінде әр түрлі интернет-ресурстардан (ақпараттық агенттіктердің сайттары, газеттер мен журналдардың онлайн нұсқалары) осы тақырыпқа хабарлама дайындау ұсынылады, ал келесі сабақта алынған ақпарат салыстырылады және талданады.

Жаңалықтармен жұмыс істеу кезінде сіз студенттерден қысқа жазбаны таңдап, оны оқып, басқаларға жалпылауды сұрай аласыз (немесе егер сіз оларды кіші топтарға бөлсеңіз, өзіңіздің кіші тобыңыз үшін). Сонымен қатар, олардың міндеті-кейбір мәліметтерді өзгерту, ал қалған студенттер қандай фактілер өзгертілгенін және қайсысы шындық екенін болжауға тырысады. [3, б. 36]

CNN веб-сайтымен жұмыс істеу үшін (www.cnn.com) мәзір жолағындағы басты бетте "білім" бөлімін таңдаңыз, ал келесі бетте сіз бірнеше бөлімдердің бірін таңдай аласыз: "Білім жаңалықтары", "CNN сыныпты білдіреді", "оқу іс-шаралары". Соңғысында пайдаланушыларға саясатты, экономиканы, қоршаған ортаны, медицинаны және т. б. талқылау үшін 50-ге жуық тақырып ұсынылады.; б) ұйымдастыру және талқылау жоспары (оқушылар қызмет салалары бойынша топтар құрады және ұсынылған сұрақтарға жауаптар дайындайды; в) жауаптар дайындау үшін ақпарат табуға болатын сайттардың атаулары

(ұйымның тарихы, БҰҰ Жарғысынан үзінділер, ұйымның құрылымын көрсете отырып, БҰҰ веб-сайты және т. б.)

Жаңалықтар видеосы шынайы бейнематериал мен саяси, әлеуметтік немесе экономикалық қызығушылық тудыратын жаңалықтардың өзектілігі үшін артықшылықтарын біріктіреді. [1, б. 30] Бейне Жаңалықтар Тіл мен сөйлеу үлгілерінің кең таңдауын ұсынады, өйткені олар әртүрлі аймақтық екпіндерді, арнайы және кәсіби лексиканы және грамматикалық құрылымдардың ерекшеліктерін, мәдени ерекшеліктерді қамтуы мүмкін. Шынайы бейнені қарау кезінде фонетикалық нормалар подсознание деңгейінде есте қалады, сонымен қатар ағылшын және американдық тіл нұсқаларының айтылу нормаларындағы айырмашылықтарға, аймақтық екпіндер мен диалектілерге назар аударылады. [2, б. 26]

Сонымен қатар, бұл бейнелер негізінен жақсы тілдік дайындығы бар студенттерге бағытталған, ал тіл үйренуді бастаушылар үшін олар сөйлеу жылдамдығына, оның жеке типологиялық ерекшеліктеріне байланысты айтарлықтай қиындықтар туғызады. Сондықтан кейбір жаңалықтар сайттары тілді меңгерудің әртүрлі деңгейіне арналған бейнелерді ұсынады. [4, б. 87]

Reuters агенттігі (www.reuters.com) - әлемдегі ең ірі ақпараттық агенттік. Негізгі бәсекелесінен айырмашылығы, Associated Press әр түрлі материалдардың көп мөлшерін ашық қол жетімді етеді. Экономикалық мамандануына қарамастан, ол жалпы тақырыптар бойынша жаңалықтар мен мақалалар жариялайды. Көптеген жаңалықтар медиасы сияқты, олар Бизнес, Әлем, Саясат, Тікелей эфир және Бейне санаттары бойынша сұрыпталған.

Сонымен қатар, тегін қосымша бар.

Жаңалықтар құрылымдалған, қатаң ақпараттық стильде жазылған. Тіл үйренушілер үшін мұндай презентация іс-шараның мәнін сөздіксіз түсінуге, сондай-ақ көптеген пайдалы өрнектерді үйренуге көмектеседі.

Кемшілігі-презентацияның біршама құрғақ стилі, іскерлік фокус.

Экономика мен бизнеске қызығушылық танытқандар үшін The Wall Street Journal, The Financial Times қолайлы, онда Ресейдің экономикасы мен қаржысы, Bloomberg және The Economist туралы бөлім бар. Олар мазмұнның бір бөлігін сайтқа жүктейді, қалғаны жазылым арқылы қол жетімді.

Voice of America веб-сайтында (<http://voanews.com>) сіз тілді меңгерудің екі деңгейі бар пайдаланушылар үшін жаңалықтар таба аласыз. Сонымен қатар, студенттер осы жаңалықтардың мәтінін оқып отырып, бейнелерді көре алады немесе ағылшын жаңалықтар подкасттарын тыңдай алады. VOA Learning English Channel сайтының бөлім материалы тіл үйренушілерге бейімделген: дикторлар өте анық және салыстырмалы түрде баяу сөйлейді және олардың мәтіні бір уақытта субтитрлермен бірге жүреді, бұл тілді өте жоғары меңгермегендерді түсінуге көмектеседі. Субтитрлердің арқасында сіз бейнемен жұмыс істеудің келесі түрін ұсына аласыз. Студенттерден сөйлеушінің айтылуы мен интонациясына назар аудара отырып, бейнені көруді сұраңыз. Содан кейін олар дыбысты өшіріп, субтитрлерді дауыстап оқуға тырысуы керек. Осылайша, олар жаңалықтар мәтінінің фонетикалық және лексикалық жағында жұмыс істей алады: сөздердің мағынасы және оларды осы контексте қолдану, айтылу мен интонацияны қайталау. Жаңалықтардың мәтінін дауыстап оқи отырып, студенттер өздерін танымал бағдарламаның дикторы ретінде көрсете алады.

The screenshot shows the Reuters website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Reuters logo and various menu items like Business, Markets, World, Politics, Tech, Commentary, Breakingviews, Money, Life, Pictures, and Video. Below the navigation bar, there are several news sections:

- THE WIRE**: A list of recent news items with timestamps (1h ago, 2h ago).
- Main Article**: "Trump torpedoes G7 effort, threatens auto tariffs" with a sub-headline "LA MALBAIE, Quebec - Donald Trump threw the G7's efforts to show a united front into disarray after he became angry with Canadian PM Justin Trudeau, and said he might double down on import tariffs by hitting the sensitive auto industry." It includes a photo of Trump and other leaders, and a list of bullet points: "After a year of nice, Trump brings Trudeau to brink of trade war" and "One 'rant,' rough talks sour G7 mood in confrontations with Trump".
- MARKETS**: A section with a line chart showing market performance and a table of stock indices:

Index	Value	Change
S&P	2,779.03	+0.31%
Dow	25,316.53	+0.30%
FTSE 100	7,681.07	-0.30%
Nikkei 225	22,694.50	-0.56%
- Other News**: "Trump and Kim set to arrive in Singapore for historic summit", "Door already ajar: Trump may struggle to isolate North Korea again", "China's Xi calls out 'selfish, short-sighted' trade policies", and "U.S. soldier killed in Somalia firefight identified".
- SPONSORED CONTENT**: A section for sponsored content.

Ересек аудиториямен жұмыс істейтін мұғалім үшін газеттердің онлайн нұсқалары бұқаралық ақпарат құралдарының бір түрі ретінде дағдыларды дамытудың құнды көзі бола алады. Олардың даусыз артықшылықтары-газет шынайы, ақпараттық, өзекті, студенттердің фондық және кәсіби білімдерін дамытады. [3, б. 33]

Студенттерді газет оқу дағдыларын дамытуға қызықтыру үшін қандай тапсырмалар ұсынуға болады?

Мақалалардың тақырыптарын оқып шығыңыз және студенттерді белгілі бір тақырыптағы мақалада не жазылғаны туралы өз пікірлерін айтуға шақырыңыз, содан кейін олардың болжамының қаншалықты дұрыс болғанын тексеру үшін мақаланы оқыңыз. Ұқсас тапсырманы тақтаға 8-10 кілт сөз жазу арқылы орындауға болады. Студенттерді топтарға бөлгеннен кейін (3-4 адам), олардан кілт сөз негізінде таңдалған тақырып қандай болуы мүмкін екенін анықтауды сұраңыз. Олар өз болжамдарын егжей-тегжейлі айтқаннан кейін, олармен бірге түпнұсқа мақаланы оқыңыз.

Оқу және сөйлесу практикасы үшін өте жақсы міндет - "жаңалықтар бағдарламасын" дайындау. Газеттің онлайн нұсқаларымен жұмыс істегенде, студенттерді шағын топтарға бөліңіз және командада жұмыс істей отырып, олардан арнайы репортаждар, сұхбаттар және тіпті ауа-райы болжамын қосуға болатын жаңалықтар бағдарламасын дайындауды сұраңыз. Олардың бағдарламасы газет сайтында ұсынылған жаңалықтар негізінде жасалуы керек және топтың барлық мүшелері оның тұсаукесеріне белгілі бір дәрежеде қатысуы керек.

Көптеген газеттерде, соның ішінде онлайн нұсқаларында редакцияға хаттар айдары бар. Студенттерге осы хаттарды қарап шығуды және оларды шағын топтарда (немесе жұптарда) талқылауды ұсынуға болады: қайсысы қызықты, бір мәселе бойынша диаметрлі қарама-қарсы көзқарастарды білдіретін хаттар бар ма. Мұндай хаттар қызықты пікірталас тудыруы мүмкін. Студенттерден ұқсас хатты олар талқылаған тақырып бойынша жазуды немесе мақаланы оқу арқылы жазуды сұрауға болады.

Қорытындылай келе, ақпараттық технологиялар дәуірінде бұқаралық ақпарат құралдары жаңа мүмкіндіктер ұсынады, соның ішінде газет мақалаларын онлайн оқу дағдыларын дамыту. Газеттердің сандық нұсқалары студенттерге сөздік қорын байытуға, ел мен мәдениет туралы білім алуға және әлемдегі қазіргі жағдай туралы хабардар болуға көмектеседі. Бір тақырыпқа арналған, бірақ әртүрлі дереккөздерден алынған мақалаларды салыстыру кезінде студенттер талдауды үйренеді, сонымен қатар баспасөз арқылы манипуляциялау әдістері мен әдістерімен танысады, бұл өз кезегінде олардың сыни ойлауын қалыптастырады.

Жоғарыда аталған жұмыс түрлерінде Интернет дәстүрлі педагогикалық әдістер мен әдістерді жүзеге асыратын жоғары тиімді құрал болып табылады.

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Information technology

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Abstract: Not so long ago, the whole world celebrated the International Day of the Internet. Including Kazakhstan, because in our country, according to the Ministry of Culture and Information, one third of the population are Internet users.

The number of domestic Internet resources is increasing, interesting educational sites are appearing, blog platforms are being created, self-respected print editions are "starting up" Internet versions.

Key words: information, internet users, opportunity, network, communication

Many companies now have IT departments to manage computers, networks, and other technical areas of their businesses. IT jobs include computer programming, network administration, computer engineering, web development, technical support, and many other related occupations.

Since we live in the "world of information", information technology has become a part of our daily lives. In the coming decades, many corporations will create so-called "IT departments" to manage computer technologies related to their business. Whatever these departments are working or will work on became the real definition of information technology.

Information Technology governance: The effective combination of policies and processes to run the IT systems smoothly and hand in hand with the need of the organization.

Information Technology operations: The operation of IT can be seen in the daily work of an IT department. It provides tech support, security testing, network maintenance, and perform device management.

This is how information is stored and transmitted using technical devices.

They are also called information and communication technologies, computer technologies, IT or IT (from the English IT — information technologies).

The concept of such technologies also includes:

- technical devices and computer technology,
- methods of data and information transmission (e.g., computer network or communication channel).

Although humans have been storing, retrieving, manipulating, and communicating information since the earliest writing systems were developed, the information technology in its modern sense first appeared in a 1958 article published in the Harvard Business Review; authors Harold J. Leavitt and Thomas L. Whisler commented that Information technologies perform certain functions. They are used to work with information and data. In particular, they carry out: data collection, data accumulation, information processing, information storage, information provision, data dissemination.

With the help of information technology, they also create data, and also manage various business processes in companies.

For this purpose, IT is used, such as, for example, databases, expert systems, decision support systems, etc.

The new technology does not yet have a single established name. We shall call it information technology (IT). Their definition consists of three categories: techniques for processing, the application of statistical and mathematical methods to decision-making, and the simulation of higher-order thinking through computer programs.

These are all created technologies that people use for various purposes. These include:
Telecommunication technologies: for example, cellular communication and computer network.
Technologies for working with text: for example, those that allow you to recognize speech and turn it into text.

Technologies for working with graphics: with the help of which we work with images.

Multimedia technologies: those that allow you to work with sound, image, text and video at the same time.

Database technologies: allow you to perform any operations with data for their storage, modification, transfer, etc.

Internet technologies: e-mail, the World Wide Web, chats, etc.

Intranet technologies: for the exchange of information within one company.

Software technologies: used for software development.

Server technologies: are intended to connect clients to the server.

Information security technologies: which are created to prevent information leakage.

Artificial intelligence technologies: the task is to teach a machine to think.

IT in education

In education, such technologies can be used to gain knowledge (for example, if Internet access is provided), to accumulate knowledge (in the form of creating a single database that students and teachers can use).

IT can also be used to manage the entire learning process, to store information (about grades, student list, etc.) and to provide communication between the learning community.

Various software, multimedia technologies, technologies of distance education and knowledge testing (test technologies) can be used in education.

Information technology helps to build and grow the commerce and business sector and generate the maximum possible output. The time taken by different sectors to generate business is now minimized with advancements in Information technology. It provides electronic security, storage, and efficient communication.

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The role of the engineering profession in the development of civilization

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Abstract:

For many centuries, even millennia before the social mode of production made possible and necessary the emergence of engineers in the full sense of the word, people faced engineering problems and individuals were able to solve them. After all, human civilization is based on the transformation of the natural world with the help of tools, that is, a set of various technical means. The history of engineering activity is relatively independent; it cannot be reduced to either the history of technology or the history of science. Its roots are lost in the depths of the past millennia.

Key words: archaeological excavations, technical component, artificial technical objects, technological progress, implementation

Often we can guess what perseverance and talent each new step in mastering and transforming the world required, what creative conflicts, ups and collapses are hidden from our eyes by the haze of centuries. Archaeological excavations allow only to very roughly reconstruct the level of knowledge and skills available to creators of the technology of the distant past. One of the centers of technical (and engineering) activities was construction. The construction of ancient cities, which became centers of handicraft production, the construction of religious and irrigation structures, bridges, dams, roads required the cooperation of a huge number of people. Obviously, no large and complex structure can be built without a detailed plan by engineers. Thus, the revolution in the technical component of the productive forces led to a change in the human component - workers and engineers appeared, who were entrusted with the task of working "mainly only with the head". The first engineers were formed among scientists who turned to technology and self-taught craftsmen who became involved in science.

The first engineers are both artists and architects, consultants on fortifications, artillery and civil engineering, alchemists and doctors, mathematicians and naturalists. They were united by the fact that for the first time they began to use scientific knowledge as a very real productive force. Thus, the mission of the engineer was formed, which is to create artificial technical objects, media and technologies necessary to ensure life and improve the quality of life of man and society, using natural resources and the use of natural science knowledge and practical experience. The birth of the engineering profession was the result of a revolution in all segments and spheres of social life without exception. Technique, mode of production, socio-economic relations, political institutions, public consciousness and psychology. Technological progress, the development of special engineering education contributed to further deepening within the professional division of labor. Comprehension of the technical problem, determination of ways to solve it began to be carried out by engineers - researchers, designers, technologists, whose work has become almost indistinguishable from the work of a scientist - an application.

The development of technical sciences has not only led to a deep differentiation of engineers - developers of new technology, but also contributed to greater rapprochement with scientists. Thus, engineers are becoming a well-established socio-professional group. The change in the "human-technics" system due to the formation of machine production consisted in the transfer of a number of human functions to the technique; the machine arises from the moment when the tools turn "from the tools of the human body into the tools of the mechanical apparatus". The movement of the function of direct control of guns from person to machine marked not just a technical revolution - such revolutions of "local importance" occur in technology in connection with any major invention. No, there was a complete revolution in the entire technical system, after which it began to develop in a new way, based on new principles, new technical forms and structures. In other words, the emergence of machines determined the beginning of a new historical stage in the development of technology - mechanization of production. The need to invent and apply various kinds of machines on an industrial scale has unwittingly created a need for specialists capable of carrying out this activity. Thus, the work of engineers began its demand in the engineering industries. The emergence of the machine industry makes a truly revolutionary revolution in engineering, which allows us to declare the entry of the profession into the institutional stage with the spread of the capitalist mode of production. Namely, the era of the machine industry generates an engineer in the modern world.

The role of the engineering profession has always been in demand, both before our era and in the modern world. The functions of engineers remained the same, but are quite rigidly separated and assigned to certain specialties.

That is: 1. Analysis and technical forecasting function. Its implementation is related to clarifying the technical contradictions and needs of production. It defines trends and prospects for technical development, the course of technical policy and, accordingly, outlines the main parameters of the engineering task. To be more precise, the answer to the question of what production needs tomorrow is formulated in the first approximation. This function is carried out by engineering "teeth" - managers, leading specialists of research and design institutes, bureaus, laboratories.

2. The research function of engineering activities is to find a conceptual scheme of a technical device or technological process. The research engineer is obliged by the nature of his activity to find a way to "fit" the task planned for development into the framework of the laws of natural and technical sciences, i.e. to determine the direction that will lead to the goal.

3. The design function complements and develops the research function, and sometimes merges with it. Its special content is that the bare skeleton of the schematic diagram of the device, the mechanism is overgrown with the muscles of technical means, the technical design takes a certain shape.

The design engineer takes as a basis the general principle of operation of the device - the result of the researcher's efforts - and "translates" it into the language of drawings, creating a technical and then a working project. From a set of known technical elements, a combination is created that has new functional properties, qualitatively different from all others.

4. The design function is the sister of the two previous functions. The specificity of its content lies, firstly, in the fact that the design engineer designs not a separate device or device, but a whole technical system, using as "details" the units and mechanisms created by designers; secondly, it is that when developing a project it is often necessary to take into account not only technical, but also social, ergonomic and other parameters of the object. The work of the designer completes the period of engineering preparation of production; the technical idea takes its final form in the form of drawings of the working project.

5. The technological function is related to the implementation of the second part of the engineering task: how to make what was invented? The process engineer must connect technical

processes with labor processes and do it in such a way that as a result of the interaction between people and technology, the time and materials are minimal, and the technical system works productively. The success or failure of a technologist determines the value of all engineering work spent before on creating a technical facility and ideal form.

6. Production regulation function. The designer and technologist jointly determined what and how to do, the simplest and at the same time the most difficult thing is to do. This is the task of the worker, but to direct his efforts, directly on the spot to organize his work with the labor of others and subordinate the joint activities of employees to the solution of a specific technical problem - the business of the engineer-production, the manufacturer of works.

7. Operation and repair function of equipment. Here the name speaks for itself. Modern ultra-complex technology in many cases requires engineering training of the employee servicing it. The operating engineer bears debugging and maintenance of machines, automatic machines, technological lines, control over the mode of their operation. Increasingly, an engineer is needed behind the operator's console.

8. The system design function is relatively new for engineering, but is more important than many other functions. Its meaning is to give the entire cycle of engineering actions a single orientation, complex character. A new profession of systems engineer is emerging, designed to give expert assessments in the process of creating complex technical and especially "human-machine" systems, where their constant diagnostic analysis is necessary, aimed at unlocking backup and bottlenecks, developing solutions to eliminate the identified shortcomings. Universal experts should help the manager reach agreement on the entire work program, including different projects.

All these functions and duties are performed only by engineers. And it's all to speak for yourself, that is, an engineer is needed in every area. The development of engineering activities after the appearance of the engineer proceeded unusually rapidly. The Union of Science and Technology gave rise to an avalanche of technical and social changes, which, as we moved forward, captured the wider layers of society. Is it possible to imagine life without representatives of this profession? Most likely not. Because engineers take part in the construction and assessment of the suitability of buildings, develop mineral deposits, design, design and operate mechanical equipment. As well as information technology software. Thus, it proves that without engineers, the path to the development of civilization is not, and the role of engineers in the development of civilization is very important.

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Development of professional communicative skills: problems, solutions, suggestions

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Abstract. *In order to achieve improvement in the educational space, it is necessary to strengthen the scientific training of personnel, as well as awareness of the importance and role of humanitarian disciplines - recognition of a person as the most important social value, respect for his personality. The educational system should provide a high level of training for graduates, in particular, within the framework of the higher professional education system. To improve the quality of training of specialists and the level of integration of the educational services market in the market of demanded labor, it is important to choose an innovatively-oriented way of developing the education system.*

Key words: *modernization, communicative skill, transformation, contradiction, educational institutions, mechanisms of survival, innovative policies*

The modernization and transformation of the educational space in Kazakhstan is quite active, and these processes affect both the structure and functions of the educational system, educational technologies and the substantial characteristics of the educational process as a whole. However, these processes are not without contradictions and internal and external problems, and this confirms the need to study the processes of development and functioning of all education systems - both continuous and networks of educational institutions and, of course, individual institutions. President of the Republic of Kazakhstan N.A. Nazarbayev in the Development Strategy of Kazakhstan until 2030 noted that a highly educated population with a high level of scientific and creative potential is an important advantage of the state. The existing invaluable capital inherited from the education system of the former Union, it is necessary to develop and create more and more civilized conditions for its development. The transition of the economy to an innovative path of development and the overall socio-economic situation in the country requires a review of certain priorities in politics and a concentration of views on building a new type of society based on the integration of three main elements: education, innovation and science.

Paying attention, for example, to the level of humanitarian knowledge of secondary and higher school graduates, we can notice the discrepancy between the education system and the requirements dictated by the modern development of society. Such disappointing conclusions as a poor knowledge of foreign languages, a low level of literary regulatory language, a low ability to express one's thoughts logically, insufficient knowledge of world and domestic history, cultural values and history, as well as legal, economic and political illiteracy are very obvious. Given these internal and external challenges, the education system must undergo a deep phased strategic modernization.

The educational process is the basis of the educational process, so its modernization always plays a major role. The educational system should ensure a high quality level of graduates,

especially within the framework of higher professional education. In order to improve the quality of training specialists and the level of integration of the educational services market, the labor market is important to choose an innovatively-oriented way of developing the education system, which will allow us to re-orient the modern higher education system not only to educational activities as such, but to the scientific and technological system of personnel training and retraining. As the researchers note, the survival and success of a higher educational institution is largely related to the allocation and organization of three integrated processes in the management system:

- quality control;
- innovation management;
- management of intangible assets (resulting from research activities).

Indeed, higher education is inherently a science, and learning with the help of science, and science as the goal and result of innovative development. The development of each particular university requires the formation of a strategy and tactics based on its own innovative potential, which will strengthen their competitive advantages and maintain their niche at all stages of innovative development, forecast the needs for the forms and volumes of educational services, and develop, rank and replicate products on the market innovation activity. In modern economic conditions, universities are quite seriously focused on the features of the current scientific and educational space. At the same time, universities are trying to master the mechanisms of survival, maintaining stable development and having different paths for this development, although the strategic guidelines are largely similar, because they are generally innovation oriented.

Higher educational institutions create various forms of cooperation in their development: training of specialists; active participation of students and teachers in conducting research; the formation of engineering centers; close interaction with employers and partners in creating innovative and investment relations. The information & research environment forms the creative activity of higher education institutions. The integration of higher education in the scientific and technical space should be organized and stimulated through the formation of innovative policies in the development of a package of measures for the higher education system. It is these integration processes that should serve as the basis for the formation of tactics and strategies for innovative development of the education system in Kazakhstan.

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Humanization in educational environments; aspects necessary for living in school today

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Summary

While it is true, quality has always been measured through statistics and percentages, often forgetting the training of the whole person.

Now, when we talk about issues such as humanism and education supported by technology, we can fall into extremes: it is common to label technology as the provider of all the evils of today's civilization; or the opposite assumption; to argue that incorporating technologies into education would be the panacea for all the problems it faces and finally, to assume that the subject of the humanities is more typical of actions and attitudes of the past than as a current need, giving vitality to any educational process. However, and fortunately for the educational community, today there are global efforts to make the educational task a human action that minimizes inequities and the abysmal differences that exist in countries like ours. Fernando Reimers says: "Equal educational opportunities must be the priority objective of educational policies, the aim of education must be to contribute to creating just societies. This requires improving the learning environments of the poor, but not only along the paths that have been started over the last decade. This aspect pointed out by Reimers is precisely the central aspect that all educational action must contemplate, the educational policies that are implemented in our country must guarantee, above all, the construction of a just and egalitarian society, strengthening the cultural wealth that we have, with respect to to the diversity of people, their past, their present and especially their future.

Keywords: Person, integrity, humanization, education, technologies

Introduction

In the discussion table of the educational institutions of the country, the design and implementation of educational programs that address the multicultural needs that exist must be a priority, to reduce the lags, reduce illiteracy and school failure, dropping out of classrooms, projects truncated, seek an education for all children and young people in the country and the incorporation of adults, with specific programs not alienating or transculturized. While it is true it is important to resume the successful experiences that other societies have had in education projects for all and for a lifetime, our project requires substantive actions, with precise objectives, with a global vision and a national mission.

EDUCATION AND TECHNOLOGY

In Chile, the government, schools and universities of the present are now concerned with designing the appropriate and relevant educational future, which allows them to face the global social and economic demands that allow the opportunity at least to insert themselves and then try to compete in the frameworks of "globalization", there are innumerable studies and actions that the various agencies responsible for educational work currently carry out with the purpose of planning from today, the future that has already been installed in our present.

The actions, at least in the discourse, are perceived impregnated with a true spirit of planning the education of tomorrow, in a less disadvantageous situation than the current one, which allows its insertion in the world market, in this context we are talking about a task certainly humanistic that tries to at least reduce the existing gap inside the country, and abroad. This gap can be observed in different dimensions: a general gap, a regional gap, a geographical gap and a digital divide, understood as the distance that separates those who have access to information and therefore to new information technologies and communications and those who have it in a limited way or do not access them. Simply put, it is the gap between the "rich in information" and the "poor in information." The digital divide has become a primary indicator of unequal opportunities.

To reduce the digital divide, it is not enough to have access to the tools, it is necessary to create a policy and regulatory environment, institutional frameworks and human training that promotes the flow of information, innovation, and the effective use of global knowledge resources.

Este nuevo modelo de accionar educativo debe tener a los derechos educativos como su centro, debe basarse en la equidad, la dignidad humana y la justicia social y debe ser guiada para abordar las necesidades y aspiraciones de todos los grupos sociales.

If we want to be inhabitants of the global village, taking into account the educational problems we have, the challenge is to achieve an education for all and for a lifetime, I end up coined by Jacques Delors in his work: Education Encloses a Treasure, where he argues that education for all, must take into account the four pillars of knowledge: Learn to know, learn to do, learn to be and learn to serve and live there because some of our questions arise; How to achieve this coexistence if we have not been able to achieve it in our own communities? Will this coexistence be possible taking into account our differences, cultural, educational, religious, ethnic, social and economic? Has current education helped to overcome these differences? Will the educational policy of our country go in the right line to achieve this goal?

The population structure of our country is a huge cultural, ethnic, religious educational, economic and social mosaic, these enormous differences place us in alarmingly unequal and inequitable contexts, with deep and lagging senses and huge inequality of opportunities of various kinds.

It should be clarified that our cultural wealth is what defines us as a strong and powerful country, our obligation is to appropriate it, maintain it and strengthen it. The school has been until nowadays the main conductive channel towards the education and culture of the people, precisely because of this, it requires today as always and perhaps more than ever appropriate policies, extraordinary supports, national consensus, that manage to diminish that enormous heterogeneity that it divides us, which distances us that makes us ignorant, that leads to inequalities, that prevents progress, and that has delayed reaching so longed for economic and social development. To locate more closely the magnitude of the problem we live, let's analyze the following data. The statistics are generally cold, produce chills when our reality is restricted in the face.

THE HUMANIZATION OF EDUCATION BEFORE ICT

The new communication and information technologies offer the ideal potential to expand the spectrum of teaching and learning, crossing the traditional barriers of time and space, as well as the current boundaries of educational systems. ICTs enable an improvement in face-to-face educational processes and offer more opportunities to learn in non-formal education systems.

Exploiting these possibilities is the task that we have to perform, the challenge is how. What kind of teacher and student profiles do we need, what is the appropriate curriculum, what activities will support that curriculum, such as maintaining the motivation of the different subjects involved. Obviously we must bet on the planning task, which privileges the necessary humanization of educational processes. Mediation with permanent dialogue becomes an indispensable attribute.

Distance education as a new modality in education will then also require the implementation of a new model, a change in the educational paradigm, where the roles for both the apprentice and the teacher have new meanings, new responsibilities, new challenges and new challenges

This new model will require a joint hierarchy of planned actions involving institutional institutions at the macro and micro levels, schools, teaching, administrative, technological and students. The responsibilities of each of the intervening subjects, is also different, there must be an effective fulfillment in the new roles that they will have to assume, the biggest challenge may have to do with promoting the necessary Dialogue, The choice of means in education, to The design of teaching materials and for tutorial support should be based on the principle of maximum interactivity.

The challenge in distance modalities is a major one, because it becomes necessary to achieve a certain relative autonomy of the students, in their learning process, and I say "certain autonomy" knowing that they will be subject to the mediation of an online program assisted by the facilitator, by the tutor. For this innovative process, it is necessary to design specific pedagogical structures, which favor interaction and interactivity and collaborative work between the actors. Shorten the distance between teacher and student, and give immediate response to the latter's requirements. For this, the use of communication technologies as teaching tools is imminent, under the premise that their effectiveness will be subject to the possibility that users access them massively.

We need to avoid that, in distal education, the spatial and geographical gap is a factor of failure because of the human need for closeness of guidance support. Obviously the internal and external motivation that the student possesses and receives in their learning process is important; Although we are talking about an autonomous and self-directed process, the teacher continues to be a fundamental piece, have this category of tutor, instructor or supportive companion, or advisor, In this order of ideas, the humanization of the Pedagogical Advice is proposed as an action line , under the focus on Distance Education of maximum interactivity of the instructional process and theories of student-centered learning (humanism, constructivism and collaborative learning). Even if the teacher is a member of an educating society for the sake of technification, it is necessary to preserve that traditional ingredient of culture that we call humanistic training.

CONCLUSIONS

The government and educational institutions face important challenges today, the main route is to continue to focus on development and overcome the gaps that have widened worryingly, within the country and abroad, gaps of various kinds. Today as we must never meet, join efforts to agree on dreams and proposals that make it possible to overcome the digital divide that separates us from the globalized world. It is important to emphasize and forgive if I am repetitive, Universities and schools need to design, plan on a prospective plane the model of the university we dream of, what should be inclusive but autonomous, preserving the diversity and inclusion of peoples. Today it is an emerging task to work on educational projects, models and actions that rescue ethical values, conserve and strengthen our cultural wealth and maintain the essential component of the humanization of educational processes, regardless of the type of teaching taught.

The central theme of the debates on education in our country focuses its attention on the establishment of a New Educational Paradigm, towards the design of alternative emerging models that diminish the great lags and social inequities, so that they can incorporate, to the school to a significant percentage of the population that have not had access to it "If we want to optimize the learning process of our students, we have to apply to their design everything we know about the human being as an intelligent creature that thinks and learns" Bruer, (nineteen ninety five). Of course it is important to highlight the importance of universal and inclusive access to the information society. In this order of ideas, the education project we need must be based on people, for meaningful learning and the social construction of knowledge. Try not to lose sight of the necessary humanization of processes, meet the individual needs of each person, their own learning rhythms, the affective need that is inherent in every human being.

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PURPOSE OF TEACHING "CIVIL DEFENSE" IN SOCIETY ROLE AND DUTIES

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Abstract. The subject of civil defense is considered a subject that must be taught to all students at the undergraduate level of higher education institutions and is included in the curriculum as a special subject. The subject of civil defense is taught to students of higher education institutions according to the valid programs. Higher education institutions draw up their Civil Defense programs on the basis of this program, taking into account the characteristics of the specialties.

What is the main purpose of teaching civil defense in higher education institutions? The aim here is to instill theoretical knowledge and practical (practical) skills in the field of civil defense for students in their future activities. The subject "Civil Defense" occupies a special place in the professional training of the young generation. When we talk about the role, structure, goals and tasks of civil defense, first of all, let's note that the subject of civil defense (MM) is the science of protecting human safety and health in the environment.

Ensuring the safety of people has become acute in recent years. This is because the number of accidents and natural disasters in industry, transport and other areas has increased significantly in recent times when science and technology are developing rapidly. In connection with all this, it is an important issue of the day to give future specialists the knowledge and ability to ensure the protection of people's life activities and the environment in production and everyday life during the application of modern weapons.

Key words: civil defense, security, emergencies, purpose of training, emergency protection, rescue measures, etc.

The subject of civil defense is considered a subject that must be taught to all students at the undergraduate level of higher education institutions and is included in the curriculum as a special subject. The subject of civil defense is taught to students of higher education institutions according to the valid programs. Higher education institutions draw up their Civil Defense programs on the basis of this program, taking into account the characteristics of the specialties.

What is the main purpose of teaching civil defense in higher education institutions? The aim here is to instill theoretical knowledge and practical (practical) skills in the field of civil defense for students in their future activities.

There are a number of requirements for mastering the subject. So, at the end of the study, the student should know:

- ✓ the main requirements of the existing normative-legal documents in the field of civil defense;
- ✓ the structure and duties of civil defense, the content and methodology of planning civil defense measures;
- ✓ characteristics of extraordinary events in peacetime and wartime;
- ✓ the main principles and methods of protecting the population from emergencies;
- ✓ rules for notifying the public about emergency incidents;
- ✓ the rules of detention of the population in collective protection facilities;
- ✓ measures to relocate the population from dangerous regions;

- ✓ rules for using personal protective equipment during emergencies;
- ✓ designation and duties of non-militarized civil defense units;
- ✓ measures related to rescue and other urgent work and restoration of life support of the population;
- ✓ measures to increase the sustainable operation of facilities during emergency events;
- ✓ the rules of training the population in the field of emergency protection, as well as the organization, forms and methods of knowledge dissemination in the field of MM;
- ✓ the rules of providing first aid during emergencies.

As a result of mastering the subject, graduates should be able to:

- ✓ to apply normative-legal documents on civil defense in their future activities;
- ✓ to compile relevant documents on planning and implementation of civil defense measures;
- ✓ to act according to the established rules of conduct during emergency situations in peacetime and wartime;
- ✓ to use individual and collective means of protection;
- ✓ the main rules of action for eliminating the consequences of emergency events;
- ✓ providing first aid to victims.

The subject "Civil Defense" occupies a special place in the professional training of the young generation. When we talk about the role, structure, goals and tasks of civil defense, first of all, let's note that the subject of civil defense (MM) is the science of protecting human safety and health in the environment. Ensuring the safety of people has become acute in recent years. This is because the number of accidents and natural disasters in industry, transport and other areas has increased significantly in recent times when science and technology are developing rapidly. In connection with all this, it is an important issue of the day to give future specialists the knowledge and ability to ensure the protection of people's life activities and the environment in production and everyday life during the application of modern weapons.

Civil defense is organized according to the territorial-production principle. This means that all measures of civil defense are planned and implemented both on the line of the executive power and on the line of the ministries and departments that lead production and economic activity. Civil defense forces consist of military units of civil defense, state emergency rescue units, non-militarized civil defense units, as well as various units, organizations and departments that are involved in the performance of special civil defense duties under the supervision of ministries, chief departments and heads of executive power. Ensuring the safety of people has become acute in recent years. This is because the number of accidents and natural disasters in industry, transport and other areas has increased significantly in recent times when science and technology are developing rapidly. The rise of scientific and technical progress (ETT), the expansion of the scale of scientific and technical and industrial activities with the introduction of complex systems, the increase of risk in their operation pose a threat to the life and health of people, the environment and the normal operation of production. Civil defense (MM) should reveal and identify dangerous and harmful factors, investigate methods and means of human protection, ways to reduce harmful and dangerous factors to the minimum level, prepare measures to eliminate the consequences of accidents and disasters that occur during peace and war.

The role of civil defense in wartime is especially great. However, it should be noted that during the period of peace, the role of MM in combating the consequences of natural disasters and major industrial accidents has increased significantly. Extraordinary events that cause great material losses and human casualties (accidents at nuclear power plants, railways, enterprises

using highly effective toxic substances, and frequent natural disasters) show that people and their living environment in the current conditions are extraordinary. In order to protect in cases, it is necessary to completely reorganize the issues of psychologically and morally based effective training of people, especially during the period of peace, it is necessary to review the MM measures that are an emergency and to reevaluate its tasks and ways. This issue is of greater importance in the transitional period of current economic relations.

On July 31, 1992, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan signed Decree No. 73 on the approval of the Regulation "On Civil Defense of the Republic of Azerbaijan" and on April 18, 1998, Decree No. 700 on the implementation of the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Civil Defense". The above is reflected in this Regulation and Law. The main goals and tasks of civil defense in the Republic, as well as the civil defense duties of state power and management bodies, public organizations, as well as responsible persons and all citizens, are defined in the new Statute and Law.

Civil defense of the Republic of Azerbaijan - protection of the population and national economy in the territory of the republic during times of peace and war from the consequences of natural disasters, as well as powerful accidents, as well as modern means of destruction (hereinafter, the expression "results of natural disasters, powerful accidents and the effects of modern means of destruction" will be called "emergencies") it is a system of social and defense measures implemented by the state, economic, and military administration bodies with the participation of all citizens in order to protect against its effects. Civil defense system of the Republic of Azerbaijan performs state functions on civil defense. It includes all management bodies, associations, enterprises, departments, organizations and other objects belonging to various forms of ownership, their forces and means. They organize the implementation of civil defense measures in the entire territory of the republic in peace and emergency situations.

Azərbaycan Respublikası Mülki müdafiəsinin əsas vəzifələri aşağıdakılardır:

- ✓ protecting the population and national economy from the consequences of emergency situations;
- ✓ timely warning of the population about the danger to people's life and health in times of peace and war and about the rules of behavior in such conditions;
- ✓ organization and execution of rescue and other urgent works in order to eliminate the consequences of emergency situations;
- ✓ preparation of civil defense system management staff, management bodies and forces for protection and action in emergency situations, as well as organization of teaching relevant protection and action methods to the population;
- ✓ is to participate in the preparation and implementation of measures aimed at ensuring the stable operation of national economy fields, enterprises, administrations and organizations in emergency situations in times of peace and war, especially engineering-technical and other measures of civil defense.

All the listed tasks are important and should be solved comprehensively. Civil defense is organized according to the territorial-production principle. This means that all measures of civil defense are planned and implemented both on the line of the executive power and on the line of the ministries and departments that lead production and economic activity. In accordance with the new Law and Regulation, the general management of Civil Defense work in the Republic of Azerbaijan is carried out by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The Prime Minister of the Republic of Azerbaijan directs the Civil Defense of the Republic of Azerbaijan and is responsible for the constant readiness of the Civil Defense to carry out the tasks before it. In order to plan and organize the implementation of civil defense measures, as well as to control the implementation, the Ministry of Emergency Situations was established in the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic,

and this ministry, along with other areas (fire protection work, rescue at sea), manages civil defense on a daily basis. Civil defense is directly managed by the following persons:

- ✓ in economic associations and facilities - their managers and entrepreneurs;
- ✓ in cities, regions, villages and settlements - relevant heads of executive power and their representatives;

Those persons are fully responsible for the state of civil protection, and this is part of their duty. They carry out management through the headquarters, services and other government bodies. Local civil defense headquarters are established to plan civil defense measures, organize the fulfillment of tasks arising from that plan, and control their implementation. Economic objects (enterprises) occupy an important place in the civil defense system. Economic objects (enterprises) have an important role in the organization of civil defense and are the main stage. It is here that the foundation of all civil defense measures is laid. Facility means administration, enterprise, educational institution and other institutions. The head of this facility (director, rector) is responsible for the organization and state of civil defense in the facility (schools, universities). The orders and orders of the head of the enterprise on the implementation of civil defense measures must be executed by all officials of the facility. Civil defense in facilities - preparing workers, servants, young people, regulars and students for protection from modern means of destruction in advance, creating conditions for the stable operation of the facility in emergency situations and timely emergency rescue and other urgent works (QX and DTI), canceling the consequences of natural disasters and industrial accidents is created to do. In order to provide assistance to the head of the facility in civil defense, there are his deputies (relocation, engineering and technical department, material and technical equipment, headquarters). A civil defense headquarters is established under the civil defense management of the facility. The headquarters is the governing body of civil defense and the organizer of all practical activities on civil defense issues at the facility. The staff is made up of full-time civil defense workers and non-commissioned officers. Local civil defense services are created to carry out special measures of civil defense, to prepare forces and means for this purpose, to ensure the activity of civil defense forces during rescue and other urgent works. Services have an important role in facilities. They are created on the basis of departments, organizations and laboratories of the facility. Heads of services are appointed from the facility's chief specialists and production managers.

Let's take a look at the history of civil defense. It should be noted that in May 1931, in Paris, the capital of France, George Saint-Paul, the medical service general, founded the "Geneva Region Association" organization. The Association was moved from Paris to Geneva by the will of General Saint-Paul, who died in 1937, and the general's colleague, Henri George, headed the Association. In 1951, Dr. Milan Bondi succeeded Henry George as Secretary General.

In 1954, the first International Conference on MM was held in Berlin. The II International Conference was convened in Florence in 1957 and it was taken into account that the "Geneva Region Association" (a non-governmental organization) became the International Civil Defense Organization. Under the new status, it was given powers to admit governments, societies, associations to its membership. According to the new status of the UN, the III World Conference on Civil Defense was convened in Geneva in 1958.

On October 17, 1966, the charter of the International Civil Defense Organization (ICDO) was registered at the secretariat of the United Nations (UN). By the decision of the General Assembly of the United Nations, since 1972, March 1 of every year is celebrated as "World Civil Defense Day" in all countries.

After gaining independence, the Republic of Azerbaijan became a member of this organization in 1993 and actively participated in all its events. In the decree No. 700 dated April 18, 1998 signed by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, in the decision No. 193 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated September 25, 1998, in the Regulation

No. 394 dated 19.04.2006 on the Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Republic of Azerbaijan In the Regulation No. 511 dated 29.12.2006 of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs on Civil Defense Forces, the main goals and tasks of Civil Defense, as well as the duties of state power and management bodies, public organizations, responsible persons and citizens in the field of civil defense are defined.

The general management of Civil Defense work in the Republic of Azerbaijan is carried out by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Direct leadership is carried out by the Prime Minister of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The Ministry of Emergency Situations is in daily charge of planning and organizing the implementation of Civil Defense measures, as well as monitoring their implementation.

Civil Defense - the security of the population (citizens of the Republic of Azerbaijan, foreigners and stateless persons in the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan) and the territory (land, water and air space, production and social objects, as well as the environment within the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan) during peace or war. is a system of measures implemented by state authorities, legal and natural persons in order to ensure

Civil Defense system is a set of relevant executive authorities, forces and means, special funds, communication, warning and information security systems entrusted with the performance of civil defense duties.

What is an emergency? An emergency event is a situation that occurred in a certain area as a result of military operations, accidents, natural or other disasters that may cause or have caused human casualties, damage to human health or the environment, significant material losses, and disruption of people's living conditions.

Prevention of emergency incidents is a system of measures implemented in advance aimed at maximally reducing the danger of emergency incidents, protecting people and their health, and reducing the amount of damage and material losses that may be caused to the environment in the event of such incidents.

- ✓ Territorial principle - organization of civil defense measures in the entire territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan;

- ✓ The principle of constant preparedness - the readiness of the civil defense system to start immediate and effective action during emergencies.

- ✓ The principle of a different and complex approach - planning and coordinated implementation of civil defense measures taking into account the military-strategic, economic and other characteristics of individual regions, cities, industrial and social objects.

- ✓ The principle of immediate warning - immediate information to the population about emergency events that may occur or have occurred.

- ✓ The principle of mass and compulsion - that civil defense measures cover the entire population and have a mandatory character.

- ✓ The principle of interaction - close and coordinated action of state authorities and civil defense forces involved in providing civil protection.

What are the objectives of Civil Defense?

- ✓ Implementation of preventive measures to prevent emergency incidents;

- ✓ Maximum reduction of possible damages and losses during emergencies;

- ✓ Elimination of emergency events and their consequences

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TRAINING- EDUCATION AND EDUCATION ISSUES IN THE CREATIVITY OF NIZAMI GANJAVI

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Abstract. In the article, the main factors that play a role in the formation of human personality and the reflection of these factors in the artistic word art are sought. Immortal works of the genius Azerbaijani poet Nizami Ganjavi were selected as the object of study. It is mentioned in the article that Nizami Ganjavi, a philosopher-poet and a great educator, put forward such valuable thoughts and ideas about a number of general issues of education, training, and education that those ideas retain their importance even today. As one of the most urgent problems facing scientific pedagogy, the attitude towards the issue of personality formation was expressed and it was noted that from time to time quite different opinions were put forward and different theories were created. Modern scientists, educators and psychologists who study this diversity note four main factors (heredity, environment, education, activity) that influence the formation of personality. Our national pedagogy prefers to study these factors not separately, but in interaction and unity. The study and analysis of "Khamsa" from the point of view of the mentioned problem shows that the genius Nizami, who was a philosopher-poet and an educator-pedagogue, realized the importance of each of those factors and put forward relevant valuable thoughts and ideas in his highly artistic and moral poems. The poet-educator, who highly appreciates the role of the teacher and educator in both training and education, has specifically addressed this issue in all his poems. Thus, in Nizami's works, we witness that the parents of the protagonists trust the fate of their children to highly educated scientists and teachers.

Key words: *Nizami, philosopher poet, scientist-pedagogue, science, education, teacher, moral values*

If we want to build the educational work and education system on a national basis, then we should start by studying our national and moral values. Our Great Leader Heydar Aliyev repeatedly noted in his speeches that "a young person who does not know our national values, national traditions, and history cannot be a patriot." It is an indisputable fact that during the Soviet empire, instead of educating the young generation in the national spirit, we tried to instill the "fundamentals of Communist morality" that took away our national and moral values. As a result, instead of young people with a sense of national self-consciousness and connected to their roots, we have produced "national nihilists", "national mangurts", in short, youth indifferent to moral values. The spiritual treasure of our nation, which has an ancient culture and a history of national-spiritual values, is selected and appreciated worldwide for its richness. In order to become the real owner of this treasure, penetrating its deeper layers in the light of our national ideology is one of the most urgent problems facing our national pedagogy. One of the most precious pearls of our spiritual treasury, which brings us pride and never fades, is the literary-pedagogical heritage left to us by Nizami Ganjavi, the unquenchable star of world poetry, "a genius in the full sense of the

word" (Y.E. Bertels). For centuries, this heritage has been used as a "textbook of morality" and will continue to be used for centuries to come. Many pages of this "textbook" have not yet been sufficiently studied. M. Muradkhanov, Y. Talibov, Sh. Mikayilov, Sh. Safarov, S. Guliyev, B. Hasanov, H. Najafov, S. Rustamova from the point of view of the study of the pedagogical ideas of Nizami Ganjavi, who was not only a poet and philosopher, but also a great teacher and educator. and others have conducted scientific research in this direction. In addition to all this, it is believed that the legal scholars of Azerbaijan have not yet been able to pay their moral debt to his immortal soul at the required level. A genius poet and a great educator, Nizami Ganjavi put forward such valuable thoughts and ideas about a number of general issues of education, training, and education that have not lost their importance even today. One of the most urgent problems facing scientific pedagogy is the issue of personality formation.

Let's try to prove our point based on concrete examples. First, let's take a look at the ideas of the genius poet-pedagogue about the heredity factor, the role of heredity in the formation of personality. In the poem "Khosrov and Shirin", when Khosrov complains about the character of Shiruya, who is an incompetent and rebellious son, his vizier tries to comfort him and make him understand that he cannot be bad because he is your son, and the end will be good:

You are good, he will not be bad,
A branch that bears a bar similar to its trunk (3,87)

The poet-educator, who clearly mentions the role of heredity in the given example, writes right here that this factor is not decisive, that often "fire comes from ashes, ashes come from fire", "every flower does not give honey" and "every reed does not give sugar".

Touching on this issue in the poem "Seven Beauties" on the example of Bahram and his father Yazdigird, the poet shows that hereditary factors are not always decisive. So, sometimes "a gem is born from a stone", and sometimes, on the contrary, a gem is created from a stone:

There is a time when a gem is born,
A ruby eyebrow is born from the amber color
An example of the ratio of a gem to a stone,
The situation in Yazdigird and Bahram (5,121).

The poet, who believes that negative qualities passed down from generation to generation face great difficulties in life, writes that:

"Everybody is born evil,
When he dies, he leaves the building in that state." (5,121).

In the poem "Iskandername", the poet once again advises people, using the language of the ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle (Aristotle), not to show their face to the "broken nature", bad people, and not to work hard for such people:

Don't turn away from the evil one.
You will suffer from feeding the worm.
Don't take a step with an evil man,
Do not add your pure chemistry to the ashes. (2, 87)

It is clear from the mentioned examples that no matter how highly the genius Nizami appreciated the role of heredity factor, he came to the conclusion that it is not the decisive and the only factor.

Among the environmental factors, the poet-pedagogue, who values the importance of the social environment more highly, wants to inculcate in his works the idea that the role of the surrounding environment in the formation of a person's moral qualities is irreplaceable. The humanist poet, who advises "If you are a human being, love people" in all his poems, considers companionship with good people and staying away from those with broken character as one of the main conditions of good education. For example,

"He who sits with fools,
Not to mention the epic from the mind and consciousness"

– the poet explains that if you are friends with knowledgeable and intelligent people, those qualities will be passed on to you:

If it happens, a person
The red gem will turn yellow.
If you are friends with a smart person,
Knowledge and wisdom will pass to you (2, 88).

In the poem "Leyli and Majnun", the poet-educator touched upon the issue of the role of the environment more broadly and tried to explain that just as a bad environment has a negative effect on a person, a good environment also causes the formation of positive moral qualities. For example, in the scene "Majnun's answer to his father", no matter how much his father begs Majnun, he does not agree to leave the waterless desert and wild animals and return home, and on the contrary, he answers his father as follows:

If man is friendly with the wild, in the world,
He also lives according to his wild habits (3,21).

The poet-educator, who firmly believes in the idea that "If you tie a horse to a horse, it will be a kindred, even if it is not the same color", writes in the same poem that Majnun feels comfortable among wild animals ("Majnun among wild animals"), and that even the most predatory animals do not touch him:

A lion kneeling above his head.
The guard stood with his sword drawn.
He had become a monster,
He would sacrifice his life (3,21).

In the poem "Seven Beauties", he mentions the importance of the environmental factor and compares hereditary possibilities to healthy tissue and unhealthy environment to "salty soil" and tries to explain that in order to get good results in the development of the personality, it is necessary to create favorable conditions. Otherwise, a person's hard work will be wasted:

The kings said out of generosity,
They blew it from fake mines.
But they sowed the seeds of saltiness,
They put antimony on the blind eyes.
Whoever sows the seed, the salinity goes out,
It brings only regret.
A fertile place to plant a tree,

May heaven bear only fruits (5,130).

According to the poet, who repeatedly noted that science, education, and acquiring knowledge play a great role in the formation of a perfect person, the main feature that distinguishes a person from other living beings is his intelligence and perfection. The lamp of the mind is science, knowledge:

"Strength is in science, no one else,
He cannot favor anyone."

Nizami opened a wide discussion about this in the chapter "Worldview and Mind Education". Although it was contrary to the ruling ideology of his time, the genius poet-pedagogue advocated the secularity of education, the right of women to receive education equal to men, etc. advanced pedagogical ideas such as Thus, while talking about the content of education, he showed the importance of the sciences that serve to provide worldly knowledge: mathematics, geometry, astronomy, cosmology, medicine, etc., and their role in the formation of the worldview.

The poet-pedagogue showed the importance of education based on scientific knowledge based on concrete examples in the scene of Alexander receiving training, which he created as the image of "Perfect Man". With this, the thinker-poet-educator attached special importance to the role of education in the comprehensive development of personality. The poet-educator, who highly appreciates the role of the teacher and educator in both training and education, has specifically addressed this issue in all his poems. For example, the parents of Kays, Bahram, and Iskander trust the fate of their children to highly educated scientists and teachers. The high education, humanism, diligence, etc. of the teacher-educator in education. At the same time, the poet, who considers such qualities as important, also mentions the student's interest and talent in learning, as well as his attitude towards the teacher. For example, Bahram Guru's teacher saw his great interest and talent in science and tried to give him deeper knowledge:

He saw intelligence, grace in the prince,
He heard that there is knowledge in him.
He brought the board, the spindle,
He taught him the secrets of the sky.
He taught how hidden, revealed
The heavens and the earth have symbols.
He taught everything, Bahram
He studied and took lessons every morning and evening (5,134).

The ideas of the poet-pedagogue about the teacher-student relationship are more widely reflected in the poem "Iskandername".

Proposing that self-education plays a big role along with education and training in the formation of personality, the poet put forward a number of valuable ideas about this in "Khamsa". For example, in the poem "Seven Beauties", the poet teaches that there is no death for a person who understands himself and knows himself well:

Who is self-absorbed,
There is no death for him, that immortal.
He who does not know his role is mortal, mortal,
The rest is a person who knows this pattern.
If you know yourself, if you leave the world,

You will live in this world again (5,137).

Right here, the poet shows that those who do not know themselves, do not want to see their own flaws, those who cannot say "sour to their own butter" are unfortunate, such people will leave the world the way they came, that is, they will not be able to rise to the level of personality:

Not everyone is aware of himself,
He enters through one door and leaves through another...
... No one takes the remark to heart,
He does not make his existence perfect.

In addition to giving advice to others about self-education, the thoughtful poet-educator mostly admonished himself, instructed himself, encouraged himself, admitted his shortcomings, evaluated himself, etc. has repeatedly used such self-education methods. Let's look at a few examples from each poem to prove our point.

From the poem "Treasure of Secrets":

He refreshed my world, the king of the heart's estate,
The court of angels is open to Nizami.
If I am far from purity and nobility, what am I?
I am a holy servant to the lord of my heart (4, 61).

From the poem "Khosrov and Shirin":

Nizami, how much life is in you,
Keep coming down, that's what I want!
Look at the pearl that is fed in the sea,
As it falls, it only comes out of the head.
Fall to the ground like dawn, let your head be raised high,
Don't be like a spike - let the wind blow it down (4, 63).

In our opinion, self-education and self-education played a great role in the formation of the genius poet as a perfect personality and in the creation of the world-famous "Khamasa".

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CONDITIONS FOR THE FORMATION OF FUTURE TEACHERS' READINESS TO ORGANIZE LEARNING ACTIVITIES AT SCHOOL

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Currently, the Republic of Kazakhstan has identified the main directions of the modern development of education in both schools and HEIs. There is a constant reforming of the school education system in the following directions: the updated content of educational programs; the competency-based approach to knowledge acquisition becomes the main one. These changes are conditioned by the fact that instead of simple acquisition of knowledge and reproduction of the information received at the lesson more rational methods, such as project creative activity, able to develop students' creativity and critical thinking and to provide knowledge and skills, especially in such an important and complex subject as physics, should come. New requirements for secondary education require new teachers who know their subject well enough, who understand children's development and have professional skills based on competency-based approach, with which it is possible to organize the educational process in order to help schoolchildren study the subject (both traditional and more active creative teaching methods to which, concerning physics, the research work is first of all related). It should be noted that the foundations of the competency-based approach in the education system of Kazakhstan are laid in the conceptual, legal acts and standards of education, both higher and secondary. This is explained by the fact that it is pedagogical practice, based on the need of more competent personnel, determines the demand for research activities of a teacher, one of the most important professional competencies of a future teacher. At the same time, it is important to point out that in modern conditions of the system of updated education it is important and problematic to have physics teachers with the required professional competencies to form research abilities of schoolchildren.

The relevance of the research topic is the problem of physics teachers' training to organize research activities of schoolchildren, the need to develop the research abilities of future physics teachers as an important factor in their professional development. The importance of the problem of creating professional research competencies for future physics teachers (students of pedagogical HEIs), which they need when teaching physics in school, is expressed in the fact that such competencies allow preparing teachers capable of solving problems in the formation of research skills of their students when teaching physics. The relevance is confirmed by the

existence of many studies on this topic, which show that physics teachers and future teachers (students of pedagogical HEIs) have insufficient readiness to form students' research skills during the study of physics course. Since, on average, less than 50% of physics teachers and only more than 20% of students of pedagogical HEIs, future physics teachers demonstrate, for example, only understanding of the stages of scientific research [1]. There are contradictions, within the updated content of education, between the didactic foundations and the need to organize the research work of students in physics classes[2]. The mechanisms for the inclusion of research work in the learning process is developed insufficiently [3]. These indicators confirm the theoretical importance and practical relevance of the research topic and make it possible to determine the research purpose. The research is conducted with the purpose - to develop a model of formation of research abilities of students of physics of pedagogical HEIs from the position of the competency-based approach.

The research purpose was to determine the conditions necessary for the formation of future teachers' readiness to organize research work with schoolchildren, because modern teaching of physics at school requires the involvement of many students in research projects in order to learn to understand new things, to form skills and make independent decisions. The study of current physics teachers confirms the insufficient level of training in the HEI and the low level of technical and methodological equipment required to carry out quality work on the formation of research skills of students at school and insufficient level of motivation to conduct research.

The research skills of physics teachers were defined as the research object. The research subject was the problem of preparing future physics teachers to organize research activities of schoolchildren. The research was conducted in three stages.

At the first stage a literary analysis on the research topic was carried out. Legal acts, monographs, scientific articles, and other scientific publications on the research topic were used as research materials. Analysis of pedagogical, methodological literature, regulatory-legal acts, and practice of formation of research abilities are defined as theoretical methods of research. According to E.F.Zeer, the traditional tasks of the learning process, including higher education were: acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities. And at the present stage it is important to prepare a HEI graduate, who can form independently and successfully project culture, expressed in the ability to solve problems independently and to navigate in non-standard situations of their professional activity [4]. J.M.Bitibaeva notes that the analysis of requirements to the results of training of bachelors and masters, future physics teachers to organize research activity is based on how much the competency-based approach in education is implemented. It is noted that the competency-based approach implies not only the acquisition of professional knowledge, but also the ability to apply the acquired abilities in practice regarding students. This approach suggests that it is important to organize the training of a future teacher in a pedagogical HEI so that he or she acquires the professional skills (competencies) required in school practice [5]. D.A. Ivanov points out that regarding higher physical education in pedagogical HEIs there is a change in updating the content and changing purposes and objectives. Thus, in practice improvements (curriculums and plans) that are not always carried out, lead to growth of efficiency of all process of teaching and efficiency of the results obtained. There is a separation of the training process on the content from the requirements concerning practical activity, monotonous approaches are traced in the course of training, which leads to the fact that professional competences of future teachers of physics are underdeveloped [3]. Kazakhstan Committee for Control of Education and Science of on higher and secondary education envisages for the development of professional competencies of future competencies in the first place, in the second the need to develop students' research abilities[6]. Z.P. Mastropas, Yu.G. Sindeev point out the importance of the research approach in teaching physics, which is based on its characteristic features expressed in the implementation of the studied idea "through discovery". Within the framework of such an

idea the student should be able to investigate: to discover physical phenomena, laws of physics, physical properties of regularities; to select ways of solving individual problems, which are not yet known to him/her, and so on. This should be based on the existing knowledge of conducting research: from the simplest - observation, to more complex (conducting experiments); making a hypothesis or constructing an abstract model; formulating conclusions from theoretical research materials; experimental verification of the obtained results. It is offered usually to use an additional lesson or a session in which students are researchers - experimenters and try, for example, to receive on their experience new information on physical properties of materials or substances, having answered independently the questions offered by the teacher in cards or in laboratory classes[7].

At the second stage, the practice of forming research skills among teachers and future physics teachers was analyzed and evaluated. To analyze objectively, the practice of physics teachers' research skills formation was evaluated. The methods of empirical research were defined: a pedagogical experiment, within which a diagnostic questionnaire was conducted. The objectives of the experiment were to establish the level of formation and motivation of research abilities in graduates of the HEI, physics teachers and to establish the effectiveness of the proposed model for the formation of research skills in students. At the diagnostic stage, the level of formation of skills in conducting and organizing research work, as well as the level of motivation to conduct research works were established for 30 teachers. The main questionnaire questions were: do you know what kind of research skills a physics teacher should have; have you received teaching materials on how to teach children to do research; do you use goal setting and testing and hypothesis formulation in teaching; do you use project and creative methods in teaching; do you have analytical and inference skills; how often do you conduct research with students; what prevents you from doing research at school?

The next stage was to develop a model for training future teachers to form the research skills of students. We used methods of modeling. When developing the model, it was based on the fact that the formation of research activity is a controlled and directed process that begins within the walls of the HEI under the guidance of experienced teachers. The HEI should give future teachers the knowledge and skills that they can use in their pedagogic work. The proposed model provides for stage-by-stage formation of research stages in future teachers of physics. Each of the stages requires the formation of the required professional qualities and depends on the corresponding set didactic tasks. It should be noted that the implementation of stage-by-stage training in higher education institutions consists in periodic complication of not only the previously set tasks, but also in the formulation of research questions regarding them.

Analysis of the literature has shown that insufficient attention is paid to the problem of training future physics teachers to form research skills of future physics teachers to organize research with schoolchildren. The available scientific developments do not fully disclose the ways of training future physics teachers in the designated direction. Contradictions have been established between: requirements on the part of school, society and state, caused by the need to improve the results of teaching physics to schoolchildren and difficulties in their implementation by young teachers, as they have not formed the necessary professional competencies; the need and importance of organizing training of future physics teachers to obtain competencies to organize research activities of schoolchildren and insufficient methodological development of the research work organization when training at school.

The results of the assessment of the practice of research skills formation of teachers and future physics teachers; only 10% know what research minimum should have a physics teacher; during the training 21% received methodological materials to teach children research work; only 10% use the setting and testing of objectives and hypothesis formulation during training; 100% use project and creative methods during training (brainstorming and others); do students have

analytical and inference skills - 12%; only 10% often conduct research work with students; what hinders research work at school: lack of methodological recommendations - 100; lack of assessment criteria for research work - 25; heavy workload - 70; lack of time - 25; lack of special equipment or classrooms - 20%. The results obtained indicate the presence of many problems among teachers, the main of which are the insufficient level of training in HEI and the low level of technical and methodological equipment.

The model of future teachers' training includes: a content component; an assessment component; a motivational component; an organizational component, which allows developing comprehensive and high-quality professional competencies. The first stage of training provides for students to learn the methods of scientific research and adaptation to the new conditions of teaching, which allows students to perform reproductive-research types of research classes. The main distinctive feature of the stage is frontal didactic support. In the classes it is proposed to consider questions with practical research activities, which allows to practice the acquired knowledge: research activity, its main types and their content; making an abstract, reviews, referee reports; formulation of a hypothesis and its justification; ways of coding research results, choice of methods; analysis of obtained results from research; formulation of the conclusion (outputs); making a report. It is important to visually describe the research process to the students, which allows us to put students as subjects of learning. At the second stage, the learning tasks become more complicated. It is recommended for the students to conduct thesis as independent research under the teacher's control. The content component is characterized by peculiarity, which is based on the use of studied forms of research activity, by establishing analogies and associative links. The third stage gives students the opportunity to take part in research conducted by the HEI. In this case, the teacher should form the students' existing needs in the need to conduct independent research work, which gives an opportunity to develop research skills and for their future professional activities (to use in school practice a set of learned research skills). At this stage the forms of research activity of future physics teachers are improved and proactive indicators such as independent formation of research purposes and problems, development of research plan and organization of research are developed.

Thus, we found that the problem of preparing physics teachers for research work remains relevant and needs to be solved as soon as possible. It is conditioned by the fact that modern teaching of physics at school should be built in such a way that students should be involved with interest in research works, which provide an opportunity to teach them to understand new things, to form skills and make independent decisions first based on research results, and then in practical activities. These requirements also impose demands on pedagogical HEIs, which must update the quality of teacher training, with a focus on the competency-based approach.

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Literature

SOCIAL THEMES IN THE PROSE OF MUKHTAR AUEZOV

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Annotation :In this article an attempt was made to analyse the social themes in the prose of Mukhtar Auezov. Being one of the outstanding writers of the XX century, Auezov in his stories told about ordinary

people and their difficult fate. After analyzing the works of Auezov in the 20-30s ,it can be concluded that

in stories the writer described the relationship between social classes in Kazakh society.

Key words: Mukhtar Auezov, Kazakh literature, social realism, Soviet era, fate of ordinary people.

Mukhtar Auezov made an invaluable contribution to the development of Kazakh literature. His work is a proof of the immense possibilities of the method social realism. The creator of the first Kazakh epic novel, playwright, translator of Russian and European classics, scientist truly inexhaustible literary heritage of the great writer. The merit of the writer lies in the fact that in the Kazakh literature, which had no prose, drama, criticism in the past Auezov contributed to their formation, the

development of genre forms, traditions and original Kazakh style school.

Kazakh prose and drama went through the

process of formation at the beginning of the 20 century. The influence of oral folk art was noticeable in fiction. This influence applies to the plot and composition, the technique of creating a human character, from folk to art there is also an upbeat

manner of presentation.

The works of Mukhtar Auezov differ in content and artistry, in historicity, in folk character, when they are considered within the framework of world literature the mystery and essence of creative potential can be revealed. In his stories the fate

of country is covered in detail, it tells about the conflicting and contradictory moments in the life of society and does not leave indifferent events from life experience.

The main theme of Auezov's stories and novels of the 20s and 30s is not only the suffering of ordinary people, oppression, but also the spiritual awakening of the people, their desire for freedom. The writer condemns tribal strife, contrasting them

with the unity and cohesion of the people. Most of the stories of Mukhtar Auezov are based on tragedy. There are opposites in theme of the work, the course of events, the storyline, the confrontation between the characters. In these stories evil, enmity

and arbitrariness prevail and the main characters are in a deplorable state and the story usually ends in tragedy.

Speaking about the prose of M.Auezov, it is known that in the 20s he wrote in the method of social realism, depicting pre-revolutionary life, and in the 30s –life of the Soviet era. He went through creative evolution, moving step from step as a writer, reveling and discovering new things at every step of his artistic journey[Коньратбаев А., 2007.

c.24-27].The writer is increasingly expanding the field of stories. The volume of stories becomes longer and begins shift more voluminous prose.

Mukhtar Auezov wrote the works “Qarash- qarash oqigasy”(1927), “Kokserek”(1929), “Kily zaman” (1927).

Among the works of the writer of 20s the story “ Qarash-qarash oqigasy” takes special place. A special feature of this work is the naturalness of a mature artistic and progressive, combative worldview. This story clearly shows a new field in

the artistic journey of Mukhtar Auezov. Therefore this work can be considered as a milestone work of the writer. In the previous works of the author, the victims are not able to fight against them, no

matter how angry they are with the abuse of the exploiters. All the main characters unable to cope with their opponents, often fall, sacrifice themselves [Адибаев М.Х., 1984. С 32].This story shows the open battle of the exploited and exploiting. In the terms of ideological and artistic content this story is the pinnacle of the Auezov’s prose of the 20s. it tells about the life of Kazakh poor Baktygul. The brave horseman has seen a lot in his time. He does not agree to bear the calamities patiently. At first, he works honestly and then becomes a thief. Baktygul is hired as a farmhand to the rich man Zharasbai, and he pushes him to steal. In the end, Zharasbay is acquitted and Baktygul is convicted of the crime.Avoiding the court of the biys and rulers,the man goes away from people, is exposed to dangers and persecution however Baktygul kills Zharasbai [Ауезов.М., 2002. С 192].M. Auezov masterfully showed how the class struggle in the feudal Kazakh aul affects the fate of people. Relentless oppression changes the appearance of the poor, who are naturally quiet and modest. Baktygul becomes bitter, becomes on a slippery path. He is associated with the rich man Gaasbek.

Mukhtar Auezov refuses to give an unambiguous characterization of the heroes characteristic of folklore.He does not like to use only black colors when drawing negative images: life is complex and contradictory. M. Auezov prefers to refrain from direct characteristics

On the transformation of the reality life into an artistic life in this work of M.Auezov , doctor of philological sciences, professor Zh.Dudabayev said: “ the works of Mukhtar Auezov "Qarash-qarash oqigasy”, “Kily zaman”, "Osken Orken", "Abay Zholy", "Enlik-Kebek" reflect the best examples of artistic understanding of the creative development of life material, real phenomena of reality.”

Mukhtar Auezov using skillfully a large stock of Kazakh language brought to life such works that are unique in content and meaning. In 1921 the newspaper “Qyzyl Qazaqstan” published one of his an outstanding work “Qorgansyzydyn kuni ”. Sabit Mukanov claimed that the writer was elevated to the rank of truly European prose with his first story “Qorgansyzydyn kuni ”. K.Syzydykov said : “In this story is not only sadness, but sadness, where there is some unstoppable force, as if there ‘s a wave underneath hollow for fate.”Through the “Qorgansyzydyn kuni ” he hold a terrible story that evoked the inner feelings of the reader, showing the true picture of his time , the bitter truth, the sadness of a whole world of defenseless people. In conveying this bitter, insidious truth, Auezov excelled: he created beautiful portraits of the people involved in the event, and also expressed the behavior of the participants in the action. By describing the appearance of nature he was able to convey the inner thoughts of a person, as well as the message of what will happen, create a beautiful composition.Professor B.Maitanov gives a fair assessment of the work :“Akan and Kaltai are symbols of evil and violence and Gaziza is a sacrifice. In fact it was a work in a modernist style, which is innovative step in the result of deep assimilation of the best examples of world literature”[Майтанов Б. М., 2006. С 54.].As M.Auezov wrote in the article “Modern era of Kazakh literature”, “Karaly sulu” is a work that “contains a lot of images of life, a little history, a lot

of secrets of inner life, a lot of sadness that make a person to look inside himself". The main thing here is the state of feelings. The story is based on a female drama. The combination of incompatible words in the theme of the story reflects the future tragedy. The story tells about the tragic fate of young woman Karagoz, who lost her husband and became a widow. As if life itself has lost its meaning for a young woman. However, after six years the wound in the heart gradually began to heal. The place of sadness is gradually replaced by the natural desire of a woman to love her soul, the desire of feelings. Karagoz internally opposes the state of mourning and the tragedy in the life of the hero turns into a drama. The longing for love and the pain of the inner contradictions of the woman, who could not resist the sound of life are skillfully depicted. Karagoz's own struggle with herself, the struggle of her mind and feelings become the core of the dramatic conflict in the work. The ideological meaning of the work is to overcome the dogma of love, passion. The originality of characters, the isolation of their extreme destinies over the situation, the tragic death of the beloved, the aestheticization of love are among the signs of the poetics of the romance epic.

The next story "Jetim" tells about ten year old orphan boy, who leaves uncle's house because of injustice shown by his uncle and his quarrelsome wife and dies at night in search of cemetery of his

parents' grave. The writer conveys the last moment of a child's life, based on a tragedy, in words that go beyond the complex skill. Opens the ideological curtain on the content the events of the whole story, paves the way to a solution that excites the reader. The author, correlating the events in the work with each other, noted that the story is a work of art with a great emotional effect.

The constantly changing psychological profile of the boy is also important. According to the description of Kasym's appearance, the reader understands how hard it is for him in the family of his

relative Isa- "A little time passed, and Kasym, round faced and strong, inquisitive and cheerful, turned into a thin, gloomy, heartbroken boy, his whole appearance spoke of abandonment and misery." At

the end of the story, the author conveys the fear of a lonely boy walking in the steppe through the description of evil spirits in the boy's imagination- "It seemed to Kasym that the night was staring at him with thousands of black terrible eyes. An eye from under every rock, from under every bush. And on the mountains wanders a star-eyed, stonebrowed, with a face as black as night, an evil old woman, whispers some spells and sneezes loudly."

The writer is deeply immersed in the fate of orphaned children and expresses his pity. The writer considers it a shame to calmly treat such humiliation.

Despite the fact that the topic of orphanhood is constantly raised in both prose and poetry, it is still considered an epidemic of society. The main theme of Mukhtar Auezov is the fate of the nation, the fate of the people. His work had a positive impact not only Kazakh literature, but also on the world literature. His creative activity and civic identity are an example and indelible mark for every writer.

M. Auezov thought about the welfare of his people, about man as a carrier of spirituality. Brought up on Eastern philosophy and poetry, he expands his horizons, worldview boundaries, turning his face to European, Russian culture, armed with an artistic and critical approach not only to literature, but also to life itself.

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АҚЫТ ҮЛІМЖІҰЛЫ ШЫҒАРМАШЫЛЫҒЫ: ТАРИХИЛЫҚ, ДЕРЕКТІЛІК, КӨРКЕМДІК

Серік НЕГИМОВ

Қазақстан еңбек сіңірген қайраткері, Халықаралық «Алаш» әдеби сыйлығының лауреаты, филология ғылымдарының докторы, профессор

Халық рухы мен ойлау тәсіліне, ұғым-түсініктеріне, мұрат-тілегіне, пайым-парасатына, ғұрпы-дәстүріне лайықтап, мысалдап, тәмсілдермен тұздықтап, есілтіп-төгілтіп жырлау – Ақыт Үлімжіұлының сүйікті ақындық мәнері. Кең құлашты, кемел білімді, көркемдік дүниетанымы, тарихи зердесі, интеллектуалдық-мәдени дәрежесі биік эпик ақынның:

Мысал қылдым пайғамбар, патшаны да,

Мысал қылдым ұрыны ат жалында.

Мысал қылдым даугерді дауа таппас,

Мысал қылдым ғайыпты қас қағымда –

дегенінен телегей шығармаларының кесек, ірі тақырыптық ауқымын, импровизаторлық, тапқырлық қабілет-қарымын, шалқар шабытты шығарымпаздық шеберлігін нақты тануға болады. Я болмаса ел әдебиетінің мұхитынан сусындаған майталман жыршы «Насихат сөз көп жаздым жалпыға арнап» шынайы пейіл-көңілін мөлдір тазалықпен жеткізіп, «Қазылық жолына бұл өрнек болып», «Халық сөзі сақталған даналық боп» деп суреткерлік ұстанымын, азаматтық көзқарасын, елдік мінезін танытады.

Ақыт Үлімжіұлы – халық тарихы мен ұлт руханиятының білімпазы, замана тамыршысы (оның поэзиясында зар заман, қан заман, тар заман, сұм заман, шерлі заман дейтін тіркестер жиі қолданылады).

Халық трагедиясын сай-сүйегімен, жан-жүрегімен қабылдаған зерек зейінді, ұшқыр ойлы, жалынды ақынның «Замананы сөйлейін» атты толғауында күрсініске-күйінішке толы елдің зары мен ерекше жаратылған жақсылардың бекзат болмысы

18-де жасымыз,

Ақыт деген атымыз.

Руы Молқы Машаннан,

Қазақтан ата затымыз.

Мұны жазған Ақыт-ты,

Өлең жазды, хат тұтты.

Замананы сөйлейтін,

Өтіп кетті көп мықты!

Ел ұстап өтті Бейсенбі,

Сөйлейтін топта шешен-ді.

Сол Бежең кетіп арадан

Қайран елі теңселді.

Басқалқаң кетсе панасын,

Кім көтерер еңсеңді – деп, шамырқанған шабытпен

өрнектеген.

Мұнда, «7 атасы Қаракөк» Құлыбек би, «Айтқан сөзі дәрі би» Кәрі би, «Асыл туған ғайыптың құсы жел еді (Атыкең-тәйжі)» дейтін көркем мінездемелері қандай десеңізші!

Ақынның асыл ойларының көркемдік әсерлілігі де айрықша. Мәселен:

Жақсының іші кірленді,

Сіңген жейде **кіріндей**.

Ендігінің пысығы –
Оқ жыланның **түріндей**.
Ғадыл болса ұлығың,
Үйшілердің **тезіндей**.
Парақор болса ұлығың,
Жанған өрттің **көзіндей**.

Я болмаса:

Ел қорғаны ұлықтар,
Жолбарыс жатқан *түбектей*.
Жан күйттеген ұлықтар,
Отқа салған *бүйректей*.
Көпке жаққан жігіттер,
Жапанға біткен *теректей*.
Ел сүймеген жігіттер,
Ағаштан кескен *иректей*.
Мінезі сұлу қыздар бар,
Қолға салған *жүзіктей*.
Бошалақ салақ кей қыздар,
Жиегі жоқ *үзіктей*.
Ұқып та, ыспар қыздар бар,
Кестеленген тор *жіптей*.
Шашылған олақ қатын бар,
Түтеленген құр *жіптей*.
Көпті көрген шалдар бар,
Ақылы артық *көсемдей*.
Түйтеленген шалдар бар,
Отқа салған *көсеудей*.

Халық тағдыры, замана суреті, «білген мен білмегеннің екі арасы, аспан мен жердей болып айрылады» деп өзі айтқандай, жақсы-жайсаңдар мен кәззап сұмырайлардың бейнелерін түйдек-түйдек **ұлттық бояу-нақыштарға толы** теңеулермен келісті **кестеленген. Және теңеулердің сыңғыры ойды, пікірді, мағынаны үстемелей түседі.**

«Зырлаған заман белгісі» де шынайы:

Бұзылды заман қағына,
Жылпостардың бағына.

Ел басына төнген қорғасындай қара бұлт апалаң-топалаң тудырғанын, ерлер шөгіп, әумесер есерлер дүрілдеп-гүрілдеп, баскесер болғанын, бейбастақтық жасағанын баяндайды.

- 1) Замана кімді айырмас,
Жақсыны жаман танымас.
Көнбеймін деген кеудеңнен,
Қиылып түсер қайран бас.
- 2) Замана келді қырланып,
Борандай соғып сұрланып.
- 3) Тай көкірек бозбала,
Шерлі болып өлесің – деп безек қағады.

Оның «Тайтекеңнің үйінде» дейтін толғауында ойран-асыр, апыр-топыр уақыттың сұмдықтары айшықты бедерленген:

Хан-қайқы, биің – бүкір, молла – соқыр,
Мен түзу дегеніңнің бәрі бұраң.

Жігерлі, өнерлі, өнегелі, рухы биік Ақыт елдің жарқын келешегіне не қажет екендігіне де назар аударады:

Ақыры өнер менен білім керек,
Көксеген қай бір жұртқа жетем десең.

Тіл үйрен шүршіт, моңғұл, орыс болсын,
Мейлі түзу, мейлі ол бұрыс болсын.

Ғылымның анық ұғын білсең затын
«Ақылы қамал жаралған,
Ұмтыла озған жүйріктерді» жырға қоса отырып, әлеуметтік топтарға да сипаттама беріп отырады:

Жомарт болса бай адам,
Дария шалқар көлмен тең.
Сыған болса бай адам,
Қылтанақсыз шөлмен тең.

Күн қарайды аспаннан,
Сұлудай қасы қиылып.

Тілге, ойға, суретті сөйлеуге шеберлігі сүйсіндіреді.

* * *

Сөз – базар, ақ қағазға салсам назар,
Мысал сөз қыз ұзатқан бейне жиын.

«Күңіреніп тұрған жер Алтай» көрінісі де әсерлі.

Он сегізінші ғасырдың соңғы шені,
Алтайға қайта айналды Қазақ Елі.
Жер айналған мұхиттың бәрі толқып,
Тиіп тұр әрбір жұртқа соққан сеңі.

Немесе:

Өнер, ғылым қайда бар,
Қандай істе пайда бар.
Тіршілікте байланар,
Береке қалай айланар.
Замананың заңында,
Неше түрлі қайла бар.
Кейбіреу көкке ұшып жүр,
Ұшқан құстан пысық жүр,
Жер бетімен зырылдап,
Су астына түсіп жүр.
Қайда жүрсе сор қазақ,

Мал соңында көшіп жүр,
Оян қазақ намыстан,
Өнер ізде алыстан.
Қайлалы жұрт – арыстан,

Қайласыз жұрт – көртышқан – деуінде философиялық тереңдік бар. Елдің келешегі, өнер-білім мәнісі, замана сыры тұжырымдалған.

Ақыт Үлімжіұлының білгірлігі, кісілігі, тереңдігі, ұстаздығы, төрелік айту, қазылық жасау шеберлігі, шешендігі, әңгімешілдігі ел ішінде абыройын, тұлғасын асқақтатты. Ол бұрынғылардың көркем дәстүрін дамытты. Мысалы, Әмір Темір көреген Құдайдың құтты күні «түн базарын қыздырып, ойды, даланы жап-жарық күндізгідей қылдырып, ғұламалар мәжілісін жасатып, заманындағы жүйріктерді сөйлетіп отырады екен» (Мәшһүр Жүсіп). Сол сияқты Ақыт та өз қауымының сөз ұстаған дүлдүлі, өз білгенін ішіне жыймай, ақсұңқарша айналасына нақышына келтіріп, тамылжытып ғибратты тәмсілдерден, кейбір сөз-ұғымдардың, фразалардың құпиясын, адамның ой-санасына сәуле түсіретін шығармалардың мазмұнын жан-жақты, толық, әйбәт ғып түсіндіріп, жетесіне жеткізіп беретін де дағды-машығы бар. Бұл орайда баласы Қалманның мынадай естелігіне жүгінейік:

Әкем бір күні «Хаятұл-хайуан»- яғни, «жандылар тіршілігі» аталатын оғыз тілінде жазылған бір кітапты оқи отырып, бізге мына бір әңгімені айтып бергені әлі есімде:

«Мұхаммед пайғамбардан (с.ғ.с.) кейін – Мұхаммед пайғамбардың (с.ғ.с.) әкесі Ғабдолла мен бір туысқан Ғаббас деген адамның тұқымы араб түбегіне миләди 750-жылдан 1258-жылға дейін 508 жыл Халифа болады. Халифалардың ішінде әділі де, залымы да болыпты. Соның ішінде мөлшермен миләди 750-інші жылдарда «Хұжжж» деген бір залым халифа болған екен. Бұл адам шу дегенде әскербасы болып, кейін халифалыққа көтеріледі. Халифа болғаннан кейін өте қатыгез болып, тура айтқанның басын алады. Өзіне қарсы келсе-ақ болды, оның нақақтығына қарамайды. Сол басы алынғандардың ішінде «Сағид ибну Жабир» деген бір мәшһүр ғалым бар екен. Дәл сол дәуірде оған тең келетін ғалым жоқ екен. Бір күні әлгі жауыз халифа бірқанша нөкерлерімен аң аулауға сейілге шығып бара жатып, өзінің хатшысына:

- Менің нақақ өлтірген адамым қанша болды? – деп сұрайды. Хатшысы:
- 50 мыңдай болды, - дейді.
- Күмәнмен өлтіргенім қанша болды? – деп сұрайды.
- 20 мыңдай болды, - дейді.

Хұжжж басқалардың барлығын күшпен өзіне қаратса да, сол кезде Мекке шаһарын билеп тұрған «Ғабдолла ибну Зубайыр» деген әділ және диянатты адамды оңай-оспақ бағындыра алмайды. Хұжжж Мекке шаһарына барлық әскерімен жаза жорығын жасап, Меккені басып алып, Ғабдолла ибну Зубайырды тұтқындайды да, онан:

- Мен әділмін бе? Залыммын ба? енді айт дейді. Ғабдолла көкірегін керіп тұрып:
- Нақ залымсың, - дейді.

Хұжжж сол майданда оның басын алуға бұйырады. Ғабдолла – Лә Илаһа Иллалаһу, - деп иман айтып еңкейе бергенде Ғабдолланың басы алмас қылышпен шауып түсіріледі. Ғабдолланың басы жерге түскеннен кейін де, әлгі айтқан иманын бірнеше рет қайталайды. Бұған қарап тұрған Хұжжж одан шошып кетіп, көтеріліп (есінен адасып) ауырады. Көзі іліне берсе-ақ болды «Әнтә қаталтәни бихайри хаққин – язалим» («Мені жазықсыз өлтірдің, ей залым») деп Ғабдолла Хұжжждың жағасынан алатын болады. Ақыры Хұжжж бір ай құтырып ауырған бойы қиналып жан береді.

Хұжжжждан кейін, Ғаббас тұқымынан һарун Рашид деген адам 786-жылдан 809-жылға дейін 23 жыл халифа болды. Бұл адам халыққа жағымды, әділ, ғылымды құрметтейтін турашыл екен. Ол бір күні дәрет алып, екі ракағат истихара намазын оқып «Иә, Жаратқан маған Хұжжждың о дүниедегі хал-жағдайын көрсет, ұйқыда аян қыла гөр» - деп мінажат етіп

ұйықтап қалады. Дәл осы күні түнде һарун Рашидтың түсіне Хұжжаж кіреді, бірақ өте сұрықсыз, адам көрсе шошитын бейнеде кіреді. Екі көзі үңірейіп ішіне кіріп кеткен. Екі шекесі қушиып суалып, екі беті қап-қара, денесі тілім-тілім жара, үсті-басында сау-тамтық жер жоқ, өрім-өрім болып кіреді. һарун Рашид халифа:

- Ей Хұжжаж, о дүниеге барғанда жағдайың қалай болды? – деп сұрайды, Хұжжаж:

- Қандай болушы еді?! 70 мың адам өлтірген екенмін. Сол 70 мың адам үшін 70 мың рет өлтіріп, 70 мың рет қайта тірілтті. Соның ішінде бір адам үшін және де 70 мың рет өлтіріп, қайта тірілтті – дейді. һарун Рашид:

- Ол адам кім? – деп еді, ол:

- Сағид ибну Жабирды өлтірдім емес пе, сол адам үшін, - деді де, өз обалым өзімде, - деп өкіріп жылап жіберді.

Әкем осы бір хикаяны айтып болып, көзілдірігін бір қозғап қойып, екі көзін қарсы алдына қадап, аз-кем үнсіз отырды да: «Дүниеде екі түрлі жауһар бар. Бірі – ғәділдік, бірі – ғылым. Ғабдолла ибну Зубайыр – ғәділ еді. Оны өлтірген Хұжжаж ес-ақылдан айырылып құтырып, рәсуә болып өлді. Сағид ибну Жабир – ғалым еді. Оны өлтіргендігі үшін 70 мың қайта өліп, 70 мың қайта тірілді. Ғибрат алыңдар» - деп барып сөзін доғарды» (Ақытұлы Ғазез. Қазақ тарихындағы әйгілі адамдар. Алматы, 2008. 42-44 беттер).

Қайраткер, ағартушы, ақын, романшы, мешіт пен медресе ұйымдастырушы Ақыт Үлімжіұлының білімпаздығына айғақ ретінде ол араб тілі грамматикасын, жер тарихын, Күншығыс елі мен Ислам тарихын және есеп, астрономия, география пәндерін жақсы білген.

Ел ортасында жұртты аузына қаратқан, өнеге-білім, ізгілік нұрын таратқан Ақыт қажы Абай мұрасын жанқиярлықпен насихаттап, оның күрделі ой-байламдары мен мазмұнының терең сырлары мен мағынасының нәзік тұстарын өзіндік пайым-көзқараспен «Ғақлиялық үндеулерін» шығарған. Осының әсерінен ел ішінде Абайға қызығушылық өрістеген, ойшыл ақынның кәусарынан сусындаған.

Абаймен неге ой, сөз, пікір жарыстырасың деп баласы Қалман сұрайды ғой. Сонда Ақыт қажы: «Құранның да, хадистердің де түсіндірмелері бар ғой...» деп, уәж айтады.

Ғазез Ақытұлының көрсетуінше, ол Жүсіп Баласағұнның, Мұхаммед Хайдар Дулатидің, Құрбанғали Халидидің, Рабғузидің, Мақсудидың шығармаларын зерделеп оқыған.

Жомарт мінезділік, ақ жүректілік, дархан пейілділік, мейірбандық, ұлттың рухани жетілуіне жойқын үлес қосқан, «бала – жер періштесі» деп қайрат-жігерін, білім-білігін жұмсап оқытқан жаны «жақұт қазына» Ақыт ақын ғылым жайында мынадай кесек пайымдау жасайды: «Ғылым деген қабат-қабат асқар тау сияқты. Бір тауға шығып алсаң, ар жағында тағы бір тау көрінеді, бәріне де шыққың келеді. Бұл бір жағы. Ғылымның тағы бір ерекшелігі – ғылым адамзат алған сайын, үйренген сайын молайып отырады, таусылмайды.

Ғылымды алты түрлі тәсілмен қолға қондырасың: 1. Табиғи зеректік. 2. Ғылымға қызығу – ынтығу. 3. Шыдамды-қажырлы болу. 4. Ғылыми отырыстарға көп қатынасу. 5. Мықты ұстаздың жетегінде болу. 6. Ғылым іздеу уақытын ұзаққа созу».

Тұмысынан тегеуірінді, отты, турашыл Ақыт Үлімжіұлы қара қылды қақ жарған үздік әділдігімен де ерекшеленген. Қылмыстық және азаматтық істер дауында толық, әділ тексеру, дұрыс кесім айту, шешім шығару – негізгі бағыты болған. Төрелік айту мәдениетінде жүйріктік, тапқырлық, мейірбандық танытқан. Ол жәбірлеуші жақ пен жәбір-жапа көруші жақтың өзара келісімге, пәтуаға келуіне күш жұмсаған. Себебі, ағайын арасы, ел іші қайшылықтар шырмауында қалмауы үшін. Көбінесе жамандықтан жирендіру жолымен шешкен. Бір мысал: 1920-жылдар мөлшері, Шеруші мен Жәдік арасында оңтүстік отарда қыс ішінде қораға таласқан төбелес-жанжал болып, Жәдік жағы Шеруші Жіптелбайды сойылға жығып өлтіріп қояды. Бірақ төбелесте екі жағының саны орайлас болғанымен, сан жағынан Шеруші көп болғандықтан, Жәдік жағы майданнан сытылып шығады. Сонда Жәдік Шәкер би

«Қолмен істеген ісімізді мойынмен көтереміз, шариғатпен кескен бармақ ауырмайды» деп, жанына үш-төрт адам ертіп Жіптелбайдың сүйегін түйеге артып алып, тұп-тура сүйекті Ақыттың алдына алып келеді. Сол арада Шеруші жағынан мал қуу, жарғы жару, ауыл шабу істері басталып кетіп, мәселе екі ру арасына айналғанда, Ақыт қазы «Шәкер би өз қылмысын өзі танып, Жіптелбайдың сүйегін шариғат алдына алып келді. Атамыз қазақта «Иілген мойынды қылыш кеспейді» деген мақал бар. Оның сыртында қазақ арасында ерегіс пен айқаста, не қата тиіп, не бата тиіп туылған оқыс өлім болмаса, дәл өз қолымен әдейі кісі өлтіріп, өлім жазасына тартылған жағдай болған емес. Осы жолғы өлімді өлуші мен өлтіруші арасындағы мәселе ретінде қарау керек, кісі орнына кісі аламыз деу – силай рахымды үзіп атыс пен шабыс сарпалдаңын тудырады» деп төрелік айтып ақыры 100 жылқы құнға тоқтатып (құнды ру болып үстіне алады) мұның көп бөлімін телімге түсірмей Жіптелбай туыстарына бергізеді. Бұл билікке екі жағы да разы болысады. Ақыт қазының 28 жыл ішінде нешеме түрлі дау-жанжалдарға билік-кесім шығарғанда мүлт кеткен жері болмаған.

«Насихат» дейтін толғауында әлеуметтік топтардың әрқайсысын іс-әрекетіне, мінез-құлығына, жүріс-тұрысына, көзқарасына, қыр-сырына сыншылдықпен саралап, әділетті сипаттама береді. Айталық:

Билерге

Ұлық болсаң, әділ бол,
Шариғат ұстап кәміл бол.
Елдің ғұрпын, жұрт жолын,
Жете байқап, таныр бол.

Әділдік жоқ, арсыз би,
Ақыреттен қамсыз би.
...Табансыз тайғақ жаман би,
Ойсыз, мисыз сабан би.
Оқу да жоқ, тоқу жоқ,
Шариғатқа шабан би.

Байдан пара алмаңдар,
Ауызға арам салмаңдар.
Қайсаңдатпа байыңды,
Мұқатып байқа залымды.
Залымдарды түзетіп,
Құрметтендер ғалымды.

Мұнда бидің басты қағидаты, тағлиматы берілген.

Байларға

Ақыл мен дәулет серік боп,
Нұрланып туған ай болсаң.

Моллаларға

Анық молла жан шырақ,
Ғылым – жарық, шам – шырақ.

Атыңа затың сай болсын,
Ғылымнан азық ал, құрап.

Кәрілерге

Дүниенің кірме көзіне,
Қарауыл қой сөзіңе.

Жігіттерге

Көңіл көзін аш жігіт
Еліңе өнер шаш жігіт!

Осыларда ардагер ақынның өмір тәжірибесінен алынған тағылымдық іс-әрекеттері өрілген.

Ақыт Үлімжіұлы – классикалық білім мен кемел шығармашылықтың иесі. Телегей ақындық пен ділмарлық, қазылық пен ұстаздық, қайраткерлік пен кісілік – оның заңғар шығармашылық тұлғасын, жаратушылық қабілет-қуатын айқындайды. Асан қайғы хақында айтқан «ақылдың дана кені еді» дегенді Ақыт қажының өзіне де айтуға болады. Ол тудырған жыр мұхитына – сыр мұхитына ден қойсақ, оның қаламынан «Керей ешені Мұхаммет момын», «Хажы Баян» атты тарихи-этнографиялық және сапарнамалық өлең-романдары, «Ескендір Зұлқарнайын», «Ұлықпан қиссасы», «Жиһаншаһ», «Ахуал-и-Қиямет», «Жауыз патшаның жаңылысы», «Сүлеймен мен Байғыздың қиссасы», «Жәнібек батыр», «Жеті қажы» дейтін дастандары ұлт игілігіне, халық мұрасына айналған.

Сахара халқының өмірінде сахна әдебиеті (яғни келісті, нақысты орындалуы, Мәтін мен мелодияның, ым-ишарат, қимыл-әрекеттің біртұтастығы тыңдармандармен тікелей байланыста болғандығы) кең қанат жайғандықтан, оның дастандарының көркемдік әлемінде қызығушылық тудыратын қиял-ғажайып ертегілік, аңыздық сюжеттері жеткілікті. Бұл тұрғыдан келгенде «Жиһаншаһ» дастанының көркемдік құрылымына, оқиға желісіне, баяндау тәсіліне ойысайық. Кәбіл шаһарында бір перзентке зар Тайпұз патша билік құрған. Уәзірі Хұжжәддың ақыл-кеңесімен Хорасан елінің патшасына қызын сұрап хат жазады. Ол сұлумен қосылған соң, Жиһаншаһ есімді ұл дүние есігін ашады. 15 жасында «Тәуратты» жатқа заулатады. Әкесі алтын тағын береді. Бірде Жиһаншаһ аңға шыққанда бір шалқыған ақ теңізге кезігіп, патша Жиһаншаһ кемеге жайғасады. Дүлей дауыл мен ұйытқыған боранның тұтқынында қалады. Мағұрық шаһ – анасы – пері, ата заты – адам-дүр Сүлеймен пайғамбардың Жарлығымен құстардың патшасы болыпты. Ол жыл сайын құстарды жинап, Сүлейменнің рухына дұға жасайды екен. Бұл өлкеде 3 халифа бар көрінеді. Әрқайсысының арасы алты айшылық жол. Шал Жиһаншаһқа сарайларын тамашалатады.

Шал бір есікті ашады да, бұл үйде саған сай ешнәрсе жоқ, егер тіл алмай темір үйге кірсең, көзің жұмылғанша қайғы-шер тартасың дейді. Бірақ Жиһаншаһ қоярда-қоймай аштырса, алтын сарай, алтын тақыт, жемісті бұлақ. Ең кереметі үш ақ көгершін. Үшеуі де сілкініп дереу үш қыздың кейпіне енеді. Кіші қызды көргенде Жиһаншаһ талады. Шал бетіне су бүркіп тірілтеді. Дастанда:

Жылында бір келеді осы жерге,
Шомылып бір түседі осы көлге.
Бұларды ешбір адам ұстай алмас,
Түседі ғашық оты көрген ерге – делінген.

Бұлар патшаның 3 қызы еді: Райса, Қамарбану, кішісі Шамшабану.

Жиһаншаһ тұтқиылдан кенже қыздың көйлегін құшады, шал екеуінің некесін қияды да, өлгенінше көйлегін ұстата көрме дейді.

Шамшабану Жиһаншаһты арқасына мінгізіп, зеңгір көкке қалықтап-шарықтап самғайды. Жиһаншаһ Кәбіл шаһарын көрсетеді. Шамшабану ата-анасымен қауыштырады.

Ұсталар мәрмәрдан сандық жасап, қанат көйлекті сонда сақтайды. Шамшабану кірген бетте көйлектің исін алып, темір сандықты талқандап көйлегін киеді. Жиһаншаһ күйініп зарланады.

Шамшабану өз ата-анасының рұқсатын алу үшін Халифа Гауһар – Негін шаһарына бет түзейді. Бұл шаһардың ұлылығы сондай, үш айлық жерден жарығы көрінеді. Шамшабанудың ой дүниесінің іңкәрлігін естіп-сезіп, Жиһаншаһ Жаратқан Иеге мың мәртебе шүкірлік етіп, көңілі масайрайды.

Оқиғаны қызықтыра қыздырып баяндау, әсерлендіріп суреттеу, қаһарманды тағдыр талқысына ұшырату, трагедиялық ситуациялардың ортасында көрсету – Ақыт Үлімжіұлының көркемдік дәстүрі, ұстанымы.

Атақты Керей Ер Жәнібек батыр туралы дастанында Бас кейіпкерін «Қап тауындай қорғанға», «мың кісілік періге» теңейді. Батырдың балауса шағындағы бір сәтін, яғни ханға тамақ істеп беру үшін ағаш бейіт молаға жұмсайды. Ол соған барғанда аяқ-астынан қабірден ақ кебін киген батыр шығып ұмтылмасы бар ма, сонда ол «Хақыңды Құран оқып бергем» дейді абыржымастан.

Дастанда Ер Жәнібек бейнесі ерекше. Ол ұйықтап жатқанда алып денелі аюға ақырғанда сеспей қатады, жыланның басын қыршып тастайды.

Дастаншыл ақын «Ахуал – Қиямет» (Ахирет баян) туындысында Адам Атадан бастап Әбіл, Қабыл, Нұқ, Лұт, Зүлкә, Ибраһим, Ысмағұл, Ысқақ, Жақып, Сыдық, Жүсіп, Шұғайып, Айып, Дәуіт, Сүлеймен, Лұқпан, Хакімдердің ізгілікті істерін баяндайды. Жалғанның өткінші екенін түсіндіреді:

«Жан бергенге – дән берген патша Құдай,
Кедей де күн көреді жоқтан байып.
Жалған мен ахиретті бірдей ойла,
Бұл дүние баяны жоқ өтер ғайып.
Асқар тау, өзен-судың бірі қалмас,
Ақ теңіз, Қара теңіз, Еділ, Жайық!

Адам өміріндегі басты құндылықтырды былайша жырлайды:

- а) Адамға ахиретте иман нәсіп
- б) Сұм жалған ойлағанда опасы жоқ,
Төкпеңдер тірі күнде беттің арын!

Ақырзаман кейпі:

Құлшылық Құдайына қылмай өткен,
Барғанда ахиретке соры қайнар.
Сол күнде өз басына куә болар,
Жалғанда адамзатқа қылған айбар.
Аспаннан найза бойы күн түскенде,
Қып-қызыл жердің беті *мыстай* қайнар.
Қызарар *әуе мыстай, жер темірдей,*
Адамзат күнәсі көп *миы қайнар.*

Тозақтың түрі мынадай: Тозақ аузын ашып жұлқынар, күрзімен соғу, тілін шайнау. Жылан мен шаянның соруы, от кісен салынады. Кей қатынның желкесінен жеті кез тіл шығуы,

бұтынан сасық ірің ағуы, оттан кебіс кию, оттан жейде кию секілді құбыжық көріністерді тізбелейді.

Тілегі таза, ісі ақ кісінің келбеті мынадай:

Ақ істілер, тірілер айдай болып,
Толықсып жүзі көркем майдай болып.
Басына тәж оранып, тахыт мініп,
Қас-кірпігі тұрады жайдай болып.
Көңілі имандының жарық нұрдан.

Дархан дарынның дария дастандарында «тарпаң мінез тарихтың бір сарсаңы», терең теңіздей толқыған халық өмірі мен тұрмысы, ұлттың ұлы жолдағы ізгілікті істері, білім, ғылым, парасат мәселесі ұлпа-отанымен (түп-тамырымен) жырланады.

Ойы шуақты, сөзі қуатты Ұлықбек Есдәулеттің тебірене толғағанындай, «ілімнің қазығы», «жақұт қазынаның» иесі, заңғар, мәшһүр ақын Ақыт шығармаларының жариялану тарихына үңілсек, өз халқының рухани өрлеуіне қаншалықты үлес қосқанын көреміз. Бұл тұста мына бір деректі келтірсек, 1917 жылға шейін қазақ тілінде 2 млн 201105 дана кітап басылған екен, соның ішінде А.Үлімжіұлының «Жиһаншаһ» (1897), «Қисса-и Жиһаншаһ Тамузшаһ оғлы» (1901), «Қисса-и Сәйпілмәлік» (1895, 1909, 1914), Қисса-и «Ғабділмәлік» (1902, 1904, 1909,), «Тәржімә-и Ақыт уәләд», «Ахуал-и қиямет», «Қисса-и Манақыб нуран ғазизан» («Ғазиздер нұрының естелігі»), «Әбиат ғақдия» («Ғибрат жыр») (1909) дейтін жыр-толғаулары мен дастандары бар.

Сонымен қатар, 2011 жылы Түркияның Кония шаһарында қос томдық шығармалары (көлемі 1104-бет) басылды. Осынау жыр мұхитына – сыр мұхитына бас-көз болған, атап айтқанда, құрастырған, алғы сөз жазған, ғылыми, тарихи, әдеби өмірбаяндық түсініктемелермен толықтырған философия ғылымдарының кандидаты Гүлнәр Омароваға мың да бір рахмет.

Қазақ халқының ауыз әдебиеті қазынасын, Шығыстың классикалық әдебиетін, Абай мұрасын, араб-парсы, түркі-монғол, орыс тілдерін еркін меңгерген Ақыт Үлімжіұлы Шәкәрімше де сөз саптайды. Мысалы:

Салынған қала жоқ,
Оқытылған бала жоқ,
Өнер-ғылым үйретер,
Талабы бар дана жоқ.
Әзір астың иесі,
Көбінде елдің сана жоқ! («Ал, жарандар, тыңдай бер»)

Тоқетері, ұлт әдебиеті тарихында Ақыт Үлімжіұлының поэзиялық мұрасы көркемдік, әуезділік, философиялық, тарихи-этнографиялық, ертегілік-аңыздық, халықтық-шығармашылық мәнерімен, тамылжыған қасиеттерімен айрықшаланады. Дәуірнамалық сипаты да бөлекше. Тұлғатану оқулығы десек те әділеттілік. Ұлпат-тұлғаның трагедиялық тағдыры да ұлт тағдыры. Рухани игіліктері – ел, халық, замана шежіресі.

HUMAN AND TIME PROBLEM IN MODERN LITERARY CRITICISM

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Abstract. There is a famous saying: "Life flows like water." This is the time hidden under the expression "life" itself. It is that time that drags the human life up and down in its flow, and dissolves it in its transcendence. Generations change, time sometimes wears out, sometimes renews. In all this flow of time, the time that comes together with a person becomes an eternal image that cannot be erased from the stage of life.

That is why the thoughts about man and time have always troubled the owners of creative thinking, and they have tried to create poetic lines of this inseparable duo. At this stage of the research work, the concept of man and time was taken as a problem, and in order to achieve a real artistic solution, the works of the folk writer Anar were turned to as a source.

As a result of the research, it was found that time is constantly moving. Being a part of nature, if a person wants to keep pace with time, live the time, even the moment, then he must understand life correctly, and be able to draw timely and correct conclusions from the happenings.

A person succeeds in life when he transcends the time that carries him along, does not take it for granted and does not allow time to overtake him by being constantly in motion. He fights not only for what life has given him, but for what he is supposed to have. He does not give up the path he knows is right and is always dynamic. Because life loves dynamism.

Keywords: man, time, truth of life, time and luck, fate, literary thought, literary criticism, literary hero

Man is the highest being among all other creatures of nature with all his internal and external signs, inner world, spirituality, mind, understanding and feeling-emotional mood. Therefore, all points related to people and people have always been relevant and are. The problem of man and time, which we involved in the research, has been a very important issue that all artists think about. If we pay attention, we will see that it is not possible to think of a person without time, nor time without a person. These two concepts are organically connected and co-exist.

We can prove our point if we make an effort to analyze the unknown - not time, but the known - person in order to distinguish the dependence of man from time, or time from man.

Let's look at the process of human birth and growth. Adolescence, childhood, adolescence, youth, middle age and finally old age. All these processes occur in separate periods, and we distinguish them, of course, based on those periods. It takes a certain amount of time for a person to grow, mature, and fully understand life. It is because of this characteristic that it is impossible to think of a person outside the flow of time.

As for the role played by time in human life, without any hesitation we try to create a magnificent image of it in our imagination. In fact, no matter how much this image, which is invisible to the eye and impossible to touch with the hand, keeps itself inside, it is not so difficult to determine its signs, direction of movement, flow, speed.

The concept of time is of deep importance as a tool that directly shapes the hero as a hero, reflects him in the mirror of reality, complements him, helps him to be comprehensively understood, and creates conditions for his analysis. It is possible to think of neither a timeless hero

nor a time without a hero. Because everyone is a hero of his time. If he is a true hero, and his dream, ideals, words and deeds as a hero not only correspond to the requirements of the times, but also manage to go ahead of the times, then he stands out from his contemporaries and contemporaries as a true hero, and is transferred to literature and eternity as a symbol of heroism.

The image of Time that makes Anar think should be evaluated as a literary fact born from the perfect artistic solution of his literary-philosophical searches. Time, the author's abstract hero, is vivid, believable, and also quite thought-provoking. When a person tries to analyze this hero, he reaches the transcendence of time, which is polished with various shackles, both clear, complex and contradictory, and full of mystery and mystery, he thinks, lives the time, the moment, lives inside, and after making it his own, the essence of this image moves away from its nodal point and goes. begins to be perceived in clear shades.

In his literary and artistic article entitled "Thoughts on Time and Happiness", the writer's comments about the work "Javids" written by Rafael Huseynov at the time do not doubt our conclusion, but arouse deep confidence: "But in addition to the four main real and artistic images, the writing "Javids" contains one great image. - The image of time. Turning Time into Luck. Man's relationship with time. Man's ability to rise above time... Creating the image of time requires bold searches in forms and means of expression" (16, 397).

As it can be seen, Anar fully understood this image - this magnificent image that is invisible to the eye, but does not break its own flow, its rhythm, reigns with its eternal unrepeatability, not only in his works, but also in other works that have been created, the regularity of time, the fact that time surpasses man, sometimes man was able to distinguish its rise from time to time, and was able to create a complete, exhausted image of this concept, which is dark for many. Therefore, it would be correct to apply the careful thoughts of the artist who analyzed Rafael Huseynov's sense of time to himself.

Let's pay attention to Anar's story "Taxi and Time". No matter how much is said about the work, it is still necessary to note the time, the role played by time in the life of the heroes from different perspectives. In the work, it is remembered as a relative memory that time takes human life in its own way, or rather, that human life comes and goes like water.

Life goes on. Times are changing. Time sometimes wears out and sometimes it renews. In the course of this lifetime, the hero loses what life has given him as well as what he gains. He feels the flow of time later, he is sad, he is excited, as if he longs to hold on to time, to return what has gone and to fill the place of what was lost. He can stop the taxi again at the request of his will at any time, but he is not able to stop the time. Because the taxi may be the same time, sometimes it is not the same time.

No matter how much the hero of the work tends to past memories, feels the need to relive them, to get them, time makes him realize the impossibility and inaccessibility of this with its harshness, its unique cycle, even if it is similar. Time wins, surpasses the hero. The hero has not yet acquired the ability to rise above time. Here the image of Time is idolized. The hero's fate melts away in the time they live in. As long as he wants to relive the happy moments he lived, time deprives him of this happiness.

Every person makes a change in his life and spiritual world due to the influence of great joy or endless sadness. This turn can be based on both reason and feeling. At the end of his endless sadness, the author's hero understands the reason for his failure, he realizes that in order to achieve happiness, not only the feeling, but also the power of the mind is greatly needed, and he understands the importance of acquiring and protecting what the life that wants to leave you has given you by acting wisely says: "Yes, everything has changed. I now knew that happiness exists and one must fight for it. I knew that if happiness is similar to the horizon, this similarity is not in its inaccessibility, but in the fact that even when the horizon moves towards happiness, we find

new worlds, we discover new truths and truths. As long as we fight for happiness, for the right, we win over time" (3, s.35-36).

However, as you can see, after the hero wakes up from the shock of life and controls his feelings, finally, it is true to say that even if not in his actions, he wins over time and time in his thoughts. This is characterized by his late understanding of time.

Let's pay attention to the end of the story. No matter how hard this ending is, the hero's bitter confessions about his lost happiness, his wasted life, and the carelessness of time: "The sound of music descending the last step was clearly heard. A wandering melody with a tired melody seemed to be looking for its break, calmness, end, but could not find it.

- I went to the street. The taxi was gone. What is the difference! I could walk or take a separate taxi

i could Maybe I could stumble upon the taxi from earlier. Eh! It is very easy to return a taxi... (3, s.43)".

In the end, the hero was looking for his past, his lost happiness, like a "wandering melody" looking for its place within all this time, but could not find it. He was waiting for the moment when the thoughts would leave him, the past memories would fade completely, the passions would sleep, the feelings would fade, and at the end, death would sweep away all the ornaments of emotions and excitement with its black color... In the end, "Eh! It is very easy to return the taxi," says the hero, who feels with all his horror that the past days and the lost life have left him without regret and that he will never return, he has lost his way in the endless desert, he has wandered around the world with years of pain in his soul - he forgets his direction and direction like old dervishes who are tired of wandering.

As it can be seen in the work, the author advises him to tell his hero about the rule of time, the value and essence of time, as he understands it, and to know the value of what fate has given you in time, at any cost, while happiness is in the bosom of happiness, and not in another world. The following words spoken by Anar from the mouth of his hero are a clear artistic expression of the author's tendency: "I knew now that there is happiness and one should fight for it. As we fight for happiness, for the truth, we win over time..."

Our outstanding academician Yashar Garayev, in his monograph entitled "The road starting from the White Harbor", writes the preface to the first volume of Anar's "Selected works", analyzes the image of time created by the author with all the details and intricacies, and sprinkles the reader's imagination with the light of time: "In the world of this prose, Time and Although I sometimes move in a closed circle, the direction of the idea, the thought, never starts backwards, "in reverse". The single line of historical-moral progress, the flight curve of movement, emerges from the destruction of the circle and never returns to the previous point.

Time is needed for him as a confession, a moment of truth, a moment of wisdom, the most merciless judge, synonymous with Themis. The weight of joy, the volume of sin, the weight of repentance, the sensitivity of memory - all is time. The flow and amount of time is the calendar, sequence, detail of artistic-psychological, philosophical analysis. Time, flowing through the rough course of the striped network woven by curved and straight lines, traces left on the journeys and journeys of the clock, days, pasts and thousands of years, is the main hero in almost all of Anar's works. Address, flight, phone, speed, date of birth, season - these are only superficial details. The soul, nervousness, substratum of these works is understood by the "philosophy of time" (3, s.5-6).

Academician Yashar Garayev turns to various works of the writer and reveals fundamental conclusions, explains the broad manner of his sense of time and the planetary significance. Our distinguished academic who analyzed the story "Taxi and Time" made the following statement at the end of the analysis: "the author's desire to keep time as a taxi, to return the moment, and the impossibility of this infuses the story with a light of sadness that will not fade throughout Anar's entire creativity." (3, s.7).

However, it seems to us that this last conclusion of Yashar Garayev is perhaps a somewhat premature decision about Anar's work. It is a thesis as heavy as the notes of sadness written in Anar's works. In our opinion, it is not only her desire to return the taxi, but the inevitability of time itself, that infuses Anar's works with a sense of infinite sadness. Because the time that once tied him to his natives is already behind. Rasul-Nigar, immortalized in the spiritual memory of the Azerbaijani people, took away its completeness from Anar both as a material and spiritual being. Such a being that even if centuries pass, time is not able to bring them back again. In our opinion, Anar's sad thoughts about time became more clear from here - after a cruel sentence given by time, fate, and life. The time, full of both mystery and clear details, made the artist think deeply from that moment. Because only then the truth of life finds its big, real reflection in art, when it has confirmed itself in the real world with its forms and methods.

Such relative thoughts about time, time, fate, and life were formed and stood in the center of thought directly after the heavy blow inflicted by time on our hero of life, which creates heroes.

If we use the expression we used above, it is true that the heavy blow of fate inflicted on Anar not only instilled a light of infinite sadness in the heart of the one who created the world of "Sizli" - "Sizziz", which will not be erased from his memory throughout his creativity, but even throughout his life. It is the result of this that the time that takes away a person's happiness and never returns, with its harshness and unrepeatable cycle, is revived at the level of one of the main characters in Anar's works.

There is no work of the writer in which the problem of time is not touched upon. "The Last Night of the Last Year", "Conversation of a Woman Working in Asilgan", "Georgian Surname", "Me, You, He and the Phone", "Molla Nasreddin-66", "Dante's Jubilee", "Dade Gorgud", "Magal", Time is reflected in different forms in his works such as "Contact", "Communication", "Sixth floor of a five-storey house" and "Ağ liman". In each work, different roles of time in human life require researchers to analyze and interpret them.

Anar's image of Time comes to life in our imagination with a contrast born from nature itself. This image makes us happy, sad and makes us think.

Among the analyzes given by our distinguished academician A. Huseynov to the works of writers who wrote and created in the 70s and 80s of the 20th century, we also find the analysis and sometimes criticism of Anar's works. Although the critic mostly analyzes and criticizes the work "The Sixth Floor of a Five-Storeyed House", he also tries to justify his opinion by referring to "Georgian Surname". A. Huseynov, who evaluates the actions he does not want to see in Tahmina as a flaw, also says this about Asmar's image: "We see the same picture in the depiction of Sariya and Asmar... Asmar meets her ex-lover secretly from her husband. These are not commendable actions..." (4, s.204-205).

Let's pay attention to the notes of Sabir Bashirov, one of our contemporary researchers, who tries to illuminate Anar's creativity in the necessary aspect. The researcher writes: "It seems to me that Asmar's visit to Ogtay is not a commendable event, but it is the truth of the heart. When we read the story "Georgian Family", we knew that Jamal's well-decorated, luxurious house and "seven pieces of ice cream wrapped in cheap paper" in exchange for this luxury will never bring happiness to Asmara. Indeed, Asmar is an object of that well-decorated house, the world, which cannot find its place and will never find its place. Asmar is Tahmina's successor. There is no doubt that Asmar will leave Jamal-Manaf and be upset with him once and for all. Nothing, nothing will make him change his mind." (5, s.65).

"Undoubtedly, literature is a mentality, it is the embodiment of the soul that has passed through the tumult of time and the test of fate and survived the words ("soul" - Fuzuli). Only the unconscious and memoryless, "sclerosed" consciousness puts the national history and destiny in front of the next stress and the next total crisis of the artistic memory, and only then the tragedy

of Mankurd is written in the fate and destiny of art as well. Literature bypasses the eternal theme - time and death" (6, s.19).

Acad. Y. Garayev, in his article "Concept of the history of literature", highly appreciates literature and art as an important moment in the spiritual history of the people, unconditionally reflecting its destiny, dreams and aspirations, and an important factor leading to the development of the society. At the same time, it brings to the attention of the literary community how important the problem of Man and Time, which we have involved in the research as a problem.

Academician Yashar Garayev's critical article entitled "Memorylessness and Timelessness - "The Market Age" expresses concern about the future fate of our literature, which is a mirror of our nation's spirituality, in every line of the critic. Yashar Garayev, reviewing the literature of the period of the country's transition to the market economy, writes: "The people whose historical destiny and national existence are being tested always reveal everything they have, "bring it to the market", except for two things: a land, and a national memory (new culture). !). It's a pity that our last losses were precisely the losses of land and culture. The second of these losses is even more severe than the first: those who lost their land will become refugees and wanderers in fifty years, and those who lost their memory will become barbarians and mankurd in fifty years... Returning from a mankurd to an intellectual is much more difficult than returning from a refugee to a citizen..." (20, s.692). What is the point here? What are the thoughts that disturb the critic? Of course, the period when the state censorship over our literature ended coincided with a time when socio-political events in Azerbaijan became more acute, and at the same time, it was a period of transition of our society to a market economy. As a people whose freedom and material wealth were taken away for many years and whose spirituality was crucified, our spiritual wealth was in danger because we did not have the material wealth to bring it to the "market environment". Our people faced the harsh test of history and suffered heavy losses. Both the loss of eternal ancestral lands and the penetration of foreign thoughts and thinking into our spirituality for many years have led our people to fall away from the national and moral values, and as a result, the people have led to civil strife. Azerbaijan was condemned to disintegration from within. Fortunately, the bringing of Heydar Aliyev, the savior of the people, the National Leader of the Azerbaijani people, put an end to this conflict and saved our national and moral values from suicide shackles.

Man and time again became the subject of literary thought. Dozens of novels, narratives reflecting the behind-the-scenes tragedies of our people during the years of occupation were written. The chronicle of our changing fate was written by the judgment of time and fate.

Today, the horizons of our literature are clearer and brighter. We believe that the literature of the victorious people, who put an end to thirty years of slavery, will write heart-filled works from the history of our Victory, the wisdom of our glorious sons, and will continue to be at the forefront of the struggle for the education and moral purity of the young generation.

In the absence of a free literary atmosphere, freedom of speech and thought, it is impossible for artistic thought to expand. We felt the bitter consequences of this during the Soviet rule in the last century. The period of independence, which ended the special control over the artistic-aesthetic thought, is first of all marked by the fact that it is free from ideological pressure and shackles, and there are no obstacles to its engagement in artistic-aesthetic analysis. It is of particular importance to show the characteristics of literary criticism in the period when we gained independence, to give an understanding of the merits and demerits of the historical stage it passed, and to find out what new evaluation principle it approaches to literary texts.

At present, it is necessary to study the difficulties of modern literary criticism, what changes it has undergone, and what new tendencies of theoretical-aesthetic thought have emerged.

If we approach the issue a little more carefully, we will see that literary historians are also the first literary critics. It means that a literary historian should first of all have the professionalism of a critic so that he can correctly analyze the subject of life and correctly define the idea he puts forward and include it in the literary circulation. A critic who evaluates the modern literary process must have a clear idea of all periods of literature in order to be able to correctly determine the essence of the literary text created today. Otherwise, the critic is no different from the ordinary reader.

Our literary criticism should not be limited only to writings about the contemporary literary process. There are more important issues that his concepts should be developed. Critics themselves should be extremely careful about this issue. For example, the article "Overture on the Forgotten" written and published by Nizamuddin Shamsizadeh in 1987 actually has the effect of a conceptual work. Works such as Anar's "Thoughts on Azerbaijanism", Nizami Jafarov's "Introduction to Azerbaijan Studies", Nizamuddin Shamsizade's "Azerbaijanism", Sona Valiyeva's "Rise of the National Statehood Movement and the Idea of Azerbaijanism during the People's Republic" should not be left out of the thinking area of Azerbaijan literary criticism.

Unfortunately, in the matter of criticism, we made a direct transition from Akhundov to literary criticism of the Soviet era. However, even before the Soviet era, new aspects of literary criticism appeared in Azerbaijan.

From the not-so-distant past of literary criticism to the present day, the landscape changes, the revolutions we are talking about, revolutions related to both social conditions and purely artistic issues, become somewhat more complicated. As we mentioned above, the literary community immediately reacts to the written works of art. Because there are many newspapers and magazines and literary oriented portals. Moreover, these works themselves, the events in the literary world and social life demand it.

Literary criticism cannot fully explain the aesthetic essence of artistic works in recent times. This is due to the fact that there are many genres of criticism, and it is good to write articles in these genres. However, unless the work of art is studied as an aesthetic phenomenon, these efforts will produce an immediate effect, spread a little noise and have no results.

But where is the competence to intervene flexibly in the works written today? Life changes every moment, the dynamics of the reader, author, thought, and also philological thought change. However, our criticism and literary studies are stuck in the interest of going back to the past and reviving the archives of the past.

Some critics, after becoming famous as critics, turn to fiction, and instead of writing fiction, according to observations, they create an atmosphere around fiction, because those "writers" already have a weapon of criticism in their hands, and are so self-promoting that it's a ridiculous situation. arises. It becomes a source of danger not for itself, but for our literature. The fact that a critic or a literary critic engages in artistic creativity after gaining a special position is the aspect that makes his personality as a critic or a literary critic defective.

One of the notable defects of criticism is its gradual loss of connection with serious literary studies. In the world, and partly in us, the space of criticism is expanding, but the base is poor, most of the critical writings are without ideas and concepts, and they add to the analyzed work and give an extra load effect.

We believe that in order for literary criticism to survive, it must fulfill its eternal duty. The critic's environment, the institution dealing with criticism should know its statistics so precisely that, for example, to what extent can ideology influence, to what extent does the gender problem influence? To what extent can intervention affect Azerbaijan? How many works have been written against Azerbaijan abroad? The literary critic of today should know this and serve to prevent the harmful seeds of misconception from being sown in thought.

A critic should feel the world literary process, and should be able to solve the obvious-hidden connections between this process and the work he is analyzing and writing about. It is in this case that one can hope that perfect works of art will be created in the future.

There is a fact that no interesting case of literature has escaped the eyes of criticism, and probably, good works will not remain outside the subject of analysis of critical thought.

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Geological and Mineralogical Sciences

ON PROSPECTS OF HYDROCARBONS ACCUMULATIONS DETECTING IN TRADITIONAL RESERVOIRS IN DEEP HORIZONS OF CROSS-SECTION WITHIN SHALE BASINS

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Annotation The results of a reconnaissance survey using direct-prospecting technology of satellite images and photographs frequency-resonance processing within some areas of shale gas production in the USA, Argentina, England and shale oil play in the Williston Basin in the north of the United States are presented. The investigations were conducted with the aim of developing and improving the methodology of mobile direct-prospecting methods applying at various stages of prospecting and exploration for ore and combustible minerals, as well as water. The deep channels for fluids, chemical elements and minerals migration, filled with 1-6 groups of sedimentary rocks, were found in all surveyed shale gas production sites. The received measurement data of the work carried out can be considered as additional evidence in favor of the concept of deep (abiogenic) synthesis of hydrocarbons, including those in shale formations. Within the survey site in England a significant number of local zones of visible hydrogen degassing are located. It is advisable to conduct additional research on these sites in order to study these local zones in more detail. Experimental studies within area of shale oil in the Williston Basin also confirmed the presence of hydrocarbon deposits in the deep horizons of cross-section. To the east of Williston Basin, a large cluster of basalt volcanic structures with hydrogen and living (healing) water, as well as the process of hydrogen and phosphorus migration into the atmosphere were revealed by instrumental measurements. In general, the materials of the experimental work carried out can be considered as additional evidence in favor of the volcanic model of formation of structural elements and the external appearance of the Earth's surface, as well as deposits of ore and combustible minerals and water. The research results indicate the feasibility of using mobile technology of frequency-resonance processing and decoding of satellite images and photographs for the detection and localization of oil and gas accumulation zones within large blocks and local areas. The use of super-operational and low-cost direct-prospecting technology will significantly speed up the exploration process for oil, gas, natural hydrogen and ore minerals, as well as reduce the financial costs of its implementation.

Keywords: USA, Argentina, England, shale basin, oil, gas, living water, basalts, hydrogen, phosphorus, bacteria, direct searches, deep structure, volcano, abiogenic genesis, sounding of the cross-section, remote sensing data processing.

Introduction

From the standpoint of the deep (abiogenic) origin of hydrocarbons within the framework of the concept of deep degassing of the Earth [1–2], it can be assumed that in shale basins, oil, condensate, and gas deposits also exist in deep (and deep) horizons of the cross-section. In this regard, in some areas of shale gas production in the USA, Argentina and England in 2019, reconnaissance studies were carried out using mobile direct-prospecting methods. In 2021 the investigation was conducted also within a large deposit (play) of heavy oil in the Williston Basin in the north of the United States. The results of the experimental work performed are presented in this report.

Research methods

Experimental investigations of a reconnaissance and detailed nature are carried out using low-cost and direct-prospecting technology, including modified methods of frequency-resonance processing and decoding of satellite images and photo images, vertical electric resonance sounding (scanning) of the cross-section and a method of integral assessment of the prospects of oil and gas potential (ore content) of large prospecting blocks and local areas [4]. Standing electric waves, discovered by Nikola Tesla in 1899, are at the heart of certain methods of mobile technology. The processing of satellite images and photo images is carried out using resonant frequencies of various rocks (sedimentary, metamorphic, magmatic - <http://rockref.vsegei.ru/petro/>), oil, condensate, gas, ore minerals and chemical elements as samples. The features and capabilities of the methods used, as well as the measurement technique, are described in more detail in published articles and reports at conferences [4-6].

In local areas in shale gas production basins, work was carried out in order to detect possible accumulations of hydrocarbons (oil, gas, condensate, amber) in traditional reservoirs in the lower (including deep) horizons of cross-section.

Eagle Ford basin (USA)

Satellite images from this basin (Fig. 1) were borrowed from the site [7]. Comparison of Fig. 1b and 1c makes it possible to form an idea of how many wells were drilled in certain parts of the basin over 15 years.

When processing a fragment of an image of a basin with wells (Fig. 1c), responses from oil, condensate, gas, and amber, as well as 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 groups of sedimentary rocks, were recorded; there were no signals from igneous rocks. By fixing the responses from 2 groups of sedimentary rocks at different depths, the root of the sedimentary rock channel was established at a depth of 470 km.

Fig. 1. Satellite images of the Eagle Ford shale basin and its separate section (rectangular contour) [7]. a - February 15, 2016; b – December 17, 2000; c – December 18, 2015.

At the surface of 56.9 km, responses were obtained from oil, condensate, gas, and amber, and at a depth of 57 km, from oxygen, hydrogen, carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus. On the surface of 57 km, only responses from phosphorus were obtained from the upper part of cross-section.

By scanning from the surface (step 1 m) responses of oil were received from the intervals: 1) 380-650 m; from 1 km step 5 m, 2) 2270-3550 m; 3) 5200-7600 m; 4) 11250-14700 m (up to 15 km).

Gas intervals were also determined by scanning: 1) 380-650 m; from 1 km step 5 m, 2) 2270-3550 m; 3) 5200-7600 m; 4) 11250-14700 m (up to 15 km traced). Condensate responses were obtained from the interval 585-765 m.

Signals from the 1st group of sedimentary rocks were recorded by scanning in the interval of 410-630 m. No responses from the 1st group of sedimentary rocks were received in the interval of 2270-3550 m; signals from group 2 were recorded in the interval of 2270-3580 m. Additionally, a fragment of the dark image in Fig. 1a was processed. Responses from the 1st group of sedimentary rocks were obtained from the interval of 350-650 m (approximately). When scanning the cross-section with a step of 10 cm, gas signals were recorded from the interval) 370-634 m.

A very intensive signal was obtained from gas and the 1st group of sedimentary rocks; responses from these components were recorded from the interval of 345-650 m (approximately). This allowed us to make a preliminary conclusion that shale gas is a gas in the 1st group of sedimentary rocks.

Somewhat later, additional experiments were carried out to determine which samples from the first group of sedimentary rocks contain gas. Responses were received only from one sample from the 1st group of sedimentary rocks - mudstone breccia. Signals from this sample were fixed by scanning from the interval of 380-625 m; from 2000 m there were no signals from the breccia.

It is advisable to pay attention to the following circumstance. Figure 2 shows individual areas (counties) in different US states with the largest volumes of hydrocarbon production (including shale plays) [8]. When processing satellite images of all seven of these areas, responses from breccia and shale gas were recorded.

Vaca Muerta basin (Argentina)

A photograph of the shale gas production site in the Vaca Muerta basin is shown in Fig. 3 [9]. During its processing, responses were obtained from gas, condensate, oil, amber, coal, breccia (argillic), as well as 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 12 (weak) groups of sedimentary rocks. No signals were received from igneous rocks.

By fixing the responses from the 2nd group of sedimentary rocks at different depths, the root of the sedimentary rock channel was established at a depth of 470 km. Responses from oil were obtained at the surface of 56.9 km; they were absent at a depth of 57 km.

Signals from argillite breccia were recorded by fixing responses at various depths and scanning in the range of 345-730 m

Fig. 2. A schematic map of the location of individual regions in various US states, in which the largest volumes of hydrocarbons were produced in shale plays [8].

Fig. 3. Photograph of the shale gas production site in the Vaca Muerta basin (Argentina) [9].

By scanning (step 1 m) responses from oil were recorded in the intervals: 1) 1120-3820 m; 2) 7300-10250 m (tracked up to 15 km).

At the surface of 800 m, signals from shale gas (gas + breccia) were not received, but from gas they were recorded. Gas responses were obtained in the range of 960-1130 m; deeper signals were absent. At the surface of 1130 m, responses (weak) from condensate were obtained from the upper part of the cross-section, but there were no signals from the lower part.

Areas of large volumes of gas production in the United States

Satellite images of seven regions (counties) (Fig. 2) of gas production in the United States [8] are presented in Fig. 4. Frequency-resonance processing of all these images was performed in order to assess the prospects for oil and gas potential of the deep horizons of cross-section.

Fig. 4. Satellite images of individual regions (counties) in various US states, where the largest volumes of hydrocarbons were produced (Fig. 2) in shale plays [8].

When processing satellite images of survey blocks in Fig. 4 signals of oil, condensate, gas, amber, oil shale, coal were recorded from the surface on all blocks; signals from rocks with gas hydrates, gas hydrates, ice, hydrogen, and salt were absent on all blocks. Weak signals from anthracites were recorded on the Midland and Eddy blocks.

Signals from 1-6 groups of sedimentary rocks were recorded on all blocks, and from the first group of igneous rocks (granites) - only on the Lea block. The roots of sedimentary rock channels in all blocks, except for the Lea block, are located at a depth of 200 km. On the Lea block, the root of the sedimentary channel is located at a depth of 470 km, and the granite channel is located at a depth of 996 km.

At the surface of 56 km, responses from oil and amber were recorded on all blocks, and at a depth of 57.1 km, the signals were already absent.

The results of fixing (determining) the intervals of responses from oil by scanning the cross-section from the surface with a step of 1 m to 5 km and a step of 5 m to 15 km are as follows (the values of the intervals below are given in meters).

Beachy Point block: 1) 680-940 m; 2) 1330-1860; 3) 2145-2240; 4) 2500-3170; 5) 3415-3650; 6) 4140-4420; 7) 5730-6400; 8) 8670-(strong)-10750; 9) 13530-15130 m.

Block Weld: 1) 800-980; 2) 1330-1550; 3) 2400-2700; 4) 4800-5430; 5) 10650-(intensive)-(very strong)-14400.

Block Kern: 1) 490-1160; 2) 1470-1735; 3) 1890-2330; 4) 2690-2780; 5) 5240-6780; 6) 7760-8680; 7) 14730-16800 m.

Block Lea: 1) 550-770; 2) 1270-2650; 3) 3330-3500; 4) 5050-9200; 5) 13000-15100 m.

Block McKenzie: 1) 430-1300; 2) 1700-2100; 3) 3880-4220; 4) 9150-11500; 5) 13750-14300 m.

Midland block: 1) 470-520; 2) 1430-1770; 3) 2330-2620; 4) 3200-(intensive)-3760; 5) 4020-4375; 6) 8750-9400 m.

Block Eddy: 1) 930-(intensive)-(very intensive)-1500; 2) 2180-(intensive)-2510; 3) 3060-3180; 4) 3660-3780; 5) 4370-4470; 6) 6430-8950; 7) 12520-13850 m.

Shale gas production site in England

In early October 2019, information appeared on Internet sites that Cuadrilla Resources [10] had stopped hydraulic fracturing (fracking) in a well on Preston New Road (Lancashire, England) [11]. The main reason for this situation is an earthquake after a series of hydraulic fracturing in August 2019.

In this regard, it was advisable to process the photograph and satellite image of the well location area. The photograph for processing (Fig. 5) was borrowed from the information message [11], and the satellite image (Fig. 6) from the Cuadrilla Resources website [10].

The analysis of the satellite image of the site (Fig. 6) shows that local areas (shaded zones) of visible hydrogen degassing are fixed within its boundaries.

At the initial stage, only the determination of the presence (absence) of oil, condensate, gas and amber in the cross-section of the survey site was carried out.

When processing a photograph of the location of the well (Fig. 5), responses from oil, condensate, gas, shale gas, amber, as well as 1-6 groups of sedimentary rocks were recorded. The root of the channel (volcano) of sedimentary rocks is established at a depth of 470 km.

Signals from oil, condensate, gas and amber were recorded up to 57 km. In the process of processing a satellite image of the well location (Fig. 6), responses from oil, condensate, gas, shale gas, amber, coal, anthracite, and hydrogen were recorded. Signals were also received from 1-6 groups of sedimentary rocks. The root of the channel (volcano) of sedimentary rocks was determined at a depth of 470 km.

Responses from basalts were also registered, they were recorded up to 95 km.

Fig. 5. Photograph of a well at Preston New Road (Lancashire, England) [11].

Fig. 6. Satellite image of a well in the Preston New Road (Lancashire) area [10].

We draw attention to the following circumstance. When processing a satellite image of the site, responses from hydrogen and basalts (6th group of igneous rocks) were recorded. This indicates that the dark areas in the image (Fig. 6) are in fact local zones of hydrogen degassing.

Considering this, the images of eight such local zones, indicated in Fig. 6 by rectangular contours were processed separately. As a result, responses from hydrogen and basalts were recorded within each of these zones. Signals from basalts were recorded up to 95 km.

Reconnaissance research in the Williston Basin

Area of shale play. A structural map of the upper part of a large shale play in the Williston Basin (USA) is shown in Fig. 7 [3], and satellite images of the study area are shown in Fig. 8. Markers with coordinates 1) 48°59'60.00"N, 103°59'60.00"W, 2) 48°59'60.00"N, 102°0'0.00"W, 3) 46°30'0.00"N, 102°0'0.00"W, 4) 46°30'0.00"N, 103°59'60.00"W in the area of the central (main) part of the shale play is indicated on the images. At the first stage of the work, a fragment of the image in Fig. 8a, marked with markers, was processed.

During frequency-resonance processing of a fragment of a satellite image in Fig. 8a, responses are recorded from the surface at the frequencies of oil, condensate, gas, amber, carbon dioxide, bacteria (methane-oxidizing bacteria, the populations of which are analyzed in the method of microbiological exploration for oil and gas of company MicroPro GmbH), phosphorus (yellow), oil shale, gas hydrates, anthracite, ice, dead water and sedimentary rocks of 1-6th groups. Responses from hydrogen, salt, and igneous rocks were not received.

By fixing the responses at different depths (50, 99, 218, 480, 460 km), the root of volcano of 1-6th groups of sedimentary rocks was recorded at a depth of 470 km.

Fig. 7. Structural map of the upper part of the Three Forks shale play. The contour interval is 500 feet. Areas of heavy oil production from the play are indicated by red dots [3].

On the HC synthesis surface of 57 km, responses were recorded at the frequencies of oil, condensate, gas, amber, phosphorus (yellow) and living water. Responses from dead water and carbon dioxide were obtained at a depth of 59 km.

On the day surface (0 m), responses from carbon dioxide, gas (methane) and phosphorus (yellow) were obtained from the upper part of the cross-section, which indicates their migration into the atmosphere.

By scanning the cross-section from the surface, step 1 m, responses at oil frequencies were obtained from the following intervals: 1) 1240-1650 m, 2) 2740-3710 m, 3) 4320-4700 m, 4) 6970-(7400-intensive)-7620 m, 5) 8140-(8700-intensive)-8880 m (up to 10 km traced).

At the surface of 10 km, responses from oil, condensate, and gas were also recorded, which indicates their presence in the deep horizons of the cross-section.

Region of hydrogen degassing. When analyzing satellite images of the territory of play location, the attention of authors was attracted by local sites and large areas with relief features (earth's surface) characteristic for zones of visible hydrogen degassing. The survey of hydrogen

degassing zones and sections began with a large zone, indicated in Fig. 8b by a colored (oval) outline in upper right corner.

During frequency-resonance processing of a fragment of a satellite image in this polygonal contour (Fig. 8b), responses from phosphorus (red), hydrogen, hydrogen bacteria (Fig. 9), living water (intensive), dead water (of low intensity) were recorded from the surface.

Fig. 8. Satellite images of the area around the shale layer in the Williston Basin in the north of United States.

Fig. 9. Photos of bacteria that absorb ("devour") hydrogen.

At the surface, signals were also recorded from sedimentary rocks of 1-6th groups, as well as igneous rocks of the 6th (gabbro and basalts) and 6A (dolerites and andesites) groups.

By fixing the responses at different depths (50, 99, 218, 480, 470 km), the root of basalt volcano was determined at a depth of 470 km. And by scanning cross-section from surface, a step of 1 m, the upper edge of basalts was fixed at a depth of 320 m. On the surface of 320 m, signals of sedimentary rocks of 1-6th groups and hydrogen (of low intensity) were received from upper part of cross-section.

On the day surface (0 m), responses of hydrogen and phosphorus were obtained from upper part of cross-section, which indicates of their migration into atmosphere.

When scanning the cross-section from 320 m, with a step of 1 m, signals at hydrogen frequencies began to be recorded from basalts from 425 m, and living water – from 490 m.

When processing a fragment of the image in Fig. 8b, indicated by a rectangular contour in the lake, signals at the surface were recorded from living water, dead water (of low intensity) and igneous rocks of the 6th and 6A groups.

The root of the basaltic volcano was identified at a depth of 470 km, and the upper edge of the basalts was fixed by scanning at a depth of 190 m.

On the day surface (0 m), responses from hydrogen were obtained from the upper part of the cross-section, which indicates its migration into atmosphere.

When scanning the cross-section from the surface, with a step of 1 cm, responses at the frequencies of living water began to be recorded from 1 m.

When scanning cross-section from 180 m, step 10 cm, responses at hydrogen frequencies began to be fixed from basalts at 204 m, and of living water – at 216 m.

Additional research. When carrying out additional instrumental measurements, photographs of the core from a well within the shale play (Fig. 10) [3], as well as methanotrophic

bacteria (a group of methylotrophs, 7 individuals from different orders) (Fig. 11) were used. At this stage, frequency-resonance processing of individual fragments of the satellite image in Fig. 8b, indicated by polygonal and rectangular contours, was performed.

During frequency-resonance processing of a fragment of a satellite image in Fig. 8b without a fragment in the polygonal contour in the upper right corner, responses were recorded from the surface at the frequencies of oil, condensate, gas, amber, carbon dioxide, methane-oxidizing bacteria, phosphorus (black and yellow), oil shale, gas hydrates, anthracite, lonsdaleite, potassium-magnesium salt, sedimentary rocks of 1-6th and 7th (limestone) groups and igneous rocks of 7, 8, 9, 10 and 14th groups.

When scanning the cross-section from the surface up to 5000 m, step 1 m, signals at the frequencies of all core samples (Fig. 10) were recorded from the following intervals: 550-675 m, 930-(1300-intensive)-1410 m, 1880-2210 m, 4460-4900 m. On the surface of 5000 m from the lower part of the cross-section, the responses at the frequencies of the first core sample (sandstone) were recorded, but not received from the other three. Responses from sandstone were recorded in the interval of 920-1500 m when scanning the cross-section with a step of 1 m.

Fig. 10. Photographs of the core from the borehole within the shale layer, (a) - sandstone) [3].

Fig. 11. Photos of methanotrophic bacteria.

Rectangle 1. When processing a fragment of the image in rectangle 1 (Fig. 8b), responses were recorded only from the 9th (marl) group of sedimentary rocks.

Rectangle 2. Within the second fragment of the image, responses from the 7th (limestone) group of sedimentary rocks, oil, condensate, gas, methane-oxidizing bacteria, phosphorus (yellow) and dead water were recorded.

Signals from oil, condensate, gas, phosphorus, and living water were recorded on the HC synthesis surface of 57 km. Responses from dead water were obtained at a depth of 59 km, while there were no signals from carbon dioxide at this depth.

At the 0 m surface, responses from gas and phosphorus were obtained from the upper part of the cross-section, which indicates their migration into atmosphere.

Rectangle 3. When processing the image fragment in rectangle 3 (Fig. 8b), responses were recorded only from the 8th (dolomite) group of sedimentary rocks and dead water.

Rectangle 4. At the location of the image fragment in rectangle 4 (Fig. 8b), only responses from the 9th (marl) group of sedimentary rocks were recorded.

Rectangle 5. Within the area, responses from phosphorus (white) and salt are recorded. On the surface of 57 km, responses from oil of low intensity were received. Signals of weak intensity were also recorded from oil, condensate and gas from the surface of 0 m.

No gas responses were received at the 0 m surface from the upper part of the cross-section, which indicates the absence of its migration into the atmosphere.

Experiments with methane-oxidizing bacteria. Within the shale play (Fig. 8a), responses from 7 bacteria (Fig. 11) were recorded from the surface of 0 m. At a depth of 540 cm, signals from these bacteria were already absent, and at the surface of 520 cm they were recorded.

In rectangle 2, signals from 7 bacteria were also recorded from the surface. When scanning the cross-section from 500 cm, step 1 mm, responses from these bacteria were recorded up to 528 cm.

Signals from 7 bacteria within the fragment of the image in rectangle 5 from the surface were not recorded. Within this fragment of the image, the migration of gas into the atmosphere (and, consequently, to the day surface) was not established by instrumental measurements.

At the site in the lake (rectangle), no signals from 7 bacteria (Fig. 11) were recorded from the surface. Within this fragment of image, the migration of gas (methane) into the atmosphere (and, consequently, to the day surface) was not established by instrumental measurements.

Experiments with hydrogen bacteria. Figure 9 shows photographs of 4 hydrogen bacteria. Within the polygonal contour (Fig. 8b, upper right corner), the signals from the first 3 bacteria in Fig. 9, as well as the 4th one (separately) were recorded from the surface, but at a depth of 540 cm there were no responses from them. When scanning the cross-section from 500 cm, step 1 mm, responses from 3 bacteria were recorded up to 524 cm, and from one (4th) – up to 530 cm.

On a local fragment in the lake (rectangle), the responses from the 1-3rd and 4th bacteria were recorded at a depth of 500 cm. When scanning the cross-section from 500 cm, with a step of 1 mm, the responses from the 1-3rd and 4th bacteria were recorded to a depth of 525 cm.

In the area of the shale play, responses from the 1-3rd and 4th hydrogen bacteria were not recorded from the surface (0 m), and also at a depth of 500 cm (there is no migration of hydrogen into the atmosphere within the play).

Discussion of results and main conclusions

The article presents the materials (results of instrumental measurements), obtained during experimental studies for the purpose of additional testing, as well as improving the methodological technique of mobile direct-prospecting methods using during solving various geological problems. Brief comments on the submitted materials can be formulated as follows.

The experimental studies carried out in the areas of shale gas production are of reconnaissance character. A limited (incomplete) number of “search” operations was performed at all survey sites.

Deep migration channels for fluids, chemical elements and minerals, filled with 1-6 groups of sedimentary rocks, were found in all surveyed shale gas production sites.

The results of instrumental measurement within shale basin allowed us to make a preliminary conclusion that shale gas is a gas in the 1st group of sedimentary rocks (psephites). Additional experiments with aim to determine which samples from the first group of sedimentary

rocks contain gas showed that responses at gas frequencies were received only from one sample of the 1st group of sedimentary rocks - mudstone breccia.

Of particular interest is the survey site in England, within which a significant number of local zones of visible hydrogen degassing are located. It is advisable to conduct additional research on its territory in order to study these local zones in more detail.

Experimental studies carried out within the shale oil play area in the Williston Basin in the northern of United States once again confirmed the presence of hydrocarbon deposits in the deep horizons of the cross-section. Responses from oil, condensate, gas, and amber were obtained within the play at the boundary of hydrocarbon synthesis at 57 km. When scanning the cross-section from the surface up to 10 km, signals at oil frequencies were obtained from 5 intervals of deposits search. At the surface of 10 km, responses from oil, condensate, and gas were also recorded, which indicates their presence in the deep horizons of the cross-section.

In the north of the United States, east of the Williston basin, by instrumental measurements the existence of a huge (by area) cluster of basalt volcanic structures with hydrogen and living (healing) water were confirmed, and the process of hydrogen and phosphorus (red) migration into the atmosphere within the basalts was recorded.

A large number of experiments with methane-oxidizing and hydrogen bacteria were also carried out within the surveyed area in the north of United States. The measurement results showed that methane-oxidizing bacteria create their colonies only in the areas of gas (methane) migration into the atmosphere, while hydrogen bacteria – only in areas of hydrogen migration. The thickness of the layer (interval) of the cross-section with bacteria does not exceed 550 cm. This allows us to conclude that bacteria do not produce methane and hydrogen, but use these gases to maintain the viability of their populations. The facts of recording responses from bacteria during instrumental measurements are additional criteria for the presence of methane and hydrogen accumulations within the survey areas.

A fundamentally important result of the performed experimental work are additional facts (evidence), obtained during the processing of satellite images, in favor of the deep (abiogenic) genesis of oil, condensate and gas in the process of hydrogen degassing of the Earth [1, 2]. At the moment, most specialists are guided in their practice by the principles and provisions of the biogenic theory of the hydrocarbon's genesis. From this point of view, the estimates of the volumes of methane that migrate into the planet's atmosphere can be significantly underestimated. Numerous facts of fixing signals (responses) from oil, condensate and gas at the boundary of their synthesis 57 km in various regions of the world (including within the surveyed areas) allow us to make an assumption about the migration of abiogenic methane into the Earth's atmosphere in colossal volumes!

We also focus attention on the fact that the results of experimental works, presented in this article, as well as in other publications of the authors, performed using the developed measuring equipment, are weighty arguments in favor of the "volcanic" model of the formation of various structural elements and the external appearance of Earth, planets and satellites of the solar system, as well as deposits of combustible and ore minerals (including hydrogen and water).

The results of the experimental reconnaissance studies, presented above, once again clearly demonstrate the operability, information content and efficiency of direct-prospecting methods for frequency-resonance processing of satellite images and photographs during the integral assessment of the prospects of detecting accumulations of oil, gas and natural hydrogen within survey areas, as well as when determining the depths of occurrence and thicknesses of predicted deposits in the cross-section. The materials of the article testify to the expediency of using the mobile technology of frequency-resonance processing and decoding of satellite images and photographs for the detection and localization of oil and gas accumulation zones within large blocks and local areas. The technology can be used also for the search and exploration of the

"shale" hydrocarbons industrial accumulations. The use of super-efficient and low-cost direct-prospecting technology will significantly speed up the exploration process for oil, gas, natural hydrogen and ore minerals, as well as reduce financial costs for its implementation.

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Political Studies

Миф саяси шындықты құру технологиясы ретінде

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Аңдатпа

Баяндама саяси мифология мәселесін саяси жүйенің даму контекстінде зерттеуге арналған.

Баяндамада архаикалық мифтер қоғамның саяси дәстүрлерінде бекітіліп, кейіннен саяси мәдениеттің мазмұнына енеді деп қарастырылады. Дағдарыс жағдайында, өмірдің саяси саласындағы ұтымды негіздер мен мотивация жойылған кезде, қоғамдағы саяси мифтердің рөлі едәуір артады. Өйткені, осы тарихи кезеңдерде саналы реттеу тетіктері ұжымдық бейсаналық реттеудің тетіктеріне жол береді.

Қорытындысында, саяси мифтік дизайнның құрылымы мен жасалу жолдары сипатталады. Саяси мифті құру кезінде ескерілуі тиіс кейбір аспектілер де талданып, мифтің өзін құрастыру үрдісі, оның ішінде, мифодизайнды құрудың және бұқаралық санаға енгізудің белгілі бір тетіктері қарастырылды.

Түйінді сөздер: мифодизайн, саяси мәдениет, саяси миф, саяси дәстүрлер.

Кез келген тарихи дәуірде билеуші топтар өздерінің бұқарамен қарым-қатынаста, үгіт-насихатта белгілі бір дәрежеде мифологияға жүгінеді. Мифодизайн технологиясы саяси шындық фактілерін түсіндіру және дүниеге қажетті көзқарастарды қалыптастыру үшін пайдаланады.

Саяси күреске қатысушы топтар мен олардың жетекшілері өздері шешетін міндеттерге сәйкес әртүрлі мифологиялық бейнелерге жүгінеді. Осыған байланысты саяси шындықты мифодизайн арқылы құру мәселесі ерекше өзекті және мәнді болып табылады.

Мифодизайн саяси мәдениеттің генетикалық элементі ретінде халықтың ұжымдық жады сақталатын, қоғамдық-саяси тәжірибені қамтитын тарихи қалыптасқан бейнелер жүйесі болып табылады.

«Ұлттық мифология – деп жазады В.С. Полосин - бұл халықтың санадан тыс санасы, үлкен отбасының «уақыт құдығы», ... оның шынайы тәжірибесі туралы аллегория, оның архетиптері символдық бейнелермен көрсетілген». Өйткені, архетиптің өзі, К.Юнг түсіндіргендей, тек қана қауымдастықтың тарихи даму барысында нақты бейнелерден ада және нақты мазмұнға толы орталық бастапқы идеяның бір түрі ғана.

Архетиптер – өзінің формальданған күйінде әрбір нақты халықтың архаикалық мифтерінің негізін құрайтын нақты сюжеттер түрінде көрінетін мифологиялық мотивтер. Оның үстіне ұжымдық бейсаналық өзін әр халыққа ғана тән мифтік сюжеттер арқылы дәл ашады.

Мифтерде, М.Элиаданың айтуы бойынша, халықтың киелі тарихы баяндалады, «мифте «барлық бастаулардың басы» деген есте қаларлық кезеңде болған оқиға туралы айтылады. Сонымен қатар, архаикалық мифтер қоғам дамуымен бірге жойылмайды, тек ұжымдық бейсаналық деңгейде ғана көріне отырып, халықтың бүкіл тарихында сақталады.

Белгілі бір «ата-бабалар құлытын» қамтитын және қазіргі заманның саяси мифтерінің прототипіне айналған архаикалық мифтер қоғамның саяси дәстүрінде бекітіліп, сол арқылы саяси мәдениеттің мазмұнына енеді. Мифтер қоғамның немесе халықтың өзін-өзі ұйымдастыру саласына жобаланған архетиптік құрылыс қана емес, олар шын мәнінде «мәдениеттің аса күрделі шындығының» бірі болып табылады.

Мифтік бейнелердің табиғатының өзі, архетиптік шарттылық, дәстүрлер мен қазіргі заман арасындағы байланыстар оларды саяси және мәдени генотипті көрсетудің ерекше формасы ретінде сипаттайды. Өмірдің саяси саласындағы ұтымды негіздер мен мотивация жойылған дағдарыс жағдайында саяси мифтердің қоғамдағы рөлі айтарлықтай арта түсетіні де маңызды.

Осы тарихи кезеңдерде саяси психология саласындағы зерттеушілер атап өткендей, саналы реттеу элементтері ұжымдық бейсаналықтан реттеу механизмдеріне орын береді. Мұндай сәттерде, әдетте, саяси және мәдени генетика мәселесі өзекті бола бастайды және ерекше өткір ретінде қабылданады.

«Егер ұтымды қабаттар жойылса», - деп атап көрсетеді А.Н.Калиев, онда миф арқылы сананың ұтымды қабаты қайтадан толтырылады. Өйткені, кейде мифке деген қажеттілік азаптай дерлік сезіледі де, мифті меңгеру дүниенің суретін қалпына келтіреді».

Қазіргі ақпараттық қоғамда қажеттіліктер туралы мифтер үлкен мәнге ие болды. Ақпараттық технологияның дамуы мифтің бұқаралық санаға тез және тұрақты енуін қамтамасыз етеді. Сонымен қатар миф арқылы қажеттіліктерді қанағаттандыру мифті жасаушы бағдарламалаған сананың өткінші әсері ғана. Айта кету керек, мифтің бұқаралық санаға енуі қарым-қатынас кезінде орын алады. Хабарды бір коммуниканттан (мифті жасаушы) екіншісіне (мифті тұтынушыға) жеткізу механизмін сипаттау үшін атақты неміс социологы Никлас Луманның коммуникация теориясына жүгінейік. Оның теориясы бойынша коммуникация үш құрамдас бөліктен тұрады: хабарлама, ақпарат, түсіну. Сонымен бірге, Луман ақпаратты «жүйенің күйін өзгертетін оқиға» деп анықтайды.

Бұл бірнеше мүмкіндіктердің ішінен таңдау болып табылады. Байланыс оның қатысушыларының бірі белгілі бір таңдауды басқасына бергенде, сол арқылы оны қандай да бір таңдауға итермелегенде жүзеге асырылады. Басқа қатысушының оны қабылдау немесе қабылдамау мүмкіндігі бар. Саяси мифология тұрғысынан алғанда, берілген іріктеу – мифте қамтылған және мифті жасаушы қарым-қатынас жасауға тырысатын ақпараттық, мінез-құлық және эмоционалдық қатынастың жиынтығы.

Кедергілер мен қауіптердің симуляторлары (иллюзиялар, жалған бейнелер) мифтерді жасау және жүзеге асыру үшін де қолданылады. Мифодизайнда қандай да бір қауіптің болуы туралы пікір қалыптастырылады (сыртқы саяси жаулар, терроризм және т.б.).

Бұл қауіпті бұқараның бірлігі арқылы ғана жеңуге болады. Біріктіру процесі – бұл мифтің негізгі мақсаты.

Мифті қабылдау белсенділіктің бақылауға дейін төмендеуімен жеңілдетіледі. Бұл индивидтің қандай да бір кезеңді және дамып келе жатқан әрекетпен әлеуметтік тұрақсыздануына мүмкіндік береді. Адам өзінің алдында ашылатын саяси картинаға – саяси қозғалыстардың, партиялардың, олардың жетекшілерінің, т.б. күресіне қанағаттанады. Ал өзі саяси өмірге белсенді араласпай, сырттан бақылаушыға айналады.

Сонымен қатар, миф пен оның кейіпкерлерін қабылдау жұмбақ түрде (яғни, саяси өмір субъектісі оны басқалардан ерекшелендіретін ерекше қасиеттерге ие; осы арқылы оған деген ынтық сезімге деген қажеттілік белсендіріледі), сонымен қатар, оны бұрмалау сияқты механизмдерді қолданумен байланысты. Мысалы, дүниетаным, жалған стереотиптерді, рөлдерді, мінез-құлық сценарийлерін ұсыну; дүние мен символизмнің дәйекті суретінің қажеттілігі сипатталады. Саяси шындық тақырыбына табыс символының мәні беріледі (жарқын мысал - Ұлы Отан соғысындағы Сталиннің рөлін асыра көрсету)

Қорытындылай келе, саяси миф бүгінгі саяси үдерісте барған сайын оның алатын орны ерекше маңызды бола түсуде. Ол қоғамды тиімді басқару технологияларының біріне айналады. Саяси миф кез келген классикалық және қазіргі идеологиялық концепциялардың ажырамас элементі. Сондай-ақ, сайлау науқандары кезінде санаға әсер етудің негізгі әдісі болып табылады. Қалыптасқан саяси шындықты негіздейді және қоғам тарапынан билікке белгілі бір көзқарасты қалыптастырады.

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ЭЛЕКТРОМАГНИТТІК ТОЛҚЫНДАРДЫҢ АДАМ АҒЗАСЫНА ӘСЕРІ

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Аңдатпа

Бұл мақалада электромагниттік толқындардың адам ағзасына әсері көрсетілген. Жаңа технологиялық құралдардың пайда болуы адам үшін үлкен көмегін тигізуде, сонымен қатар, адам ағзасына кері әсерін де тигізуде. Бұл қазіргі заманның өзекті мәселенің бірі болып саналады.

Кілтті сөздер: *электромагнитті толқын, сәулелену, радиолокация, өріс, жиілік*

Электромагнитті толқындардан таралған сәуленуді көзгекөрінбейді, ал оны елестету қиын, сондықтан қарапайым адам одан қорғанбайды деп айтсақ болады. Егер дүние жүзіндегі барлық құрылғылардан шығаратын электромагниттік сәулелену әсерін қосып көрсек, ол кезде Жер бетіндегі табиғи геомагнитті өрістер миллиондаған есеге асып кетер еді. Электромагниттік ластанудың масштабы жер бетінде жоғарылап келе жатқандығы соншалық, Бүкіләлемдік денсаулық сақтау ұйымы адам өміріндегі өзекті мәселесі ретінде қарастырып отыр.

Алғаш рет ағылшын физик – ғалымы М.Фарадей, электромагниттік толқындардың бар екенін 1832 жылы айтқан болатын. Ал, 1865 жылы электромагниттік толқын кеңістікте шектелмей, шығу көзінен жан-жаққажайылатындығын, басқа ағылшын ғалымы Дж.Максвелл айтқан. Дж.Максвеллдің теориясына радиотолқынды, оптикалық сәулелену, рентген және гаммасәулелерінің сипаттауына жол ашты. Бұл барлық сәулелену түрлері табиғаты бойынша бір – бірімен ұқсас, өздеріне тән әр түрлі толқын ұзындығы бар λ электромагниттік толқындар екені анықталды. Ғылыми-технологиялық революцияның дамуымен адамдардың күнделікті өмірлеріне заманауи-жаңа технологиялар енді (компьютерлер, спутникті байланыс, радиотелефондар). Радиолокациялық, радиорелейлі және телевизиялық телемұнаралардың пайда болуына байланысты электромагниттік сәулелену көздерінің ұлғаюына ықпал етті. Көптеген адамдар осы электромагниттік толқындардың ағзаға қалай әсер ететіндігі алаңдатуда. Электромагниттік сәулелену 40 ГГц-тен 70 ГГц-ге дейін адам үшін қатерлі болып саналады.

Физикалық сипаты бойынша электромагниттік толқынды сәулелер (ЭМС) бір бірімен байланысқан, электрлік және магниттік алаңдарда уақыты бойынша өзгертін, және бір

бірімен әсері, электромагниттік алаңды түзеді. ЭМС толқындардың жиілігі және ұзындығымен сипатталады. Электромагниттік толқындар жиілігі герцпен өлшенеді (Гц). 1 Гц секундтағы тербеліске өлшенеді. Герцтің туындыларына жатады: килогерц (кГц) = 1000 Гц, мегагерц (МГц) = Гц және гигагерц (ГГц) = Гц құрайды. Радиосәулелер толқындарын келесі негізгі диапазондарға бөледі: өте төмен жиіліктегі (ӨТЖ), төмен жиіліктегі (ТЖ), жоғары жиіліктегі (ЖЖ), ультражоғары жиіліктегі (УЖЖ) және өте жоғары жиіліктегі (ӨЖЖ). Оларға өте ұзын, ұзын, орташа, қысқа, ультра қысқа және микротолқындар (дециметрлер, сантиметрлер, миллиметрлер) тән.

XXI ғасырдың басында жерсеріктерімен байланыстың жиіліктері 11 ГГц құрап, өте жоғары болып есептелген. Ал, 2009 жылы базалық станциялардың арасындағы байланыстың жиілігі 25 ГГц жоғарлатқан болатын, ұялы байланыс орталықтың операторларымен. Бұл байланыстың сапасы мен жылдамдығын жоғарлатқан. Сондай-ақ, адам ағзасына электромагниттік толқындардың 40-70 ГГц жиілік арасында әсерлері арта түсті. Электромагниттік сәулелерді кеңістікте тудыра алатын техникалық құрылғылар электромагниттік сәулелерді тікелей шығару көздері болып саналады.

Қазіргі таңда, кішкентай балалардан ересектерге дейін заманауи технологияларды жиі қолданады. Техникалардың бәрі розеткаларға қосылады және тоқ өткізеді – бұл электромагниттік сәулеленудің негізгі таралу көздерінің бірі болып табылады. Күнделікті өмірдің өзінде адам электромагниттік өрістердің (ЭМӨ) әсерінде жүреді: жұмыстағы компьютерлер – 10 – 80 ГГц дейін сәулелендіреді; пәтерлеріңіздегі техникалардың өзі де әсерін тигізеді. Электромагниттік толқындар энергияны таратады және заттармен әсерлескенде жылуға айналады. Түрлі құрылымдық деңгейде осы толқындардың әсерінен әр түрлі реакцияларды береді. Егер, электромагниттік толқындар 10 Вт/см қуат тығыздығынан жоғары болса, тірі ағзалар үшін теріс әсер етеді.

Ұялы телефондарды пайдалануының өзі бас миға бірнеше компонентті қатты әсер етеді:

1. мидың орталық құрылысына тікелей әсері;
2. перифериялық рецепторларға, вестибулярлы, есту және көру анализаторларына әсері;
3. құлақ мүшесінің биологиялық нүктелеріне қатты әсері;
4. бет және құлақ терілерінің рецепторлары арқылы рефлексогенді миға әсер етуі;

Соңғы мәліметтерге сүйенсек, Швеция мен Норвегия тұрғындары GSM ұялы телефоның қолданушыларының 20 мың адам саны бастың жиі ауруы мен тез шаршауының жиілеткені байқалған [4]. АҚШ-тың зерттеуші ғалымдардың зерттеулеріне қарасақ, ұялы телефоннан шыққан толқын бас миға 37,5 мм дейін сигналын жеткізеді екен. Бұл мидың биоэлектрлік белсенділігінің өзгеруіне әсерін тигізеді, ал, Ресейдің зерттеушілері тышқандар мен егеуқұйрықтарға радиотелефоннан шыққан толқынның әсерін анықтау үшін жасаған тәжірибелерінде (ұзақтығы екі апта) мынадай нәтижелерді алды: көздің әйнешігі, қанның құрамы және жыныс мүшелерінің функциялары өзгеріске ұшырады. Осының салдарынан, Ұлыбритания елі радиотелефондарға кішкентай балаларға қолдануға тиім салды.

Электромагниттік толқындардың нәтижесінде адамның иммундық, жыныстық, эндокриндік, жүйке және жүрек-қан тамырларының жүйелеріне теріс әсер етеді.

Электромагниттік толқындардың ағзаға деген әсерін төмендету үшін келесі маңызды нұсқауларды орындаған жөн:

- Тұрмыстық техникаларды қажет емес жағдайларда көп қолданбау (ұялы телефон арқылы сөйлесу ұзақтығы 4-5 минут);
- Заманауи гаджеттерді сатып алу кезінде сәулеленудің қуаты максималды төменің таңдау;
- Магниттік өрісі бар жерлерде көп серуендеуден аулақ болу;

- Үй жағдайында электроқұрылғылардан, электр сауыттан және кабельдерден 3-4 метр ара қашықтығында жиһаздарды орналастыру;
- Компьютермен жұмыс барысында санитарлы-гигиеналық нормалар мен ережелерді сақтау;

Жоғары жиіліктің жүзден-мыңнан бір Ватт бөлігі адамға қауіпті болып саналады, себебі осындай өрістердің интенсивтілігі адам ағзасының қалыпты жағдайдағы сәулелену интенсивтілігімен шамалас болады. Соның нәтижесінде адам денесіндегі өріс бұрмаланып, ағзаға көптеген ауруларды тудыруына септігін тигізеді. Электромагнитті сигналдардың айрықша бір қасиеті ол – ағзаға уақыт өте келе жиналатындығы. Түрлі оргтехникалармен, оның ішінде компьютерлермен, ұялы телефондармен көп жұмыс жасайтын адамдарда имунитеттің төмендеуі, жиі стресске ұшырауы, көп шаршау сияқты белгілері байқалған. Бұл электромагниттік толқындардан тараған зияндарының барлығы емес.

Заманның дамуына сай адам қажеттіліктері артып, соған байланысты, әлі қаншама техника шығатындығы айдан анық. Осы техникалардың пайдасынан зияның көріп жатпауымызға ешкім толық кепіл бере алмайды. Әрине, адам денсаулығын және қоршаған ортаны қорғау ұйымдарының талаптары болады, алайдабүгінгі күннің өзінде сол талаптарды орындамайтын кәсіби компаниялар жоқ емес. Ұялы телефондар, компьютерлер және әртүрлі тұрмыстық электротехникалар от секілді. Бірақ, олардан бас тарта алмаймыз, себебі ол құрылғыларсыз қазіргі заманда өмір сүру мүмкін емес. Тек, оларды ұқыпты қолдансақ, ол өз пайдасымен қуантады және ағзамызға деген кері әсерлерін төмендете аламыз.

Preparedness of the country's healthcare system for a pandemic on the example of Azerbaijan

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Sustainable development involves the harmonious development of social, economic and environmental subsystems in order to meet the needs of humanity of present and future generations. The tasks of sustainable development include an extensive list of areas, ranging from sustainable trends in increasing economic growth and population to ensuring a high standard of living for the population, accessibility and standards of healthcare, education, environmental safety, etc.

At the present stage, the world community is most acutely facing problems in the social sphere, which emphasize the relevance of social parameters in achieving sustainable development goals. The importance of social indicators is confirmed by the fact that among the 17 formulated by UN sustainable development goals until 2030, more than half are occupied by socially oriented parameters, such as the eradication of poverty, hunger, the availability of healthcare, the quality and accessibility of education, the reduction of inequality, etc.

These parameters of social development reflect the key areas of society and are related to the well-being of citizens, issues of socio-economic inequality, problems of the formation and development of human and social capital, accessibility and quality of public goods for all segments of the population.

One of the social guidelines and factors of sustainable socio-economic development of countries is the state of the healthcare sector. In this regard, the study of the scale of accessibility and quality of healthcare and the development of ways to optimize this area for sustainable development are of particular relevance.

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development adopted by the United Nations in 2015 and the United Nations General Assembly Meeting on UHC in 2019 reaffirmed that as a target for health and well-being considers achieving universal health coverage by 2030, including access to quality health services and medicines. To achieve this goal, according to WHO experts, it is necessary to constantly increase annual investments in health-related projects from 134 billion US dollars in PPP to 371 billion, or 58 US dollars per person by 2030.

Accessibility and quality are determined by the level of funding from the budget, investments in fixed capital, the material and technical equipment of medical institutions, the availability of medical personnel and beds in hospitals, as well as the stability and degree of development of the preventive care system.

To date, ensuring the availability and quality of health care services remains an acute social problem, and a set of actions in the field of primary, secondary and tertiary prevention, aimed at reducing the causes of the main types of morbidity and mortality, is of particular relevance in this direction.

Many countries are already well on their way to achieving UHC, even as the COVID-19 pandemic around the world has affected the capacity of health systems to deliver uninterrupted health services.

Improving health coverage and health outcomes depends on the availability and accessibility of health and social workers and their ability to deliver quality, people-centred integrated health care. The COVID-19 pandemic has clearly demonstrated the invaluable role of health and social workers and the importance of increasing investment in this area.

It is projected that by 2030, the growing demand for a health workforce will lead to the creation of approximately 40 million additional jobs in the global economy through the health sector. The public and private sectors should allocate funds to train health workers and to create and fill funded positions in the health and related sectors of the economy. The COVID 19 pandemic, which initially disproportionately affected health workers, highlighted the need to protect health and social workers, prioritize investment in their training and employment, and take advantage of partnerships to ensure decent working conditions for them.

The reforms carried out in Azerbaijan in the field of healthcare, in accordance with the orders and instructions of President Ilham Aliyev, the constructed and reconstructed medical institutions indicate that the development of healthcare in the country today continues at the highest level.

Successful healthcare reforms in various aspects are aimed at ensuring the health of the population and establishing it at the level of world standards. At present, in order to improve the quality of medical services in the country, compulsory medical insurance is applied in order to ensure the availability of these services to the population. For this purpose, by Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan No. 1125 dated November 24, 2016, a state agency for compulsory health insurance "public legal entity" was established.

Over the past period of almost 10 years, Azerbaijan has made economic progress, the country's economic potential has increased, which in turn created conditions for the development of the country's healthcare system and the achievement of a lasting solution to the problems of protecting the health of the population. To develop healthcare as one of the important directions of the long-term development strategy determined by the country's leadership, and to provide the population with medical care that meets international standards, large-scale reforms are being carried out. Large investments are made every year. Over the past 10 years, the amount of budgetary funds allocated to health care has increased more than 10 times. During this period, more than 500 medical institutions were built or overhauled (most of which are located in the regions of the republic), all institutions were provided with modern medical equipment and technology. Significant results have been achieved in the fight against infectious diseases. This area is constantly in the spotlight as a priority area of practical healthcare.

The healthcare system is a social sphere that requires large budget expenditures. For this reason, in order to carry out large-scale reforms in this area, rebuild and provide hospitals with the most modern equipment, and build new treatment and diagnostic centers, it was necessary to expand the country's economic opportunities. From this point of view, since 2004, health care reforms in Azerbaijan began to expand in parallel with the start of the rapid development of the country's economy. For the successful implementation of reforms in the healthcare system, familiarity with the experience of developed countries, cooperation of Azerbaijani healthcare institutions with various international organizations is of great importance. The Government of Azerbaijan is actively cooperating with WHO, UNICEF, the USAID (USAID) Primary Health Care Project, the Open Society Institute Assistance Fund, the Bloomberg Initiative Foundation, the World Bank, the European Commission, relevant UN agencies and other organizations.

In September 2006, the government of Azerbaijan signed a financial agreement with the International Development Association of the World Bank within the framework of health system

reforms. This agreement provides for the implementation of a project for structural and managerial reforms of the health care system over a period of 6 years. The project covers strengthening the management capacity of the Ministry of Health, improving the provision of medical services, developing human resources, etc. The progress of the reforms is monitored by a special mission of the World Bank, which positively evaluates the results. Also, the reforms of the healthcare system in the past few years have received a positive assessment of the progress reports on Azerbaijan by the European Commission, prepared within the framework of the European Neighborhood Policy.

Since the very first days of the pandemic, practical measures have been taken in Azerbaijan to minimize the negative impact of COVID-19 on the population and control the situation. Below is a chronology of operational state measures to combat the spread of the epidemic within the country, as well as Azerbaijan's international contribution to the fight against the pandemic during 2020.

Due to the spread of the coronavirus epidemic in Azerbaijan, preliminary preventive measures have been launched since January 2020. The State Customs Committee of Azerbaijan has stepped up border controls related to the deadly Chinese virus, which include thermometry, medical and visual inspection, thermal imaging and other diagnostic methods. Several measures were taken at once, including a ban on the import of certain goods from China and increased infection control at home. On January 29, air communication between Baku and China was suspended.

On January 30, by order of the Cabinet of Ministers, the "Action Plan to prevent the spread of a new coronavirus infection in the Republic of Azerbaijan" was approved. On February 27, 2020, the government created an Operational Headquarters under the Cabinet of Ministers to coordinate the government's response to the spread of coronavirus in the country. On this day, special laboratories were placed in the country, and mobile hospitals were placed on the border with Iran.

The spread of COVID-19 in Azerbaijan began on February 28, 2020, when the first case of COVID-19 coronavirus infection was registered in the country, which was established by the Operational Headquarters under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan: it became known that a Russian citizen who crossed the border from Iran to Azerbaijan, contracted the virus. After the first COVID-19 disease was detected on February 29, the Azerbaijani Border Service closed the border with Iran.

As of March 2, 2020, the Azerbaijani government has adopted a strong COVID-19 strategy to minimize the impact of the pandemic on the population. In March, the Operational Headquarters took a number of restrictive measures aimed at preventing the spread of infections, including the closure of land and air borders with Turkey, Russia, Georgia, and some cities in Europe, Central Asia and the Middle East. Mass events, worship services in Christian churches, visits to mosques are prohibited. Shopping centers and large commercial facilities, restaurants, gyms, theaters, cinemas, museums and other entertainment venues are closed to the public.

On March 19, 2020, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan signed the Decree "On measures to protect the health of the population of the Republic of Azerbaijan and strengthen measures to combat coronavirus infection." According to the decree, a Special Fund for Supporting the Fight against Coronavirus was established to provide financial assistance to the country for the response. Approximately \$12 million was allocated from the President's Reserve Fund.

On March 20, one billion manat was allocated from the state budget of the country to finance measures to reduce sharp fluctuations caused by the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic and global energy and stock markets. Also, the Operational Headquarters under the Cabinet of

Ministers decided to send employees of some state institutions on special leave from March 29 to April 29 with salary.

The presidential decree dated March 19, 2020 regulates a number of measures related to reducing the negative impact of the coronavirus pandemic on the Azerbaijani economy, macroeconomic stability, employment and entrepreneurship. Large-scale, prompt and effective measures are reflected in the action plan for the implementation of the Presidential Decree. 2 billion US dollars have been allocated for these purposes.

From 00:00 on March 24, 2020, in accordance with Article 25 of the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Sanitary and Epidemiological Safety", a special quarantine was announced in order to combat Covid-19 infection, protect health and prevent the spread of coronavirus infection in the country and its possible consequences. The duration of this regime was determined taking into account the epidemiological situation in the country as a whole, the level of infection with COVID-19.

Since March 2020, more than 20 public hospitals in Azerbaijan have started providing services to patients with COVID-19. On March 28, with the participation of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev, the Yeni Clinic medical facility was opened in Baku, where patients with severe symptoms of coronavirus have been treated since March 29. This is a medical institution with a capacity of 575 beds and a medical staff of more than 1,500 doctors and medical workers. According to the Decree signed by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on April 7, 2020, 13 modular hospitals for patients with COVID-19 were built as part of additional measures within six months. These modular hospitals are provided with an additional 4,100 hospital beds. Thus, the total number of hospital beds in the country for the treatment of patients with COVID amounted to more than 10 thousand, the number of laboratories for testing for COVID-19 was increased from 6 to 44.

Local production of face masks, disposable protective clothing, disinfectants, etc. has been launched in the city of Sumgayit on the basis of Gilan Tekstil Park, which has become the next effective measure in the fight against the global coronavirus pandemic.

Since the end of 2020, vaccines against COVID-19 began to appear, and mass vaccination against COVID-19 began in a number of countries.

Vaccination of the population of Azerbaijan in order to create collective immunity against the COVID-19 coronavirus infection began on January 18, 2021. The State Agency for Compulsory Health Insurance has launched a new electronic service "Registering for vaccination against Covid-19". The purpose of creating an electronic service is to distribute calls according to the capabilities of medical institutions, as well as effectively manage the flow of people, minimizing the waiting time at vaccination stations. From the very beginning of vaccination in Azerbaijan, CoronaVac (SINOVAC) has been used, since 10/12/2021 the following vaccines have become available: Vaxzevria, AstraZeneca, Pfizer/BioNTech, Sputnik V.

During 2021-2022 4,862,494 were fully vaccinated, which accounted for 48.3% of the population. The total number of vaccine doses administered was 13,857,111.

As Azerbaijan's international contribution to the fight against the pandemic, the government of Azerbaijan has donated US\$5 million to the WHO for the global fight against the COVID-19 pandemic, and an additional US\$5 million has been donated in solidarity with the Non-Aligned Movement (NAM) countries most affected by the virus. In addition, Azerbaijan has provided humanitarian and financial assistance to more than 30 countries belonging to the Non-Aligned Movement in order to support the fight against coronavirus, including technical and medical supplies, financial assistance, 150,000 doses of vaccines to four countries, the provision of transport aircraft, etc.

At the beginning of 2020, when the world faced the COVID-19 pandemic, Azerbaijan assumed responsibility for chairing the Movement and made serious efforts to respond to the

threats caused by the pandemic in a timely and adequate manner. Azerbaijan has put forward a number of initiatives to mobilize global efforts in the fight against the pandemic. In May 2020, Azerbaijan took the initiative to hold an online Summit at the level of heads of state and government of the countries participating in the Non-Aligned Movement and on the initiative of President Ilham Aliyev, as chairman of the Non-Aligned Movement, on May 4, a summit meeting was held on the theme "We are together against COVID-19 » via videoconference. In a video message from the UN Secretary-General, Mr. António Guterres, and the Director-General of the World Health Organization, Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus, words of gratitude and appreciation were expressed for the financial and humanitarian support provided by the government of Azerbaijan in the fight against COVID-19. As a result of the summit, a database containing the basic humanitarian and medical needs of the Non-Aligned Movement member states was created, which was used by WHO as a reference source for meeting the urgent needs of the member states of the Non-Aligned Movement. As Chairman of the Non-Aligned Movement Ilham Aliyev noted in his speech, Azerbaijan has put forward a number of global initiatives. In order to draw attention to "vaccine nationalism", Azerbaijan initiated the adoption of a resolution on ensuring equal access to vaccines for all countries in the UN Human Rights Council on behalf of the Non-Aligned Movement, and this document was unanimously adopted in March.

In addition, based on the proposal of President Ilham Aliyev at the Summit, which was subsequently supported by more than 150 countries, a special session of the UN General Assembly at the level of heads of state and government was organized in December 2020. dedicated to the fight against coronavirus. In his speech at the 15th Economic Cooperation Organization (ECO) Summit, President of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev reported that Azerbaijan has provided financial and humanitarian assistance to almost 80 countries of the world directly and through the World Health Organization in order to support the fight against coronavirus infection.

Thanks to timely and necessary preventive measures to prevent the spread of the virus in Azerbaijan, the figures for the dynamics of morbidity and mortality from coronavirus in Azerbaijan with a population of 10 million, according to the latest data, were: all cases of the disease - 827,823; mortality - 10,077. Due to a systematic approach and the above measures, it was possible to significantly reduce the negative impact of the pandemic on public health and the economic and social consequences caused by it.

At the same time, Covid 19 was a trigger for identifying problems in the country's healthcare system. Statistical analysis of the situation showed a shortage of medical personnel, especially in the regions of the country. There is a trend of dispersal of medical workers in large cities, which negatively affects the provision of doctors and medical workers in other regions in relation to the population and the unsatisfactory level of digital medicine in remote regions of the country.

In order to improve the staffing of the health system, develop a long-term personnel strategy for the health system, streamline the structure of human resources in accordance with the needs of the population, outpatient and inpatient medical services, develop human resources, as well as meet the need for qualified personnel in remote areas, there is a need developing an additional incentive strategy. Also, a special role can be played by expanding the opportunities for continuing medical education of medical workers, adapting the system of undergraduate and postgraduate medical education to the requirements of the modern system of medical education, providing the necessary material and technical base and staffing needs.

To prevent the spread of the coronavirus pandemic in the country, a registration program was created in a short time, established centers for receiving tests for coronavirus and modular hospitals of the country, as well as specially designated medical institutions were provided with computers, printers, barcode devices and other technical equipment, as well as software. Electronic registration posts have been created in 61 medical institutions. 42 coronavirus testing

laboratories are fully automated and the results are processed electronically. An SMS notification system has been set up to inform citizens about the results of coronavirus tests.

Digital health is seen as a new strategic health priority. The use of digital health technologies to improve the efficiency of health systems and services was widely recognized even before the start of the COVID-19 pandemic. The importance of applying digital health technologies is essential to achieving universal health coverage. The use of digital tools such as contact tracing applications to monitor outbreaks and provide online advice to ensure the safety of healthcare professionals and patients and ensure continuity of care is an example of how digital technologies can be harnessed.

The fight against the pandemic has intensified the course of economic reforms in Azerbaijan. One of the significant negative consequences of the virus is the emergence of autoimmune diseases. As a factor in post-viral recovery, autoimmune response therapy can become an optimization of health tourism. The abundance of mineral springs, the presence of salt caves and the world's only deposit of medicinal oil - Naftalan, contribute to the formation of medical tourism in Azerbaijan.

Licorice industrial park was opened in Azerbaijan. Literally three or four months before the pandemic hit, Azerbaijan launched the production of extracts and syrups from licorice, a plant around which serious excitement could begin. Research work done at the University of Frankfurt showed that glycyrrhizin, which is believed to be the main biologically active substance in licorice root, inhibits the replication of the SARS-associated virus. Comparisons were made with other acids - with ribavirin, 6-azauridine, pyrazofurin and mycophenolic acid. Other publications state that there is significant antiviral activity of glycyrrhizic acid against the herpes virus. Thus, licorice extracts can be widely distributed in world markets.

Summing up the above, Azerbaijan faced a pandemic in the mode of an innovative model of public administration, the implementation of healthcare reforms in the field of optimizing human resources, modernization and digitalization of the industry. The fight against the pandemic has intensified the course of personnel and structural reforms in Azerbaijan. The pandemic has accelerated the e-government revolution by allowing the state to assess shortcomings and prepare new solutions.

Philological Sciences

DİL ZAMANLARI

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Açar sözlər: temporalıq, adlarda zaman anlayışı, sintaktik vahidlərdə zaman anlayışı

Məlumdur ki, icra edilən və edilməyən hər hansı bir iş, hal, hərəkət, proses müəyyən bir məkan və zaman daxilində baş verir. Zaman anlayışı həm obyektiv, həm də qrammatik zaman olmaqla iki yerə ayrılır. Obyektiv zaman kainatın, maddi aləmin, obyektiv gerçəkliyin özündədir. Bir kimsədən asılı olmadan daim hərəkət edir. Obyektiv zaman fəlsəfə elminin tədqiqat obyektidir, ümumbəşəridir. Heç kimdən və heç nədən asılı olmadan bütün bəşəriyyətə eyni dərəcədə aiddir. Obyektiv zamanın nə başlanğıcı, nə də sonu var. Bu zamanın heç bir ifadə forması yoxdur.

Feillərə xas olan qrammatik zaman isə dilçilik elmində araşdırılır. Hər bir xalq onu öz dilinə uyğun olaraq ifadə edir. Qrammatik zaman hissələrə ayrılır: keçmiş (şühudi, nəqli), indiki, gələcək (qəti, qeyri-qəti). Zaman kateqoriyası keçmişdə icra olunmuş, indi icra olunan, gələcəkdə icra olunacaq işin zamanı ilə icra olunmuş, olunan və olunacaq iş, hal və hərəkət haqqında məlumat verilən vaxt arasındakı zamandır.

Qrammatik zamanın müxtəlif ifadə formaları, qrammatik əlamətləri vardır. Xüsusi olaraq felin zaman şəkilçiləri: indiki zaman (-ır, -ir, -ur, -ür); keçmiş zaman – nəqli və şühudi keçmiş zaman (-miş, -miş, -muş, -müş; -ib, -ib, -ub, -üb; -dı, -di, -du, -dü); gələcək zaman – qəti və qeyri qəti gələcək zaman şəkilçiləri (-acaq, -əcək; -ar, -ər), həmçinin feli bağlama və feli sifət (-dıqda, -dıqca, -anda, dığmda⁴, -an, -ən; miş, -miş, -muş, -müş, -ası², -acaq², -malı²) şəkilçiləri temporalıq yaradan qrammatik vasitələrdir. Felin digər şəkilləri (əmr, arzu, lazım, vacib, şərt) zamana görə dəyişməyə də, yəni konkret olaraq zaman kateqoriyasının morfoloji əlamətini qəbul etməyə də, iş, hal və hərəkətin icrasının gələcəyə aid olması heç bir şübhə doğurmur. Məsələn, *Qalmışam* su ilə od arasında (A.Azafli). *Qəza tutdu*, *qədər yıxdı*, *Fələk döydü* qara baxtı (A.Azafli). Bir ədalət *ola*, *odlar səngidən*, *Azafli qurtara cida-cəngidən* (A.Azafli). *Yerin, yurdun viran qalsın*, *Bürünəsən* qara, *zindan* (A.Azafli). *Keçən* qara günü ağ gün unudar... (A.Azafli). *Dost qəmgin olacaq* siz *ağlayanda*, *Bilirəm*, *güləcək* düşmən bu yerdə (A. Azafli).

Bunlardan əlavə, leksik və sintaktik vahidlər də zaman anlayışının yaranmasında mühüm rol oynayır. Temporalığın (dil zamanlarının) leksik və sintaktik vahidlərlə ifadəsini nəzərdən keçirək:

Zaman məzmunlu isimlər: *gün, həftə, ay, il, fəsil, vaxt, əsr, qərinə, zaman, çağ, axşam, gecə, yay, payız, qış, əyyam* və s. Məsələn, *Axşamım* qan tökər, *sabahım* ağlar... (A.M.Azafli) *Yaralı sinəmin min bir dağı var*, *Qara günlərimə* gül, a bəxtəvər. (A.M.Azafli) *Zaman* saçlarımdan çarmıxdan asdı, *O* sübhan qocaltdı, mən qocalmazdım (A.M.Azafli). *Baharım* qış oldu, *gözüm* yaş oldu, *Bülbül*, sən ağlama, qoy mən ağlayım. (A. M. Azafli) *Görürsən* ki, *zaman* tərsə hökm edir, *Mərd* namərdə daldalandı bu *çağlar*. (A.M.Azafli) *Gəzsən əsrləri, qərinələri*, insana bağlıdır elmi əsəri. (A.M.Azafli) *Dan* quşu oxuyur, deyir, *sabahdı*, *Gözüm* dan yerində, *səhər* açılmır. (A.M.Azafli) *İl ildən* çətindi, *gün gündən* yaman... (A.M.Azafli)

Göründüyü kimi, bu leksik vahidlər qrammatik mənasına görə isimdir, lakin hər birinin daxili məzmununda zaman anlayışı açıq-aşkar özünü büruzə verir.

Bu cür temporal isimlər "Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud" un, klassik poeziyanın dili üçün də səciyyəvidir: *ay, yıl, küz, kış, vədə, məhəl (zaman), vəqt, əyyam, zəman* və s. Məsələn, *Axır zamanda* xanlıq geri *Qayıya* dəgə, *kimsənə* əllərindən almaya, *axır zaman* olub *qiyamət* qopunca. *Əcəl vədə*

irməyincə kimsə ölməz. Bu *məhəldə* oğuz ərənləri bir-bir yetdi. *Küz* almasına bənzər al yanaqlım... *Alar tanla* yerindən turan yigit, nə yığitsən? *Alar sabah* Dirsə xan yerindən uru turdu. (KDQ) Ey saqi, gətir dövr əyağın, dövr elə, sun kim, Bu dövr əyağın *dövrən* bilir ancaq; *Bahar* oldu, gəl, ey dilbər, tamaşa qıl bu gülüzərə, Buraxdı qönçələr pərdə bəşarət bülbülü-zarə; Bu halə qərar eyləmə *ayyam*, keçər ömür, Ey əhli-nəzər, baxma bu halə, nəzər eylə; Gəl bu *dəmi* xoş görəlim, ol keçən *dəm* dəm degil; Gör bu lətifeyi ki, mən *dəhrü zəmanə* sığmazam; *Vədəyi* qoy, ey könül, gəl bu *dəmi* xoş görəlim; Sən nə *qış* oldun ki, sənin təzə *baharın* yox imiş; *Yazü küzündür* suyumuz, mai-nəindir meyimiz... (İ.Nəsimi)

Ə.Tanrıverdi türkologiyada işlənmə yerinə görə bəzən isim, bəzən də zərf başlığı altında verilən zaman məzmunlu vahidlərin isim başlığı altında verilməsini daha məqbul sayır. “Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud” un dilində istifadə edilmiş temporallığın (dil zamanlarının) elmi izahını verən Ə. Tanrıverdinin “alar” vahidi ilə bağlı mühakimələri maraqlıdır: “Alar. “sübh vaxtı, dan vaxtı, üfüq qızardığı vaxt” və s. anlamlı “alar” sözü “Kitab” da I növ təyini söz birləşməsinin birinci tərəfi kimi çıxış edir: alar sabah. ...Qorqudşünaslıqda “alar tan” daha çox birinci növ təyini söz birləşməsi modelində izah olunur. Amma bu sinonim qoşa sözlər baxımından da şərh edilə bilər (müq. et: alar – üfüq qızardığı vaxt, sübh vaxtı; tan – sabah açılarkən, günəşin üfüqdə ilk ağarması...). (1, s. 226)

Yeri gəlmişkən, II növ təyini söz birləşməsi modeli əsasında formalaşan “dan yeri” birləşməsində də zaman məzmunu açıq hiss olunur: Dan yeri ağarır – Günəş doğmağa başlayır; İşıqlaşır; Səhər açılır; Sübh vaxtıdır və s. Bu cümlələrin hər birinin məzmununda “sübh gün çıxan vaxt, səhər çağ, ala-toran” anlamını verən zaman anlayışı vardır.

Temporal isimlər leksik-semantik cəhətdən olduqca rəngarəngdir: zamanın hesablanmasını ifadə edən sözlər: saniyə, dəqiqə, saat, gün (səhər, günorta, axşam, gecə), həftə, ay, il, qərinə, əsr, era; fəsil adları: yaz, yay, payız, qış və s.

Zaman məzmunlu düzəltmə sifətlər: *dünənki*, *axşamki*, *çoxdankı*. Bu cür sifətlərin temporallıq qazanmasına, təbii ki, zaman zərfləri təsir edir. Çünki *dünən*, *axşam* leksik vahidləri zaman zərfləridir. Sifət -ki, -kı şəkilçisi vasitəsi ilə zərfdən əmələ gəlmiş olduğundan kökdəki zaman məzmununu qoruyub saxlayır. “Çoxdankı” sifəti də “çoxdan” düzəltmə zaman zərfindən əmələ gəlmişdir. “Çoxdan” zərfi isə -dan şəkilçisi ilə “çox” qeyri-müəyyən miqdar sayından yaradılmışdır. Məsələn, il ildən çətindi, gün gündən yaman, Bir gün şeytan olur *dünənki* insan. (A.M.Azafli) *Axşamki* fırtına, *axşamki* ruzgar, Düşmüş nağıl kimi xalqın ağzına. (M.Müşfiq)

Cümlələrdəki “dünənki” və “axşamki” leksik vahidləri qrammatik mənasına görə sifətdir, nisbi sifətdir, hansı? sualına cavab verir. Əvvəlki sətirlərdə də qeyd etdiyimiz kimi, kökdəki zaman məzmunu qorunub saxlanır. Sintaktik vəzifəsi isə təyindir, zaman təyindir. Deməli, cümlələrdəki temporallığın yaradılmasında həmin vahidlər müstəsna əhəmiyyət daşıyır.

Zaman zərfləri ilə ifadə olunan temporallıq: *indi*, *əvvəl*, *əzəl*, *sonra*, *həmişə*, *hey*, *bildir*, *dünən*, *səhər*, *axşam*, *sabah*, *axşamüstü* və s. Məsələn, Muğan həsrət yağışa, buludlar xəsis, Yağış tökülür Talışa *hey*, *hey*, gərəksiz. (*Qabil*) Boynu bükük bənövşə o gündən *həmişə* kol dibində bitir. (*Az.əfsanələri*) Mən özüm də qayıtmaq istəyirdim, ancaq *bayaq* dediyim kimi, pullar çıxıb getmişdi, ona görə də kişiyyə yalan satmalı oldum. (*İ. Əfəndiyev*) *Əvvəl* evin içi, *sonra* çölü. (*Atalar s.*) *Axşam-sabah*, çeşmə, sənin başına, Bilirsənmi, necə canlar dolanır... (*A.Ələsgər*). *Axşam* sultan olan qul olur *sabah*. (*A.M.Azafli*) Dünya belə gəlib, belə gedərmiş, *Əzəldən* qanmadım, ağılı udurdum. (*A.M.Azafli*) Klassik poeziyamızın dilində zaman zərfləri ilə yaradılan temporallıq üstün mövqedədir. Mənşəyinə görə klassik poeziyada işlənen zaman zərfləri türk və qeyri-türk olaraq bölünür. Təbii ki, ərəb-fars mənşəli leksik vahidlər üstünlük təşkil edir. Bəzi türk mənşəli zaman zərfləri isə müasir dil baxımından arxaikləşmiş (yarın, dün- gün, danla), bəziləri isə fonetik tərkibcə müəyyən dəyişikliyə (imdi\şimdi –indi) uğramışdır Nümunələri nəzərdən keçirək: Yürəgim yaralı eylədi qəmzən, iriş, Yarasına bax bu gün, qoyma anı *yarına*; Yara, Nəsimi, bu gün canını qurban qılana, Məhrəm olur ta *əbad* məxzəni əsrarına; Eşq içində dinü dildən gəl keç *imdi*, ey fəqih, Şeyx Sənan kimi ol gəl sən dəxi tərsayi-eşq; Kim *əvvəl* tanımadı kəndi vücudi şəhrini, Ol gədəhimmət nə

yoldan varə sultan istəyə?; Düşdü saçının zülmətinə könlüm, ilahi, Şol hali-pərişanə bu *şamı səhər* eylə; Münacat eylərəm, *dün-gün* sənin dövlətli kuyində, Üzün nuri-təcəllidir, dəxi mən eylərəm Turi; Qaşındır vəhy, eynin ayətullah, *Naharü leyl* anın ağı, qarasi; Mən *bu gün* səbr etsəm, *danla* fəğanı neylərəm?; Dün də keçdi, *danla* qaib, bəs bu dəm xoş dəmdür. (İ.Nəsimi)

Zaman zərflərinin bəzilərinin semantikasında ümumi zaman məzmunu qabarıq hiss olunur: həmişə, hey, axşam-sabah, arabir, ara-sıra və s.

Zaman məzmunlu isimlərə (yaz, yay, payız, qış, gün, ay, il), “gənclik, cavanlıq, qocalıq” kimi düzəltmə isimlərə *-da, -də*; “çox” qeyri-müəyyən miqdar sayına, “gah” bağlayıcısına *-dan*; “o” işarə əvəzliyinə (tarixən ol və şol fonetik tərkibdə olub) **-da** şəkilçilərini artırmaqla (şəkilçidən qabaq **n** bitişdiricisi əlavə edilir) temporallıq yaradılır. Əslində zaman zərflərinin böyük əksəriyyəti semantik cəhətdən feillə ifadə olunan qrammatik zaman anlayışının məna tutumunu daha qabarıq şəkildə üzə çıxarmağa, konkretləşdirməyə xidmət göstərir. Məsələn, Tərlan dağda, bülbül bağda, Ceyran yazda çöldə gəzə. (M.Azaflı) *Son ayda* bənzərsən yetkin bostana... (A. Ələsgər)

Qeyd. Misradakı zaman məzmununu I növ təyini söz birləşməsi (son ayda) yaradır və cümlə daxilində ayrılır, cümlənin zaman zərfliyi vəzifəsini icra edir. *Gahdan* çiskin təkər, gah duman eylər... *Gahdan* qeyzə gələr, nahaq qan eylər... (A.Ələsgər) “Gahdan” zaman zərfliyi “arabir, hərdənbir, bəzən” leksik vahidləri ilə sinonimlik yaradır.

Zaman zərfləri bəzən də ismi xəbərlə cümlələrdə zaman anlayışı yaradır. Məsələn, *Cavanlıqda* qazanılmış bilik *qocalıqda* müdriklikdir. (Atalar sözü) Cümlədəki zaman məzmunu ümumi xarakterə malikdir. Ümumi zaman anlayışı həm düzəltmə zaman zərfləri (cavanlıqda, qocalıqda), həm də feli sifətlə (qazanılmış) mümkün olmuşdur. Feli sifətlər də feillər kimi zaman məzmunu daşısa da, feli sifətdəki zaman ümumi zamandır və feillərin qəbul etdiyi zaman kateqoriyasının morfoloji əlamətini qəbul etmir.

Başqa bir nümunə:

İndi adamlar, deyəsən, cindilər,
Cin nədi, şeytan nədi, bidindilər... (M.Ə. Sabir)

Misraların ümumi semantikasına nəzər salsaq, zaman anlayışının məhz “indi” zaman zərfliyi ilə formalaşdığını müşahidə edirik. İsmi xəbərlərdəki (cindilər, bidindilər) *-dir* xəbərlilik şəkilçisi də indiki zaman məzmunu yaradır. Yeri gəlmişkən, şəkilçidəki (*-dir -di*) **r** ünsürü işlədilməyib, ədəbi tələffüz transkripsiyasına uyğun verilib.

Digər bir nümunəni də nəzərdən keçirək:

Onda ki övladi-vətən xam idi,
Ax, necə kef çəkməli əyyam idi.
(M.Ə.Sabir)

Zaman budaq cümləli tabeli mürəkkəb cümləsinin də ümumi semantik tutumunda zaman məzmunu qabarıq şəkildə hiss olunur. Birinci cümlənin semantik yükündə keçmiş zaman məzmunu qabarıqdır. Keçmiş zaman mənası həm “onda” zərfində, həm də “xam idi” ismi xəbərində açıq şəkildə təzahür edir. “İdi” hissəciyi həmin sözün cümlədə xəbər olmasını təmin etdiyi kimi, həm də cümlədə ifadə olunan fikri keçmiş zamana bağlayır.

İkinci cümlənin (baş cümlənin) ismi xəbəri zaman mənalı əyyam ismi və “idi” hissəciyidir. “Əyyam” leksik vahidi ərəb mənşəli söz olub “günlər”, “zaman” mənalərini bildirir. Baş cümlədəki “əyyam idi” ismi xəbəri ilə təzahür edən keçmiş zaman məzmununu budaq cümlədəki zaman mənalı bağlayıcı söz (onda ki) və “xam idi” ismi xəbəri daha qabarıq şəkildə üzə çıxarır.

Nümunələrdən də aydın olur ki, zaman zərflərinin semantikasi həm felin qrammatik zamanlarının ifadə etdiyi semantik yükün konkretləşməsində, həm də ismi xəbərli cümlələrdə zaman anlayışlarının yaradılmasında mühüm əhəmiyyətə malikdir.

Qoşmalar: *bəri, əvvəl, sonra, kimi, qədər* və s. Məsələn, Neçə gün bundan *əvvəl* Koroğlu atını nallatmağa gəlmişdi... *(Azərbaycan ədəbiyyatı inciləri)* Bir dözmüsən, bir də döz, Gələn *payıza kimi (Bayatı)*. Mən səni görəndən *bəri*, Sinəm oldu qəm dəftəri... *(A.Ələsgər)*. Tez yatmaqğa adət etdiyinə görə çay içdikdən *sonra* Pərşan əsnəməyə başladı *(M. İbrahimov)*.

Qeyd. Məlumdur ki, qoşma hallana bilən sözlərə qoşulur və müxtəlif mənə qrupları yaradır. Axırıncı nümunədə “sonra” qoşmasından əvvəl gələn “içdikdən” sözünü feli bağlama saymaq olmaz, çünki feli bağlama hallanmır. Deməli, *içdikdən* vahidindəki şəkilçilərin bu cür sıralanması daha doğrudur: *-dik* (feli sifət) şəkilçisi + *-dən* (çıxışlıq hal şəkilçisi) + qoşma (**sonra**). Bu mühakimənin təsdiqi olaraq Q.Kazımovun elmi şərhini vermək yerinə düşər: “... Bu şəkilçi (*-dik* feli sifət şəkilçisi) substantiv planda *-dan* çıxışlıq hal şəkilçisini də qəbul edir və bu zaman *sonra* qoşmasını tələb edir. *-dıqdan sonra* strukturunun ifadə etdiyi iş icra olunub qurtardıqdan sonra şəxsi feildəki iş başlanır. Məsələn, *Müəllim məsələsində ümidi kəsildikdən sonra* Rüstəm kişi maşın-traktor stansiyasına yollandı *(M.İ.)*”. (2, səh.299)

Yeri gəlmişkən, əvvəlki nümunədə də (Mən səni *görendən bəri*) substantiv feli sifət *+-dən* (çıxışlıq hal şəkilçisi) + qoşma (*bəri*) strukturu ilə zaman məzmunu yaradılıb.

Cümlələrin hər birinin semantik yükünü müəyyənləşdirərkən məlum olur ki, qoşmaların, onların qoşulduğu sözlərin və feillərin arasında zaman baxımından çox güclü semantik bağlılıq var. Ərəb mənşəli “əvvəl” sözü qoşma kimi çıxışlıq hal şəkilçisi qəbul etmiş sözlə (bundan) birlikdə hadisənin (Koroğlu atını nallatmağa gəlmişdi) keçmiş zamana aid olduğunu bildirir. “Gəlmişdi” feli də nəqli keçmiş zamanın hekayə formasındadır. Göründüyü kimi, temporallıq həm qoşma, həm də qrammatik zaman forması ilə qovuşuq şəkildə təzahür edir.

İkinci cümlədə *kimi* qoşması yönlük halda olan zaman məzmunlu “payız” sözünə qoşularaq gələcək zaman anlayışı yaradır. Qoşmanın semantik yükünün qüvvətlənməsinə əmr şəklində olan “döz” feli təkan verir. Məlumdur ki, əmr gələcək zaman üçün verilir, baxmayaraq ki, əmr şəklində olan feillərin morfoloji əlaməti yoxdur. “Gələn” feli sifətində də gələcək zaman anlayışı hiss olunur. Bunu cümlənin semantik tutumu diktə edir. Baxmayaraq ki, *-ən* şəkilçisi indiki zaman mənalı feli sifət yaradır, ancaq cümlədəki prosesin, hadisənin gələcəyə ünvanlanması sözlərin semantik inteqrasiyasından qaynaqlanır. Onu da qeyd edək ki, qoşma istənilən sözlərə qoşulmur, çünki onları əlaqələndirən semantik yaxınlıq olmalıdır. Semantik yaxınlıq əlaqələnmə sözlərin həm daxili məzmunu, həm onların birlikdə ümumi semantikasi ilə bağlı yaranır. Verdiyimiz nümunədə biz bunun şahidi olduq. Konkret fakt kimi “payız” və “kimi” qoşmasının əlaqələnməsini nəzərdən keçirək: Bu iki sözün – leksik mənaya malik olan “payız” və yalnız qrammatik mənası olan “kimi” sözləri ümumi zaman hüdudunun meydana çıxmasını şərtləndirir. Zaman məzmunu “payız” sözünün fərdi semantikasında olsa da, zaman hüdudu yoxdur. Zaman hüdudunun yaranması “payız” zərfinə artırılan yönlük hal şəkilçisidir. Yönlük hal hərəkətin yönəldiyi şəxsi, əşyanı, hərəkətin istiqamətini, hərəkətin çatacağı son nöqtəni, zaman və məkan hüdudunu bildirir. Demək, zaman məzmunu *payız* zərfinin daxili semantikasında olsa da, zaman hüdudu qrammatik forma ilə (-a) yaransa da, *kimi* qoşmasının həmin sözlə əlaqələnməsi zaman hüdudunu daha konkret edir, onu dəqiqləşdirir.

Zaman məzmununun şəkilçiləşmiş *-mı (-mi, -mu, -mü)* ədatı ilə ifadəsi. *-mı* ədatı, əsasən, sual cümlələrinin qurulmasında istifadə edilən vasitələrdən biri kimi çıxış edir: Qardaşın gəldimi? “Bu cümlə növündə müəyyən bir əşyanın, əlamətin, hərəkətin və sairənin təsdiqi və ya inkarı soruşulur”. (3. səh. 89)

Eyni zamanda yüksək poetik siqlətli ritorik sualın yaradılmasında da iştirak edir: Yoxmudur, gülüm, səndə heç insaf? *(H.avid.)*

-mı (-mi, -mu, -mü) ədatı həmçinin tabeli mürəkkəb cümlələrdə budaq cümləni baş cümləyə bağlayan vasitə kimi çıxış edərək zaman məzmunu yaradır. Yəni zaman budaq cümləsinin bir tipi də məhz -mı⁴ ədatı ilə formalaşır. Məsələn, Bu hissələr baş qaldırdımı, onlardan qaçmağa çalışırdı (*G.Hüseynoğlu*).

Zaman məzmununun I növ təyini söz birləşməsi ilə ifadəsi: buraya I növ təyini söz birləşməsi modeli əsasında yaranan, lakin cümlə daxilində məntiqi cəhətdən ayrıl-mayan *bu vaxt, o vaxt, bu zaman, o zaman, axır zaman, bu dəm, bu an, bu saat, o gündən, bir dəfə, bir gün, bir axşam, hər gün, həməm gün* və s. kimi birləşmələr daxildir. Məsələn, *Bu vaxt* bir inilti eşitdim, zalım ovçu ox ilə maralı yaralamışdı. (*Az. əfsanələri*) Boynu bükük bənövşə *o gündən* həmişə kol dibində bitir. (*Az. əfsanələri*) Elə *bu zaman* Eyvaz dayı Bayram babama neçə gün əvvəl başına gəlmiş qəribə bir hadisə danışdı. (*İ.Əfəndiyev*) *O vaxtlar* qadının yad kişi ilə danışmağı məqbul sayılmadığı üçün Tofiq bəy anamla salamlaşmadı. (*İ.Əfəndiyev*) *O zaman* babam acıqlanıb Fatma nənəmə dedi... (*İ.Əfəndiyev*) *O vaxtdan* bənövşə xəcalətindən başını da qaldırmır, həmişə başısaşağı kola söykənir. (*Az. əfsanələri*) *Bir gün* Ağgülün budağına xallı kəpənək qonur. (*Az. xalq əfsanələri*) *Bir dəfə* Şeşən yenə də bağçada təkcə oturub həmin çiçəyə tamaşa edirmiş. (*Az. əfsanələri*) *Bir axşam* onların qapısını bir qoca döydü, bircə gecə yatmağa, dincəlməyə bir bucaq istədi. (*Az. əfsanələri*) Həyat *hər gün* mənim zehnimdə, təbiətimdə bir iz buraxaraq keçirdi. (*İ.Əfəndiyev*) Yenə də *hər axşam* eyvandakı taxtın üstündə oturub, gözünü dikirdi Yevlaxa gedən şose yoluna. (*İ.Əfəndiyev*)

Zaman anlayışının II növ təyini söz birləşməsi ilə ifadəsi. Bu cür birləşmələrin bir çoxu zaman məzmunlu isimlərin birləşməsi ilə formalaşır: *ömür boyu, yaz vaxtı, axşam vaxtı, səhər çağı, axşam çağı, günorta çağı, günorta vaxtı, yay vaxtı, şər vaxtı, azadlıq vaxtı, tənəzzül çağı, Rəsul əleyhissəlam zamanı, Nuh zamanı, Oğuz zamanı* və s. Məsələn, *Rəsul əleyhissəlam zamanına* yaqın Bayat boyundan, Qorqud ata diyerlər, bir ər qopdı ("*Kitabi- Dədə Qorqud*"). *Yaz vaxtı* yaylağa min ellər köçər, Cəfasını çəkər, suyundan içər. (*M.Azaflı*) *Ömür boyu* oldum dövrən dustağı... (*M.Azaflı*) *Tənəzzül çağında* vəfalı olsa, Qohum-qardaş gəlməz, yar gələr-gələr. (*M.Azaflı*) *Bayram qabağı*di, yaz gəldi, çatdı, illərə baxıram, gah azadlığa (*M.Azaflı*). Zindan dostluğunu *azadlıq vaxtı*, Çalanda sazımda tellər unutmaz. (*M.Azaflı*) *Könül verməzlər şər vaxtı* və s.

Verilən nümunələrdən də aydın görünür ki, zaman məzmununun II növ təyini söz birləşmələri ilə ifadəsində ümumi, nisbi zaman anlayışı üstün mövqedədir.

Zaman anlayışının III növ təyini söz birləşməsi ilə ifadəsi: *yayın ortasında, yayın əvvəli, günlərin bir günü, səhərin erkən çağında, günün ikinci yarısında, qışın oğlan çağında (məcazi mənəlidir), ayın ortasında, ilin başlanğıcında* və s. Məsələn, *Yayın ortasında* yağdırırsan qar, Səf çəkmir üstündən sərdarın, dağlar. (*A.Ələsgər*) *Yayın əvvəlində* dönürsən xana, Son ayda bənzərsən yetkin bostana... (*A.Ələsgər*)

Feli birləşmələrlə ifadə olunan zaman anlayışı: *dərs başlanarkən, gün çıxmamış, şər qarışanda, qaranlıq qovuşanda, qış gələndə, gecədən qalan, payızdan əkilmiş* və s. Temporallığın feli birləşmələrlə ifadə olunmasında zaman məzmunu yaradan feli bağlama və feli sifət şəkilçiləri əsas rol oynayır. Məsələn, Ey can, mən *camalın görünəcə* can derəm, Görsət kim, ol *camalın görsəm*, rəvan derəm. (*Ş.İ.Xətai*) *Könlüm açılır zülfi-pərişanını görgəc*. (*M.Füzuli*) Mənsiz də əmin ol, sizə rəhbərlik edən var: *Qan püskürən, atəş sovuran* kinli krallar, *Min hiylə quran* tülkü siyasilər, o hər an, *Məzhəb çıxaran, yol ayıran* xadimi-ədyan (*H.C.*). *Sizin güldüyünüz* çoban torpağı Nizamilər, Füzulilər yetirmiş. (*S.Vurğun*) *Camalın görəli* can buldum, ey can, *Yüzünü nuri-iman* buldum, ey can. (*Ş. İ. Xətai*)

-alı² şəkilçili feli bağlamalar bəzən ismi xəbərli cümlədə işlənir və hadisə, əhvalat məzmununu zamanla qovuşuq ifadə edərək cümlənin mübtədası olur. Bu məqamlar, əsasən, danışiq dilinə xasdır. Məsələn, *Rəhman evləneli* üç il idi, ancaq hələ də uşaqları olmamışdı.

Zaman anlayışının bağlayıcı sözlərlə ifadəsi: *elə ki, o zaman ki, o vaxt ki, o gün ki, o gündən ki, onda ki, haçan ki, nə qədər ki, nə zaman ki, haçan ki* və s. Bu vasitələr tabeli mürəkkəb cümlələrdə budaq cümləni baş cümləyə bağlayır. Bağlayıcı sözlərə (nisbi əvəzlilərlə) formalaşan

bu quruluş tipində budaq cümlə əvvəl, baş cümlə isə sonra gəlir. Məsələn, *O zaman ki* məni günəş salamlardı yar kimi, Çırpınardım ürəyimdə bir xəstəlik var kimi... (*S.Vurğun*) *O gün ki* parladı şahların tacı, Sən oldun bir çörək, bir haqq möhtacı. (*S.Vurğun*) *O gündən ki* gəldin bizə, Mail olduq ala gözə... (*A.Ələsgər*) *Nə qədər ki* zalım var, seyraqub ölməz. (*M.Azaflı*) *Nə vaxt ki* zəmanədən gileylənibdi, Şairin məskəni zindanlar olub. (*M.Azaflı*)

Zaman anlayışının hansı vasitələrlə yaranmağından asılı olmayaraq, nəticədə hər bir hadisə, iş, hal və hərəkət müəyyən zaman və məkan daxilində icra edilir. Bütün bu vasitələr obyektiv zamanın dildə ifadə vasitələridir.

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Language policy in European countries in the XIX-XX centuries

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The 20th century was a turning point in world and especially European politics in the society's attitude towards regional or little-used languages. At the beginning of the century, European society wanted to protect them from discrimination. The next phase was a period in which linguistic rights were sought to be realized on an equal basis since the promulgation of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights in 1948, and a sign of the third phase that began in the last decade of the 20th century. The European community emphasized the need to recognize and support the linguistic diversity and identity of peoples, and this was reflected in the adoption by European organizations of a number of documents on the protection of the rights of national minorities, including linguistic minorities. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights, promulgated by the UN in 1948, was the first important international legal document. The Declaration did not say much about languages, but it did mention that language should not be the main reason to deny someone's rights. In the following decades, this principle was developed in many other UN and UNESCO documents related to human rights and freedoms.

In Europe, there is a language minority in the vast majority of countries. These languages are called regional or lesser-used languages. In connection with the intensification of human rights protection processes, along with all other basic human rights and freedom protection issues, the problems of supporting a person's language rights also become relevant. In the second half of the 20th century, European sociolinguists paid much attention to the issues of language policy and language planning. During this period, scientific interest in bilingual and multilingual phenomena increased.

Legal, economic, socio-cultural and psychological factors influencing the language situation are investigated. The results of the joint work of scientists and politicians are laws and other documents regulating language relations in individual multinational countries of the European continent, as well as conventions and agreements with a common European status.

One of the reasons for the remarkable progress and positive results achieved in language planning based on democratic principles in Europe is the broad scientific sociolinguistic base available in most European countries. One of the most important scientific works on this subject is "Bilingualism" (Bilingualism), published in English by S. Romein in Oxford. The book deals with the most common problems in both linguistic, sociolinguistic, and psycholinguistic aspects. The author gives his definition to the concept of mother tongue, which finds various interpretations in modern sociolinguistics. The author considers the native language to be the language that the speaker knows best.

Analyzing the situation of linguistics in Europe, S. Romeyn calls the oppression of the linguistic rights of the national minorities in the states internal colonialism, and the linguistic minorities themselves the fourth world. The author separately examines the psychological side of bilingualism, its connection with the mind, and the interaction of two languages in the human mind.

In the collection of articles "Language in politics - politics in language" published in German in 1990, a number of sociolinguistic problems devoted to language policy, research on the languages of national minorities and political negotiations were investigated.

In his article, R.Vodak examines the problem of the state language and analyzes it in terms of its megaphoric and theological origins. Therefore, the language of the state, like almost all the concepts of the theory of the state, appears from the point of view of the secondary theological concept of political theology.

In the collection, a lot of attention is paid to the problems of national minorities in Austria, in the example of Carinthia, one of the lands of the Republic of Austria. In his article "Language of mortal enemies: language and ethnic oppression in the example of the Carinthian Slovenes", V. Vakouning sees the reason for the national tension in Carinthia in the use of language as "a tool to rank people".

The author attributes the division of Carinthian words between German and Slovenian speakers to their opposition to each other, as the former shows loyalty to Carinthia and Austria more broadly, and the latter to Yugoslavia. As a result, this leads to people not wanting to be included in the "enemies of Carinthia" group. Another reason for the disappearance of the Slovene language is related to the desire of its learning process, as well as insufficient development of the sense of self-awareness.

As an example of the sociolinguistic approach to the study of language legislation in foreign countries, the book "French language and European integration" (1991) by R. Haas can be cited. The author emphasized that this work is relevant not only for France, but also for other European countries. To fully understand modern French law, the author suggests an excursion into history. Already in the 16th century, King Francis I decreed the use of French instead of Latin in court and office work.

The further expansion of the functions of the French language allowed it to take an equal position with the Latin language in all areas of linguistic activity until the end of the 17th century. At the end of the 18th century, the next stage in French language policy begins. Thus, Talleyran shows that it is necessary to learn the language in which the laws are written, and the dialects spoken by more than 20% of the population, mainly in rural areas, are remnants of the feudal system, and it is time to eliminate them.

The main document defining the language policy of modern France is the law "On the use of the French language" of December 31, 1975, which strictly regulates and defines the use of French terms in the design and manuals for the operation of foreign equipment when advertising foreign-made goods and various types of services.

The language situation in modern France is characterized by the fact that citizens of the French state use the French language without exception in all spheres of life. In addition, it should be noted that one third of the country's population is bilingual, that is, they speak the language of the national minorities living in France (Occitan, Catalan, Basque, Breton, Flemish, German and Italian). Since 1951, it has been possible to study regional languages only in the process of learning.

The author examines the general characteristics of the language policy implemented in France in relation to the French language, the state language of France, and the means of increasing its influence in the international world.

He also paid great attention to the language problems between the 1960s and 1980s, characterized by the decline in the prestige of the French language due to the process of anglicization, as well as the "Language Act" (1994). In the book "Minority languages in the modern world: Caucasian languages" (2002) by Z. M. Gabuniya and R. Tirado Gusman, the authors analyze the linguistic situation with the minority languages of the Caucasus, examine the historical experience of learning and teaching these languages, and examine the relationship between minority languages in this region. They emphasize the current linguistic situation. In the book, the linguistic problems of the language are investigated in a certain typological classification of Caucasian languages. Additionally, the book includes excerpts from language laws and some provisions of the European Charter for Regional and Minority Languages.

One of the most relevant contemporary publications is a 2006 collection of essays by the Irish sociolinguist Donal O'Reagan in English entitled *Diverse Voices: Education in Europe's Lesser Languages*. The book contains materials on the development of education in minority and regional languages in different countries and regions of Europe: the Basque Country, Hungary, Estonia, Malta, Slovenia, etc. Russia was represented in this collection by reports of scientists from Kalmykia, Khakassia and Tatarstan. In 2006, a book called "Report on World Languages" was published in English. Articles and reports on the state of all world languages are included here.

This publication is the fruit of the UNESCO project of the same name, which started in 1998. The main purpose of the report is to provide a complete documentary description of the sociolinguistic situation related to the languages that exist in the world in order to create a foundation for the world language heritage.

Spain belongs to the so-called "constituent states" category. Through this concept, the states whose constitution stipulates the territorial division of political power are determined. In more common terminology, these states are called "federal states", although other options are possible. It is also known that the political form of Spain is called by the phrase "state of autonomies". In 1984, Spain became a member of the European Union.

Spain's government system is a constitutional monarchy. Administratively, Spain is divided into 52 provinces united in 17 provinces, and these regions mainly solve their own development issues. Each region has its own parliament and government. Now let's consider the ways of applying the national languages of some regions of Spain and more specifically of Catalonia and the Basque Country.

Catalonia is an autonomous region occupying a significant part of the Iberian Peninsula in the north-east of the Spanish state and the border between Spain and France. The capital of Catalonia is Barcelona. Catalonia has about 7 million inhabitants. The Spanish Constitution defines it as a "nation" within the Spanish nation. However, most Catalans consider it a nation within multi-ethnic Spain. Catalan belongs to the Neo-Romance group of languages, like Spanish, French and Italian.

The choice and development of the Catalan language was directly related to the formation of the Catalan people as an independent ethnic community, which in turn was connected to the historical processes taking place in that region.

Immediately after the Arab invasion in the 8th century, Northern Catalonia (Catalunya Vella) was conquered by the Franks, who gave their new province extensive self-governing rights. Already in the 19th century, during the fall of Charlemagne's empire, Catalonia finally broke away from it as an independent county of Barcelona. The definitive historical isolation of Catalonia from the rest of Spain, a very long and significant cultural and especially linguistic influence from France, at the same time the early and quickly achieved state-legal independence of the region developed at this stage, the formation of linguistic, cultural and national psychological characteristics and the new led to the emergence of a natural process for the formation of an ethnos.

In the 13th century, the Catalan language was already fully developed as an independent language unit. At the same time, the kingdom of Balearic and Valencia, whose population spoke only Arabic at that time, was conquered by the kings of Catalonia. As a result of the resettlement policy and other measures, the Catalan language in these regions completely replaced the Arabic language in all spheres of social life in a short period of time. Later, on its basis, an independent language - the Valencian language - was formed in the territory of Valencia, which is close to the Catalan language in terms of its structure and phonetic features.

After Catalonia became part of the Spanish kingdom, the Catalan language continued to develop. At the beginning of the 20th century, the modern literary Catalan language was already fully formed. At the level of spoken speech, a number of dialects of the Catalan language have developed.

During the Spanish Civil War of 1936-38, Catalonia experienced an explosive development of mass national identity among the population. Thanks to the idea of creating a federal state and recognizing the rights of national minorities, including their right to self-determination, announced by the republican government, Catalonia has become one of the main strongholds of the republicans.

After the defeat of the Republic, the use of the Catalan language was completely banned in all spheres of public life, including education, office work and the media. The situation changed only in the late 70s, with the beginning of democratic restoration after the death of Franco.

Now let's consider the main features of the language situation in other regions of Spain.

Galicia is characterized by the widespread use of the Spanish language in large cities. This linguistic advantage is explained by the similarity of the two state languages and the historically established superiority of the Castilian language over the Galician language. Castilian has a greater dominance over regional languages in Aragon. It is used by 95% of the population. The remaining inhabitants speak both Aragonese and Catalan.

Aragonese is spoken only in the foothills of the Pyrenees, the total number of speakers does not exceed 30 thousand out of two million ethnic Aragonese. Another autonomy for the Spanish state is Asturias, the only autonomous community outside of Catalonia to adopt a new language law at the end of the 20th century.

The Asturian Language Law of 1998 actually completely regulates the position of the local language. The language situation here is similar to that in Arayun. However, the complexity of the situation is that despite the fact that Catalan is recognized by most linguists as a separate language, many specialists do not want to recognize the existence of a separate Asturian language, Babel. Its similarity to Castilian suggests that Babylonian is a dialect of Castilian. This is confirmed by the majority of Asturias residents.

The Asturian Language Law is quite lenient, especially with regard to studying Babel, which is considered the local language. This allows us to think that the Asturian language does not have a full official status. The Balearic Islands, like Valencia, are regions where the Catalan language is spoken.

Ireland, or the Republic of Ireland, occupies most (83%) of the island of Ireland, located in the Atlantic Ocean. Part of the island - North

Ireland belongs to Great Britain. The capital of Ireland is Dublin. The population of the country is about 4 million. Ireland joined the European Union in 1973. The Irish experience is especially valuable for the regions of the Russian Federation, because the language situation in this country is in many ways similar to the situation in the republics of the Russian Federation. This also applies to the historical conditions for the development of language problems and the situation at the present stage. The official languages of Ireland are English and Irish.

The history of the colonization of Ireland by the English begins in the 12th century. In 1169, the first Anglo-Norman feudal lords appeared in Ireland and formed an English colony here. Over the next two centuries, English colonists appropriated approximately 85 percent of all Irish land. Since the end of the 17th century, there have been regular Irish uprisings in the country, which were brutally suppressed by the British government. Another serious tragedy in Ireland was the famine in 1847-1851 due to the shortage of the potato crop, which was the main food of the peasants. Since the middle of the 19th century, Ireland's population has steadily declined for a hundred years.

In 1845, over 8 million people lived in Ireland. During the Great Famine, about a million people died of hunger, and millions of people fled to America, Canada, Australia and other countries. The mass exodus of desperate people continued not only because of famine, but also because of the centuries of oppression the Irish had suffered in their own country. By 1911, the

country's population had dropped to 4 million and continued to decline until 1961. In 1916, riots started in Ireland, which were suppressed like the previous ones. However, the Irish Republican Army started a guerrilla war, and under the pressure of this movement, in 1921, England and Ireland signed a bilateral agreement, Ireland was declared a free state, but Ireland only received the status of a dominion (dominion). However, the six counties with the most developed industry remained in the United Kingdom of Great Britain. Northern Ireland is still part of England today.

In 1937, a new constitution was adopted, according to which the former dominion became a sovereign state with only nominal ties to Great Britain.

In 1949, Ireland was declared an independent republic. It was announced that he was leaving the British Commonwealth. Until now, relations with Great Britain have deteriorated from time to time due to problems in Northern Ireland. Starting in the 1960s, Ireland changed its attitude towards Northern Ireland.

The Republic of Ireland continued to insist on unification, but gradually began to accept that this would require diplomatic steps rather than firm demands and ultimatums. After a series of agreements, Ireland and Great Britain resolved the issue of Northern Ireland. In 1998, a referendum in Ireland removed the claim that Northern Ireland was part of Irish territory from the constitution.

In the 60s of the 20th century, Ireland experienced an economic boom, and during the 1990s and 2000s, there was qualitative economic progress. As a result of reforms in the field of economy, taxation, education, Ireland took a leading position among the most developed countries in Europe. In two decades, the unemployment rate fell nearly tenfold, and in 2000, Ireland's GDP growth was 20% higher than the EU average. A special role in the modernization of Ireland was played by the education policy aimed at the formation of highly qualified young personnel in the most promising high-tech fields. As a result of this policy, in terms of the level of scientific and technical education in the 25-34 age group, Ireland came out on top among the 25 most developed countries in the world.

The process of mass emigration in Ireland, which lasted for many years, stopped and the migration of the labor force back to Ireland began. A cursory glance at some of the facts of Irish history and its present state is necessary for a fuller picture of this European country and a more complete analysis of the language situation. Along with Gaelic of Scotland and the dead language of the Isle of Man, Irish forms the Celtic languages of the Goidel group, which in turn belongs to the western branch of the Indo-European language family.

Despite the colonization and oppression of Ireland, the Irish language remained the language of the masses in the 19th century. Until 1800, English was the main language of the settlements in and around Dublin. Although the Irish language was mainly spoken in Ireland until the 1840s, signs of the decline of the Irish language were already visible. At this time, the emerging Irish Catholic bourgeoisie began to speak English to demonstrate their loyalty to the ruling country. From this point of view, a new attitude was born: English speakers were respected, and at the same time, speaking this language promised prospects for advancement in the social ladder. Irish became the language of the poor, the illiterate and the politically insecure. During this period, a system of free public education was developed, teaching was possible only in English. In particular, many Irish families supported the government's policy of learning English and forgetting Irish in the interests of their children. By 1890, the Irish language was in deep decline and became the language of poor, almost uneducated people living in remote areas where the influence of English had not yet been felt.

The revival of the Irish language began in Dublin in 1883, when the Gaelic League was founded. His mission was to preserve the Irish language and promote the overall development of Irish culture. The new organization was not political. The Gaelic League, contrary to all expectations, was created to show respect for the Irish people, their language, culture and history,

and became a mass organization carrying out educational work in this field. In a short time, this organization received the support of the whole society. He organized Irish language classes around the country and also designed and implemented cultural events and campaigns to support and promote the language. Although the Gaelic League did not succeed in halting the decline in Irish language acquisition, it did succeed in raising a new generation of highly educated urban youth who took Irish as their second language.

АБАЙ ШЫҒАРМАШЫЛЫҒЫНЫҢ АЛТЫН ҚАЗЫҒЫ: АДАМДЫ СҮЮ

Анар Салқынбай

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Жалғамалылық табиғатына сай, түбірі өзгеріске аз ұшырағандықтан, түркі түбірлері өзінің қалпы мен мағыналық құрылымын өзге тілдермен салыстырғанда анағұрлым жақсы және анық сақтаған. Сондықтан да болар, тілде сақталған әр түбірде мұрағаттық сипат бар. Тек оны ашудың тәсілі мен амалын таба білуге білім мен білік қажет. Сөз тарихы Сізді мыңдаған жылдар тарихына үнсіз жетелейді, сөз болмысын тану ұлт болмысын танудың тылсымына әкеледі. Тек жетекке еруге білім мен төзім болса жеткілікті. Тілде адамның ішкі сезім дүниесі, іңкәрлігі, жалпы болмысы жатыр. Ал оның ар жағында халықтық дүниетаным жатады. Сонда бір өлең арқылы алдымен сөзбен, сөз тіркестерімен берілетін ой желісімен танысамы. Сөз мағынасы арқылы оның тарихын барлаймыз. Сөз арқылы ақынның немесе жеке адамның тұлғасын, ішкі жан дүниесі мен болмысын, жүрек сезімінің куәсі боламыз да, осының негізінде ақынның артында тұрған ұлттың, елдің, халықтың бейнесін көріп, дүниетанымымен табысамыз. Сөз құдіретіне бас иген, бір ауыз сөзбен ердің құнын шешкен бабалар неткен көреген еді, десеңші!

Тіл тек дыбыстардың жиынтығы немесе адам қызметінің көрінісі ғана емес. Тіл сөйлейді, сөзбен сыр айтады, тарихты шежірелейді, сезімді паш етеді, ел мен ел, ер мен ер арасындағы жанған дұшпандық отты сөндіреді, жаныңа шуақ төгеді, көзіңнен жас мөлдіретеді, жүрегіңді «жуады» (Шаһкәрім), нұрландырады.

Ал данышпандардың жүрегін жарып шыққан поэзиядағы сөздің құдіреті тіпті ерен. Абайдың бір өлеңі «Жүректе қайрат болмаса» деп аталады. Жүрек пен қайрат ұғымдарын қатар қою арқылы олардың бағасын таразылап, бағалап, танытып, пәлсапалық ой түйіп қана қоймайды ақын. Қазақи шындықтың қатып қалған қабаттарын ашып үңілтеді, жүрегіндегі шерін ақтарады. Шындықтың бетіне тура қарайды. Қорықпайды. Өйткені ол шындықтың артында елдің болашағы, келешектің үміті мен үлесі жатыр. Өлең астарында ұйықтаған ойды түрту бар. Ойы ұйықтап жатқан кім еді? Неліктен ұйықтап жатыр ол ой? деген сұрақтар қаумалай алға шығады. Ұйқының басуы білімнің жоқтығынан, сол – надандыққа итеретін. Ұйқыдағы ойды түртетін қайрат пен ақыл, ал ақылға сәуле түсуі қажет.

Адамзаттық ақыл-ой бір арнада тоғысары анық – ол адам болмысының ізгілікпен өрілуі. Қазақ ойшылы Абай шығармаларының да алтын қазығы - Адам, адам бойындағы ізгілікке жетер жол. Ойшыл жасаған «толық адам» концепциясының басты құндылығы - жаратушы Алланы сүю, адамзатты сүю деген ұстанымдарда жатса керек. Ал мұндай ұстанымға жетудің жолы – ізгіліктің жолы. «Атымды Адам қойған соң, қайтып надан болайын», «Адамды сүй, алланың хикметін сез, не қызық бар өмірде одан басқа» дейтін ұлы ойшыл сөздерін терең зерделеу қажет.

Абайдың «Әуелі бір суық мұз – ақыл зерек» өлеңінде:

«Ақыл, қайрат, жүректі бірдей ұста,

Сонда толық боларсың елден бөлек» – деген ой тастайды.

«Үш – ақ нәрсе адамның қасиеті: ыстық қайрат, нұрлы ақыл, жылы жүрек» деп толық адамның қасиеттерін нақты талдап көрсетеді. «Адамзатты сүю – хақтың жолы, ғаділеттің жолы». Ойшыл ақын адамды атаның емес, адамның баласы болуға насихаттайды. «Әкенің баласы – адамның дұшпаны, адамның баласы – бауырыңды» ғибрат етеді.

Ия, Абай дүниетанымындағы адами қасиеттің басты үлгісі – «ыстық қайрат, нұрлы ақыл, жылы жүрек». М. Әуезов-суреткер былай деп жазған екен: «Абай сөзінің негізін адамгершілікке тірейді. Барлық өсиет ой-толғау еңбектерінің қорытындысы тағы да адамгершілік тәрбие екенін танытады. Адамды қор қылатын ең залалды жаманшылықтарды санап өтеді. Олар үш нәрсе: «надандық, еріншектік, залымдық» [1; 36].

Авторлық бағалаудағы данышпандық таңдау: «Адамды сүю, Алланың хикметін сезу». Сөздердің орынды қолданысы, етістіктердің мағыналық құрылымының түзілген ойдың мағынасын тиянақты бейнелеуі үлкен таланттың ғана емес, дананың ғана қолынан келетін өрнек екенін түсінесіз, мойындайсыз, таңданасыз. Қуанасыз! Бағалайсыз! Қуанатын себебіңіз – қазақи дүниетаныммен, қазақи түсінікте, қазақ тілінде жасалып жатқан адами құндылықты көріп, тамашалап, риясыз көңілден туған ризалық сезімнің сыртқа шығуынан.

*Адамды сүй, Алланың хикметін сез,
Не қызық бар өмірде онан басқа?!*

Өлең мәтінінің тұжырымы – осы. Бұл жастарға, балаларға арналмаған, көзі көп нәрсеге ашылған, талай жасқа келгендерге арналып айтылған. «Адамды сүю, «Алланың хикметін сезу» деген тіркестердегі «сүю», «сезу» етістіктерінің терең мағыналық құрылымы мен сөз тіркесінің беретін мағынасының арасындағы семантикалық байланыс соншалықты нақты, анық, сәтті. «Адамды сүюден» артық адам баласының қолынан келетін бір жақсылық бар ма? Барлық адамның қолынан келетін жақсылық атаулының негізгісі – сүюден басталып, сүюмен тұйықталмай ма?! Адамды сүю – жақсылық қасиет атаулының басында тұратын тегеріштей. Сүю бар жерде жамандық атаулыға орын жоқ. «Сүю» жалған болса, оның жанынан «қызғаныш» атты қызыл ит қалмай ілеседі де, өзге жаманшылықтарды ілестіре әкеліп өзінше салтанат құрады. Онда «сенімге» орын қалмайды да, сорлайды. Ал «Алланың хикметін сез» тіркесіндегі «сезу» етістігінің келуінің де семантикалық мағынасы ерекше. Алланың хикметін сезу арқылы тіршіліктің мәні туралы түсінігіңіздің өзгеретіні өлеңде анық көрініс тапқан.

Өлең мәтініндегі бағалаудың шындық болмыспен, адами кейіп-болмысымен сәйкес келуі – объективтіліктің көрінісі мен субъектік көзқарастың нақты бейнеленуінен. Бұл тағы да адами болмыстың ағымдағы нақты жағдайына негізделуінен. «Адам - бір боқ көтерген боқтың қабы, Боқтан сасық боласың өлсең тағы». Адамның жағдайы осылай, бұл – пенденің физиологиялық ағзасына қатысты; «Мені мен сен тең бе деп мақтанасың, Білімсіздік белгісі - ол баяғы» - адамның психологиялық жағдайы. Тіршіліктің қоңыр күйін тыңдай жүріп, адам баласы кіммен араласпайды, көріспейді, әңгімелесіп сырласпайды дейсіз! Сірә, мақтанбайтын, мақтана алмайтын бір қазақ баласын көрмедім. Абай данышпан қателеспеген, бұл ұлттық ділге еніп кеткен бір пенделік қасиет. Мақтанып, мен далаға қараймын, мақтанып қалаға қараймын, мақтанып зәулім үй саламын, мақтаныш тұтып мешіт саламын, мақтанып ... мақтанамын...

Ия, ендеше, Абай данышпан айтып отырған сөзде жалғандық бар ма, немесе бұл маған қатыссыз деп айта аласыз ба? Бағалаудың басты мазмұнын анықтайтын критерий - күнделікті болған жағдаят пен шындық әрекетке негізделуі. Енді бағалаудың қорытындысы немесе нәтижесіне тағы назар аударалық:

*Адамды сүй, Алланың хикметін сез,
Не қызық бар өмірде онан басқа?!*

Абай бағалауындағы байлам осы. Таңдау адам баласының пайдасын көздейді. Өлең мәтініне терең бойлап, сүңгіп қарау қажет. Біздіңше, мұнда эпистемологиялы рационалдық бар. Эпистемологиялы рационалдық адам санасында әлем бейнесі мен әлемнің өзінің арасындағы байланысты жақындата түседі, нығайтады. Ақын тұжырымы ілімдік мәнге ие. «Не қызық бар өмірде онан басқа?!» деу арқылы ақын өз тұжырымын, өз байламын түйіп айтады, түйіндеп айтады, өйткені бұл тұжырым ілімге, білімге, тәжірибеге негізделген.

Рационалды ойлау арқылы адам өз өмірінде қателікке бой алдырмас еді, айналадағы шындықты орнықты да тиянақты танып, біліп, қабылдап, жағдайды дұрыс анықтаған адам ғана оң ойлап, дұрыс шолып, нақты тұжырым жасай біледі. Абай бағалауында екі ұштылық, дүдәмалдық жоқ. Ойды тиянақтап тұратын предикаттық тұлғалар өздерінің көпмағыналық сипатына қарамастан, мәтінде нақты мағына иеленіп, бір ғана тиянақты ойды таңбалайды. Адамды сүй, алланың хикметін сез, Не қызық бар өмірде онан басқа?! – деген сөйлемдегі «сүй», «сез», «бар» предикаттық тұлғаларының мағыналық құрылымы осы контексте дара мағынасында нақты қолданылған, бұл тіркестегі тұлғаларды екіұшты түсінуге немесе прагматикалық мағынасын басқаша қарап түсіндіру мүмкін болмайды.

Бағалаудың мәнін анықтап, нақтылап тұрған предикаттар негізгі прагматикалық мағынаның қасиетін көрсетеді. Абай көрсеткен адами болмыс шындыққа сәйкес, қолданылған тұлғалардың прагматикалық мағыналары қоғамдағы адамдарға толық түсінікті, әрі олардың әлем болмысы жайындағы дүниетанымымен, өмір туралы көзқарастарымен жақын. Бұлай деуіміздің мәнісі Алланың хикметін сезу мен адамды сүю туралы айтылған толғамды ой тек Абайдан ғана басталмағаны, шығыстық даналықты былай қойғанда, қазақи дүниетаным қалыптастырған әфсаналардан бастап, қазақ мақал-мәтелдері, ақын-жыраулардың шығармалары осындай ойды, осындай бағалауды айтып келе жатқаны, жырлап келгені аян. Абай жаңалығы - Абайша жаңа бағалауында, яғни бұрынғы айтылған білімді, жасалған тілдік тәжірибе мен ойлау жүйесіндегі шұрайлы талғамды сіңіре отырып, жаңа мазмұнда, ерекше формада, жаңа нәтижелермен жеткізуінде. Танымдық тәжірибе негізге алынып, уәжделіп, жаңа сапада халық игілігіне ұсынылуында. Мәтіндегі ойды мүлде жаңа деп айта алмайтынымыз анық, алайда Абайлық бағалаудың маңыздылығы – анықтығында, нақтылығында.

«Алланың өзі де рас, сөзі де рас» өлеңіндегі үш сүю: бірінші сүю — Алланың адамзатты сүюі (махаббатпен жаратқан адамзатты), екіншісі — адамның Алланы сүюі (сен де сүй ол Алланы жаннан тәтті), үшіншісі — адамның адамзатты сүюі (адамзаттың бәрін сүй, бауырым деп).

Кей ғалымдар үш сүюдің сипатын бұдан өзгеше таратады: бірінші - адамның Алланы сүюі, екіншісі - адамның адамзатты сүюі, үшіншісі - адамның әділетті сүюі.

Екі пікірдің қайсысы дұрыс не бұрыс деп пікір тарқатудан әзір аулақпыз.

Талас туғызатын бірінші және төртінші жолдар. Бұл жеке ғалымның Абай сөзінің мәнін өзінше түсінуі деп пайымдайық.

Абай өлеңдеріндегі «адам өмірі», «адам өмірінің мәні» сияқты мәселелердің талдауын ХХ ғасырда Еуропада қалыптасқан экзистенциализм қағидаларына жақын деп қарастыруға негіз бар. Экзистенциализм - адамның өзіндік «Менін» тануы, өмір мен өлімнің мәні, еркіндіктің мағынасы, адамгершілік, рақымдылық, сұлулық, әділеттілік пен ақиқат, адамның дүниеге келудегі мақсаты, қоғамдағы орны сияқты көптеген философиялық мәселелерді шешуге ұмтылса, бағамдаған кісіге осы сұрақтардың көпшілігі Абай шығармашылығында өзіндік орын алған. Экзистенциализм бағыты өкілдерінің көзқарасы бойынша: өзіндік Менін түйсіну және өзгемен санасу адамды саналы әрекетке жетелейді. Данышпан Абай *«Ақылды қара қылды қырыққа бөлмек, Әр нәрсеге өзіндей баға бермек»* деу арқылы өзін бағалау мен өзгені бағалаудың мәнін, өзгені өзіндей бағалаудың адами артықшылығын, ақылды жанның ісі екенін ерекше көрсетеді. Абай ұлылығы сонда: ол тек өз руының, өз ұлтының жыртысын жыртып, «мен мықтымынға» ешқашан салынбаған.

«Адамзаттың бәрін сүйді» Абайдай айтқан әлемде тағы кім бар екен?

Мүмкін бар болар.

Менің білетінім - Абай.

Демек, осындай ұлық мінез көрсеткен, кісіліктің келбетін, бүтін бітімдік қасиетке жетіп, толық адам болған Абайдай данышпанды әлемдік деңгейде бағалауымыз орынды. Енді отыз

сегізінші Қара сөзінен шағын үзінді тыңдаңыз: *«Күллі адам баласын қор қылатын үш нәрсе бар. Сонан қашпақ керек: әуелі - надандық, екіншісі - еріншектік, үшінші - залымдық деп білесің. Надандық - білім-ғылымның жоқтығы, дүниеде ешбір нәрсені оларсыз біліп болмайды. Білімсіздік хайуандық болады. Еріншектік - күллі дүниедегі өнердің дұшпаны. Талапсыздық, жігерсіздік, ұятсыздық, кедейлік - бәрі осыдан шығады. Залымдық - адам баласының дұшпаны. Адам баласына дұшпан болса, адамнан бөлінеді, бір жыртқыш хайуан қисабына қосылады. Бұлардың емі, халқына махаббат, халық ғаламға шапқат, қайратты, тұрлаулы, ғадалат ісінің алды-артын байқарлық білімі, ғылымы болсын... Ол білім, ғылымы құдаға мұқтәди болсын. Ғылым әуелі ғалами ғылымға мұқтәди болсын. Яғни құдай тағала бұл ғаламды жаратты, ерінбеді, келісімменен, хикметпенен кәмәлатты бір жолға салып жасады, сіздердің ісіңіз де бір жақсылық бина қылып, арқа сүйерлік шеберлікпенен болсын. Және құдай тағала әрне жаратты, бір түрлі пайдалы хикметі бар. Сенің де ісіңнен бір зарар шығып кеткендей болмай, көпке пайда боларлық бір үміті бар іс болсын. Бұларсыз іс іс емес. Балки, бұларсыз тағат тағат та емес».*

Ақылды адамның ақылдылығы өзіне қажеттіні алумен, табумен емес, өзгені өзіндей бағалауымен өлшенеді. Экзистенциалистер де адамгершілік құндылықтарға бет бұруды өздерінің басты ерекшелігі деп танығаны белгілі. Абай көрсеткен адам баласын қор қылатын нәрселер экзистенциализмнің негізгі өкілдерін идеялық қолдаушылар саналатын Ф. Шеллинг, С. Кьеркогор, А. Шопенгауэр, Ф.М. Достоевский, Ф. Ницше сынды жазушылар мен ғалымдардың зерттеулері мен көркем шығармаларының негізі болған еді. Адамгершілік құндылықтарды адам тіршілігінің баянсыздығы тұрғысынан қарастыру басты тақырыпқа айналған бұл еңбектерді Абай шығармаларымен салыстыру көп нәтиже бермек. Алайда экзистенциализмнің барлық қағидалары Абай қолтаңбасына тән деуден аулақпыз, адам жаны, өзекмәнді іздеудегі негізгі қисындар арасында жақындық бар екенін айтпақпыз, өйткені ақын мақсаты адамды уайымға салып, күйзеліске ұшырату емес, қысқа өмірді мәнді өткізуге қозғау салу, ойландыру, іс-әрекетке жетелеу, надандықтан арылып, адамдық қалыпқа ұмтылдыру, толық адамдыққа жетуге талаптандыру. Абай болмыс мәселесін талдауда ғылыми танымға үлкен көңіл бөлген. *«Қашан бір бала ғылым, білімді махаббатпенен көксерлік болса, сонда ғана оның аты адам болады. Сонан соң ғана алла тағаланы танымақтық, өзін танымақтық, дүниені танымақтық, өз адамдығын бұзбай ғана жәліб мәнфағат дәфғы мұзарратларны айырмақтық секілді ғылым-білімді үйренсе, білер деп үміт қылмаққа болады»* деп жазады Қара сөзінде.

«Ғылым таппай мақтанба» тақырыбын кеңінен талдап жазған да Абай еді. Хайдеггер адам болмысының негізгі сипаттамаларын талдай отырып, әлемде өмір сүру таным акциясының, заттармен әрекет жасаудың іске асуы ғана емес, әлемнің өзі таңдау жасау мен мүмкіншілік, тағдырдың орны мен тарихи жүзеге асуы өтетін нәрсе екенін ерекше ескертеді.

Ғ. Есім «Хаким Абай» атты мақаласында: «Поэт стремится определить свое место в этой жизни. Со стороны может показаться, что он не разочарован в жизни, но рассуждая о ее бренности, поэт пишет: «Яд и ад во мне – пусть я с виду иной. В жизни мало успев, кончу путь земной». Эти мысли сходны с рассуждениям западно-европейских экзистенциалистов. Хорошо это или плохо, осуждать нам поэта или восхвалять? Думаю, ни то, ни другое. Ведь суть наших размышлений – в мировоззрении Абая, и эти мысли ценны самой постановкой проблемы – смотреть на мир глазами поэта и посредством этого познать, понять его» деп жазады [8].

Сонымен, «адами фактор», «адам өмірінің мәні» мәселесінің мазмұны күрделі, мәні терең. Тіл білімінде «әлем бейнесі», «әлем суреті», «әлем моделі», «әлемнің тілдік бейнесі», «әлемнің концептуалды бейнесі», «әлемнің когнитивті бейнесі» деген ұғымдарды туғызған бұл бағыт терең зерделеуді қажет ететін өзекті ғылыми мәселенің бірі санатында. Абай шығармаларындағы бағалау концептін таразылау барысында әлемнің тілдік бейнесінің

көріністерін анықтау арқылы халықтық бағалау жүйесін де саралауға, шамалауға толық негіз бар.

Біздіңше, әркім-ақ, өз заманының жыршысы, жаршысы бола алады. Заманында көргенін, білгенін түйіндеп жазу жай тарихшының да қолынан келмек іс. Ал Абай жазған ақиық ой, ақиқат шындық тек сол замандікі ғана ма? Тек кешегі XIX ғасыр ортасы мен XX ғасыр басында өмір сүрген біз бен сіздің ата-бабаларымыздың уағында «Ар ойлайтын адам азайып, пайда ойлайтын сабырсыз, арсыз, көрсеқызар, жалмауыз жандар шықты. Сырттансымақ, құсынбақ, өршілденбек бұлардың ажарын ашатын көрікке айналды. Алашқа сыртынан күліп, ішінде жаулық сақтады, жақынын тіріде аңдып, өлсе өкіріп жылайтын әдет тапты. Терін сатпай, телміріп көзін сатып, теп-тегіс аларман болды. Ұрлықпен мал табатын, егессе ауыл шабатын құдай атқандар, бойы бұлғаң, сөзі жылмаңдар, басында ми жоқ, өзінде ой жоқ, күлкішіл кердең надандар қатар түзеді ...» ме? («Абай Адам мен заман туралы», 23 ақпан, 2012 жыл, Абай институты сайтынан). Осыншама «жамандық» тараған ел арасынан Абай мен Шаһкәрім, Мәшһүр Жүсіп пен Дулат, Бөлтірік пен Сүйінбай, солардың ізін баса Әуезовтер мен Жамбыл бабалар қалай шықты екен? Абай өз заманының ғана жыршысы болса, «Адамзаттың бәрін сүй, бауырым деп» деген үн-ұранды айтар ма еді? Пайда ойламай, ар ойлау сол заман үшін ғана қажет болды ма?

Абай өз заманының ғана емес, заманалардан асып туған, бір елдің емес, адамзаттың Абайы болған ғұлама. Абай айтқан әлгіндегі ғалымдар санамалаған надандық қай елдің баласында жоқ екен? Немесе қай елдің баласы надандықтан арылып, барлығы толық адам деңгейіне жетіпті. Ел болған соң, оның ішінде еркесі де, серкесі де, тоғышары да, ақылдысы да, наданы да болатыны тіршіліктің өз заңдылығы емес пе? Яғни, Абай данышпан тек қазақ қоғамын айтып отыр деу бекершілік. Ия, негізгі дереккөз қазақ ортасы, қазақ болмысы екені анық. Алайда бұл қасиет адам баласына түгел ортақ қасиет десек қателесеміз бе? Адамзаттық мәселені көтерген ұлы Абайдай данышпанды өз көкжиегінен көру, өз деңгейінде бағалау қажет. Ол жүрек бірді емес, миллиондарды сүйіп, «мыңмен жалғыз алысты», «адамзаттың бәрін сүйуге» шақырды.

«Распенен таласпа мү'мин болсаң,

Ойла, айттым, адамдық, атын жойма!» - дейді ғой Абай.

Адамзатқа сөз арнаған Абайдай данышпан бір рудың немесе бір елдің жоғын жоқтап, өзгелердің бәрін қаралап сөз арнады деу – надандық болар еді. Абай заманында сыналған жандар, қазір жоқ деуге келмес, олар қай заманаларда да болған, бар, бола бермек. Бұл қарама-қарсылықтың бірлігі мен күресі дейтұғын диалектика заңдылығына сыятын, адам баласының пешенесіне жазылған тіршілік-ғұмырдағы тағдыры. Адамдық пен надандықтың тартысы әлмисақтан бері келе жатыр, тартыс жүре бермек. Қызғаныш, бәсекелесу Адам атаның бел баласынан бастап, бүкіл ұрпағына мирас етілді, бұл да даму үшін болатын қажеттілік, бәлкім.

Өйткені табиғаттың өзі Алланың жаратқан сұлулығы. Одан артық сұлулықты адам баласы қолымен жасамақ емес. Абайдың қарапайымдылығы мен ұлылығы сол – ол әлем болмысын сол қалпында кестелі сөзбен өрнектегені. Ештеңені әсірелемей, «әсемпаз» болмай, өнерпаз болған. Нағыз суреткер табиғатты өз қалпында өзгеріссіз, авторлық интенциямен беру арқылы өзінің хас шеберлігін де танытқан. Өлеңдегі етістіктің көп кездесуінің мәнісі – табиғи көріністі өзінің ішкі қозғалысында бұзбай көрсету, шын сұлулықты асырып айту емес, өйткені ол мүмкін емес, өз бояуымен, өзінің қозғалыстағы әрекетін таныту арқылы беру. Авторлық кредо «әсемпаздық» емес, өнерпаздық.

Поэтикалық лебіз логикалық терең байланысқа құрылған. Күн мен жердің махаббаты өлеңнің негізгі композициялық жүйесін де, логикалық мәнін де айқындайды. Тіршіліктің негізі – осылар. Ал қалғаны осы ұлы махаббат нәтижесінде, соның себебінен туындайтын салдарлар. «*Жан-жануар, адамзат анталаса, Ата-анадай елжірер күннің көзі*». Бұл сурет

емес, бұл әлеми болмысты тану. Күн адамзат баласына ортақ, күннің елжіреуі де Адамзат баласының пейілінен! Пейілінен, таңдауынан. Адамзат баласы пейілі тұзу болса, күн ата-анадай елжірер. «Елжірер» сөзінің грамматикалық семантикасы мен лексикалық мағынасына көңіл бөлейік. Автор мұнда «елжірейді, елжіреп тұр, елжіреп кетті» деген сияқты осы шақ немесе жедел өткен шақ формаларын қолданбайды, «елжіре» етістігіне – р (-ар, -ер) есімше тұлғасын жалғау арқылы келер шақтық мән үстеп, мүмкіндік семасын үстейді. Яғни «елжірер» семасында келер шақтық, мүмкіндік мағына бар, өйткені бұл адамзаттың өзінің пейіліне, ниетіне, «анталай қарауына» байланысты.

Бүгінгі жазғытұры осындай Күннің елжіреген сәті. Жер масатыдай құлпырып, «қырдағы ел ойдағы елмен араласып, Күлімдесіп, көрісіп, құшақтасып» жатыр. Достық пейіл, оң көзқарас, тұзу ой – жаз жайлауға шығып, қауымдасқан қазақ баласының таңдауы. Шаруа жасап, мал бағып, егін егіп, тіршілік нәпәхасын жасап жатыр.

*Безендіріп жер жүзін тәңірім шебер,
Мейірбандық, дүниеге нұрын төгер.
Анамыздай жер иіп емізгенде
Бейне әкеңдей үстіңе аспан төнер.
Жаз жіберіп, жан берген қара жерге
Рахметіне Алланың көңіл сенер.*

Адамзат таңдауы тура жолда болып, тұзу ойда болса, Алланың Рахметі, шапағаты мол. Абай жазғытұры шақты тек суреттеп тұрған жоқ, бұл әлеми таным дегенде, айтпағымыз осы өлең жолдарынан анық аңғарылады. Жер жүзін безендіріп тұрған тәңіріден артық «безендіру» кімнің қолынан келмек...

«Жазғытұры» өлең мәтінінде «адамзат» сөзі екі рет қолданылған. Кісі баласына айтылатын өзге сөз емес, «адамзат» сөзінің пайдалануын да кездейсоқ деп тани алмайтынымыз түсінікті. Жазғытұры жайлау қазақ ауылына ұқсап, «түйе боздап, қой қоздап - қорада шу» болып жатқандай көрінгенімен, өлең мәні тереңде. Жазғытұры табиғатта болып жатқан өзгерістерге «Адамзаттың көңілі өсіп көтерілер» деу арқылы автор ойының астарының тереңде, танымының биікте екенін аңғаруға болар еді. Данышпандық сіңген дархан ой «алысқа сермеп» жүректі тербейді.

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3. СӘНІК ШЫҒАРМАШЫЛЫҒЫНДАҒЫ ҚАЗАҚТЫҢ ҰЛТТЫҚ ӨЛШЕМДЕРІ АТАУЛАРЫНЫҢ МАҒЫНАЛЫҚ ҚҰРЫЛЫМЫ

М. Сатекова

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Қазіргі біздің қолданысымыздағы түрлі өлшемдер бұрынғы заманда басқа сөздермен алмастырып қолданылған. «Елі», «сүйем», «қарыс», «құлаш» деген деп аталатын арнайы халықтық өлшемдер қазақ өмірінде аса маңызды рөлге ие болған. Мәселен, киім пішу, тігу, сырмақ жасау, тұскийіз кестелеу, үй ағаш жасау, киіз басу мен қатар қолөнер бұйымдарын жасаудың бәрі де осы өлшемдер бойынша орындалып отырған. Олардың өздеріне сай белгілі бір мағыналары болған. Тіпті қазақтарда осы өлшем туралы түсінікердің ертеден қалыптасып, қолданыста болғанын көрсететін бірнеше мақал-мәтелдерді мысалға келтіруге болады. Мәселен, «Жеті рет өлшеп, бір рет кес», «Қарыстан сүйем жуық», «Ауру батпандап кіріп, мысқалдап шығады» секілді мақал-мәтелдер легін айтуға болады. Тіпті «Қабанбай батыр» жырынан мына үзіндіні алып қарастырсақ болады:

Амалмен құрған қақпанды,
Ақылды пенде баспайды.
Тәңірім жазған жазудан
Өлшеулі ғұмыр аспайды.

Ғалым, Зейнолла Сәнік Мұбаракұлы «Қазақ этнографиясында» ұлттық өлшемдерді мынадай топтарға бөліп қарастырған:

1. Ұзындық өлшемі
2. Шамалық өлшем
3. Ауырлық өлшем
4. Көлемдік өлшем
5. Уақыт өлшемі
6. Тереңдік өлшемі

Енді олардың әрқайсысына жеке дара тоқталып өтейік. Қазақтың ұзындық өлшеулеріне берген атаулары: бір елі, бір қарыс, бір сүйем, сынық сүйем, әудем жер, қозы көш жер, құнан шаптырым, атшаптырым жер, айғай жетер жер, көз көрім жер. Ал сырт биік өлшемдерін «кісі бойы», «арқан бойы», «құрық бойы» деп те атап жатады.

Бір қарыс – өте аласа, тапал мағынасында қолданылатын сөз [11, 744]. Зейнолла Сәнік бір қарысты 20-21 см-ге тура келеді деп көрсетеді.

Осы сөзге қатысты Мұзафар Әлімбаевтың «Таңдамалы өлеңдер жинағынан» мына өлеңді мысал етіп алуға болады:

Ол сыншы тыжырынды сөзімді ұқпай,
Бірқарыс бойы, өзі жұдырықтай.
Соңыңнан ақын, сірә, шығар ма екен?
Дегені бар емес пе өзін құптай.

Бір елі. Қазақ әдеби тілінің сөздігінде бұл сөзге мынадай анықтама берілген:

а) Саусақтың қалыңдығындай. Бетіндегі сап-сары қаймағы бірелі болып, кастрюльде піскен сүт тұрады (Б. Соқпақбаев, Балалық.).

ә) Сәл ғана, зәредей. Бірақ сол бес-алты күннің ішінде менің өзімнен, не тапсырған кісімнен бірелі оңаша шықпайсың, оған көнесің, - деді Бекболат (С. Шарипов, Шығ.).

Әудем жер. Аса қашық емес, тиіп тұрған жақын жер [16, 752].

Сынық сүйем. Журналист Тоқан Бодаұхан бұның бас бармақ пен сұқ саусақтың екінші буынына дейінгі қашықтыққа тең өлшем екенін атап өтеді. Ал «Қазақ әдеби тілінің сөздігінде» бір сүйемнің төрттен үш бөлігі екені көрсетілген. Ал Зейнолла Сәнік өз еңбегінде бұл өлшемнің 14-15см-ге тең келетінін атап көрсеткен.

Қозы көш жер. Шамамен алты-жеті шақырымдай қашықтықты білдіретін халықтық өлшем [16, 752]. Белгілі жазушы Әбдіжәміл Нұрпейісовтің «Қан мен тер» романынан мынадай үзіндіні мысар ретінде алып қарастырсақ болады:

Теңізден көз ала бергенде, қозы көш жерден балықшылар аулының түтіні көрінді.

Құнан шаптырым. Ісмет Кеңесбаевтың «Фразеологиялық сөздігінде» сегіз-он километр шамасындағы алыстыққа тең қашықтық өлшемі деп келтірілген. Ал «Қазақ әдеби тілінің сөздігі» мен «Қазақ дәстүрлі мәдениетінің энциклопедиялық сөздігінде» бұл 3-4 шақырымды құрайтын жер деп көрсетілген.

Әдетте, атшаптырым жер 40-50 километрлік ұашықтықты көрсетеді. Тай шаптырым, құнан шаптырым 10-20 километрге сәйкес келеді. Ал атшаптырымның ең қашығы – аламан бәйге. Ұзаққа жіберілетін мұндай бәйгелер көбінде 70-100километр қашықтықтан жіберілетіні мәлім. Бұдан да ұзақ жолды қазақ «атқа бір күндік жол», «10 күндік жол», « 3 айлық жол...» деп айтады. «Айшылық алыс жолдарды алты-ақ күнде басады» дейтін халық жырлары да содан туған. Мысалы, Манчиң деректеріне қарағанда, кезінде Абылайдың сауда тоғанақтары Үрімжіге – 3 айда, ал Қабанбайдың сауда тоғанақтары бір айда келеді екен. Осыған қарап Көкшетау мен Үрімжі арасын – 3000 километр деп, ал Алакөл мен Үрімжінің арасын 1000 километр деп шамалауға болады [11, 273].

Арқан бойы. Сәл ғана деген мағынада, ұзындық, биіктік өлшемі туралы айтылады [17, 800]. Халқымызда осыған байланысты айтылған «Арқан бойы жердің тұсау бойы төтелігі бар» деген мақал бар.

Құрық бойы. Құрықтың бойымен бірдей ұзындықты білдіретін халықтық өлшем [18, 368]. Ал құрық дегеніміз – жылқы ұстау үшін, ұшына ілмек жіп бекітілген ұзын құрал. Құрық сабының ұзындығы 5-6 метр кепкен, жіңішке, түзу жас қайыңнан жасалады. Демек құрық бойы халықтық өлшемі шамамен 5-6 метрге тең.

Саусақтың көлдеңенін «елі» деп атайды. Сонда бір елі дегеніміз – 1,5 сантиметрді құраса, екі елі дегеніміз – 4-5 см, төрт елі дегеніміз – 8-9 см, бес елі дегеніміз – 10-11сантиметрге тура келеді. Әдетте, жылқы сойғанда жылқының семіз-арығы қазысының қанша елі шыққанымен өлшенеді. Айталық, жылқының арықтауын «бұлт қазы», «пышақ сырты болды» деседі. Бұл жарты сантиметрды құрайды немесе одан да жұқа дегенді білдіреді. Ал тәуір қазыны –екі елі, ең семізін «төрт елі» немесе «табан қазы» деп атайды.

Зейнолла Сәнік Мұбаракұлы халықтық өлшемдердің келесі бір тобын «шамалық өлшем» деп бөліп қарастырған. Шамалық өлшемдерге – бір шымшым, бір атым, бір шөкім, бір қасық, бір асым, бір таба бір ошар, бір буда, бір күрек, бір қора, бір көжелік, бір мөшек, бір дағар, бір тұлып, бір жайым деген сөздер жатады. Халқымыз ғасырлар бойы осы қлшемдерді қолдана отырып, өздерінің күнделікті жұмыстарын орындап, сауда-саттық істерін жүргізіп келген. Бұлардың ішінде «бір шымшым», «бір түйір», «бір жұтым» деген сияқтылар осы шамалық өлшемнің ең аз шамасын көрсетеді. Қазіргі өлшеммен есептегенде шамамен грамдыө немесе миллиграмдық өлшемдерге тура келуі мүмкін. Айталық, тарының түйірі, бидайдың бір түйірі, бір тамшы су, міне, осылар осылар миллиграмдық өлшемге ай келуі ықтимал. Ал «бір асым», «бір дағар» деген өлшемдер едәуір мол дүниені көрсетеді. Қазақта:

«Құлахмет, ендеше, Құлахмет, Құлын сойса, болады бір асым ет» деген халық өлеңі бар. Бұған қарағанда, бір құлынның еті де бір асым етке кіретін көрінеді. Сол сияқты бір дағарға 100кг астық сияды деп есептесек, бұл да едәуір мол өлшем. Әдетте қазақтың бір үйір жылқы дегені – 15-20 жылқы, бір қора қой дегені – 300-500 тұяқты құрайды. Бұл да за сандар емес екені белгілі-ақ. Қазақтар малды нақ санақ бойынша санап дағдыланған. Мысалы, «10 мың қой біткен ірі бай», «5000 жылқы біткен жылқылы бай» деп аталады. Малға қатысты алыс-беріс те осы сан бойынша жүргізіліп отырған. Мысалы, біреуден алынатын несие мал, қыздың қалыңмалына берілетін 30-40 қара, алман-салық, т.б. бәрі де осындай сан бойынша есептеліп отырған.

Қазақ арасындағы халықтық сауда-саттық, алыс-беріс сияқтылардың бәрі де осы жоғарыдағы өлшемдер бойынша жүргізілген. Айталық, біреу біреуден бір шелек астық қарыз алған болса, қайтаратын кезде сол шелекпен, сондай етіп қайтарады. Егер оның алғаны үйме шелек болса, қырма шелек қайтарған. Көп жағдайда бұдан пәлендей артық-кем шықпайды. Мұның өзі өлшеуішті алыстан іздемейтін ең қолайлы әрі көпшілікке қолжетімді шара есептеледі. Қазақ ішінде жеті сенсең, бір ішік шығады. 5 үлкен қойдың терісінен бір тон шығады. Үш қойдың терісінен бір шалбар шығады. 200 түлкі пұшпағынан бір пұспақ ішік шығады, т.б. тұрақты өлшемдер бар. Егер біреуге бір киімді тері жинап беруге тұра келсе, міне, осы сияқты өлшемдер негіз етіледі.

Қазақ сахарасындағы сыйлау-жазалау ережелерінің де өзіндік өлшемдері болған. Мысалы, ердің құны – 100 қара, көздің құны ердің жарым басымен тең делініп, 50 қара бойынша жөніндегі өлшемдер де осындай: төмен айып – жай тоғыз, орта айып – қосақ тіркеуімен қосылған тоғыз, ең ауыр айып – тоқал тоғыз, яғни 99 ірі қараға тең болған. Айыппен бірге 30 қамшы, 50 қамшы.. бойынша дүре соғылған [8; 273].

Жоғарыда аталған бір шымшым, бір қасық, бір уыс секілді сөздер өлшемдәк көлемді білдіргенімен, ауырлық өлшемін білдіретінде сөздер аз кездеседі. Мысалы, қазақ арасында атқа жем бергенде әдетте екі қос уыс немесе үш қос уыс жем беріледі. Мұнысы екі килограмм немесе үш килограмм ауырлыққа тең келеді. Бір уыс сөзі мұнда әрі шамалық, әрі ауырлық өлшемді білдіріп тұрғанын байқаймыз. Мұнан сырт қазақта ең көп қолданылатын ауырлық өлшем – бір көтерем. Әдетте, арқалы азаматтарбір көтергенде 100-150 килограмдық астық көтереді екен, қарулы әйелдер 50-100 килограмдық жүк көтере алатын көрінеді. Сонда бір көтерем деген ауырлықты 50-150 кг айналасындағы жүк деп межелеуге болады.

Зейнолла Сәнік кітабында кездесетін ауырлық мағынасын білдіретін өлшем сөздеріне «түйенің теңіндегі ауыр», «қазандай қара тасты қозғалтты», «зіл батпан» дегендер жатқызылған. «Қазақ тілі түсіндірме сөздігінің» 2-том, 203-бетінде: «Батпан – ескі салмақ өлшемі (бір батпан – 200-300 грамм). «Бала атадан батпақ артық туады» (мақал) деп түсінік берілген. Бірақ көп адамның ұғымында батпан «ауыр», «салмақты» деген мағынаны білдіреді деп есептеледі. Әсіресе «зіл» сөзімен қосылып келгенде ол «айрықша ауыр» деген ұғымды білдіреді. «Зіл» сөзінің «оның дауысы зілді шықты», «оны аяқ астынан зіл басты» деген сияқты басқа мағыналық жақтары да бар.

«Тең» сөзі қазақтың көшпенді өміріне қатысты шыққан сияқты. Өйткені тең жүктің екі жағын тең басып тұратын салмақта болуы шарт етіледі. Сонда бір тең өгізге теңделетін болса, 50-60 кило, түйеге теңделетін болса, 80-100 кило болуы мүмкін [8, 274].

Келесі көлемдік өлшемдерге «от орнындай», «үй орнындай», «бір қора қойдың орнындай», «шынының аузындай», «шелектің аузындай», «аудың апанындай», «түймедей», «оймақтай», «иненің жасуындай», «танадай», «тулақтай» секілді сөздерді жатқызамыз. Бұлардың ішінде «иненің жасуындай», «оймақтай», «танадай» деген сияқты сөздер кішкене аумақтық өлшемді білдіреді. Төменде біз көйлекке тығылатын тананың, әдеттегі шай ішетін шынының аузы қаншалық жерді алатынына есеп жүргізіп көрелік:

1. Тана

$$C = 2Pr$$

$$R = \frac{1}{2} = 0.5 \text{ см}$$

$$C = 2 * 3,14 * 0,5 = 3,14 \text{ см}$$

Демек, тананың периметрі – 3,14см.

2. Әдеттегі шай шыны

$$C = 2 Pr \quad dd = 11.5 \text{ см} \quad rr = 5,75 \text{ см}$$

$$C = 2 * 3,14 * 5,75 = 36,1 \text{ см}$$

Демек, шай шыны аузының периметрі – 36,1 см.

Міне, осындай өлшемдер бойынша от орнының, үй орнының, бір қора қой орнының қаншалық жер екенін шығаруға да болады. Бірақ өмірде қазақ халқы осындай аумақтық өлшемдер арқылы сахара жүзіндегі көптеген көлемге қатысты көптеген мәселелерді шешім етіп, осы өлшем бойынша өз жұмыстарын жүргізген. Көлемдік өлшем ішіне кіретін сөздердің қатарындағы «ұлтарақтай», «далайықтай», «аюдың апанындай», «есік пен төрдей» деген сияқты сөздердің кейде нақты санның емес, жалпы кеңдік мөлшерді білдіретін, үлкендікті ұғындыратын жағы бар екендігін де білгеніміз жөн [8, 275].

Зейнолла Сәнік өлшемнің келесі бір түрін уақытқа арнайды. Уақыт өлшеміне «қас-қағым», «көзді ашып-жұмғанша», «шай қайнатым», «сүт пісірім», «ел орынға отыра», «ақырғы тауық», «басқы тауық», «орта тауық», «жұлдыз шыға» деген сөздерді жатқызамыз. Бұлардың ішінде «қас-қағым», «көзді ашып-жұмғанша» деген сөздер жарты секундтық, тіпті одан да қысқа уақытты меңзейді. Ал бие сауым уақыт жарты сағат уақыпен барабар екенін қазіргі жылқышылар дәлелдеп жүр.

Алғашқы азан уақыты қыста қаңтардың екі жаңасы күні 8 сағат 24 минутқа тура келсе, екінті уақыты 17 сағат 28 минутқа сай келеді. Жазда, яғни маусымның екі жаңасы күні азан уақыты 5 сағат 15 минутқа тура келсе, екінті уақыты 20 сағат 26 минутқа сай келеді. Осындай есептеу жолымен басқы тауықтың қай мөлшерде шақыратынын, орта тауық, аяққы тауықтың қай мөлшерде болатындығын, жұлдыз туар уақыт дегеннің қай уақыт екенін, Үркердің қай кезде жамбасқа түсетінін есептеп шығаруға болады. Осы есеп бойынша «сүтпүсірім уақыттың» 10 минут, шай қайнатым уақыт – бір сағат, бие сауым уақыттың жарты сағат екенін межелеуге болады.

Зейнолла Сәнік өзінің «Қазақ этнографиясы» еңбегінің 8-томында осы өлшемдік ұғымдарға қатысты тақырыбында қазақи өлшемнің ең ебдейлі әрі бірегей қаруы ретінде пайдаланылған қол және оның саусақтары және қазақи қлшемнің ғаламат туындысы киіз үй туралы да мәліметтер қалдырып кеткен.

Автор бес саусақтың ең әуелі сан құралы болғанын алға тартып, бес саусақты екі қабаттаса – 10, үш қабаттаса – 15, төрт қабаттаса – 20 саны шығатынын айтады. Осылайша малдың, адамның және басқа нәрселердің санын шығаруға ең қолайлы «қару» ретінде бес саусақ пайдаланылған.

Бармақтың қарсысына біткен төрт саусақтағы буын саны – он екі. Санаудың бұл түрі жыл қайыру – мүшел есебіне, ай ретін санауға, бір тәуліктегі сағат санын сағауға пайдаланылған. Осы төрт саусақ жылдың төрт мезгіліне де пайдаланылған. Мысалы, сұқ саусақ – наурыз, көкек, мамыр. Ортанқол – маусым, шілде, тамыз. Аты жоқ қол – қыркүйек, қазан, қараша. Шынашақ – желтоқсан, қаңтар, ақпан.

Қазақтар саусақтардың ұзындығын күн ұзындығымен қарайлас деп санаған. Айталық сұқ саусақ пен аты жоқ қолдың ұзындығы қарайлас болғандықтан, бұл мезгілдегі айлардың (күз, көктем айларының) ұзақтығы да қарайлас келеді. Ал ең ұзын саусақ ортан қолдың ең ұзын бірінші буыны маусым айын (22 маусым), яғни ең ұзақ күн мезгілін көрсетсе, ең қысқа саусақ шынашақтың бірінші буыны желтоқсан (22 желтоқсан) ең қысқа күнге тура келеді деп білген.

Саусақ апта, ай, күн санын шығаруға да қолданылған. Саусақтардың түп буындарының саны бойынша бір апталық есепті шығарып отырған. Мұндағы сұқ саусақтың түп буыны – дүйсенбі, ортан қолдың түп буыны – сәрсенбі, аты жоқ қолдың түп буыны – жұма, шынашақтың түп буыны – жексенбі, буын аралығындағы ойықтар – сейсенбі, бейсенбі, сенбі күндерін көрсеткен. Демек, буынның дөңес жері аптаның тақ күндерін, ойыс жерлері жұп күндерін білдірген.

Бармақтың екі буынын қосқанда бес саусақтың жалпы буын саны 14 болады. Бұл – екі апталық күн, бес саусақ екі қабатталса, 28 буын болады. Айдың көріну мерзімі де 28 күнге тура келеді. Апта күндері де әр 28 жыл сайын айдың дәл сол күнінде қайталанып келіп отырады. Айдың толуы-кемуі деп бөлсек, әр қайсысы 14 күннен болып шығады. Халқымыз бұрын ай есебін осы жолмен шығарып, сол арқылы халық арасында жеті қат көк, жеті қат жер, жеті дыбыс (нота), жеті бояу, жеті сезім (көз, құлақ, мұрын, тіл, тері, бұлшық ет, көңіл-күй) ұғымын қалыптастырып, соның өзінен қыруар ғылымның суатын аршыған.

Демек, саусақ әрі сан санаудың, әрі ай, әрі күн, жыл есебін шығарудың, әрі өлшемнің (елі, қарыс, сүйем, уыс) бірегей құралы ретінде пайдаланылған. Саусақтың осындай рөлін толық көрсете алған адамды қазақ «он саусағынан өнер тамған шебер» деп атаған.

Киіз үйді қазақ халқының сан ғасырлық ақыл-парасатының, өмір тәжірибесінің, табиғатты түсіне білу мен сраған сәйкесуінің әрі сахаралық сәулет өнерінің бір ескерткіші деуге болады. Халықтық өлшем өнерінің сан алуан түрі осы киіз үйдің тұла бойына сіңіріліп, содан өз жемісін көрсете алған. Оның бойынан осы заманның математика, геометрия, астрономия, т.б. ғылымдарының бірқыдыру тоғысқан үлгілерін байқауға болады. Айталық, кереге – киіз үйдің қабырғасы. Керегенің басы мен аяғы иіліп, сыртқа қарай шалқайтылады. Сонда кереге желісінің жанабы екі метр текше парабола тәрізді болып шығады. Жайылған керегенің жоғарғы және төменгі жақтары гиперболалық праболид тәрізді де, ортасы эллипсоидтің бөлігі пішінді болады. Керегенің бір қанатындағы желілер 14 ерісінен, 9 сағанақтан, 9 балашықтан тұрады. Алты қанат киіз үйдің сағанақтары мен балашықтарының саны – 108. Бұл сан – ежелгі аспан саны. Осы екеуінің бір жерден шығуы тегін емес. сыртынан айналдыра тартылған белбеу – аспан белдеуі – зодиақтық шеңбер. Алты қанат үйдің әр керегесінің екі басы – екі зодиақтық шоқ жұлдыз. Олай дейтініміз, киіз үйдің есіктері бір бағытқа қаратылып, үй жиһаздары біркелкі орналастырылады. Үйге кіргенге оң жақтағы құрулы ши өреше болады. Оның ішіне ыдыс-аяқ, тамақ қойылады. Ал сол жақ босағада ертұрман, одан жоғары ерлердің киімі, қару-жарағы ілінеді. Одан ары жүк жиналады. Әр нәрсенің өзіне тиісті орны бар. Мұның өзі зодиақтық шоқ жұлдыздардың орналасуына сәйкестендірілген. Төсектің басы төрге өаратылып салынады, яғни Темірқазық жұлдызына бағытталады. Басты құбылаға қарату салты осыдан шыққан болуы мүмкін. Әдетте, шаңыраққа бақан (сырық) көлбей ілінеді. Ол – үйдің тірегі. Бақанның көлбеу бұрышы 62 градус шамасында, яғни галактика экваторының көлбеу бұрышына сәйкес келгені байқалады.

Шаңырақ шеңбер тәрізді тоғынан және күлдіреуіштен тұрады. Түндік жабылған шаңырақтың пішіні айналма параболид. Бұл – көптеген күмбездерге ортақ пішін, яғни көк күмбезінің кішірейтілген бейнесі. Түндік шаршы тәрізді жасалады да, әлемнің төрт бағытын нұсқап тұрады.

Біз жазушы Зейнолла Сәніктің “қазақ этнографиясы” кітабы арқылы қазақтың ұлттық өлшемдері мен олардың мағыналық ерекшеліктерімен толықтай таныса алдық. Қазіргі кезде көп қолдансықа түсе бермейтін сөздер легі де бар екенін байқай аламыз.

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ШЫҒЫС ҚАЗАҚСТАН ӨҢІРІНІҢ ТОПОНИМИКАЛЫҚ АҢЫЗДАРЫ ТУРАЛЫ

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Аңдатпа

Мақалада «топонимикалық фольклор» жанрының пайда болуы мен қалыптасуының алғышарттары, топонимика мен фольклордың бір-бірін дамытатын, бірін-бірі толықтыратын, тыңдаушыны оқытатын, сөйлеушіні шабыттандыратын қайталанбас ортақ белгілері сипатталған. Фольклорлық аңыздарды тарихи және жергілікті (топонимикалық) деп бөлу, сонымен қатар Шығыс Қазақстан облысындағы елді мекен атауларының шығу тарихы туралы айтылады.

Тірек сөздер: фольклор, миф, мифтік таным, мифология, топонимика, аңыз, мотив.

Abstract

The article describes the preconditions for the emergence and formation of the genre of «toponymic folklore», the unique common features of toponymy and folklore that develop, complement each other, teach the listener, inspire the speaker. The division of folklore legends into historical and local (toponymic), as well as the history of the origin of the names of settlements in the East Kazakhstan region.

Keywords: folklore, mythical cognition, mythology, toponymy, legend, motive.

Әлемдегі қандай ұлттың болса да фольклорында бір кезеңдердегі өмір шындығы жатады. Соның бірі фольклордағы жер-су атаулары болмақ. Өйткені, жер-суға ат қою арқылы халықтың қоршаған ортаға қатынасы, эстетикалық ой-танымы, зердесі, ұлттық болмысы аңғарылып отырады.

Жер-су туралы ежелгі халықтық түсінік, пайымдаулар ұлттың ұлт болып қалыптасуымен бірге жасалған, тіпті адам санасының қалыптасып, қоршаған ортаны тануына негіз болған факторлардың бірі деп қарау керек. Қазіргі Отан ұғымы, немесе атамекен, туған жер, кір жуып кіндік кескен мекен деп жүргеніміз түптеп келгенде байырғы көне түркілік жер-су деген түсініктен шығатындығы айтылып та, жазылып та жүрген жәйт.

Жер-судың ежелгі мәні мен маңызы, әлеумет өмірінде атқарған қызметі туралы сөз қозғағанда ең алдымен еске ғаламның жаратылуы, қоршаған әлем, табиғат жөніндегі қадым заманнан бері келе жатқан адамзат түсінігі, наным-сенімі қатар түседі. Ол - заңды құбылыс. Өйткені жер-су адамның саналы тіршілік иесі болуына жағдай жасаған қойнау, кеңістік, табиғаттың өзі. Сондықтан да адам өміріндегі ең маңызды орын - жер-суға тиесілі болмақ.

Осы ойларды салмақтай келе біз топонимияға қатысты сюжеттердің фольклор жүйесіне жанр аралық қосылыстар негізінде трансформациялану үрдісін творчестволық процестің даму заңдылығы деп қабылдай аламыз. Сонымен бірге жер-судың мағынасын, оның халықтың жасампаз өнері - фольклорға қаншалықты деңгейде қатыстылығын бағамдай аламыз.

Бұдан шығатын қорытынды мынау деп білеміз:

1. Жер-су үш дүниелік ғаламды (жоғары - тәңір, төмен - ұмай, орта - адам) біріктіруші ұғым.

2. Жер-су жоғары мен төменнің қосындысы, туындысы ретінде табынатын тәңірлік мәнге ие, бірақ тәңір емес, адамзат өмір сүретін әлем, кеңістік бөлігі.

3. Жер-су кіндік кесіп, кір жуған туған жер, атамекен, отан ұғымының байырғы атауы.

4. Жер-су - табиғаттың өзі, яғни географиялық объектілер.

5. Жер-су - ықылым заманнан бергі уақыт пен кеңістік шегінде адамзат қалдырып отырған өмір таңбалары, топонимдер арқылы фольклор сюжеттерінен танылатын тарихи таным күәсі.

6. Жер-су фольклор шығармаларындағы әлем туралы, кеңістік туралы ойлар мен көзқарастардың таңба, символдық мән түріндегі жиынтық бейнесі.

7. Жер-су фольклор сюжеттерінде мотив тудырушы дәнекер, немесе кей жағдайда сюжеттік негіз[4, 16-б.].

Осы тезистер топонимдер табиғатының терендігін, оның қазақ фольклоры жанрлары құрамынан көрініп, фольклор сюжеттерімен бірлікте атқаратын қызметін белгілеп, нәтижесінде жаңадан өркен салатын топонимдік фольклор жанрының қалыптасуына негіз болады деп есептей аламыз.

Фольклордағы басқа жанрларға қарағанда, аңыздың танымдық қызметі айқынырақ, ол елдің өткен тарихынан, өмірінен мағлұмат береді. Аңыз – халықтың өзі айтып берген ауызекі тарихы десе де болғандай. *«Аңыз дегеніміз – бір мекеннің, жергілікті жердің, я болмаса бір елдің, тайпаның, рудың ауызекі шежіресі, бір аймақта болған оқиға туралы, немесе атақты қайраткер жайында баяндайтын ауызекі әңгіме. Сондықтан аңыздардың сюжеті көп жағдайда ұлттық қана болады, бір елдің аңызы екінші елге ауыспайды, тіпті, аңыздың көпшілігі аймақтық қана болады»* [3, 36-б.].

Басқа халықтарды айтпағанда, осы біздің ұлан байтақ Отанымыздың бір жерінде болған оқиға екінші жерінде қайталануы неғайбыл. Ал қайталана қалған күнде ондағы кейіпкерлердің, не болмаса жер-су аттарының басқа болуы мүмкін. Сондықтан ол оқиғаға байланысты туған аңыз басқа аймақтарға кеңінен тарамалуы да. Мәселен, оңтүстіктегі мекендер жайлы аңыздар солтүстікте белгісіз. Не болмаса, керісінше. Әрине, бүкіл Қазақстанға белгілі болған, бір ғана аймақ аясынан асып кеткен оқиғалар жайлы аңыздар барлық жерге тарауы мүмкін, бірақ мұндай оқиғалар жиі болып тұрмаған. Соның өзінде де бүкіл Қазақстанға тараған аңыздар өзінің пайда болған алғашқы аймақтық сипатын жоғалтпаған.

Аңыздарда тұрақталған, бір типті, көп шығармаларға тән сюжеттік композиция болмайды. Онда қалыптасқан, бір аңыздан екінші аңызға ауысып жүретін канондық мотив пен сюжеттер өте аз. Сол себепті аңыз жанрында сюжеттік өзек әр түрлі және ол әрі қарай өрби түсуге бейім келеді. Әдетте, аңыздардың көлемі шағын, бірақ соған қарамастан олар айтылу мәнерінің қызғылықтығымен, мазмұнының тартымдылығымен, сюжет сонылығымен тыңдаушыны өзіне баурап алады, оған зор әсер етеді.

Әдетте, фольклортану ғылымында аңызды тарихи және мекендік (топонимикалық) деп екіге бөледі. [4, 36-б.]. Бұлай болудың шартты екенін бұған дейін де бірнеше ғалымдар айтқан болатын. Топонимикалық деп бөліп жүрген аңыздарда тарихи негіздер, ал, тарихи деп жүрген аңыздарда топонимикалық та мотив кездеседі. Алайда, мұнда шығарманың өзі емес, ондағы сарын ғана топонимикалық сипатта болуы мүмкін.

Сондықтан «топонимикалық аңыз» деген атауды шартты түрде ғана алу керек те, оған белгілі бір жерге, мекенге байланысты оқиғаны баяндайтын әңгімелерді жатқызу керек. Екінші сөзбен айтқанда, топонимикалық аңыз деп жер-судың, тау-тастың пайда болуы мен атын мифтік ұғыммен, немесе мифтік кейіпкердің іс-әрекетімен емес, бір оқиғамен, я

болмаса белгілі қайраткер атымен байланысты түсіндіретін әңгімені айтқанымыз жөн. Яғни, фольклор туындыларында орын алған топонимдік сюжеттер мазмұнына, баяндалу ерекшеліктеріне байланысты бірнеше жанрлық түрге бөлінеді. Егер сюжет жер-су атауларына байланысты бір кезде өмірде болған жартылай тарихи оқиғаға құрылса-топонимдік аңыз, егер мифологиялық кейіпкерлердің қатысуымен діни нанымға негізделген белгілі бір жер-судың аталу себебін түсіндіретіндей маңызда болса - топонимдік хикаят, егер сюжет жер-су мекен-тұраққа байланысты ертеде болған әңгімені қиялмен көркемдеп, ғажайыпты сипатта баяндайтын болса - топонимдік эпсана деп аталады деп ұйғаруға болады.

Қандай да болмасын ғылымда белгілі бір жанрды жіктеп тану, теориялық қисынын жасау, мақсат, міндеттерін белгілеу оңай еместігі, ол үшін ортақ негізді табу керек екендігі белгілі. Біздің зерттеуіміздегі ол негіз - фольклордағы жер-су атаулары.

Алдымен жанрдың табиғатын, мөлшерін және туыстас жанрлармен қатынасын зерттемей біз дұрыс қорытындыға келе алмаймыз деген академик С.Қасқабасов сөзін басшылыққа алған жөн: «Жанрды жеке-дара бөлу үшін, сөз жоқ оның жалпы теориясы болуы тиіс» [1,12-б.],-дейді ғалым. Ғалымның бұл пікірі кеңес фольклорының әдебиеттану терминдерін пайдаланғандығы, түптеп келгенде оның заңды да екендігі, өйткені фольклордың да әдебиеттің де сөз өнеріне жататындығы және сонымен қатар фольклорды әдебиеттен ерекшелендіріп тұратын өзіндік қасиеттері де бар екендігі, осыдан келіп фольклор жанрларын зерттегенде оның осы ерекшелігін аңғару керектігі тұрғысынан айтылған. Осы орайда орыс ғалымы В.Я.Пропптың да мына пікірін ескергеніміз жөн: «Точное определение того, что понимается под жанром, невозможно вне рамок классификации жанров; жанры должны быть определены каждый как сам по себе, так и в их отношении к другим жанрам, от которых их нужно отличать. Оба эти вопроса - вопрос об определении жанров и о их классификации, по существу составляют две стороны одного большого вопроса» [2, 36-б.].

Осы айтқандай біз жер-суды зерттейтін ғылым - топонимиканы, жер-суды халық шығармашылығының өзегіне айналдырған фольклорды бір жүйеде қарастырып, ортақ жанрлық принциптерін белгілеуді мақсат етеміз. Қазіргі кезде фольклортану ғылымы алдына күрделі мақсаттар қойып, көп қырлылығымен танылып келсе, топонимика ғылымы да ономастиканың өнімді ең үлкен саласы деп кеңестік ғылым белгілеп берген шеңберден шығып, басқа ғылымдармен өрелесе, салаласа дамып, ұлттық дәстүр мен ұлттық эстетикалық ойлау мүмкіндіктерін мейлінше кең таныта алатын поэтикалық жүйеге айналып келеді.

Фольклордың әдебиеттен дараланатыны – оның синкретті өнер екендігінде, басқа ғылым, білім, өнер салаларымен табиғи байланысында деп айқындалатындығы ғылыми ізденісте жүрген жұртшылыққа белгілі. Жалпы жанрдың өзіне тән ерекшелігі ақиқатты айта білуінде және оның суреттеп - сипаттауда қолданатын әдіс-тәсілдеріне байланысты болса керек. Әдебиетте ол форма мен мазмұнның сабақтастығы негізінде түсіндіріледі. Фольклорда сәл басқаша. Фольклор шығармаларында өз қоғамы тұрғысынан кезінде ақиқат деп танылған шындықты еншілес басқа ғылымдармен байланыстылық негізінде жүзеге асырушылық байқалады және бұндай байланыс, сәйкестіктер осылай жасайық деген мақсатты көздеп жасалмайды, табиғи түрде орындалып жатады. Бұл фольклордың синкреттілік сипатынан туындап жататын құбылыс екендігі аян. Мәселен, Шығыс Қазақстан облысына қарасты **АЯГӨЗ** жер атауына байланысты аңызды алайық.

Ерте замандардың бірінде ел болып әлпештеген ауылына көркі сай, сұлулығын суреттеуге тіл жетпейтін бір қыз өмір сүріпті. Ол қыздың аты – Аяу екен. Бой жетіп, толған айдай толықсыған шағында сол елдің жігіті Жайсаңмен тіл табысып, көңіл қосады. Екеуі бірге өмір сүруге сөз байласады. Күндердің бір күнінде ниеті қара Нойыс деген бір жігіт Аяуды

айттырып алмаққа құдалық кәдесімен келіп, ауылына түседі. Бұған Жайсаңның туған-туысқандары араласып, іс насырға шабады. Әбден шиеленіскен кезде бір қапысын тауып, Нойыс Жайсаңды мерт қылады.

Осындай қайғылы оқиғаның күәсі болған Аяу нәр сызбайды, ботадай боздаған күйінде жатып алыпты. Үлкеннің сөзіне құлақ аспайды, кішіні тыңдамайды. Құрбы-құрдастарымен де қатыспайды. Сөйтіп қайғының салдарынан Аяу қаза тауыпты. Көзінен аққан жас сарқыраған өзенге айналыпты. Сонан ел жаңағы өзенді Аяудың көзінен аққан жас, Аяудың көзі деп атап, кейін келе «Аягөз» болып кетіпті [7, 44-б.].

Осы тұрғыдан алғанда фольклордың иек артатын, тығыз байланысатын саласының бірі - этнография. Этнография халықтың салты, дәстүрі, жөн-жоралғысы сияқты өзіндік ерекшеліктерін сипаттап көрсетуі арқылы фольклорға мейілінше жақын тұрған ғылымның бірі. «Белгілі бір халықтың екінші бір халықтан тілі мен сенімі, мекен-тұрағы ғана бөлек емес, сонымен бірге мінез-бітімі де, салт-дәстүрі де өз ерекшеліктерімен дараланады. Ондай ерекшелікті елемей тұрып этнос туралы, олардың мәдени-рухани әлемі туралы белгілі бір тұжырым жасау мүмкін емес. Сондықтан да, этнография ғылымы алдымен этникалық ерекшеліктерге ден қояды» [6, 25-б.]. «Фольклор жанрларын этнографияға сүйенбей зерттеу мүмкін емес. Этнографиялық материалдарды пайдалану жанрлардың шығу тегін анықтау үшін ғана қажет емес. Этнография фольклорлық жанрлардың ерте замандағы сипатын, алғашқы даму жолдарын зерттеуде өте пайдалы. Себебі жанрлардың да, сюжеттер мен мотивтердің де пайда болуы ғана емес, сондай-ақ олардың өмір сүруі мен өзгеру, даму жолдары да тұрмыспен, болмыспен тікелей байланысты» [1, 12-б.]. Осы айтылғандай этнографиялық белгілер халықтық топонимдер бойынан да ерекшеленіп танылып тұрады. Мәселен «Қостіккен», «Елқонған» топонимдері көшіп-қонуды, «Төретүскен», «Кілемжайған» атаулары төре тұқымдарын ұлықтауды, «Атансойған», «Табаққырған» топонимдері ел басындағы ауыр тұрмыстық жағдайды білдіреді. Тізе берсе халықтық салт-сана, ырым-жорамалдарды бейнелеп беретін бұл секілді жер-су атаулары біздің жерімізде көптеп саналады. Әңгіме олардың көп, не аздығында емес, әңгіме осы жер-су атауларының аталу сырын, қойылу ерекшелігін өзінің шығармашылық өнеріне арқау еткен халқымыздың өзіндік эстетикалық көзқарасында, бұл тақырып бойынша қызғылықты сюжеттер түзіп отырған таным биігінде. Шығыстағы **БАРШАТАС** аңызы осының айғағы.

Өткен дәуірлердің бірінде жаз жайлауы бар, қыс қыстауы бар бай адам өмір сүріпті. Ол өзі сондай аңқау екен. Бай болғаннан кейін дәулетке қызықпай тұра ма, қай тұстан қандай пайда түсірем деп жанталасумен жүреді екен. Күндердің бір күнінде аңқау байдың дүниеқоңыз екендігін сезген бір жігіт үйіне келіп түседі. Үстінде оқалы шапан, астында әсем сәйгүлік кербез көңілді келісті жігітті бай жалпақтап қарсы алады. Ет желінеді, қымыз ішіледі. Көңілі орнына түскеннен кейін үй иесі қонағынан жөн сұрапты. Сонда әлгі жігіт:

– Бәле, байеке, сіз мені қалайша танымай отырсыз, мені бүкіл иісі қазақ таниды. Өрісім толған мал, жерім толған алтын-күміс байлық. Көңілім түссе сізге де қарасамын, – депті.

Оның сөзіне иланған аңқау бай:

– Сен шамалы тұра тұр, мал-жан өзімде де жеткілікті. Сен маған анау алтын тастарыңнан қарайласаң. Мен де қарап қалмаспын.

Жігіт келісім бере қояды. Сөйтіп байды қасына ертіп, жігіт өзі алдында көріп кеткен бір кең өлкеге келіпті. Өлкеде жерде жатқан жылтыр тастар, жаңағы жарқырауық тастарды көрген бай алтын екен деп ойлап осы жерді маған бер деп жата кеп жабысады. Басында көніңкіремеген жаңағы жігіт артынан келісім беріп, ақысына байдан екі мың жылқы алып, алдына салып, көз көрмес, құлақ естімес жаққа кете барады. Бай болса мақтанышпен ауыл адамдарын ертіп, сол жерге алып келіп көрсетеді. Сөйтсе алтын деп жүргені жай жылтыр тастар болып шығады. Жылтыр тасты жерді көпшілік Баршатас деп атап кетеді [7, 61-б.].

Сондай аңыздың тағы бірі **АҚШОҚЫ**.

Бір жылдары бір дәулетті елде жұт болыпты. Жазы қуаңшылық болып, жаңбыр жаумай, қыстан көтерем шыққан малдың жай-күйі жайсыздыққа ұласыпты.

Көпшілік бас қосып, мал-жанды аман сақтау үшін бұл жерден қоныс аудару керек деген ұйғарымға келеді. Сөйтіп, жер ауа көшкен жұрт жайлы мекен жолыққанша жүре беріпті дейді. Бір уақыттарда көпшіліктің ішінен біреуі:

– Анау тұрған шоқыны көрдіңдер ме, сол жерге барып, қоныстанып көрсек. Малға жайлы болса, мекен етерміз, жайсыз болса тағы да көшерміз, – деген ұсыныс айтады.

Бәтуға келген көш сол жерге барып орын тебеді. Шалғыны мол, шөбі бітік, ағып жатқан өзені бар жайлы мекен малға жағымды болып тез көтеріледі. Бір жыл қоныстанып шыққаннан кейін төл егізден болып, жаңағы жердің құтты мекен екендігі байқалады. Риза болған халық:

– Шоқым, шоқы-ақ екен. Жарайсың, – деді. Сонан жаңағы биіктің аты «Ақшоқы» аталып кетіпті.

Сайып келгенде осы сюжеттер фольклор мен топонимиканы туыстастыратын негізгі мотив болып табылады. Фольклордың этнографиямен осылайша тығыз байланысты болып келетін өзіндік ерекшелігі оны атқаратын қызметіне байланысты, көтеретін жанрлық жүгіне байланысты әдебиеттен өзгеше екендігін көрсететін фактордың бірі. «Бұл жерде біз екі нәрсені анықтап алғанымыз жөн. Бірінші - фольклор мен әдебиеттің бірдей еместігі. Осыдан барып шығатын олардың пайда болу мен өмір сүру кейпінің өзгешелігі. Бұл өзгешелік оларды зерттеу әдістерінің де екі түрлі болуын тілейді. Екінші - ұғымдар мен терминдеріміздің мағынасын дәлме-дәл анықтау. Мысалы, жанрға байланысты «баяндау тәсілі», «бейнелеу тәсілі» сияқты тіркесті ұғымдар қолданылады. Біреу баяндайды, хабарлайды, бейнелейді. Фольклорда ол жыршы, ертекші, не өлеңші. Әдебиетте ол жазушы, ақын [1, 13-б.]. Осы көрсетілгендей жанрды анықтау үшін оны шығарманың өз ішінен, табиғатынан тану дұрыс. Олай болса «Жанр дегеніміз - шығармадағы сюжеттің баяндалу, бейнелену, өрілу тәсілдері», - деп орынды атап көрсеткен С.Қасқабасовтың пікірін басшылыққа ала отырып біз топонимдік фольклор жанрының туып қалыптасуына негіз болатын нәрсе - фольклорлық дәстүр бойынша туындайтын сюжет деп айта аламыз. Ал, бұл сюжет баяндалуы жағынан - фольклорлық, бейнеленуі жағынан- топонимикалық болып келсе онда біз сөз етіп отырған жанр жүгін арқалап алары сөзсіз. Өйткені, топонимика мен фольклордың байланысты екендігін әркім-ақ біледі. Алайда оны дербес жанр ретінде қарастыру қолға алына қойған жоқ. Ал топонимдік фольклор өз алдына жанр болуға қажетті шарттардың бәріне жауап бере алады. Оның халықтық шығармашылық өнердің жемісі екендігі де, әлеуметтік - тұрмыстық функция атқаратындығы да, топонимдерге байланысты сюжеттердің бірнеше вариантты болып келіп, ауызша таралуы да осының айғағы. Бұп - фольклорлық жанр жағынан туындайтын ерекшелік болса, бұған қоса оның мекендік, ақпараттық қызметтері топонимика тарапынан қосылатын ерекшеліктер болып табылады. Тағы да мысал келтірейік. Мәселен Шығыс Қазақстандағы **АҚШАТАУ**дың екі нұсқасы бар. Біріншісі: Күз мезгілі еді. Кернейден шыққан Есей батыр тобына ілесіп Жидебай да жол жүреді. Ұзақ жол жүріп, шаршаған топ бір жерге келіп ат басын шалдырады. «Ел арасында қандай жау бар дейсің?» деп, Есей мен Жидебай бастаған қырық жігіт қаннан-қаперсіз ұйқыға кіріседі. Ұйқылары қанған жігіттер ертесімен оянса, оздерінің жаяу қалғандарын бірақ біледі. Бұған намыстантан Есей батыр:

– Мынау бетке шіркеу, сүйеке таңба болды-ау, мен із кесіп жауды қуамын, – дейді. Сонда жас Жидебай:

– Мен де сізбен бірге барамын, – деген екен Қарындары ашып, шөлдеген екеуі кешкі мезгілде төбешік үстінде тігулі тұрған ақша отауды көрген. Отауға кірсе ешкім жоқ, дастархан жаюлы тұр екен. Екеуі сол жерде ауқаттанып, естерін жиып, жауды қуа кеткендерді күтеді. Ақша отаулы жерді «Ақшатау» деп атап кеткен. Ал екінші **АҚШАТАУ** нұсқасы мынау:

Қозыны жетімсініп, Баянды беруден бас тартқан Қарабай қаша жөнеледі. Қырық пары өліп, Аягөзге келгенде, Қарабай Баянды Қодарға бермекші болады. Әбден шарасы таусылған Баян Айбас деген жігітке қанатты қара биеден туған Бақа айғырды мінгізіп, Қозыға сәлемдеме деп, алтын сандыққа домбырасы мен моншағын, басындағы қарқарасын салып берген екен. Қарабайдың бар малын жалмаған ұзақ жол Айбас мінген Бақа айғырды да әбден титықтатса керек. Сол бір ұзақ та, қатерлі жолда келе жатып, Баянның сәлемдемеге берген ақ сандығын ат шалдырған жерінде ұмытып кетіпті. Бұл өңірдің алуан кенге бай болуын қариялар осы сандықтың қалуынан дейді екен. Сол сандық аппақ қалпында тауға айналған деседі. Содан алтын сандық пен «Ақшатау» деген жер аты байланыстырылыпты [5, 23-б.].

Қорытынды. Бұдан фольклор жанрларының қандай өзіндік ерекшеліктері болса, топонимиканың да сондай принциптері бар екендігі белгілі болады. Алайда бұл екеуінің басын біріктіретін негіз - фольклорлық сюжеттер екендігі анық. Осы айтқандарды қорыта келгенде туындайтын тезис біреу, ол - топонимика мен фольклордың тығыз байланыстылығы. Сонда топонимика мен фольклордың бірін-бірі дамытатын, бірін-бірі толықтыратын, тыңдаушыны үйіретін, айтушыны желіктіретін бірегей ортақ қасиеттері топонимдік фольклор жанрының туып, қалыптасуының алғышарты болып табылады.

Топонимдік атаулардың басқа фольклор туындылары секілді таза халық шығармашылық өнерінің жемісі екендігін ескерсек, оның таным тарапындағы мәнін, поэтикалық өңі мен эстетикалық құаты жоғары екендігіне көз жеткіземіз. Ғалымдарымыз айтқандай, фольклорды жіктеп танушының бірінші міндеті - өз халқының фольклорының жанрлық құрамын белгілеу. Олай болса әр кезең, әр дәуірде халық өмірінің шежіресіне айналған фольклорлық мұрамыздың ұлттық ерекшелігімізді жан-жақты танытар мүмкіншілігін шектемей оның басқа ғылым салаларымен байланысын, еншілес ғылым салаларының тыңнан соқпақ салып дамуына арқау болар қадірі мен құатын таныту, таныта отырып уақыт сұранысына орай туындайтын жанрларын белгілей алу бүгінгі өскелең ғылым міндетіне алар келелі істің бірі екендігіне дау жоқ.

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Biological Sciences

Detection of the SARS-COV-2 virus variant B 1.1 in the Republic of Kazakhstan

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Introduction. Coronaviruses (Coronaviridae, CoV) are a family of RNA viruses containing single-stranded positive RNA as genetic material, measuring up to 33.5 t.p.o in length and the diameter of the virion is up to 140 nm. Coronaviruses cause respiratory, hepatic, and neurological diseases in humans, some species of animals and birds.

Until 2020, only six strains of 2 genus of coronaviruses were known to cause respiratory diseases in humans. In December 2019, an outbreak of a new type of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus occurred in the city of Wuhan, People's Republic of China (PRC). As a result of epidemiological studies conducted by the Chinese Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC China) using the NGS method from samples, a new type of coronavirus was identified, which was named SARS-COV-2.

Over the past 2 years, a significant number of mutations have been identified that led to the evolution of the virus and various variants. According to the Global Initiative on Sharing Avian Influenza Data (GISAID) database (www.gisaid.org), currently there are 12 different clades of the SARS-COV-2 virus in the world.

Variant B.1.1 of the SARS-CoV-2 virus was first detected in February 2020 and has spread worldwide. Variant B.1.1 has several mutations, including 1 single nucleotide change in ORF1b protein, 1 single nucleotide change in S protein, 1 change in ORF8 protein, 2 single nucleotide mutations in N protein.

The aim of this study is to sequence the S gene of variant B.1.1 SARS-CoV-2 virus circulating on the territory of the Republic of Kazakhstan (RK).

Materials and methods. Clinical samples were obtained from the branch of the Scientific and Practical Center for Sanitary and Epidemiological Expertise and Monitoring of the RSE at the National Center for Public Health of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

To achieve the goal of the work, molecular genetic studies and methods were used, such as virus isolation, RT-PCR, PCR, gel electrophoresis, purification of PCR products and sequencing.

Results and discussion. As a result of real-time PCR studies with the SARS-CoV-2 Fluorescent PCR Kit (Maccura Biotechnology Co., Ltd, China), the resulting test sample showed a positive result for COVID-19. Specific primers were selected based on the S gene of the reference strain Wuhan-Hu-1([NC 045512.2](#)) the SARS-CoV-2 virus. According to the results of sequencing of the S gene, about 12 single-nucleotide mutations were found. The results obtained indicate that the mutational variability of the S gene is different from the original strain that originated in Wuhan.

Conclusion. Genetic analysis of the nucleotide sequence of the studied samples showed many mutations. According to the results of the conducted studies, the ubiquitous distribution of strains of the "B 1.1" variant was established on the territory of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

The work was carried out within the framework of the grant project AP09058338 "*Study of antiviral activity of drugs in relation to the SARS-COV-2 virus in vitro and molecular epidemiological analysis of circulating COVID-19 strains*".

Historical Sciences

INTERDISCIPLINARITY IN HISTORICAL RESEARCH

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In academic research and teaching, interdisciplinarity is widely preached and practiced. Interdisciplinarity is defined as a form of scientific imperialism, an intersection of the social sciences .

Interdisciplinary research develops over time in the lives of scientists, as an attitude that gradually develops in a spiral during the research practice of the humanities and social sciences. Often , interdisciplinarity is characterized as the connection of social sciences with art, medicine, natural sciences and computer science.

Many of the problems in modern society are so complex that they can only be solved by overcoming the boundaries that separate traditional disciplines. Disciplines mutually and positively "infect" each other in ways that go beyond traditional project-based interdisciplinarity .

The exercise of interdisciplinarity is especially important in history, whether it be anthropology in history, philosophy in innovation studies, history in development studies, or art in the sciences, and so on.

The search for scientifically based landmarks in the reorganized research field of history, where methodological pluralism and balanced methodological tolerance coexist today, is facilitated by the idea of interdisciplinarity , designed to solve many problems of planning, organizing and high-level scientific research results.

An important prerequisite for the actualization and potentially large-scale connection of the idea of interdisciplinarity to the study of historical facts, phenomena and processes in the second half of the 20th century was a phenomenal phenomenon called the "information explosion". Its essence is expressed in the ever more accelerating growth of scientific knowledge in the course of the intellectual development of human society. So, for example, if from the beginning of our era it took 1750 years to double scientific knowledge, then by 1950 the total amount of knowledge was doubling every 10 years, by 1970 - every 5 years, since 1990 - annually.

The formation of large flows of information was due to the extremely rapid growth in the number of documents, reports, dissertations, reports, etc., which presented the results of scientific research; an ever-increasing number of scientific periodicals and monographs; the emergence of a variety of data, usually recorded on magnetic tapes of large computers and therefore not falling within the scope of the social communication system among a wide range of scientists.

The "information explosion" of the mid-1950s resulted in an information crisis, which manifested itself in a contradiction between the exponentially growing volume of information and the limited possibilities for its perception and processing. In historical science, the consequence of this process was the emergence of new sources of the most diverse information and new factual data, which forced scientists to look for more and more advanced methods of their analytical processing. Historians in such conditions had to face not only a significant array of previously

accumulated historical and historiographic sources, but also a flurry of a new source base that had qualitatively changed in form and content. The variety of sources posed before theoretical and applied source studies the problems of their systematization and classification, identification of their specificity, general and special in each of the groups of sources. Of particular interest began to attract mass sources previously not in demand by researchers, containing both qualitative, but to a greater extent, quantitative information, which is extremely difficult, in some cases, almost impossible, to process using traditional methods. To a large extent, it was the need for a comprehensive processing of mass sources, especially characteristic of modern and recent history and reflecting mass phenomena and processes of the historical development of society, that required historians to develop a comprehensive, integral approach to their study, to involve mathematical and formal-quantitative methods and computers in their research.

Thus, the objectification of the interdisciplinary approach to historical research in this period was associated, first of all, with the realization by the historians themselves of the insufficiency of only the "sectoral" disciplinary approach in the scientific and theoretical development of historical reality and a clear attraction to an integral, holistic (systematic) consideration of historical objects. , phenomena and processes; secondly, with the difficulties of operating with a huge amount of accumulated knowledge and a rapidly growing flow of new information; thirdly, with the inclusion in the scientific circulation of mass historical sources that are difficult to analyze by traditional methods of source study; fourthly, with the need to apply, along with descriptive, quantitative and formalized methods for analyzing historical sources, especially mass ones, and the effective use of new information technologies in the process of processing and presenting source information into knowledge.

The history of science proves that "information explosions" and the accompanying "information revolutions", major scientific discoveries in the field of exact and natural sciences or advanced technology and more advanced information processing technologies directly or indirectly influence the development of social and human sciences and their aspirations. to a change in the configuration of interdisciplinary integration fields and a redistribution of the intradisciplinary hierarchy of scientific disciplines, the emergence of new, more effective methods for obtaining new knowledge and ways of its presentation, and at a higher level - to transdisciplinary integration, i.e. integration of scientific concepts, theories and methods in philosophical concepts. This provision applies equally to historical science. It is known that at all stages of its development there are two interrelated and multidirectional trends in the development of historical knowledge - integration (relationship - from "many" to "single") and differentiation (relationship - from "single" to "many"), each of which in certain periods tend to prevail. Some historiosophists associate this situation with dominance in the intellectual academic environment, which directly depends on the level of development of society, its transitional or stable state, generalizing (generalized, complex solution of cognitive problems to identify certain trends and patterns of the historical process) or individualizing (detailed, in-depth study of certain aspects of phenomena and processes) approaches to historical research, defining their influence as a variable, changing, as it were, along a sinusoid, experiencing ups and downs. And, if integration is largely a consequence of transscientific reflection on it, then differentiation or disciplinary dismemberment, as a more objective process, is dictated by the practical need to study all new subject areas within historical science itself, narrower professionalization and specialization, both researchers and practitioners .

Integrative processes in modern science, including historical science, are a very complex multidimensional socio- cognitive phenomenon. Structurally, they include elements such as the integration of scientific knowledge; cooperation and mutual exchange based on communications of creative (productive) activity of scientists of various specialties and disciplines; integration (interpenetration) of the scientific activities of various institutions, in general, the process of

forming an integral subject of scientific knowledge, the interchange of material and technical means and scientific methods in the conduct of scientific research, etc.

The process of interaction both within each of these structural elements and between them, leading to interpenetration, generalization, concentration of scientific activity, methodology, knowledge and information, in fact, is called integration. It is assumed that when solving general, complex cognitive problems, as well as traditional objects of scientific disciplines, common research goals are pursued and there is a unified system of cognitive means.

In historical science, types of integration characteristic of scientific knowledge as a whole are observed. First of all, in the epistemological field, the emergent strong type is associated with the synthesis of scientific knowledge of those sciences that are involved in the emergence of a new integral, "boundary", "docking" science, for example, historical geography, historical demography, historical professionalism, historical computer science, etc. At the same time, in methodological terms, the integrative process is accompanied by the borrowing of methods, techniques, research technologies, the expansion of the field of their application, the introduction of new ideas and concepts. An extremely significant factor in this type of integration is the priority of preserving the research field of the science that "initiated" the interdisciplinary interaction of the collective efforts of scientists from different specialties.

In contrast to the strong type, the light one does not always lead to the birth of a new scientific discipline and is realized in the course of a specific interdisciplinary- complex research. For example, a historical source acts as a single object of various social sciences and humanities with a variety of their subjects of study, thereby creating a single basis for interdisciplinary research and integration of sciences. Therefore, with the specialized use of sources in the state-legal sciences, linguistics, literary criticism, art history, statistics and other scientific areas, there is an interconnection and interpenetration of research methods and techniques, interdisciplinary scientific contacts are established.

Within the framework of historical science, the particular emergent type is extremely relevant (the general type of integration is applicable when studying one global object by different sciences, for example, space exploration). It manifests itself during the endogenous, intradisciplinary synthesis with the help of the so-called vegetative mechanism for the creation of new related historical disciplines, such as sphragistics, numismatics, vexillography, etc. But even in this case, intradisciplinary is not expressed in a refined form, it is combined with an exogenous, interdisciplinary synthesis. For example, the original theoretical foundations of semiotics, its main ideas and methods are necessarily present in the study of objects and phenomena of the above subdisciplines.

Firstly, the determination of historical events and phenomena is multilevel, since the combined action of natural-climatic, biological, economic, socio-psychological, cultural-ethical, ideological and other determinants creates what we call the historical process. Therefore, historical theories that describe the course of the historical process in a particular space-time interval inevitably include in their cognitive "arsenal" the corresponding laws and phenomena of biological, geographical, physical and other disciplines. For example, the natural and climatic conditions of the territory of Kazakhstan are the subject of physical geography, but at the same time they form the subject of nomad studies, becoming a prerequisite for a rational explanation of the emergence and development of a nomadic society. The nature of radioactivity, its impact on living organisms is studied by the relevant sections of physics, biology, genetics, and the search for and explanation of sources of natural radiation is studied by geological science. But without the application of the knowledge developed by these disciplines, it is impossible to imagine archaeological or anthropological research.

As for the narrative, due to the length of time between the creator of a historical source and its modern researcher, the study of historical sources is limited to a certain amount and quality

of information received, but this obstacle is achieved not only by expanding the source base of research, but also by deep penetration into the structures of objects - carriers of information about the past - by attracting new research methods, technological and technical means of the natural sciences: mathematical statistics, computer science, computational mathematics, etc., the development of which is becoming one of the most important conditions for the development of historical science.

Thus, interdisciplinarity is an immanent property of any scientific historical reconstruction, being based, "on the one hand, on the specifics of the object of historical knowledge, its multi-level determination, and on the other hand, on the specifics of cognition of the object due to its temporal remoteness" But nevertheless, it should be noted that in Ontologically, almost all specific historical studies actually contain elements that are to some extent interdisciplinary in nature (for example, the use of factual databases or databases, the conceptual and categorical apparatus, individual research techniques and methods of other disciplines), but they cannot be considered as methods of interdisciplinarity .

Thus, the process of interdisciplinary interaction of historical science with such complex integrating sciences as mathematics and informatics, and the institutionalization of quantitative history and historical informatics at their intersection in the second half of the 20th century, were due both to the internal laws of the development of historical science itself and to the strong influence of mathematization processes. , informatization and computerization in all branches of scientific knowledge, an objective growth of tendencies towards the integration of social, humanitarian and natural sciences in the conditions of mankind's transition from an industrial society to an information one.

Technical Sciences

IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF PROCESSES IN THE LOGISTICS SECTOR

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Abstract *The Japanese leadership model has demonstrated that progress with small but rapid steps leads to sure and long-term victories. Kaizen is a concept of Japanese origin that essentially means continuous improvement. Currently, Kaizen is also studied outside the borders of Japan, in important institutes in the USA, Canada, and Western Europe. In the Kaizen approach, the focus is on the fluency of the improvement process and its efficiency. Another important principle lies in the fact that the responsibility for improving products and processes lies with the entire staff in the company, not only with specialists. In the spirit of innovation, through small and quick steps, workers, foremen, engineers and managers alike are involved.*

Keywords: *efficiency, Kaizen method, production management, information flow, technological process.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Kaizen is a day-to-day process whose purpose goes beyond simply improving productivity. It's also a process that, when done right, humanizes the workplace, eliminates overwork, and teaches people how to conduct experiments on their animal using the scientific method.

Overall, the process suggests a humanized approach to workers: "The idea is to nurture the company's resources: the human, by praising and encouraging them to participate in kaizen activities." Successful implementation requires "worker participation in the processes".

The specific characteristics that ensure a successful approach to Kaizen activities are the following:

- forget all the ideas currently applied in the organization of production;
- totally rejects the existing situation;
- imagine how the new method will work;
- you don't have to look for perfection, a 40-50% improvement of the existing situation is also good;
- does not make large expenses;
- the problems you face give you the opportunity to use your knowledge and managerial skills;
- the ideas emanated by several people are better than the idea of a single person;
- Improvements have no limits.

2. Application of the 5 S method in a warehouse

One of the methods for establishing the Kaizen approach for an organization is to evaluate the workplace organization and visual management standards. 5S involves people through the use of standards and discipline.

It's not just about cleanliness, but also focusing on maintaining standards and discipline to manage the organization - all achieved through support and respect for the workplace (Gemba), every day.

Beyond these very clear principles, 5S primarily means a way of thinking and daily practice, to facilitate operations and optimize working conditions.

The objective is very simple: to have a workplace and to continuously improve it. Although, originally, this tool was intended for production spaces, it has proven its usefulness for any type of office, because its purpose is to allow everyone, regardless of the area of activity (production or tertiary), to optimize their effectiveness through application of five great principles:

1. Sorting (seiri): separating what is necessary from what is not necessary and discarding unnecessary things
2. Arrangement (Seiton): a place for every thing.. and every thing in its place
3. Cleanliness (Seiso): achieving cleanliness and maintaining it systematically
4. Standardization (Seiketsu): formalization of standards for the work space
5. Practice (Shitsuke): applying, enforcing and improving standards.

Fig 1 Metoda 5S

Fig. 1. Aplicarea metodei 5S în depozitul de prototip

It is impossible to perform a 5S analysis with one or two people.

It is necessary for everyone to be involved. Everything that needs to be done is quite simple.

The difficulty lies in doing that regularly.

This requires determination, perseverance and cooperation. But this combination, in turn, creates a new sense of team identity and a better climate in the company. It is important to start by doing. It is not essential how well the theory is understood, because theory does not produce

results, only action produces results. And this action has the power to change people's attitude, it has the power to transform them.

Every part of the 5S process is important. Each step has the power to "open" people's eyes. The 5S method is the best way to start eliminating waste.

To be effective, in the areas where visual management is applied, the processes must be clearly identified and controlled. First of all, there is a need for order, cleanliness and rules for keeping clean. Kaizen 5S refers to the organization of the workplace and represents a solid basis for many organizations, which are oriented towards continuous improvement. It is applicable and successful in all sectors that want to have remarkable results.

This method was applied in the prototype logistics area, named in the auto platform as Magazin X.

The problem area is represented by the sheet metal parts storage area and the storage of small and large assembly parts.

Thus, for this area we applied the 5S, namely Sorting, Ordering, Cleaning, Standardization and Self-discipline.

The analysis started with the first step

1. **Seiri** - Sorting, where the things we need will be separated from the unnecessary and the cleaning of the work environment. In this stage, the parts were sorted into body panels and mounting parts. Also at this stage, the pieces with a higher rotation were established. Also here, the pieces were divided and placed on the shelves according to the model and ABC, namely:

- A - daily use;;
- B – weekly or monthly use;
- C – rare use;

2. **Seiton** – Order - what is the arrangement of essential things so that they are easy to find and use.

At this stage, the pieces were divided into two categories:

- Sheet metal parts for the body;
- Body mounting parts;

Thus, each category was placed by location, type and size, and on each box a label of the origin of the part with a reference code and another label with its barcode (fig. 2) was pasted to make it easier to be identified.

Fig. 2 Box with the piece's origin label and barcode

3. **Seiso** – Cleaning - thus keeping the storage and reception logistics spaces clean according to a clear schedule, by defining the methods and means by which the said cleaning will be done. Thus, the proper ordering and placement of the parts on the shelves was achieved (fig. 3, fig. 4 and fig. 5) and a clear daily cleaning schedule was established by the staff involved in logistics as well as a weekly schedule, where the warehouse manager, will check the location of the parts on the locations, their type and the appropriate storage

Fig. 3 5S application in the parts storage area

Fig. 4 The application of 5S in the storage area of small and large parts

Fig. 5 The application of 5S in the external storage area

4.Seketsu - Standardization will initiate some procedures to avoid future occurrences of problems from the first 3S.

For this stage, internal rules were established for the storage and reception of sheet metal parts and assembly:

- Manufactured parts will be stored only in special locations and bins commensurate with the size of the part;
- The reception of the parts will be done only in the 1st shift, so with a schedule of 07:00 - 15:00, by the receptionist and a representative of the quality department;
- The parts that are available for transit will be stored in the transit location and in the original box with the original label from the supplier and the one with the barcode;
- Collecting the parts from the shelf will be done only by scanner where it will be automatically deducted from the stock for their visibility;
- Assembly parts are collected on specialized kits for each validation support;

5. Shituke – Self-discipline – a permanent respect for the established rules, with particular rigor and controlled by the logistics space manager. In order to make sure that the rules are respected, the storage and reception areas will be checked daily, randomly, thus there will be daily meetings with all the staff involved in logistics in the warehouse to communicate the discovered problems and their solutions, including how not to it will be repeated in the future.

Fig. 6 5S Application: representation of small and large parts

The advantages of the 5S method:

- Improving safety at the workplace;
- 5S becomes a fundamental measure in an organization and the key factor for Kaizen;
- It forms a solid base to develop a culture with continuous improvements;
- Employees acquire a sense of ownership, involvement and responsibility at the workplace;
- Improving performance in productivity, quality and morale leads to increased profitability;

CONCLUSIONS

Analyzing the functions, typology and technological process in the area of the X warehouse, a storage warehouse, where auto sheet metal components and assembly are stored for a medium or short period. Inventory management is carried out with the help of the integrated SAP system.

All transactions that affect the stocks lead to the real-time updating of the related stocks. It is possible to define multiple measurement units and automatic conversion to have a complete picture of the process of acquisition, reception, storage, transfer and sale.

According to the nature of the main activities it performs, it is a collection warehouse, which collects relatively small quantities of goods from various suppliers, and according to the form of ownership, it is a private warehouse.

The storage is considered temporary if it is done for approximately 20 days and long-term when this limited period is exceeded. It is very important to keep the goods in favorable conditions.

The rational exploitation of the useful volume of the warehouses, the reduction of the time required for the formation of orders, the ease of the workers' work, requires the provision of furniture suitable for modern storage systems based on the palletization and containerization of goods, and on the other hand with the type of commercial tools that ensure the mechanization and the automation of work processes specific to the various phases of warehouse technology.

Thus, the 5S Method was implemented in order to streamline and fix the meeting problems in the problematic logistics area of the warehouse. It was found that the parts were stored inconsistently on random shelves and were difficult to identify.

To begin with, I made the parts according to the ABC method, to prioritize the most common parts. After applying this method, a specific label was imposed on 2 groups of products: assembly and bodywork. Each label contains details about the part with reference and a barcode to be easier to identify and to communicate directly with the internal SAP-RACINE storage program.

Thus, the first 3S (sorting, arranging, cleaning) were applied very well, but the approach must continue and have a permanent character. Thus, this strong point must be followed by the last 2S (standardization and practice), under the leadership of managers, who must define the standards, check if they are respected.

After these changes, the logistics area offers a visibility of the parts in the storage area, because the parts are stored according to size, group and use. A set of internal rules was imposed to preserve these changes and for a continuous improvement of the logistics processes in the warehouse.

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СОҚА ТҮРЕНДЕРІНІҢ ҚАЖАЛУЫНА ТОПЫРАҚТЫҢ ФИЗИКА-ХИМИЯЛЫҚ ҚАСИЕТІНІҢ ӘСЕРІ

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Аннотация: Ауылшаруашылық машиналарының жұмысшы құралдарына топырақ өңдеу жұмыстарын орындау кезінде түрлі қысымдардың әсерінен қажалып тозуға ұшырайды. Әсіресе топырақтың түйіршіктері әсерінен түреннің тұмсық бөлігінің беттік жағы өте қатты сырылып-қажалуға ұшырайды, осыған байланысты түрен тұмсығы өзінің беріктігін жоғалтады және жерге енгізу күшінің әсерінен төмен жүйек түбіне қарай майысады, бұндай жағдай түрендердің жарамсыз күйге түсуіне және оларды жұмысқа жарамсыз болуына әкеп соғады. Топырақ түйіршіктерінің жұмысшы беттікке түсіретін қысымы топырақтың түріне және оның физика-химиялық қасиеттеріне тікелей байланысты болады.

Кілт сөздер: жұмысшы бет, соқа, түрен, топырақ, сырылып-қажалу.

Қызылорда облысының шаруашылықтарында егіндік жерлердің топырақтарын өңдеу кезінде ауылшаруашылық машиналарының жер өңдеу құралдары, біздің жағдайда соқа түрендері беттіктеріне әртүрлі қысымдар әсер етеді. Жүргізілген зерттеулер ауылшаруашылық машиналарының жер өңдеу құралдарының (соқа түрендері) жұмысшы беттіктерінің қажалуы жер жағдайына байланысты екенін көрсетеді. Қолданылатын соқа түрендерінің жұмысшы беттіктеріне түсетін күштердің әсері және беттік бойымен қозғалатын жер топырағының жүретін жолы әр түрлі болуына байланысты жұмысшы беттіктерінің, әсіресе түрен ұштарының қажалуы бір келкі болмайды.

Қызылорда облысының шаруашылықтарындағы құмдырақ, және құмшауыты топырақтарды жыртып өңдеу барысында ауылшаруашылығы тракторлары соқалары төстігінің беттіктері толығымен тырналады, ал соқа қанатының тек төменгі жағы ғана қажалуға ұшырайды. Ауылшаруашылығының егіндік жерлерінің барлық топырақ түрін жыртып өңдеу барысында соқалар түрендерінің ұшына ең үлкен қысым түседі. Түреннің өкшесіне түсетін қысым 40-50 пайызға кем болады. Жер жыртып өңдеудің технологиялық үдерісі кезіндегі бұндай құбылысты, соқа түрені өкшесінің аударылған топырақтың ашық жағында болатынымен және ол жерде топырақ қысымының әсері өте төмен болатынымен түсіндіріледі.

Ауылшаруашылығы машиналарының соқалары түрендерінің ұшына түсетін күштермен қатар тығыз топырақтарды жырту кезінде тік және көлденең жазықтықтағы қосымша күштер әсер етеді. Соқа түрендерінің жұмысшы беттігінің тырнанып қажалу мөлшерін салыстыру барысында, олардың арасында байланыс жоқ екенін көруге болады. Топырақты өңдеу барысында соқа түренінің өкшесіне қарағанда, ұшына түсетін қысым 1,5 есе, ал қажалуы 4-5 есе көп болады.

Қызылорда облысының шаруашылықтарында егіндік жерлердің топырақтарын өңдеу кезінде ауылшаруашылығы машиналарының құралдарының жұмысшы беттіктерінің тырнанып қажалуы, егіндік жердің физика-механикалық қасиеттері- жабысқақтығы, қаттылығы, жылжуға қарсылығы, ылғалдылық және үйкеліс коэффициенттеріне тікелей байланысты. Егіндік жердің ылғалдылығы 2,8...4 пайыз болатын құмшауыты топырақты жыртып өңдеу кезінде соқа түрендерінің ұшы негізінен ені бойынша, ал ылғалдылығы 9,4...12 пайыз аралығында болғанда қалыңдығы бойынша қажалады. Жер топырағы құрамының бөлшектері және металдың беткі қабатының қасиеттеріне судың да әсері үлкен болады (1.1-кестесі).

Топырақ ылғалдылығының мөлшері ауылшаруашылық машиналарының топырақты өңдеу құралдарының сырылып-қажалуын тездетеді. Сазды топырақтарда су металл беттігіне олардың жабысқақтық қасиетін көтереді. Бұндай жағдайда сырылып-қажалу үдерісі үйкеліс әсерінен өседі. Осыған байланысты топырақтың ылғалдылығы көтерілген сайын топырақты өңдеу құрал беттіктерінің сырылып-қажалуы өсіп, сонымен қатар топырақ құрамындағы қышқылдар мен тұздардың әсері де сырылып-қажалу үдерісінің өсуіне әкеп соқтырады. Сазды жердің бетінде ылғал азайған кезде қатты қабат пайда болады, оны бұзуға үлкен күш керек етеді. Осыған байланысты түрен ұшына түсетін күштің мөлшері өсіп нәтижесінде сырылып-қажалуға әкеп соқтырады.

Осыған байланысты ауылшаруашылық машиналарының топырақты өңдеу құралдарының беттіктерінің сырылып-қажалуы негізгі екі өзгеріп отыратын мөлшерлерге, топырақтың ылғалдылығы және беттікпен қозғалатын топырақтың жылдамдығына байланысты болады.

Кесте №1.1

Өңдеу күрделілігі бойынша топырақты бөлу

Өңдеу күрделілігінің көрсеткіші	Топырақтар түрі				
	Жеңіл	Орташа	Орташа-ауыр	Ауыр	Өте ауыр
Жерді жыртыу кезіндегі меншікті қарсыласу коэффициенті,кПа	30-ға дейін	30-50	50-70	70-120	120-дан жоғары
Физикалық саздың жобалық құрамы(0,01 мм кем бөлшек)	20-ға дейін	20-30	30-50	50-70	70-тен жоғары

Ауылшаруашылығының жер жыртыу машиналарының соқа түрендерінің тырнанып қажалуы жиілігінің өсуі негізгі үш аймаққа бөлінеді (сурет1): тұмсық бөлігі(1), жүзі (2)және ортаңғы бөлігі (3).

Түрен жүзінің алдына шығып тұратын ұшы ең бірінші болып топыраққа енеді, түреннің әрі қарай жерге енуін және жер жыртыу кезінде түреннің тұрақтылығын қамтамасыз етеді. Осыған байланысты жұмыс нәтижесінде түреннің тұмсық бөлігінде топырақ қысымы пайда болып, жүзіне қарағанда тұмсық жағы тез тырнанып қажалады. Түрен тұмсығы бөлігіне түсетін орташа қысым, оның ортаңғы бөлігіне түсетін қысымнан 2,8...4,6 есе артық болады.

Сурет1.1. Түреннің сырылып-қажалу аймақтары:
1-тұмсық бөлігі; 2-жүзі; 3- ортаңғы бөлігі.

Қызылорда облысының шаруашылықтарындағы егіндік жерлерде жүргізілген іс-тәжірибелер көрсеткендей, еңкейу бұрышы, желкелік фасканың пішіні және түреннің беткі беттігінің тырналып қажалуы жер топырақтары түріне (механикалық құрамы) және қолданыстағы ауылшаруашылығы агрегаттары күйіне тәуелді. Сазды топырақты жерлерді жырту кезінде желкелік фаска γ көрсеткіші 35° жетеді, бұндай жағдайда түреннің кесу жүзі мұқалып қалады (сурет1.2). Қатты топырақтарда түреннің бұндай жүзінің жұмыс істеу барысында жекелік фаскада пайда болатын R_b күшінің құралымы түреннің ені бойынша сәл ғана сырылып-қажалуына байланысты, оны өзінің бағытында пайдалануға болмайтындай қылып түренді топырақтан шығарып тастайды, ал жиектік R_r күші соқа кедергісін және кесу күшін жоғарылатады. Жартылай сазды топырақтарды жырту кезінде $\gamma = 8...15^\circ$ (сурет 1.2б) , ал құмды және құмшауыт топырақтарды жыртқанда $\gamma = 5...10^\circ$ (сурет 1.2в), фаска жіңішке алаңша тәріздес болып келеді, ол өткір жүзді құрайды және екі бойынша жарамсыз күйге дейін сырылып- қажалғанша жұмысқа жарамдылық күйін қамтамасыз етеді. Бұл келтірілген фаска параметрлері жөніндегі мәліметтер жалпы жұмыстарға арналған отандық долото тәріздес түрендері бар П-702 (ПНЧС), соқаларға арналған, олардың жүзінің егелу бұрышы $\alpha = 23...32^\circ$, ал кесу бұрышы $\beta = 30^\circ$ құрайды.

Сурет 1.2. Топырақ құрамына байланысты түрендердің желкелік фаскасының пайда болуы және жүзінің қажалу сипаттамасы:
а- сазды; б- жартылай сазды; в- құмды және құмшауыт.

Сурет 1.3. Жұмысқа қабілеттілігін анықтайтын түреннің негізгі геометриялық сипаттамасы:

H және H_{np} – тұмсық бөлігінің бастапқы және жарамсыз күйдегі биіктігі;

h және h_{np} - жүзінің бастапқы және жарамсыз күйдегі ені;
 v және a - жүзінің бастапқы және жарамсыз күйдегі қалыңдығы.

Түреннің беттік жағы сазды топырақтарды жырту кезінде мүлдем сырылып қажалмайды, ал жартылай сазды топырақтарды жыртуда шамалы ғана сырылып-қажалады, құмды және құмшауытты топырақтарда қатты қажалады. Бұндай жағдай әсіресе түреннің тұмсық бөлігінің беттік жағы өте қатты сырылып-қажалуға ұшырайды, осыған байланысты түрен тұмсығы өзінің беріктігін жоғалтады және жерге енгізу күшінің әсерінен төмен жүйек түбіне қарай майысады, бұндай жағдай түрендердің жарамсыз күйге түсуіне және оларды тастауға әкеледі.

Осыған байланысты түрендердің жұмысқа жарамдылығын және ұзақ мерзімділігін қамтамасыз ететін негізгі геометриялық параметрлері болып, тұмсығының биіктігі H (сурет3), бетінің ені (жүзі) h , жүзінің қалыңдығы v саналады.

Бұл параметрлер сонымен қатар түреннің жарамсыздық күйін көрсетеді. Осы көрсеткіштердің шеткі мәніне қарай түрендерді ауыстырады, өйткені:

- тұмсық бөлігінің сызықтық қажалу $W_1=H-h_{np}$ нәтижесінде соқа корпусының топыраққа енгізу қабілеті төмендейді, жырту тереңдігі азаяды, қамту ені нашарлайды;

- түрен енінің сызықтық қажалу $W_2= h-h_{np}$ нәтижесінде қамту ені төмендейді, топырақты майдалау сапасы нашарлайды, соқаны тарту кедергісі артады;

- желкелік фасканың пайда болуымен және түрен жүзінің a қалыңдығына дейін қажалу нәтижесінде, алаңның қатты жерлерінде соқаны қайта-қайта енгізу нәтижесінде біркелкі тереңдікте жер жырту қамтамасыз етілмейді.

Соқа түрендерінің қажалып-сырылуы салдарынан істен шығу себептеріне жасалған талдаулар бойынша 2,2% балқымамен қатырылған және 8% қатырылмаған түрендер өзінің конструкциялық ресурсын толықтай пайдалана алатындығын көрсетеді. Ал қалған шамасы процесс барысында белгілі бір параметрімен, не тұмсық бөлігінің мүжіліп қалуы немесе майысып қалуы, не пышақ жүзінің майырылып өтпей қалуы салдарынан іске жарамсыз болып табылатындығын көрсетеді.

Psychological Sciences

MODERN APPROACH TO AUTISM TREATMENT IN KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

According to the United Nations, the number of people diagnosed with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is increasing every year, with delays and impairments in social skills, speech and behavior that make it difficult for them to integrate socially. This problem is also relevant for Kazakhstan, since according to statistics in recent years, people with autism in Kazakhstan have grown. Along with the growth of people with ASD, the issue of treating autism is acute. Kazakhstan, as a country integrated into globalization, is trying to improve the methods of treating autism and apply the experience of the leading countries of the world. In this regard, this article discusses modern methods of treating autism in Kazakhstan. The article is descriptive and based on a review analysis.

Keywords: autism spectrum disorders, autism, autism treatment, autism drug treatment, integrated approach to autism treatment.

Introduction

Autism is a mental disorder that is diagnosed in 2% of children. This is a relatively rare pathology in the general classification of autism spectrum disorders. The causes of the disease are unknown, there is no single mechanism for its development. Autism is manifested by antisocial behavior, lack of communication skills, a tendency to ritualistic behavior and systematization. An autistic child does not make contact with either adults or peers. Such children usually do not smile, do not make eye contact, do not play with other children. Autism spectrum disorder is a spectrum of psychological characteristics that describes a wide range of abnormal behavior and difficulties in social interaction and communication, as well as severely limited interests and frequently repetitive behaviors [1].

The system of assistance to people with autism and their families necessarily reflects the sociocultural characteristics of society. Unlike in developed countries, where already in the XX century began to create a holistic system of social services for children and adults with autism, in Kazakhstan, the diagnosis itself was institutionalized only after 2000. Moreover, universities still pay insufficient attention to the training of specialists of the relevant profile. As a result, high-quality social and medical assistance with such developmental features can only be obtained in large cities such as Almaty or Astana.

In Kazakhstan, in rural areas, the situation is complicated by the special pessimistic attitude of parents to the diagnosis of "autism" in their child. This attitude is formed because of the influence of many opinions about autism, its nature, prognosis, gleaned from various sources (neighbors, specialists, media, literature, acquaintances, etc.). It is aggravated by the lack of standards, officially approved methods, certified specialists who could guarantee the quality of special care for children and adults with autism. Also, the lack of forms of mandatory statistical reporting of the Ministry of Health of Kazakhstan on autism (currently in Kazakhstan there are no statistical data on the incidence of ASD, on the number of people of different ages). As a rule, with

the insufficiency of special social services, the problems of social integration worsen with age the use of medical, pedagogical and psychological technologies does not lead to the desired result [2].

Currently, the demand for services for the correction of autism spectrum disorders is many times greater than the supply. Some state and educational institutions accept children with autism and similar disorders for education, but there are very few such institutions, their activities at the state level are not regulated in any way, they are not provided with either specially trained personnel, or in methodological and organizational terms. There are several approaches to correcting autism, and a lot of literature has appeared in recent years. Methods such as applied behavioral analysis, an emotional-level approach, various options for aesthetic therapy, methods using animals, and the impact on sensory are widely known. The main reason for this diversity lies in the very definition of childhood autism syndrome and ASD, identified on the basis of behavioral characteristics.

The purpose of the research is to study modern methods of treatment and correlation of autism in Kazakhstan.

The object of the study is modern approaches to the treatment of autism, and **the subject of the research** is the content of methods and techniques aimed at correcting autism spectrum disorders.

Methods of the research

The research work is based on a systematic review. The review was conducted on the basis of international scientific and Kazakh literature. All selected articles were published in peer-reviewed journals. We conducted an electronic search in the database of Google Scholar, Elsevier, Citeseer, PubMed, Web of Science, Scopus. Articles with good methodology from the last ten years have been selected. As a result, those articles that met the selection criteria were included in the analysis. The search for materials was carried out on such keywords as: "autism", "treatment of autism", "disorders of the autism spectrum". Data extraction and analysis were synthesized in a descriptive form describing the importance and effectiveness of autism treatment. The study used publication meta-analyses, combining results from different studies, as well as systematic reviews of the literature.

Autism spectrum disorders: classification, definition of concepts, symptoms

There are several approaches to the classification of autism spectrum disorders. Consider some of them: the International Classification of Diseases of the 10th revision (ICD-10) and the classification of autism spectrum disorders proposed by K. Gilbert and T. Peters in the book "Autism. Medical and pedagogical impact [3]. According to the International Classification of Diseases of the 10th revision, the spectrum of autistic disorders is placed in the class "Mental disorders and behavioral disorders", the block "Disorders of psychological development". According to the ICD-10, ASD includes: Childhood autism (F84.0), Atypical autism (F84.1), Rett syndrome (F84.2), Other childhood disintegrative disorder (F84.3), Hyperactive disorder associated with mental retardation and stereotypical movements (F84.4), Asperger's syndrome (F84.5) [4].

According to the classification of K. Gilbert and T. Peters, ASD includes: classic autism or Kanner's syndrome, Asperger's syndrome, childhood pervasive (disintegrative) disorder, other diseases similar to autism, autistic conditions. According to these classifications, it is clear that many of their components are similar or identical. For example, childhood autism and classic autism or childhood pervasive (disintegrative) disorder and other childhood disintegrative disorders. If we consider them together, then it is necessary to study the manifestations of the following major disorders: Classical autism or Kanner's syndrome, Asperger's syndrome and the Savant's syndrome included in it, Rett's syndrome, Atypical autism, Childhood pervasive (disintegrative) disorder, Autistic states [5].

In correctional work, the goal is always to achieve a free and independent life for a person with autism, which in practice means to teach as many ways as possible to adequately interact with the outside world. In the traditions of Russian special pedagogy, it is customary to use complex intervention, that is, a combination of medical and psychological-pedagogical methods. The range of prescribed medications is very wide, from neuroleptics to antidepressants, from antihypertensives to anticonvulsants. Main principles: use medications only in cases where they cannot be dispensed with; use long-term low-dose maintenance therapy rather than high-dose course therapy; not to try to cure autism, but to mitigate the symptoms that interfere with the work of the teacher and psychologist, to remove, if possible, the accompanying symptoms. Of the current negative trends, we are concerned about the use of large doses of stimulants and nootropics, non-compliance with age restrictions on the use of certain antipsychotics, especially risperidone. Unfortunately, in these matters, control by the state is clearly insufficient [6].

Among the psychological and pedagogical methodological approaches to the correction of autism, two groups can be distinguished. The main ones, which allow you to master communication skills, household, educational, professional, labor and other practical skills that are necessary in real life. The use of one of these approaches is a necessary condition for the organization of training, but this is not always enough. Auxiliary methods create conditions for the implementation of the main ones, which is sometimes necessary, but never sufficient (except for a few mild cases in combination with adequate conditions for education and training, primarily in the family). Among the auxiliary methods, you can find hippotherapy, swimming with dolphins, and holding, various methods of aesthetic therapy and game therapy, and even yoga. Using only helper methods is one of the most common mistakes. Other most typical problems are an unfortunate combination of methods and an inadequate choice of the main method [7].

Tactics for the treatment of early childhood autism

The autism syndrome is one of the most difficult problems of modern psychiatry. Not only psychiatrists, but also psychologists, teachers, biologists, specialists in the field of social rehabilitation are trying to treat children's atypical autism. Modern clinical and biological studies indicate the nosological heterogeneity of this disease, a wide variability of various types of autism spectrum disorders.

In childhood autism, drug therapy facilitates psychological and pedagogical correction, helps to relieve productive painful symptoms (anxiety, fears, psychomotor agitation, obsessive phenomena) and also raises the general and mental tone. The drug "pillow" makes a child with autism more accessible to psychotherapy, education and training. Combining biological and social correction contributes to their mutual potentiation. From the point of view of the main goal - the reconstruction of mental development, the possibility of adequate education and training - the main task of drug treatment of children with autism is to stimulate the energy potential and remove sensory-affective hyperesthesia. A complex of neuroleptics, anticonvulsants and tranquilizers carries this out.

An important factor is the role of the "background" on which RDA develops. First, we are talking about organic insufficiency of the central nervous system. Often at the very beginning of treatment with neuroleptics, pronounced side effects, such as extrapyramidal ones, are observed. Obviously, here there is a summation of organically determined side effects of the drug with a probable extrapyramidal insufficiency inherent in RDA itself. Therefore, methods of hardware diagnostics remain mandatory: electroencephalogram, echoencephalogram, and electrocardiogram. The "background" factor also concerns the somatic characteristics of an autistic child. A number of signs suggest that early childhood autism has its own somatic appearance in terms of both constitutional physiological features and an innate tendency to insufficiency of a number of systems. A significant part of autistic children have an asthenic physique, pallor of the skin, reduced muscle and skin turgor, and general hypotrophy. Many are

prone to allergic reactions, including medicinal ones. There is often a general delay in physical development. Weakness and perversion of appetite, paradoxical reactions to certain medications, "unexplained" gastrointestinal disorders and other symptoms quite often make it possible to suspect an enzymatic deficiency of an unclear nature and origin. This requires not only increased caution in the choice of psychotropic drugs, but also the search in each individual case for adequate symptomatic therapy with enzyme containing, antihistamine drugs, as well as supportive restorative treatment [8].

In case of malnutrition and general retardation of physical development, in order to avoid overdose, one should also remember about the orientation of the dose of the drug not to the calendar age, but to the actual weight of the child. According to the theory of amygdala kindling, in individuals with residual organic pathology, with prolonged exposure to nonspecific social stress, exogenous organic asthenic factors, excessive stimulation of the limbic system occurs with depletion of the energy potential of GABAergic neurons and the formation of either an irritative-paroxysmal or epileptiform focus. This can be corrected by prescribing thymoisoleptic and antiepileptic drugs (AEDs) [9]. There are data in the literature on the use of various AEDs (carbamazepine, lamotrigine, valproic acid, topiramate, levetiracetam) in children with autism. They are usually used in combination with 2nd generation atypical antipsychotics, in particular risperidone. When prescribing AEDs in combination with risperidone, the following points should be considered.

Carbamazepines are quite potent inducers of liver enzymes. It is known that carbamazepine reduces the concentration of risperidone and its active metabolite in blood plasma [10]. If carbamazepine is added to risperidone, the concentration of risperidone decreases with chronic co-administration of drugs, and sometimes quite significantly. This fact must be taken into account when titrating doses of risperidone. With regard to topiramate, the literature describes the effectiveness of the combined use of risperidone and topiramate in children with autism. Rezaei et al. conducted an 8-week study that included 40 children aged 4-12 years. Patients were randomized into groups, one of which received a combination of topiramate and risperidone at doses of 100-200 and 2-3 mg/day, respectively, the second - risperidone and placebo. The results of treatment were assessed by changes in the baseline indicators of five generally accepted subscales on the scale of aberrant behavior (ABC). At the end of the study, patients treated with topiramate and risperidone showed a statistically significant decrease in ABC-I scores by 9.25 compared with baseline, and in children with risperidone and placebo, the scores decreased by 1.5 points. Statistically significant differences in favor of the combination of risperidone and topiramate were noted on other ABC subscales - stereotypic behavior and hyperactivity/non-compliance [11].

Some foreign researchers point to the effectiveness of other anticonvulsants, in particular levetiracetam, in the treatment of autism symptoms. For example, a study by Rugino et al. evaluated the effect of levetiracetam on autism symptoms such as hyperactivity, impulsivity, emotional instability, and aggressiveness. The study lasted 4 weeks and included 10 children aged 4-10 years. The effectiveness of therapy in relation to autism symptoms was assessed using generally accepted scales. According to the results obtained, the use of levetiracetam led to a statistically significant improvement in the scores compared to baseline. There was improvement in attention deficit, hyperactivity, and impulsivity as measured by the Achenbach Attention Scale, Conner Rating Scale, and Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder Index scale. Mood stabilization was also observed on the scales of the Conner Global Emotional Lability Index and the Conner Global Index. In addition, there was an improvement in the aggression scale of the Achenbach questionnaire in children who were unsuccessfully treated for autism with risperidone, carbamazepine and desipramine. The authors, however, caution that prior therapy should not be discontinued when prescribing levetiracetam [12].

Given the special role of epileptic brain dysfunction in the development of autism, levetiracetam can be successfully used in this category of patients. In addition, the positive effect of levetiracetam on cognitive and, in particular, speech functions makes it the drug of choice in patients with learning difficulties, developmental delay, speech disorders, mental disorders, in the treatment of which there is an improvement in mood, attention, speech functions, sleep, appetite, clarity of consciousness, behavior, psychotic symptoms disappear. Levetiracetam is chemically similar to piracetam. It does not have a negative effect on cognitive functions, and in some cases it has a stimulating effect. Unlike some other AEDs, levetiracetam does not affect the concentration of other drugs, so the addition of drugs to it does not cause clinically significant fluctuations in their plasma concentrations. This positive characteristic of levetiracetam is due to the fact that its metabolism does not depend on hepatic cytochrome P450, in addition, the drug does not stimulate microsomal liver enzymes. It is known that levetiracetam does not affect the concentration of risperidone, the main drug for the treatment of autism in children. Taking into account the data on the effectiveness of levetiracetam in some symptoms of RDA (table 1), the goal was to evaluate the clinical efficacy of the combined use of risperidone and levetiracetam in children with RDA [13].

Table 1. - Medicines for the treatment of RAD

Symptoms	Tactics			
	Levetiracetam	Sertraline	Risperidone	Carbamazepine
Somatovegetative insufficiency	+			
Symptom of identity, neophobia, impulsivity	+			
Stereotypical games	+		+	
Expressive speech disorders			+	
Affective manifestations	+		+	
Pathological fantasies			+	
Psychopathic manifestations			+	+
Neuroleptic depression	+	+		

Anticonvulsants, in particular levetiracetam, can be considered as adjunctive therapy in the treatment of RDA in combination with atypical antipsychotics, such as risperidone, in a certain group of patients with organic CNS insufficiency. Two aspects of levetiracetam in the treatment of children with autism are extremely significant for a practitioner: it does not impair liver function and does not adversely affect the cognitive functions of patients (in particular, memory and attention). All of the above makes the task of individualization of therapy in RDA particularly relevant, and also indicates the frequent unacceptability of standard treatment regimens and methods. The lability of the psychosomatic status of a child with autism, the need for frequent adjustments in therapy indicate the need to increase the requirements for the dynamics of observations of such children.

In Kazakhstan, there is a clinical protocol for the treatment of autism. Includes the following categories: Atypical autism (F84.1), Hyperactive disorder associated with mental retardation and stereotyped movements (F84.4), Autism in childhood (F84.0), Asperger's syndrome (F84.5) [14]. In Kazakhstan, a complex treatment of drug and non-drug methods is used in combination with psycho-educational and social work with the patient's family. The high efficiency of complex therapy is possible only with close, interdepartmental relay-race interaction of specialists: psychiatrists, neurologists, pediatricians, psychologists, teachers, speech pathologists and social workers. All types of therapeutic effects in ASD are used on the basis of an individual clinical assessment of the condition of patients [15].

Types and methods of providing medical care according to the protocol in Kazakhstan:

In cases of "Help Needed", i.e. regarding orderly behavior and the absence of dangerous for the patient and surrounding tendencies in patients with autism spectrum disorders, predominantly non-drug correction is prescribed on an outpatient basis.

In cases of "Significant Assistance Required", i.e. of moderate severity of the condition, as well as to ensure continuity in the provision of assistance when transferring from a hospital to an outpatient network, a day hospital can be used, where psychopharmacotherapy is also carried out (taking into account the movement of children, drugs in minimal dosages are prescribed in a change of scenery), all patients undergo habilitation / rehabilitation , social correction.

In cases of "Very Significant Assistance Required", i.e. acuteness of the condition with severe non-specific catatonic, behavioral disorders that pose a danger to oneself or others, it is recommended to prescribe psychopharmacotherapy, especially with atypical antipsychotics, and be carried out in a hospital, combined with non-drug correction. The outpatient stage of care (while maintaining a relatively orderly behavior and the absence of dangerous tendencies for the patient and others) follows the inpatient stage, or is independent and includes more advanced pedagogical correction, and if indicated, drug therapy is possible [16]. The primary diagnosis, determination of the route of management is carried out by a psychiatrist for adults and children. In cases of relatively orderly behavior and the absence of dangerous tendencies for the patient himself and surrounding tendencies, mental disorders are stopped during dynamic observation. After a diagnosis of pervasive developmental disorder has been established:

- the issue of the need for drug treatment of comorbid disorders is decided by a psychiatrist for adults, children, discussed with the parents or legal representatives of the child, guardian of an adult patient in case of deprivation of legal capacity and / or with their informed consent;

- the issue of the type of dynamic observation and its necessity is decided by the adult psychiatrist, the child's question is discussed with the parents or legal representatives of the child, the guardian of the adult patient in case of deprivation of legal capacity and / or with their informed consent.

Kazakhstan provides for complex intervention. Comprehensive intervention programs are based on the principles of applied behavior analysis. Early intensive behavioral intervention to develop cognitive abilities (verbal and non-verbal), language skills (expressive and receptive) and adaptive behavior (including social skills, communication skills and life skills) for preschool children. There are several models. Denver model of early intervention, for children with ASD aged 14 to 30 months to develop language skills. A Comprehensive, Inclusive LEAP (Learning Experiences - An Alternative Program for Preschoolers and Parents) program for preschool children with ASD aged 4+ to develop cognitive, language and social skills, and reduce ASD symptoms [nineteen]. A comprehensive program TEACCH (Treatment and Education of Autistic and Related Communication Handicapped Children for the treatment and education of children with autism and related communication problems) for children, adolescents and young people with ASD in order to improve social behavior and reduce the frequency of unwanted behavior, develop cognitive, verbal , motor skills, perception skills [17].

The above methods of treatment in Kazakhstan are quite modern and effective. However, the question of how well these methods of treatment are implemented, in particular complex correlation remains important. As we wrote earlier in Kazakhstan, there is a problem with the centers where the correlation and treatment of people with autism is carried out. Most of the centers are located only in large cities like Almaty, Astana. Many who live in villages or small towns simply do not have access to such centers. Therefore, it is very important to consider the availability of autism treatment methods throughout Kazakhstan. Moreover, it is necessary to strengthen work with families and relatives, since in Kazakhstan there is a social problem of perception of people with autism. Today in Kazakhstan, many people with autism still remain isolated at home. Kazakhstan has begun to develop inclusive education, which in the future will

enable children with autism to study in regular schools with everyone. Therefore, the integration of people with autism into society is considered in the autism treatment program in Kazakhstan, but it has begun to develop. Therefore, in the future we will be able to see the results of these methods.

Conclusion

Summing up, we can say that the literature on the research problem allows us to determine the following conclusions. Autism is a severe disorder of mental development, in which, first of all, the ability to communicate and social interaction suffers. The behavior of children with autism is also characterized by stereotypy and often destructiveness. Without specialized education, more than 90% of children with autism and similar disorders are doomed to severe mental disability, while with timely and adequate correction, up to 60% get the opportunity to study according to the school curriculum, and almost everyone can adapt to family conditions. As a result, it is important to carry out the correction already in childhood, so that adults with such disorders reach a satisfactory level of social adaptation. Many of these people, having sufficient knowledge, skills and abilities in various fields, are completely unadapted to independent life in society due to the lack of treatment by the correlation method.

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Geographic Sciences

БИОЛОГИЯНЫ ОҚЫТУДА БІЛІМ АЛУШЫЛАРДЫҢ ТАБИҒАТТЫ ҚОРҒАУ ІС- ӘРЕКЕТІН ҰЙЫМДАСТЫРУ

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Аңдатпа

Бұл мақалада биологияны оқытуда білім алушылардың бастауыш сыныптан бастап, жоғарғы сынып оқушылар арасындағы табиғатты қорғау іс-әрекеттерін ұйымдастыру іс-шаралары қарастырылған.

Адамзатты қоршаған табиғи орта (су, топырақ, ауа, өсімдік, жануарлар) биосфераның жай құрам бөліктері емес, олар бір - біріне тығыз байланысқан біртұтас ғаламшарлық жүйе. Табиғатты сүюге, қорғауға, қоршаған ортаны қорғайтын санамызда салауатты адамзаттар тәрбиелеуге бүкіл оқу тәрбие мекемелері, саяси ұйымдар, ғылыми орталықтар, оқу орындары, сондай - ақ әрбір жеке адамдардың біртұтас жұмыла атсалысуы өмір талабына айналады. Себебі адамдар тарапынан болған зиянды әрекет әлі де жалғасып, табиғи орта көркемдігі бүлінуде. Табиғатпен мәдени қарым - қатынасты қалыптастыру, адам экологиясы мәдинетін дамытуға қатысты екенін рухани қазынамызды жасаушылар қашан да дабыл көтеріп, араша түсіп, тәлім - тәрбие ісі шараларына жол салып келеді. Жалпы қазақ қаламгерлері өз туындылары арқылы сай - сүйекті сырқататын табиғи апаттардан қалай құтыламыз, ертеңгі күнге не қалдырамыз деген мәселелерді шешуді ғана алға тартпай, оның жолы ең алдымен, адам биологиясын дұрыстауды, туған өлке табиғатына жан- ашыр ұрпақ тәрбиелеуді жедел қолға алуды үндейді.

Кілт сөздер: биология, табиғатты қорғау, қоршаған орта, су, топырақ, ауа, өсімдік, жануарлар.

ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ ПРИРОДООХРАННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ОБУЧАЮЩИХСЯ ПРИ ИЗУЧЕНИИ БИОЛОГИИ

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматриваются мероприятия по организации природоохранной деятельности обучающихся в преподавании биологии, начиная с начальной школы и заканчивая старшеклассниками.

Окружающая человечество природная среда (вода, почва, воздух, растения, животные) - это не просто составные части биосферы, это единая планетарная система, тесно связанная друг с другом. В любви, защите природы, воспитании здоровых людей в нашем сознании, защищающем окружающую среду, жизненным вызовом становится сплоченность всех учебных заведений, политических организаций, научных центров, учебных заведений, а также каждого отдельного человека. Потому что вредная деятельность со стороны людей все еще продолжается, и красота природной среды разрушается. Что

касается формирования культурного взаимодействия с природой, развития культуры экологии человека, то создатели нашей духовной сокровищницы всегда поднимают тревогу, пробиваются в воспитательные мероприятия. В целом казахские писатели призваны не только решать вопросы, как мы избавимся от стихийных бедствий, что оставим на завтра, но и, прежде всего, наладить биологию человека, оперативно взяться за воспитание подрастающего поколения в природе родного края.

Ключевые слова: биология, охрана природы, окружающая среда, вода, почва, воздух, растения, животные.

ORGANIZATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL ACTIVITIES OF STUDENTS IN THE STUDY OF BIOLOGY

Annotation

This article discusses measures for the organization of environmental activities of students in biology teaching, starting from elementary school and ending with high school students.

The natural environment surrounding humanity (water, soil, air, plants, animals) is not just components of the biosphere, it is a single planetary system closely related to each other. In love, protection of nature, education of healthy people in our consciousness, protecting the environment, the cohesion of all educational institutions, political organizations, scientific centers, educational institutions, as well as each individual becomes a vital challenge. Because harmful activity on the part of people is still going on, and the beauty of the natural environment is being destroyed. As for the formation of cultural interaction with nature, the development of the culture of human ecology, the creators of our spiritual treasury always raise the alarm, make their way into educational activities. In general, Kazakh writers are called not only to solve the issues of how we will get rid of natural disasters, what we will leave for tomorrow, but also, first of all, to establish human biology, to promptly take up the upbringing of the younger generation in the nature of their native land.

Key words: biology, nature conservation, environment, water, soil, air, plants, animals.

Қазіргі кезде дүние жүзінде ғылыми - техникалық жетістіктің қауырт өсуі зиянды өнеркәсіп қалдықтарын көбейтіп, қоршаған табиғи ортаға және ондағы тіршілікке көп зиян келтіре бастады. Табиғаттың көптеген заңдылықтарын білмей оңай олжа табуға бағытталған өндіріс табиғатқа жасаған қастандықпен тең. Елбасымыз Н.Ә. Назарбаев "Қазақстан -2030" жолдауында "Біздің табиғат ресурстарымыз орасан зор байлық, әлемдік тәжірибеде табиғи байлығы бар елдер оны дұрыс игере білмегендіктен кедей елдер қатарынан шыға алмай қалғаны" туралы айтқан. Олай болса қазақ жерінің байлығын бағалайтын, табиғатын аялайтын жас ұрпақтың білімі мен тәрбиесіне көбірек көңіл бөлу - қазіргі өмір талабы

Бүгінгі таңда жасөспірімдерге үздіксіз биологиялық білім беру жүйесін жаңаша құру және оны өміршең ету республикамыздың білім беру тұжырымдамасында жан-жақты қарастырылған. Оның үстіне жалпы білім беретін мектептерді 12 жылдық оқу жүйесіне көшу қалыптасқан оқу үрдісіне көптеген өзгерістер әкелгені сөзсіз.

Осы тұрғыда бастауыш сыныптарда оқушыларды 6 жастан бастап оқыту көзделіп отыр. Соңдықтан оның оқу жоспары мен бағдарламаларын оңтайландыру қажеттігі туары анық. Соңғы жылдары бастауыш сыныптарда «Жаратылыстану» пәні оқытылады. Бұл пәннің жасөспірімдердің дүниетанымын қалыптастыруда рөлі зор. Яғни, үздіксіз білім берудің біртұтастық, жүйелендіріп кіріктіре оқыту ұстамдарының бірізділігін жүзеге асырады. Тағы бір жағдай соңғы жылдары үздіксіз биологиялық білім беруді жүзеге асыру барысында кейбір бастауыш мектептерде биология курсы енгізіле бастады. Көптеген мұғалімдер өзінің авторлық бағдарламалары бойынша сабақ жүргізеді. Бастауыш мектепке арналған биологиялық оқу бағдарламаларын бір жүйеге келтіру міндетті тұр. Бастауыш сынып

биологиясы бүгінгі талапқа сай «Жаратылыстану» курстарына қосымша білім беруге бағытталған.

Алдына қойған негізгі мақсаттары:

1. Жасөспірімдерге табиғатты қорғау адам өмірімен байланыстыра отырып білім беру.

2. Жасөспірімдерге табиғаттың бір-бірімен үнемі байланыста болатынын ұғындыру.

3. Оқушыларда алғашқы биологиялық ұғымдарды қалыптастыру және табиғатқа деген жауапкершілік ой-өрісін дамыту.

Мәселен, 1-сыныпта: Қоршаған орта мен адамның арасындағы қарым-қатынастар, табиғи ортаның біртұтастығы және бір-бірімен қатынас түрлері, табиғат нысандары, өсімдіктер мен жануарлар туралы алғашқы оң және теріс көзқарастар туралы білім беріледі.

Екінші сынып бойынша – адамның табиғатқа деген сұранысы мен қамқорлығы, туған өлке мен атамекен, тұрмыстық ғимараттар, оның табиғаттан алынып жасалатын, тұрған мекені мен оның құрауыштарының қажеттілігі туралы ой-өрістер дамытылады.

Үшінші сыныпта – адамның табиғатты пайдалану кезіндегі теріс іс-әрекеттерін көрсету арқылы олардың табиғатқа деген қамқорлығын, аяушылық сезімдерін ояту, өсімдік пен жануарлар дүниесінің адамға қажет екеніне толық көздерін жеткізу, үй және мектеп үлесіндегі өсімдіктерге қамқорлық жасау элементтерін бойларына дарыту.

Төртінші сыныпта оқушыларда өсімдіктер мен жануарлардың әр түрлілігі мен бірлестіктерін, топтарын ажырату, олардың тіршілігі туралы қызығушылықтары мен ынтасын арттыру көзделеді. Алғаш рет тірі организмдерді қорғау керектігін түсіндіру. Қызыл кітаптың мақсатын ұғындыру. Сол сияқты оқушылардың қоршаған ортаның сапасы, ластану және адамның денсаулығы арасындағы байланыстарды ажырату деңгейіне дейін білімдері дамытылады. Әрбір курсты аяқтауы табиғатқа шығу арқылы бекітіледі. Оқушылар естіген және көргендерін қолымен ұстап түйсініп, табиғаттың әр түрлі құбылыстарынан ләззат алады.

Туған мекенге деген алғашқы патриоттық сезімі оянады. Оқушылардың білім мен біліктілігіне қойылатын негізгі талаптар (I-IV сыныптар).

I сынып бойынша оқушылар:

- айнала қоршаған ортаны бағдарлауды;
- табиғаттағы заттарды, өсімдіктер мен жануарларды;
- ауа, су, топырақты ажыратып олардың адам үшін қажеттілігін;
- адамның табиғаттағы орнын ажырата білулері тиіс. Оқушылардың біліктілігі:
- табиғаттағы заттарды (өлі және тірі заттар) ажырата білу;
- ауа, су, топырақты ажырату және олардың пайдасы туралы айтып бере алу;
- өсімдік пен жануарларды ажыратып, олардың адам үшін қажеттілігін іс жүзінде білу.

II сынып бойынша оқушылар:

- өзінің тұрған үйін, мекеннің тазалығын, жеке басының гигиенасын сақтауды;
- ірі құрылыстар, көліктердің түрлер мектеп т.б. мекемелер туралы;
- тұрған мекенінің айналасындағы табиғат құрауыштарын, азық –түлік сапасын, айнала мен көше тазалығын сақтауды;

- үй және жабайы жануарларды ажыратып, олардың адам өміріндегі маңызын білулері тиіс.

Оқушылардың біліктілігі :

- үйдің айналасы, көше, үй –іші және өзінің жеке басының тазалығын сақтауды;
- ірі ғимараттар мен мекемелерге бару, жол жүрудің қарапайым ережелерін;
- азық-түліктің сапасын ажырату, үй және түздегі жануарлармен қамқорлық қарым-қатынас жасау және сақтану шараларын;
- өсімдік пен жануарларды немесе ғимараттардың аттарын біліп ажырата алады.

III сынып бойынша оқушылар:

- табиғаттағы заттардың бір-бірімен байланысы, адамның табиғатты пайдалану себептерін;

- табиғаттағы өзгерістерді байқау, мәдени өсімдіктер мен орманның ерекшеліктерін;

- бау-бақша, мектеп үлесі, гүлдердің түрлері, оны күту, олардың пайдасы мен зияны туралы мәселелерді білулері тиіс.

Оқушының біліктілігі:

- табиғаттағы заттарды атап, оның не үшін керектігін;

- өсімдіктер мен орманның түрлерін ажыратып, олардың маңызын;

- пайдалы мен зиянды организмдердің бірнешеуін атап, олардың адам үшін маңызын айтып беруді меңгереді.

IV сынып бойынша оқушылар:

- адамның табиғат байлықтарын дұрыс пайдалануы немесе пайдаланбауы;

- өсімдік пен жануарлардың мәңгі еместігі, олардың сиреп немесе біржола құрып кететіні;

- тірі организмдердің өмір сүруі және тіршілігінің адамға тәуелділігі;

- қызыл кітаптың маңызы және кейбір сирек аң мен құстар жайлы және оларды қорғау;

- өзен мен көлдер және жерді қадірлей білу мен олардың ластануының себептері;

- ауаның сапасы және адам денсаулығы туралы мәселелерді білулері тиіс;

- табиғи байлықтардың бірнешеуін атап, олардың қорын, дұрыс пайдалану барысына баға беруді;

- сирек өсімдіктер мен жануарлардың бірнеше түрлерін атап және кездесетін жерлерін білу, оларды қорғау жолдарын;

- қызыл кітапты оқып, оның мәнін түсіндіріп және өз өлкесінде кездесетіндерін есепке алуды; - өзен мен көлдер, ормандарда тіршілік ететін аң мен құстарды ажыратып, оларды қорғауға қорғау туралы істәжірибелерді;

- ауа мен судың сапасы және тазалығын ажыратып, олардың немен ластанатынын ажыратып, талдау жасауды игереді.

“Табиғатты қорғау” тақырыбына пәнаралық конференция өткізу. Мақсаты: “Табиғатты қорғауға адамның іс-әрекеттерінің тигізетін әсері” тақырыбына пәнаралық конференция өткізу.

Жоспар:

1. Конференция міндеті мен мақсаты.

2. Мұғалімнің қосымша жұмыстары және оқушылар тапсырмасы. Сценариді оқушылар біліктілігін қалыптастыру бағытында өңдеу: жалпылама ойлау, биосфераны тіршілікке қажетті сфера тұрғысынан жалпылама қарастыру. Экологиялық мәселелердің өзектілігі, болашақ және қазіргі ұрпақтардың өмір сүруіне қажетті қолайлы жағдайларды қамтамасыз ету мақсатында оларды шешуге деген объективті қажеттілік мектептің алдына оқушыларға экологиялық білім мен тәрбие берудің жаңа міндеттерін қойып отыр.

Бастауыш мектеп оқушыларында табиғатқа деген жауапкершілік қатынасының процесі оның көпжақты бағалығы – эстетикалық, танымдық, экономикалық, практикалық меңгеруі негізінде жүзеге асырылады. Табиғатты қорғауды жауапкершілікпен әрекет етуге дайындық пен қабілеттілік және адамның интеллектуалдық, эмоциялық және жігерлілік сапаларының дамуымен тығыз байланысты. Оқушылардың қоршаған табиғатқа және азаматтық қатынастарының күшеюі тек білімдер жүйесі ғана емес, белгілі бір дағдылар, іскерліктер, әдептердің қалыптасуымен байланысты.

Оқушы қоршаған ортаға және табиғатты қорғау жауапкершілік қатынасы үш салада көрінеді: жеке мінез-құлығының мәдениетінде, қоршаған табиғи ортаны жақсарту, оны күту,

қорғауда қоғамдық-пайдалы еңбекті орындауға белсенді қатысуда; табиғат қорғаудың қазіргі заманғы идеяларын кеңінен насихаттауда.

Олай болса, оқушылардың табиғатты қорғау туралы білімдердің органикалық бірлігі нәтижесінде, оны қорғауға іс жүзінде қатысудың қажеттілігін ұғынуы нәтижесінде қалыптасады.

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Agricultural Sciences

ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS OF FOOD INDUSTRY WASTE AND FOOD LOSS USE OPTIONS

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Annotation: If food loss and food waste were a country, it would be the third largest source of greenhouse gas emissions. The Sustainable Development Goal envisages halving food waste and minimizing food loss by 2030. In support of this important goal, UNEP's first Food Waste Index report presents the scale of food industry waste and a methodology that allows countries to measure and track baseline indicators. The report estimates that food waste from households, retail chains, and the food service industry averages 931 million tons annually. About 570 million tons of this food industry waste occurs at the domestic stage. The report also shows that the global average of about 74 kg of food wasted per person per year is remarkably similar to low-middle-income to high-income countries, indicating that most countries have room for improvement.

Global levels of food industry waste are of increasing concern and thus require urgent action to minimize their negative environmental and socio-economic consequences. In the developed world, on average, 20-40% of food industry waste originates in the production phase of supply chains, and that food industry waste is often managed in non-optimized, irrational ways and causes significant negative side effects on the environment. This study describes a modern decision-making tool that enables food industry manufacturers to evaluate a range of food industry waste management options, including identifying the most sustainable solution.

Key words: Food production, environment, food waste, greenhouse gases, food supply chain

Analysis and analyses.

Waste generation is often a natural consequence of food processing operations such as sugar factories, dairies, meat, fish, fruit and vegetable processing plants. As environmental regulations become more and more stringent, proper management of food waste has become an essential part of modern food processing management. The amount of waste generation and the controllability of the waste generated by the process have become criteria for evaluating the applicability of the process. The continuous growth of the world's population increases the demand on the food supply, thereby increasing food waste in the supply chain, which in turn leads to environmental pollution and depletion of natural resources. In addition, the food processing industry produces large volumes of inedible food waste. Landfilling and also incineration are not promising approaches of a rational food industry waste management system for environmental sustainability and economic efficiency. Recycling and reuse are important principles of the circular economy, which focuses on energy and resource recovery from food industry waste for a sustainable ecology. Food industry wastes are mainly rich in organic matter such as carbohydrates, proteins and even lipids, which can be used as feed stock for the production or regeneration of biofertilizers, biofuels, biogases, rich bioactive mixtures, natural nutrients and industrial enzymes. In addition, an integrated biological approach with a zero solid discharge concept for the recovery of energy and resources from food industry waste has been determined to be optimal from an economic point of view. This review highlights technological advances in the rational management of food industry waste, including processing methods and product recovery[9,11] .

Waste can be produced in a food processing plant in many forms, including solid waste such as husks and scraps and liquid waste such as sewage and sludge. This article focuses primarily on wastewater because wastewater management is more difficult than solid waste management.

Most food waste is generated at only two stages of the supply chain:

1. during production
2. in the consumption stage

Currently, several initiatives aim to raise consumer awareness of the costs of food waste and provide advice on how to prevent food waste. As a result, the food industry often manages its food waste in non-optimized ways and makes decisions based on a limited number of factors, such as the availability of waste management facilities and the resource requirement to implement the solution. In addition, a large part of industrial food waste is unavoidable, commonly known as food by-products, which in some cases indicates that food waste management is more necessary than preventive measures.

EU research shows that food industry waste is directly responsible for:

1. 42% of households
2. 32% of food industry producers
3. 5% of retailers
4. 15% of catering (cafe, restaurant) sector.

To further improve waste management practices in the food industry, it is important to properly understand the various elements involved in the process [8]:

1. Food industry waste: understanding the characteristics of the raw material to be managed (i.e. food industry waste).
2. Food industry waste management alternatives: be aware of the available food industry waste management options and understand their performance.
3. Sustainability implications: to recognize the environmental and socio-economic implications of various food industry waste management practices.

FAO's Food Balance statistics show that supply cycle losses for food groups such as fruit, meat and vegetables, including vegetables, are below about 5 percent of production or domestic supply. Food industry losses reported by national agencies and government departments indicate that consumer food waste typically averages 20 percent or more of food purchased.

Redistribution structures and community-based actions have emerged that have been successful in removing food industry waste from supply chains. Thus, redistribution of nearer-to-use-by foods and structures that facilitate the provision of food to recipients, such as "community refrigerators," play a particularly important role in reducing food industry waste, particularly in areas where communities face limited food availability and accessibility. . It is clear in this area that the reduction of food industry waste from the food supply chain to the point of sale of the consumer directly depends on the application of many measures. That is, there is no concrete solution here, and many actions that redistribute, engage communities and use modern online technologies will contribute to minimizing food industry waste and creating awareness of responsible food use. The research presented here highlights the value of modern conservation technologies, including the need for food category models that take into account different shelf-life as well as quality considerations, as these will in turn help coordinate food policy.

Previous studies of fresh and frozen food shelf life have shown a reduction in household waste associated with frozen food use. A Dutch study developed a stochastic model to show the effect of environmental, frozen and also fresh canning on household food industry waste. This study is extremely important because it shows how food preservation methods that extend the shelf life of food at home can minimize food industry waste over an annual period. These studies also show the importance of food preparation in food industry waste minimization, as well as education about the best use of food in households.

Schemes that attract and redistribute resources to reduce food industry waste do not fully address the issue of consumer wastage of food, including beverages, because they are not designed to minimize food industry waste. They redistribute food that would otherwise go to waste. The research conducted here is aimed at reducing the waste of food purchased for consumption. Food preservation and the types of food preservation methods available to consumers can greatly facilitate this, as it minimizes food degradation and improves food utilization in the household. Although the production of food industry waste raises greenhouse gas emissions or the carbon footprint of food consumption, this is a largely overlooked approach. It is important to consider reducing food industry waste as a consequence of using canned foods, as previous research has shown that consumers can help determine the sustainability of prepared meals.

This study demonstrates how frozen preservation can provide greater consumer use of food and minimize household food industry waste. It is not intended to imply that frozen is the only option for minimizing consumer food industry waste. It is hoped that the research will highlight the use of preservation methods in reducing consumer food industry waste and that there are several factors that must work together to be successful in reducing food industry waste. UK market research compared household consumption of fresh and frozen foods. Thus, it was determined that the amount of consumer food industry waste directly depends on the method of food preservation. The study found that household food industry waste for frozen products was reduced by an average of 47 percent compared to fresh products. In this study, frozen foods are defined as all foods frozen by the quick-freeze method. This, in turn, ensures the immunity of the cell and, among other things, preserves the nutritional value of the food.

It should be noted that frozen foods have played a significant role in the evolution of the global food supply chain. Otherwise, food losses in agriculture and also in processing will increase. Many of the food supply chain issues highlighted in current food loss and food industry waste research are not present in frozen foods because flash freezing allows for the extended shelf life sought by many food industry waste minimization initiatives. However, ice cream is kept in the midst of "clean label" trends and often provides more portion control at home. Thus, the "Clean Label" trend is clearly defined in the retail setting, where there are demands for an ingredient label that analyzes ingredients and communicates any potential allergens introduced in processing and manufacturing.

Continuous consumption and production is a new concept for achieving productive growth that attracts more interest in optimal and sustainable use of resources, energy and infrastructure to ensure a high quality of human life. It seeks to formulate overall development strategies by minimizing economic, environmental and social costs, increasing global productivity and minimizing poverty. Global natural resource use reached an average of 92.1 billion tons in 2017, up from 27 billion tons in 1970, with annual production rates increasing since 2000, up 254%. Bioeconomy is characterized as the development of biologically renewable resources and the transformation of these resources into value-added products, including food, biofuels, feed and also bioenergy.

Due to the developing bioeconomy, the demand for land is increasing, where a certain part of land must be preserved to meet essential needs. An example of this is sequestering carbon forests. In this way, rather than multiplying the pressures on resources, the optimal and synergistic exploitation of resources should be promoted by the growth of the bioeconomy. This study intends to determine how a circular economy can be achieved through the rational management of sustainable food industry waste.

Also, food industry waste is a global issue that deserves attention in developed and developing countries, linking food health, food safety and other important aspects of

sustainability. Why is there still food waste when we know that humanity has a global problem in the food industry? Let's consider a few aspects that create this food waste:

1. Economic entities refuse to present food products that are not in good shape.
2. Catering facilities (cafes, restaurants) throw food waste into the street.
3. Sales networks engaged in the sale of food products keep food shelves full in order to attract the attention of buyers.
4. Households throw away food scraps with or without expiration date.

As a result of these processes, most of the food is thrown into landfills. This, in turn, results in the accumulation of those foods on top of other food residues. At the end of this process, it ends with the formation of methane gas, which we consider dangerous. In particular, it should be noted that methane gas, which is considered dangerous, is about 25 times more effective than carbon dioxide. Due to its type, methane gas is considered a greenhouse gas. For this reason, indirect methane gas seriously harms the environment. It should also be noted that greenhouse gases are a means of increasing climate instability[4].

What solutions should we implement to overcome these global problems? Let's look at some aspects of this issue:

1. To achieve a minimum carbon footprint
2. Avoiding additional costs when shopping in store chains
3. To be able to save as much as possible on labor costs, as well as labor costs
4. To achieve the maximum prevention of contamination during the production process of food products and also during the process of their sale

Research shows that every step of the processes considered important to eliminate waste in the food industry today needs to undergo necessary changes. In other words, changes mean processes from farmers and food processors to supermarkets and individual customers. More importance should be given to balancing the flow of supply and demand. This means that less natural resources are used to produce food that is not currently considered essential. If supply exceeds a certain amount, then food redistribution processes must be implemented. From another point of view, arrangements can be made to send those foods to those in need.[5]

The main benefits of reducing food industry waste streams are:

1. To save labor costs due to the preparation of food products and, including, the storage of those products
2. Which food products will be used, to achieve a more rational management of those products
3. Achieving a rational reduction of methane emissions from the sites while also resulting in a lower carbon footprint.
4. When we buy food to the extent of our demand, we should save as much as we can and avoid external expenses that are considered additional.

In the text of the article, the "Hierarchy of Food Recovery" prism is explained. This prism plans aspects of handling food products. The shown prism shows the methods from the most optimal to the least optimal [10]:

1. Early prevention by minimizing the total volume of food products produced
2. Donation of leftover food products to community structures
3. Giving the collected food product waste to the farmers to feed the animals
4. Delivery of used oils for the preparation of biodiesel fuel
5. Composted food waste for the production process of organic matter used to fertilize the soil
6. Last resort for unconsumed food products

Food industry waste is not the same for different products. Thus, food industry waste can be divided into two types:

1. plant
2. animal.

In addition, food waste can be divided into seven subcategories:

1. roots and tubers,
2. fruits and vegetables,
3. cereals,
4. oil plants and legumes,
5. dairy products,
6. fish and seafood
7. meat products.

The most wasted of these categories are fruits, vegetables, roots and tubers. Worldwide, an average of 40-50% of fruits, vegetables, roots and tubers are wasted or lost. In grains and fish, this rate reaches about 30%, and in meat, milk and also 20% in oil plants. These statistics call for finding the causes of food waste, including solutions to this harmful process [1.2]

In addition, retailers and markets also contribute to food industry waste and losses. In some cases, the products are not stored at the right temperature or in the right conditions. For example, various microorganisms and domestic animals can damage food stored in warehouses. As a result, food may be wasted after being purchased by consumers. In many cases, consumers buy or cook too much, which in turn results in the process of throwing away products. Food (or inedible parts of food) removed from the food supply chain and sent for animal feed, biomaterial processing or other industrial uses is considered "valorization and conversion" rather than "food waste". "

Food waste also includes food losses due to low quality vegetables, damaged crops left in the field and crops with low commercial value. Food waste and food loss can occur for a variety of reasons, including damage during transportation, improper storage or packaging, contamination, or problems at the processing stage, according to the FAO report.

Ecologically, food industry waste leads to chemical use such as fertilizers and pesticides, maximum fuel is used for transportation, and the more food corrodes in landfills, the more methane gas is produced, which is considered one of the most harmful greenhouse gases worldwide. There are two aspects to the contribution of food industry waste to greenhouse gas emissions[6.7] :

1. The process of decomposition of food industry waste after disposal in landfills
2. Life cycle from production to consumption (distribution, sale and also consumer waste).

Food industry waste, in particular, maximizes the level of greenhouse gas emissions by producing methane gas, one of the most potent gases. As global warming and climate change affect the environment, there is an increasing demand to minimize waste from the food industry.

The annual report of the FAO organization managed to reveal a clear pattern in food industry waste on a global scale. Although middle- and higher-income regions show more food loss and food waste at the downstream or consumption level, developing countries are more likely to lose or waste food at the upstream stage due to lack of appropriate harvesting technology and also infrastructure. . Food industry waste that ends up in landfills is a large volume of methane - a greenhouse gas even more powerful than CO₂. It should be noted that the maximum amount of greenhouse gases such as methane, CO₂ and chlorofluorocarbons results in the absorption of infrared rays. This, in turn, heats the earth's atmosphere, causing warming and climate change.

As agriculture accounts for an average of 70 percent of water used worldwide, food industry waste is also a major waste of fresh water and groundwater resources. The negative impacts of the food industry are significant in terms of water consumption and energy use. Throughout the supply chain, the food industry uses significant amounts of water and generates correspondingly large amounts of wastewater. Wastewater from the food industry consists of biological materials and dissolved organic and inorganic solids, which pose a significant

environmental burden. In terms of waste generation, the largest producers are dairy, cocoa/chocolate/confectionery, as well as brewing/distilling and meat processing industries. Prevention of food industry waste and prevention of environmental pollution, energy-saving process technologies, including water conservation, are always considered a priority. In addition, food industry waste reduction and disposal processes are also desirable strategies. This is due to the fact that waste streams from the food industry have a large organic content. These food industry wastes contain fats, sugars, antioxidants, etc. rich in valuable compounds such as[8]

As a general trend, developing countries face more food loss during agricultural production, while food waste at the consumer level is higher in middle and high income households. According to the FAO report, this is about 31-39 percent of total waste (compared to low-income regions (4-16 percent).

Food waste continues into the post-harvest process, but the exact amount of post-harvest losses is relatively unknown and difficult to estimate. Thus, the various factors that contribute to food waste, whether from a biological-ecological or socio-economic point of view, will limit the usefulness and, by extension, the reliability of the overall figures. Food safety requirements can also claim non-compliant foods before they are placed on the market [11]. Although this contrasts with efforts to recycle food industry waste (such as animal feed), safety regulations are in place to ensure consumer health. They are especially vital in the processing of food products of animal origin (for example, meat and dairy products). This is because products contaminated from these sources can cause and are associated with microbiological and chemical hazards [6.7]

Saving an average of one-fourth of all food currently wasted would feed a large number of undernourished people. From the point of view of future food security, research shows that. Halving the total amount of food calories currently lost and wasted (from 24% to 12%) by 2050 would save an average of 1.314 trillion kcal of food per year, which in turn would save enough to feed the world's population in 2050. about 22% of our predicted calorie needs. This is based on business-as-usual forecasts related to food demand. According to forecasts, minimization of food loss and food industry waste in the near future can lead to the following positive results [9]:

1. Minimizing poverty statistics and supporting the development process of rural areas by providing more food for the sales process and personal consumption of farmers;
2. benefiting women by increasing the return on investment and thus minimizing the total time spent working in the fields, as well as minimizing household food costs while spending less;
3. to help prevent the spread of agriculture to natural ecosystems;
4. to minimize the amount of water needed for agricultural production by rationally using already grown foods;
5. reduce agriculture-related greenhouse gas emissions by making greater use of food grown and including landfilling food industry waste.

In short, minimizing food loss and waste provides an opportunity to optimally benefit many sustainable development issues, including food security. However, the rational reduction of food loss and food industry waste will require an integrated vision system from all stakeholders in the supply chain, as well as a modern global food system where waste is not used as a profit mechanism. Nutrient losses during agricultural production occur when harvestable crops remain in the soil. It may be that weather conditions make harvesting unfavorable or impossible, or that the product does not meet high quality standards for the customer. It should be noted that in the United States, it has become common for farmers to grow more than they plan to sell in order to avoid the risk of a portion of their crop being destroyed by weather or pests. However, in cases where farmers produce more than the norm, but the market is not favorable for sale, many will leave the majority of the crop in the ground. The reason for this is that the collection of the product is more expensive than the sales. In this way, food markets work against farmers and policies

should be in place to protect farmers when crop losses occur and also to encourage harvesting during excess production to create surplus food supplies.

A major contributor to food loss is the lack of rational management and storage of fresh produce such as fruit, vegetables, meat and fish, especially in developing regions. In developing countries, an average of 19% of fruit and vegetable losses occur during processing and storage. Those nutrients can spoil more quickly in hot climates and thus require proper cool storage conditions after the capture, cutting or harvesting process. In addition, failure to store grains or legumes in an airtight environment allows moisture and pests to enter, which in turn potentially leads to contamination of the product with mold, toxins, or pests. This means that farmers have to sell their entire crop after the harvest process, which in turn can mean getting minimum prices, as supply will be maximum at this time. Thus, in low-income countries, the application and investment in technologies that facilitate the rational management and storage of fresh produce and grain can help minimize food loss.

Proper handling of fresh fruits and vegetables after the harvesting process and also during transportation is of great importance because these products are easily crushed and cannot be marketed in these cases. In developing countries, sacks and bags are often used in the process of transporting products, but they are poorly protected. One option is to use plastic crates, which can be reused for up to five years and are often easier to handle due to their manageable size and handles. A study in Sri Lanka found that plastic boxes reduced vegetable losses from about 30% to 5% compared to previous management strategies. Thus, research is needed to better manage and transport containers using locally sourced and environmentally friendly materials. Thus, increasing investment in infrastructure (i.e. construction of reliable roads) and including the introduction of basic refrigeration facilities for storing food products will minimize food losses and prevent spoilage of fresh food products, allowing them to reach the market faster [5].

In several countries, there are a number of problems with the disposal/treatment process of food industry waste due to inadequate waste management systems. The waste management practices used for the food industry waste disposal process are as follows:

1. landfill
2. incineration of waste
3. composting
4. anaerobic digestion

Landfills are a method that causes odor, methane and leaching problems. It is not recommended to use this method because it leads to social, ecological and even hygienic problems. The incineration method is an old technique used for the disposal process of a significant amount of solid waste (80-85%). This method produces heat that can be exploited for energy purposes in industry. In addition, since the combustion process takes place in uncontrolled conditions, it leads to the formation of more carbon emissions.

Composting and anaerobic treatment methods are based on the process of biological degradation of organic matter. Composting takes place under aerobic conditions and the end product is called compost. This method ensures the production of fertilizer that can be exploited in agricultural production. The main essence of this method is the mixing of obtained food industry waste with possible garden waste. So, that mixture is shredded, and then it is composted in a closed environment at a temperature of up to 70°C for a period of 2-4 weeks, on average. This intended process further accelerates the composting process. Thanks to this process, harmful microbes are destroyed. In the next step, the material is left outside to mature for about 1-3 months under high quality control before being used as a soil conditioner.

Implementing a composting process policy can lead to increased compost sales. It can also lead to many economic benefits. Also, relevant municipal institutions can pave the way for strengthening sustainability by minimizing greenhouse gas emissions, including preventing

erosion, and improving important soil quality. However, with the application of this technique, a number of problems such as NH₃, leakage, greenhouse gases and odors arise.

Anaerobic treatment method is a method that converts biomass into biogas and also digestion products in a controlled anaerobic atmosphere. The obtained biogas is a great source of energy with 60-70% methane, 30-40% CO₂ and other trace components. At the same time, the production of biogas fertilizer rich in components is ensured. Although this method is often used as a rational waste management method for sewage and animal manure, this practice also has a number of drawbacks. These include the following[3] :

1. Methane productivity
2. uncontrolled processing environment due to accumulation of volatile free fatty acids
3. Foaming problem due to lipid and high protein content
4. low buffering capacity due to rapid digestion of volatile fatty acids

When the methods used for food industry waste management are studied, it is seen that there is a need for sustainable and alternative methods of disposal. If the countries of the world can achieve minimum food industry waste, the benefits we will gain can include the following:

1. Saving labor costs due to rational management of food products to be used, including their preparation and storage.
2. Cost saving when we buy food as much as we will consume and also avoiding extra external expenses.
3. Minimizing methane emissions from landfills and achieving a lower carbon footprint.
4. Rational management of energy and resources, prevention of pollution related to the process of growing, producing, transporting and selling food products.

Land waste related to food industry waste is divided into two categories:

1. Using land to produce food
2. Land used for throwing food waste

There are two types of land, arable and non-arable. Arable land is where crops can be grown, and uncultivable land is not ideal for crops. These uncultivated lands are perfect for livestock. On average, about 900 million hectares of uncultivated land are used for meat production. An average of 11.5 billion hectares of the global land surface is used for agriculture. The land used for cultivation or animal husbandry is not a problem. The main problem is food industry waste. We never realize what we waste with food.

It should be noted that an average of 67 million tons of food is wasted in India every year, of which about 70-75% of food industry waste rots in landfills. In the short term, if we don't pay attention to the losses, the potential for over-yielding will also deteriorate. The concept of biodiversity includes the full spectrum of life among different species and types of organisms in an ecosystem. Thus, deforestation processes are being carried out in order to increase or increase animal husbandry. This, in turn, seriously affects our natural flora and fauna. If the number of livestock increases, more natural land is converted to pasture. The more cattle graze on the land, the more it becomes unfit for cultivation. Land becomes less natural and diverse.[10]

Conclusions

From what was previously presented, it should be noted that food industry waste is generated throughout the supply chain. In short, agricultural production - storage - processing - distribution - management - consumption processes. As a result, the main responsibility for food safety, including taking certain measures to prevent food waste, rests with those involved in that chain. In some EU countries, it is forbidden to sell food below cost. As a result, retailers are unable to sell fresh food products (toward the end of the day) at lower prices. This ban increases food waste in the supply chain we mentioned earlier. Actions taken by the states against food losses and food waste should be aimed at improving the optimality and sustainability of food supply chains. Since 2011, EU member states have been conducting targeted campaigns to inform the

public about the causes and consequences of food industry waste. Thus, measures to reduce food industry waste are proposed, and scientific information related to the sustainability and solidarity of the population is delivered. Legislative measures promoted by countries as well as positive practices aim to increase the optimality of food chains. These measures are very important for the sustainable development of economies and for the balancing of flows in the world trade system of agricultural products. There is a close relationship between food industry waste and the ecological situation. For every kg of food produced (through processing), about 4.5 kg of CO₂ is released into the atmosphere. Thus, if we take into account the approximately 89 million tons of food industry waste produced in Europe, this will lead to an average of 370 million tons of CO₂ equivalent, resulting in a greenhouse effect.

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Agricultural Sciences

ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS OF FOOD INDUSTRY WASTE AND FOOD LOSS USE OPTIONS

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Annotation: If food loss and food waste were a country, it would be the third largest source of greenhouse gas emissions. The Sustainable Development Goal envisages halving food waste and minimizing food loss by 2030. In support of this important goal, UNEP's first Food Waste Index report presents the scale of food industry waste and a methodology that allows countries to measure and track baseline indicators. The report estimates that food waste from households, retail chains, and the food service industry averages 931 million tons annually. About 570 million tons of this food industry waste occurs at the domestic stage. The report also shows that the global average of about 74 kg of food wasted per person per year is remarkably similar to low-middle-income to high-income countries, indicating that most countries have room for improvement.

Global levels of food industry waste are of increasing concern and thus require urgent action to minimize their negative environmental and socio-economic consequences. In the developed world, on average, 20-40% of food industry waste originates in the production phase of supply chains, and that food industry waste is often managed in non-optimized, irrational ways and causes significant negative side effects on the environment. This study describes a modern decision-making tool that enables food industry manufacturers to evaluate a range of food industry waste management options, including identifying the most sustainable solution.

Key words: Food production, environment, food waste, greenhouse gases, food supply chain

Analysis and analyses.

Waste generation is often a natural consequence of food processing operations such as sugar factories, dairies, meat, fish, fruit and vegetable processing plants. As environmental regulations become more and more stringent, proper management of food waste has become an essential part of modern food processing management. The amount of waste generation and the controllability of the waste generated by the process have become criteria for evaluating the applicability of the process. The continuous growth of the world's population increases the demand on the food supply, thereby increasing food waste in the supply chain, which in turn leads to environmental pollution and depletion of natural resources. In addition, the food processing industry produces large volumes of inedible food waste. Landfilling and also incineration are not promising approaches of a rational food industry waste management system for environmental sustainability and economic efficiency. Recycling and reuse are important principles of the circular economy, which focuses on energy and resource recovery from food industry waste for a

sustainable ecology. Food industry wastes are mainly rich in organic matter such as carbohydrates, proteins and even lipids, which can be used as feed stock for the production or regeneration of biofertilizers, biofuels, biogases, rich bioactive mixtures, natural nutrients and industrial enzymes. In addition, an integrated biological approach with a zero solid discharge concept for the recovery of energy and resources from food industry waste has been determined to be optimal from an economic point of view. This review highlights technological advances in the rational management of food industry waste, including processing methods and product recovery[9,11] .

Waste can be produced in a food processing plant in many forms, including solid waste such as husks and scraps and liquid waste such as sewage and sludge. This article focuses primarily on wastewater because wastewater management is more difficult than solid waste management.

Most food waste is generated at only two stages of the supply chain:

1. during production
2. in the consumption stage

Currently, several initiatives aim to raise consumer awareness of the costs of food waste and provide advice on how to prevent food waste. As a result, the food industry often manages its food waste in non-optimized ways and makes decisions based on a limited number of factors, such as the availability of waste management facilities and the resource requirement to implement the solution. In addition, a large part of industrial food waste is unavoidable, commonly known as food by-products, which in some cases indicates that food waste management is more necessary than preventive measures.

EU research shows that food industry waste is directly responsible for:

1. 42% of households
2. 32% of food industry producers
3. 5% of retailers
4. 15% of catering (cafe, restaurant) sector.

To further improve waste management practices in the food industry, it is important to properly understand the various elements involved in the process [8]:

1. Food industry waste: understanding the characteristics of the raw material to be managed (i.e. food industry waste).
2. Food industry waste management alternatives: be aware of the available food industry waste management options and understand their performance.
3. Sustainability implications: to recognize the environmental and socio-economic implications of various food industry waste management practices.

FAO's Food Balance statistics show that supply cycle losses for food groups such as fruit, meat and vegetables, including vegetables, are below about 5 percent of production or domestic supply. Food industry losses reported by national agencies and government departments indicate that consumer food waste typically averages 20 percent or more of food purchased.

Redistribution structures and community-based actions have emerged that have been successful in removing food industry waste from supply chains. Thus, redistribution of nearer-to-use-by foods and structures that facilitate the provision of food to recipients, such as "community refrigerators," play a particularly important role in reducing food industry waste, particularly in areas where communities face limited food availability and accessibility. . It is clear in this area that the reduction of food industry waste from the food supply chain to the point of sale of the consumer directly depends on the application of many measures. That is, there is no concrete solution here, and many actions that redistribute, engage communities and use modern online technologies will contribute to minimizing food industry waste and creating awareness of responsible food use. The research presented here highlights the value of modern conservation technologies, including the need for food category models that take into account different shelf-life as well as quality considerations, as these will in turn help coordinate food policy.

Previous studies of fresh and frozen food shelf life have shown a reduction in household waste associated with frozen food use. A Dutch study developed a stochastic model to show the effect of environmental, frozen and also fresh canning on household food industry waste. This study is extremely important because it shows how food preservation methods that extend the shelf life of food at home can minimize food industry waste over an annual period. These studies also show the importance of food preparation in food industry waste minimization, as well as education about the best use of food in households.

Schemes that attract and redistribute resources to reduce food industry waste do not fully address the issue of consumer wastage of food, including beverages, because they are not designed to minimize food industry waste. They redistribute food that would otherwise go to waste. The research conducted here is aimed at reducing the waste of food purchased for consumption. Food preservation and the types of food preservation methods available to consumers can greatly facilitate this, as it minimizes food degradation and improves food utilization in the household. Although the production of food industry waste raises greenhouse gas emissions or the carbon footprint of food consumption, this is a largely overlooked approach. It is important to consider reducing food industry waste as a consequence of using canned foods, as previous research has shown that consumers can help determine the sustainability of prepared meals.

This study demonstrates how frozen preservation can provide greater consumer use of food and minimize household food industry waste. It is not intended to imply that frozen is the only option for minimizing consumer food industry waste. It is hoped that the research will highlight the use of preservation methods in reducing consumer food industry waste and that there are several factors that must work together to be successful in reducing food industry waste. UK market research compared household consumption of fresh and frozen foods. Thus, it was determined that the amount of consumer food industry waste directly depends on the method of food preservation. The study found that household food industry waste for frozen products was reduced by an average of 47 percent compared to fresh products. In this study, frozen foods are defined as all foods frozen by the quick-freeze method. This, in turn, ensures the immunity of the cell and, among other things, preserves the nutritional value of the food.

It should be noted that frozen foods have played a significant role in the evolution of the global food supply chain. Otherwise, food losses in agriculture and also in processing will increase. Many of the food supply chain issues highlighted in current food loss and food industry waste research are not present in frozen foods because flash freezing allows for the extended shelf life sought by many food industry waste minimization initiatives. However, ice cream is kept in the midst of "clean label" trends and often provides more portion control at home. Thus, the "Clean Label" trend is clearly defined in the retail setting, where there are demands for an ingredient label that analyzes ingredients and communicates any potential allergens introduced in processing and manufacturing.

Continuous consumption and production is a new concept for achieving productive growth that attracts more interest in optimal and sustainable use of resources, energy and infrastructure to ensure a high quality of human life. It seeks to formulate overall development strategies by minimizing economic, environmental and social costs, increasing global productivity and minimizing poverty. Global natural resource use reached an average of 92.1 billion tons in 2017, up from 27 billion tons in 1970, with annual production rates increasing since 2000, up 254%. Bioeconomy is characterized as the development of biologically renewable resources and the transformation of these resources into value-added products, including food, biofuels, feed and also bioenergy.

Due to the developing bioeconomy, the demand for land is increasing, where a certain part of land must be preserved to meet essential needs. An example of this is sequestering carbon

forests. In this way, rather than multiplying the pressures on resources, the optimal and synergistic exploitation of resources should be promoted by the growth of the bioeconomy. This study intends to determine how a circular economy can be achieved through the rational management of sustainable food industry waste.

Also, food industry waste is a global issue that deserves attention in developed and developing countries, linking food health, food safety and other important aspects of sustainability. Why is there still food waste when we know that humanity has a global problem in the food industry? Let's consider a few aspects that create this food waste:

1. Economic entities refuse to present food products that are not in good shape.
2. Catering facilities (cafes, restaurants) throw food waste into the street.
3. Sales networks engaged in the sale of food products keep food shelves full in order to attract the attention of buyers.
4. Households throw away food scraps with or without expiration date.

As a result of these processes, most of the food is thrown into landfills. This, in turn, results in the accumulation of those foods on top of other food residues. At the end of this process, it ends with the formation of methane gas, which we consider dangerous. In particular, it should be noted that methane gas, which is considered dangerous, is about 25 times more effective than carbon dioxide. Due to its type, methane gas is considered a greenhouse gas. For this reason, indirect methane gas seriously harms the environment. It should also be noted that greenhouse gases are a means of increasing climate instability[4].

What solutions should we implement to overcome these global problems? Let's look at some aspects of this issue:

1. To achieve a minimum carbon footprint
2. Avoiding additional costs when shopping in store chains
3. To be able to save as much as possible on labor costs, as well as labor costs
4. To achieve the maximum prevention of contamination during the production process of food products and also during the process of their sale

Research shows that every step of the processes considered important to eliminate waste in the food industry today needs to undergo necessary changes. In other words, changes mean processes from farmers and food processors to supermarkets and individual customers. More importance should be given to balancing the flow of supply and demand. This means that less natural resources are used to produce food that is not currently considered essential. If supply exceeds a certain amount, then food redistribution processes must be implemented. From another point of view, arrangements can be made to send those foods to those in need.[5]

The main benefits of reducing food industry waste streams are:

1. To save labor costs due to the preparation of food products and, including, the storage of those products
2. Which food products will be used, to achieve a more rational management of those products
3. Achieving a rational reduction of methane emissions from the sites while also resulting in a lower carbon footprint.
4. When we buy food to the extent of our demand, we should save as much as we can and avoid external expenses that are considered additional.

In the text of the article, the "Hierarchy of Food Recovery" prism is explained. This prism plans aspects of handling food products. The shown prism shows the methods from the most optimal to the least optimal [10]:

1. Early prevention by minimizing the total volume of food products produced
2. Donation of leftover food products to community structures
3. Giving the collected food product waste to the farmers to feed the animals

4. Delivery of used oils for the preparation of biodiesel fuel
5. Composted food waste for the production process of organic matter used to fertilize the soil

6. Last resort for unconsumed food products

Food industry waste is not the same for different products. Thus, food industry waste can be divided into two types:

1. plant
2. animal.

In addition, food waste can be divided into seven subcategories:

1. roots and tubers,
2. fruits and vegetables,
3. cereals,
4. oil plants and legumes,
5. dairy products,
6. fish and seafood
7. meat products.

The most wasted of these categories are fruits, vegetables, roots and tubers. Worldwide, an average of 40-50% of fruits, vegetables, roots and tubers are wasted or lost. In grains and fish, this rate reaches about 30%, and in meat, milk and also 20% in oil plants. These statistics call for finding the causes of food waste, including solutions to this harmful process [1.2]

In addition, retailers and markets also contribute to food industry waste and losses. In some cases, the products are not stored at the right temperature or in the right conditions. For example, various microorganisms and domestic animals can damage food stored in warehouses. As a result, food may be wasted after being purchased by consumers. In many cases, consumers buy or cook too much, which in turn results in the process of throwing away products. Food (or inedible parts of food) removed from the food supply chain and sent for animal feed, biomaterial processing or other industrial uses is considered "valorization and conversion" rather than "food waste". "

Food waste also includes food losses due to low quality vegetables, damaged crops left in the field and crops with low commercial value. Food waste and food loss can occur for a variety of reasons, including damage during transportation, improper storage or packaging, contamination, or problems at the processing stage, according to the FAO report.

Ecologically, food industry waste leads to chemical use such as fertilizers and pesticides, maximum fuel is used for transportation, and the more food corrodes in landfills, the more methane gas is produced, which is considered one of the most harmful greenhouse gases worldwide. There are two aspects to the contribution of food industry waste to greenhouse gas emissions[6.7] :

1. The process of decomposition of food industry waste after disposal in landfills
2. Life cycle from production to consumption (distribution, sale and also consumer waste).

Food industry waste, in particular, maximizes the level of greenhouse gas emissions by producing methane gas, one of the most potent gases. As global warming and climate change affect the environment, there is an increasing demand to minimize waste from the food industry.

The annual report of the FAO organization managed to reveal a clear pattern in food industry waste on a global scale. Although middle- and higher-income regions show more food loss and food waste at the downstream or consumption level, developing countries are more likely to lose or waste food at the upstream stage due to lack of appropriate harvesting technology and also infrastructure. . Food industry waste that ends up in landfills is a large volume of methane - a greenhouse gas even more powerful than CO₂. It should be noted that the maximum amount of greenhouse gases such as methane, CO₂ and chlorofluorocarbons results in the absorption of infrared rays. This, in turn, heats the earth's atmosphere, causing warming and climate change.

As agriculture accounts for an average of 70 percent of water used worldwide, food industry waste is also a major waste of fresh water and groundwater resources. The negative impacts of the food industry are significant in terms of water consumption and energy use. Throughout the supply chain, the food industry uses significant amounts of water and generates correspondingly large amounts of wastewater. Wastewater from the food industry consists of biological materials and dissolved organic and inorganic solids, which pose a significant environmental burden. In terms of waste generation, the largest producers are dairy, cocoa/chocolate/confectionery, as well as brewing/distilling and meat processing industries. Prevention of food industry waste and prevention of environmental pollution, energy-saving process technologies, including water conservation, are always considered a priority. In addition, food industry waste reduction and disposal processes are also desirable strategies. This is due to the fact that waste streams from the food industry have a large organic content. These food industry wastes contain fats, sugars, antioxidants, etc. rich in valuable compounds such as [8]

As a general trend, developing countries face more food loss during agricultural production, while food waste at the consumer level is higher in middle and high income households. According to the FAO report, this is about 31-39 percent of total waste (compared to low-income regions (4-16 percent)).

Food waste continues into the post-harvest process, but the exact amount of post-harvest losses is relatively unknown and difficult to estimate. Thus, the various factors that contribute to food waste, whether from a biological-ecological or socio-economic point of view, will limit the usefulness and, by extension, the reliability of the overall figures. Food safety requirements can also claim non-compliant foods before they are placed on the market [11]. Although this contrasts with efforts to recycle food industry waste (such as animal feed), safety regulations are in place to ensure consumer health. They are especially vital in the processing of food products of animal origin (for example, meat and dairy products). This is because products contaminated from these sources can cause and are associated with microbiological and chemical hazards [6.7]

Saving an average of one-fourth of all food currently wasted would feed a large number of undernourished people. From the point of view of future food security, research shows that. Halving the total amount of food calories currently lost and wasted (from 24% to 12%) by 2050 would save an average of 1.314 trillion kcal of food per year, which in turn would save enough to feed the world's population in 2050. about 22% of our predicted calorie needs. This is based on business-as-usual forecasts related to food demand. According to forecasts, minimization of food loss and food industry waste in the near future can lead to the following positive results [9]:

1. Minimizing poverty statistics and supporting the development process of rural areas by providing more food for the sales process and personal consumption of farmers;
2. benefiting women by increasing the return on investment and thus minimizing the total time spent working in the fields, as well as minimizing household food costs while spending less;
3. to help prevent the spread of agriculture to natural ecosystems;
4. to minimize the amount of water needed for agricultural production by rationally using already grown foods;
5. reduce agriculture-related greenhouse gas emissions by making greater use of food grown and including landfilling food industry waste.

In short, minimizing food loss and waste provides an opportunity to optimally benefit many sustainable development issues, including food security. However, the rational reduction of food loss and food industry waste will require an integrated vision system from all stakeholders in the supply chain, as well as a modern global food system where waste is not used as a profit mechanism. Nutrient losses during agricultural production occur when harvestable crops remain in the soil. It may be that weather conditions make harvesting unfavorable or impossible, or that

the product does not meet high quality standards for the customer. It should be noted that in the United States, it has become common for farmers to grow more than they plan to sell in order to avoid the risk of a portion of their crop being destroyed by weather or pests. However, in cases where farmers produce more than the norm, but the market is not favorable for sale, many will leave the majority of the crop in the ground. The reason for this is that the collection of the product is more expensive than the sales. In this way, food markets work against farmers and policies should be in place to protect farmers when crop losses occur and also to encourage harvesting during excess production to create surplus food supplies.

A major contributor to food loss is the lack of rational management and storage of fresh produce such as fruit, vegetables, meat and fish, especially in developing regions. In developing countries, an average of 19% of fruit and vegetable losses occur during processing and storage. Those nutrients can spoil more quickly in hot climates and thus require proper cool storage conditions after the capture, cutting or harvesting process. In addition, failure to store grains or legumes in an airtight environment allows moisture and pests to enter, which in turn potentially leads to contamination of the product with mold, toxins, or pests. This means that farmers have to sell their entire crop after the harvest process, which in turn can mean getting minimum prices, as supply will be maximum at this time. Thus, in low-income countries, the application and investment in technologies that facilitate the rational management and storage of fresh produce and grain can help minimize food loss.

Proper handling of fresh fruits and vegetables after the harvesting process and also during transportation is of great importance because these products are easily crushed and cannot be marketed in these cases. In developing countries, sacks and bags are often used in the process of transporting products, but they are poorly protected. One option is to use plastic crates, which can be reused for up to five years and are often easier to handle due to their manageable size and handles. A study in Sri Lanka found that plastic boxes reduced vegetable losses from about 30% to 5% compared to previous management strategies. Thus, research is needed to better manage and transport containers using locally sourced and environmentally friendly materials. Thus, increasing investment in infrastructure (i.e. construction of reliable roads) and including the introduction of basic refrigeration facilities for storing food products will minimize food losses and prevent spoilage of fresh food products, allowing them to reach the market faster [5] .

In several countries, there are a number of problems with the disposal/treatment process of food industry waste due to inadequate waste management systems. The waste management practices used for the food industry waste disposal process are as follows:

1. landfill
2. incineration of waste
3. composting
4. anaerobic digestion

Landfills are a method that causes odor, methane and leaching problems. It is not recommended to use this method because it leads to social, ecological and even hygienic problems. The incineration method is an old technique used for the disposal process of a significant amount of solid waste (80-85%). This method produces heat that can be exploited for energy purposes in industry. In addition, since the combustion process takes place in uncontrolled conditions, it leads to the formation of more carbon emissions.

Composting and anaerobic treatment methods are based on the process of biological degradation of organic matter. Composting takes place under aerobic conditions and the end product is called compost. This method ensures the production of fertilizer that can be exploited in agricultural production. The main essence of this method is the mixing of obtained food industry waste with possible garden waste. So, that mixture is shredded, and then it is composted in a closed environment at a temperature of up to 70°C for a period of 2-4 weeks, on average. This

intended process further accelerates the composting process. Thanks to this process, harmful microbes are destroyed. In the next step, the material is left outside to mature for about 1-3 months under high quality control before being used as a soil conditioner.

Implementing a composting process policy can lead to increased compost sales. It can also lead to many economic benefits. Also, relevant municipal institutions can pave the way for strengthening sustainability by minimizing greenhouse gas emissions, including preventing erosion, and improving important soil quality. However, with the application of this technique, a number of problems such as NH₃, leakage, greenhouse gases and odors arise.

Anaerobic treatment method is a method that converts biomass into biogas and also digestion products in a controlled anaerobic atmosphere. The obtained biogas is a great source of energy with 60-70% methane, 30-40% CO₂ and other trace components. At the same time, the production of biogas fertilizer rich in components is ensured. Although this method is often used as a rational waste management method for sewage and animal manure, this practice also has a number of drawbacks. These include the following[3] :

1. Methane productivity
2. uncontrolled processing environment due to accumulation of volatile free fatty acids
3. Foaming problem due to lipid and high protein content
4. low buffering capacity due to rapid digestion of volatile fatty acids

When the methods used for food industry waste management are studied, it is seen that there is a need for sustainable and alternative methods of disposal. If the countries of the world can achieve minimum food industry waste, the benefits we will gain can include the following:

1. Saving labor costs due to rational management of food products to be used, including their preparation and storage.
2. Cost saving when we buy food as much as we will consume and also avoiding extra external expenses.
3. Minimizing methane emissions from landfills and achieving a lower carbon footprint.
4. Rational management of energy and resources, prevention of pollution related to the process of growing, producing, transporting and selling food products.

Land waste related to food industry waste is divided into two categories:

1. Using land to produce food
2. Land used for throwing food waste

There are two types of land, arable and non-arable. Arable land is where crops can be grown, and uncultivable land is not ideal for crops. These uncultivated lands are perfect for livestock. On average, about 900 million hectares of uncultivated land are used for meat production. An average of 11.5 billion hectares of the global land surface is used for agriculture. The land used for cultivation or animal husbandry is not a problem. The main problem is food industry waste. We never realize what we waste with food.

It should be noted that an average of 67 million tons of food is wasted in India every year, of which about 70-75% of food industry waste rots in landfills. In the short term, if we don't pay attention to the losses, the potential for over-yielding will also deteriorate. The concept of biodiversity includes the full spectrum of life among different species and types of organisms in an ecosystem. Thus, deforestation processes are being carried out in order to increase or increase animal husbandry. This, in turn, seriously affects our natural flora and fauna. If the number of livestock increases, more natural land is converted to pasture. The more cattle graze on the land, the more it becomes unfit for cultivation. Land becomes less natural and diverse.[10]

Conclusions

From what was previously presented, it should be noted that food industry waste is generated throughout the supply chain. In short, agricultural production - storage - processing - distribution - management - consumption processes. As a result, the main responsibility for food

safety, including taking certain measures to prevent food waste, rests with those involved in that chain. In some EU countries, it is forbidden to sell food below cost. As a result, retailers are unable to sell fresh food products (toward the end of the day) at lower prices. This ban increases food waste in the supply chain we mentioned earlier. Actions taken by the states against food losses and food waste should be aimed at improving the optimality and sustainability of food supply chains. Since 2011, EU member states have been conducting targeted campaigns to inform the public about the causes and consequences of food industry waste. Thus, measures to reduce food industry waste are proposed, and scientific information related to the sustainability and solidarity of the population is delivered. Legislative measures promoted by countries as well as positive practices aim to increase the optimality of food chains. These measures are very important for the sustainable development of economies and for the balancing of flows in the world trade system of agricultural products. There is a close relationship between food industry waste and the ecological situation. For every kg of food produced (through processing), about 4.5 kg of CO₂ is released into the atmosphere. Thus, if we take into account the approximately 89 million tons of food industry waste produced in Europe, this will lead to an average of 370 million tons of CO₂ equivalent, resulting in a greenhouse effect.

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Journalism

Reflection of political topics in Kazakhstan in the social networks (based on the events of January 2022)

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The January incident in Kazakhstan in 2022 caused mixed public opinion. Instagram Facebook and social networks play a special role in this sense. Residents of the country actively use these communication channels in their complaints and appeals to the authorities. Since 2019, when the head of state K. Tokayev opened a page on Instagram and started blogging on Twitter, the demand of the population for social networks has become even greater. The scope of these networks is much wider than that of traditional mass media. Here there is an opportunity to immediately express your opinion about the incident, promptly receive any information and bring the answer to the competent institutions and individuals. However, compared to various media, the information on this site is not filtered in any way. As a result, any user of the network can independently become the author of the information. It's no secret that fake news can spread quickly and create panic between countries. Social networks are currently very effective. They have a power that the everyday garden cannot use. This is the formation of public opinion. They have the same mechanism. If the user, which author, which content often reads and leaves any reaction to it (clicking, commenting, sharing information), then next time the social network will also offer content in the same direction. Facebook Instagram, however, differ in the dissemination of information. Facebook Instagram often conveys information as a fact, there is reason to believe that Facebook plays the role of a platform for the exchange of opinions, which comprehensively discusses this information. Neither during the January event, nor after the publication of information about it, these networks did not change their course. Opinions can be divided into three groups: positive, negative and neutral.

Literature review. The theorist of the American Information Society, E. Toffler, wrote that the nearest historical boundary "is as deep as the first wave of changes that began with the introduction of agriculture" ten thousand years ago... The second wave of changes was caused by the Industrial Revolution. We are the third wave generation. Toffler noted such features of the new wave as demassivization and de-hierarchization of society and culture, centralization of production and population, a sharp increase in information exchange, convergence of production and consumption, multicentricity, self-government of political systems, ecological restructuring. In the paper "Powershift" (1990), E. Toffler wrote that the information society is defined as a society in which the knowledge factor and the sphere of knowledge play a decisive role in social development. Presenting society as a system that divides its power into three bases (power, money and information), Toffler suggests the following historical periods: • at the heart of the pre-industrial era is the power; • at the heart of the industry is money; • at the heart of the modern accelerated society is education. The information literacy of a society is also related to its knowledge. Expert of the Association of Media Education O. According to Zhilavskaya, media information literacy, along with the free transmission of information and opinions, requires from

the activities of the media and other informants a critical assessment of the content of information, the presence of significant reasons for the use of this or that multimedia content (O. Zhilavskaya, 2019).

However, the second group of scientists claims that social networks are a public platform for politics. Y. Habermas noted in his book that participation in public relations opposes feudal domination. Y. Habermas compared this concept with consensus-oriented communication, which can create a real (possibly) and relevant public space for two areas of public communication.: connections of equality and politics. Yu. It is believed that an informed and resonant independent press based on a free market is important for the civil public sphere, which Habermas proposed as a platform for public debate. This press should be accessible to many people and include various arguments and points of view within the framework of rational discussions. In this public space, public policy is even discussed, which is considered part of critical thinking (Habermas J, 1991). Opinion of Yu . Habermas for the last ten years of the twentieth century corresponds to today's Facebook content. The Albanian environment (context) offers many examples showing that thanks to the ability to create virtual communities and use virtual connections, users of social networks have the opportunity to organize, discuss and resist a certain political action or a certain wrong decision. The widespread news that the dismantling of Syrian chemical weapons will be carried out in Albania caused a great resonance from the public. Given that television or newspapers deliberately ignore this issue, the Facebook community has organized an event that will unite many people. In a short time, a Facebook page directed against the destruction of chemical weapons in Albania attracted a large number of readers. This profile served to organize an opposition group during the protests that took place at that time (Erlis Çela, 2015).

The effectiveness of Facebook's work here can be clarified by the Danish researcher Michael Basset quoted. According to him, from 23% to 47% of the content in this social network consists of links. That is, links direct users to the website of any campaign or any article in the media. You can also read the second person's Facebook page or just one post at this link (Michael Bossetta, 2018). An extensive user base can easily register on the Facebook page of politicians, comment on their public letters and posts, share them on their pages or send them to other virtual friends. WebsiteRating.com According to the website, as of September 30, 2021, the number of active Facebook users has reached 1.93 billion. Michael Bassett also described four aspects of the digital architecture of social networks: network structure, functionality, algorithmic filtering and data transmission. The reason these categories are chosen is because they affect the political content published by politicians, or the access of mourning mats to political messages. The network structure contributes to how users identify and link political accounts. The functionality is based on the rules for creating and distributing multimedia on the platform. And gentian filtering determines which content users will come across. And data identification allows politicians to guide their readers. These categories do not depend on a particular platform, so they can be used as a basis for comparing the digital strategies of politicians through various social media channels. In addition, the heuristics of digital architecture are not limited to the study of policy measures. It can also be used for any aspect of political communication on the Internet, such as political debates between citizens, mobilization of protests or journalistic reports. Differences in the protocols underlying the platform's network structure affect three aspects of user interaction. The first is the search function, which means that users can find new accounts and subscribe to them. The second is to join, which tells how new accounts communicate. For example, the didactic structure of Facebook friends requires the account holder to confirm the relationship, and leads to the creation of online networks reflecting the offline relationships of users (Elli son, Steinfield, & Lampe, 2007). The third aspect of the network structure involves privacy, which refers to the ability of users to influence who can identify them with a search (search function), as well as how connections (connections) interact. Takeshita, in his research related to the increase in the

number of data sources, argues that online media have violated the traditional model of agenda formation by increasing the number of media and sources (Takeshita, 2006). Endless information has created opportunities for non-mainstream politicians to influence the news agenda. In addition, social media platforms have recently allowed citizens to play an active role in the production, distribution and consumption of news, facilitating the involvement of individuals in personal, thematic and network-dependent news streams (Klinger & Svensson, 2015; Shehata & Stromback, 2018).

Results and discussion. According to the Internet Association of Kazakhstan, the number of Kazakhstani Facebook users is 340,660. The country ranks 100th out of 200 states. For the same half-year (according to data for 2021), the growth amounted to 53 thousand or 18.5%. According to these indicators, it can be seen that the reader has more choice to get information. The information area is limitless. Any user can transmit, distribute information and turn himself into a source. Therefore, the user should be able to filter the information. This is becoming the main and main problem in our time of information. Instagram Facebook and social networks posted comprehensive information in connection with the January event. It can be divided into three groups: official (members of a state organization), independent (experts, oppositionists) and private individuals (the number of readers is below 5000). The official group includes a representative of organizations of national importance. Independent experts can be called experts from every industry with more than 5,000 readers. Representatives of the group with the number of subscribers in the last separate group less than 5000. While the two previous groups often distribute information and become the first source themselves, representatives of the last group consume this information (click, comment, publish on their page, send to other friends on the network). The official group includes Adviser to the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan Yerlan Karin (reader 14,403). There are three posts on the official representative's page regarding the January event. The first entry is dated January 10. The entire post on this page is informational in nature, aimed at informing the public, informing about what is happening. The content of the post is neutral. And analyzing the content on the comments written under the post, it is possible to trace the actions of the audience on demand, the request for a solution to the case and the anger, negativity of the population as a whole. However, the fact that Yerlan Karin immediately publishes official information on social networks and always reports to the audience about what has been done significantly contributes to the spread of fake news and the fact that the public does not panic. In the course of the study, it was noticed that there are few members of the public distributing official information to the audience. This entails trust in false and subversive messages spread through social networks due to the inability to obtain reliable information in a timely manner. And on the posts of blogger Orken Kenzhebek, we see a character calling for suppressing the discontent of the population, not to believe disinformation. The first post about the January event of Orken Kenzhebek, which is read by 14,305 readers, was published on January 5. Although objective information was recorded and urged the population not to participate in the uprising, comments written under the post are undesirable. The total number of comments is 85, the sharing post is also small. The average number is 2. Murat Abenov's posts with 61,610 readers concerning the January event are dominated by a demand of a positive nature, a demand for a report from the authorities, which keeps the audience in one position. Accordingly, the feedback here is also higher than that of those who transmit official and positive information. So, on January 7, 90 people commented on the post of public figure Abenov about the complete loss of people's trust by akims and 21 people shared. The number of likes is 555. such statistics are not found in the above group. Also, the author's post began to be published from January 2. One of the Facebook users who writes in this direction is entrepreneur Margulan Seisenbai. His first post about the January event was published on January 5. This page also has a very high level of audience feedback. The post entitled "The CSTO and the right to be a real war" (given unchanged)

was visited by 2.1 thousand people, 679 people expressed their opinion, 446 people shared with other users. 91 network users commented on the message of public figure Mukhtar Taizhan about the fall in gas prices on January 3.

Despite the fact that the number of readers did not exceed 5,000 people, representatives of individual groups continuously broadcast to their audience. There are often professional journalists and media specialists in this row. If the post of experts from different fields with more than 10 thousand readers is close to the analytical genre, then you can notice that the post from this group is in the information genre, similar to a keyhole. The use of the link, which Michael Bassett also pointed out in his research, is also characteristic of this group. Many gave links to their materials or other media materials and shared them on their pages. In addition, the audience feedback indicators for them are the same as those of the representatives of the official group. However, there is a noticeable change in the number of readers on both sides. For example, the number of readers of the authors of the material written with criticism of the authorities is at least 50,000 people. This indicator is not even comparable with those who distribute official, reliable information. Because the number of the audience that reads them is three times less. Another thing that was discovered during the study is that comments that are negative or disagree with the author's opinion for representatives of the official group are written on behalf of fake users. And if you conduct a study of commentators who subscribe to representatives of independent groups, you will notice that more than 70 percent of accounts are working. Facebook is a platform for assessing what is happening in the country from various angles, and the Instagram network is the main tool for spreading information. The same platform also reflected the features of civil society. Each person went live on the occasion of the incident he witnessed, and constantly posted videos. One of them is entrepreneur Damir Amanzholov. He helped the military during the conflict and helped protect the property of local businessmen. He filmed all this on Instagram. It is seen by millions of users and shared with each other. It should be noted that Instagram currently has several advantages over traditional media, including television. One of them is time. If there is any incident, the technical equipment of the TV for its transmission will take time. And it doesn't take much time to insert a video on Instagram in just 15-60 seconds. For example, @protenge.kz information about the resignation of the chairman of the National Security Committee Karim Masimov on his Instagram page was published in stories at p.m. 01:25.

Conclusion. The research article examines the publication in social networks of information about the January event that took place in Kazakhstan in 2022. No matter which network we take, information is distributed very freely. The only question is who transmits the information how. Facebook users who provide the information above were divided into three groups depending on the diversity of the audience, direction and industry. As for the results of the study, the feedback from the audience with official representatives of the state with an audience of more than 14 thousand people is low and all negative. And the feedback from the audience with independent authors who independently convey their thoughts and information from different angles is high. They also raise problems in society not once, but several times. This network is supported by users. There is an impression in the country that the connection between the government and the common people is not firmly established. This conclusion is once again proved in the material of this study. Independent authors publish posts on social networks from January 2 to January 3 and give an expert assessment of the situation, and the first entries from government representatives are published from January 10. Also, the number of posts is limited to two or three, posts on this topic are still published in another group. Due to the information that the Central Security Service troops are entering the country, a lot of fake information has spread among users. However, there was no explanatory information about him on the page of the authorities. If we compare the number of audiences between the two groups, then more than 65,000 users read independent

authors. So this means that the information they distribute will have many customers and their opinion will be a multiple of the reader who reads them. Firstly, State officials should still provide prompt explanatory information on any event on their social media pages and always get feedback in order to avoid spreading misinformation among the public and empty riots. Secondly, freedom of expression should not be restricted. Among the commentators who subscribed to the post of officials, it turned out that fake accounts leave a lot of comments. This suggests that the citizens of the country are still afraid to express their opinions freely. Thirdly, listen to the voice of the people. If we look at why readers read so many independent authors, they will recognize the vulnerable part of the audience that is on the same wavelength with them. And the connection between official representatives and the people is very far from the realistic world. Therefore, the topics hotly discussed in social networks should not go unnoticed by the state in creating bilateral trust.

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Culturology

Dialogue of cultures as a source of cultural integration

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In the context of modern socio-cultural processes, the problem of interaction between cultures has acquired particular relevance. The multiple acceleration of the pace of development of modern science and technology has led to a rapid increase in the pace of life and the number of intercultural communications. Based on this, it can be argued with a high degree of confidence that there is not a single nation left in the world that has not at least once experienced the need to establish intercultural ties with representatives of another nation. Contacts with other ethnic groups and cultures can be of a different nature - from aggressive to friendly and visa versa. The study of cultures in their interaction allows us to find out the principles and forms of their relationship, the degree of their "compatibility" with each other and the level of closeness of their interests.

The modern world is entering a stage when the basis for disagreements is not the 'impenetrability' of cultures, but, on the contrary, their excessively intense interpenetration, which does not leave them temporary space for a sufficiently deep assimilation with each other and thus serves as the basis for the formation of new conflicts. Dialogue as a concept built on the interaction of equal subjects has a unique property of maintaining relations equality among its members. According to the principle of its functioning, it counteracts globalization, not allowing any of the parties to take a dominant position. Thus, the dialogue ensures the interaction of two independent subjects and maintains a balance of power between them. The economic and value expansion of highly developed countries, along with the problem of mass migration of the population, raise the relevance of studying the principle of the dialogue of cultures as an approach to solving international relations to a new level.

Even though Kazakhstan is far away from the English speaking world with its geographical position, it has become to a long-standing partner in the field of cultural and economic relations with developed European countries. Despite this, nowadays, there are practically no serious research that would allow us to fully understand how Kazakh and English speaking cultures correlate in today's rapidly changing world, especially after the global social and economic changes that have completely changed Kazakhstan in recent decades. These changes had a huge impact on the perception of the world from the point of view of Kazakhstan and the Kazakhs, and also changed the idea of themselves from the outside. How does Kazakhstan appear in the eyes of the English speaking cultures; how core values are perceived in national cultures: literature, philosophy, art, sports; What aspects of social life in Kazakhstan are well known to modern English speaking world and vice versa? And the most important question for a culturologist is: what knowledge all of these based on? At the moment, science has practically no reasoned, fact-based information on this topic. The number of such questions are increasing and all of them require detailed study.

One of the main guidelines in the culturological development of such complex phenomena as ethnic and national cultures is the mentality of peoples. In the form of traditions, customs and behavioral stereotypes, they fix the most important cultural and historical constants of each ethnic

group. This information forms new generations of representatives of this or that society, in turn, determining its socio-cultural guidelines. The development of the question of the central constants of the national character is especially relevant in the indicated context, since it allows one to navigate not only in the principles of the transfer of cultural data within one cultural unit, but also to clarify the understanding of the ways of their exchange between different cultures.

Culture constants have different forms of expression. The most important way of transmitting any type of information is, of course, the verbal code presented in the literature. With its help, the characteristics of cultures are able to overcome temporal, geographical and political boundaries. Works of the largest Kazakh poets and writers of the XIX - XX centuries have become one of the main sources formation of the image of Kazakhstan in the cultural consciousness of the West. Western literature also left a noticeable mark on the Kazakh thought through its cultural legacy of outstanding people. To understand the deep foundations of Kazakh and English speaking cultural relations, it is important to know to what extent the literary heritage of both countries influenced the formation and nature of the dialogue between them. Analysis of the constant properties of literary reflections as the main mediator in the process of cultural interaction, coupled with the study of the foundations of the national the nature of both peoples as a source of the national spirit also seems to be relevant in posing problems related to the dialogue of cultures.

The increasing development of international communications has turned the dialogue between cultures and civilizations into an indisputable reality of public life. These changes gradually went beyond social relations and penetrated into the deeper layers of Kazakh lives. As elements of world culture penetrate into the lives of peoples, a common field of activity is created for representatives of various geographical and cultural communities. These fields of interaction towards finding a "common language" are a necessary condition for any dialogue.

In the context of ongoing globalization, the path of integrating Kazakh culture into the global cultural space becomes relevant for Kazakhstan in this context. Today, Kazakhstan is perceived in the international community as an equal subject of international relations: holding congresses of world and traditional religions, forums of spiritual culture, chairmanship of the Kazakhstan in the OSCE, etc.

With the acquisition of independence, the Kazakhstan opened wide opportunities for the development of their culture. There was an opportunity to open the whole spiritual palette of Kazakh culture to the world.

According to the Kazakh philosopher K. A. Abishev: "Each established culture arose, first of all, on certain cultural values. That is why this culture is specific, since it differs significantly from any other, and people who profess these values see the whole the rest of the world".

M. Auezov draws attention to the preservation of the cultural traditions of the Kazakh people and notes that the value, pragmatic principle of managing in a nomadic society predetermined the limitedness, stinginess of the objective world of nomads.

The problems of the globalization of culture are presented by Western culturologists and anthropologists. Their opinions about the phenomenon of globalization are rather contradictory. Of greatest interest are the concepts of U. Hannerz and S. Eisenstadt. Hannerz developed the theory of the ecumene as a region of constant cultural interaction, information exchange and translation of the phenomena of one culture into the language of another. According to Hannerz, the process of globalization of culture can develop in four main directions: the scenario of "blossoming" or globalization without Westernization; the scenario of "global homogenization", which assumes the complete dominance of Western culture in the world; the "saturation" scenario, which is one of the versions of such unification; the scenario of "peripheral corruption", which assumes the decomposition of Western culture in the process of adaptation on the periphery. Most preferable, as we see it, is the scenario of "blossoming" or globalization without

westernization. In the global ecumene, there is an equal dialogue and exchange of information among numerous peripheral cultures. At the same time, the metropolises act as stimulants that enliven the development of the periphery and contribute to the enrichment of local cultural values. But peripheral cultures actively interpret the introduced ideas, significantly modify the cultural flow and thus influence the culture of the metropolis.

S. Eisenstadt, joining the "blossoming" scenario and, following Hannerz, choosing the path of globalization without Westernization, having studied the history of the cultural dialogue of ancient and modern civilizations, came to the conclusion that the process of globalization of cultures in the field of inter-civilizational interactions is indeed universal. In the context of globalization, the "core of national life" of Kazakh culture should be traditional culture, dialogue of cultures, a system of cultural and civilizational values, national ideology, modern technologies and technology.

Thus, such a question might arise: What does the Kazakh culture represent? Modern Kazakh culture is, first of all, a local interethnic culture, formed on the basis of the unity of the historical fate of peoples, long and close cultural interaction and cultural exchange between them, resulting in a high level of similarity in institutional forms and mechanisms of their social organization and regulation, legal and political systems, specialized components and forms of the economic structure, religious and confessional institutions, in philosophy, science, education systems, etc., 'while maintaining more or less diversity in the features of the ethnographic cultures of the peoples that make up a particular civilization'.

The concept of 'dialogue of cultures' was formed and developed in cultural studies under the influence of the works of representatives of the dialogic school. Various approaches to the study of the dialogue of cultures are reflected in the works of such scientists as M. Kagan, G. Pomerants, V. Makhlin, M. Fridman, etc.

The subject of cultural relations between Kazakhstan and European world developed in works of Sh. Satpayeva, M. Madanova, A. Mashakova and other researchers. As for studies directly devoted to the problems of the cultural dialogue via the legacy of cultural phenomenon, their number is extremely limited. The works of Mukhtar Auezov are devoted to this topic. Meanwhile, with the development of a number of new approaches to the study of culture (in particular, thesaurus), new opportunities are opening up in the study of problems cultural dialogue.

'Dialogue of national cultures as a problem of cultural studies' is noted that the concept of 'dialogue of cultures', despite its current popularity, has recently appeared in science and everyday life. However, the signs of dialogue are known to science from the works of the outstanding thinkers since antiquity (Plato, Tacitus), the Middle Ages and the Renaissance (Petrarch, Montaigne), Enlightenment (Rousseau, Herder).

Comparison of cultures and analysis of the dialogue between them is impossible without perceiving them as independent units. The question of the existence of different cultures tied to a particular nationality played a key role in cultural studies. I. G. Herder, N. Ya. Danilevsky, O. Spengler made a significant contribution to the development of scientific ideas about a multicultural world. They revealed the fact of obvious inconsistencies of a categorical nature between the cultures of different peoples and transferred the perception of culture and cultures to a new level of understanding. The emergence of the philosophy of dialogue is associated with the beginning of the 20th century. The development of this epoch belongs to the Austrian-German school of dialogists (F. Ebner, F. Rosenzweig, M. Buber). Subsequently, the ideas of dialogue as an image and a fundamental principle of thinking were actively developed by M. M. Bakhtin, A. Toynbee, V. S. Bibler and his scientific school of dialogics, which considered the dialogue of cultures as a situation of collision of fundamentally irreducible to each "cultures of thinking and various forms of understanding'. The dialogue of cultures has cultural-philosophical, and deeply practical tasks of a political, economic and spiritual nature.

Another fundamental term and one of the most important components of the thesaurus is the concept. Following Yu. S. Stepanov and using his formulations, we understand the concept as “the core of culture in the mental world of a person”, as well as “a clot of culture in the human mind”. In the thesaurus approach, the concept is characterized as an fusion of meaning and sensory perception, an internal image expressed in a sign. It is connected with other concepts not only by a logical, but also by a value relationship. The content of some concepts is more figurative, others are more conceptual, but this does not change the bilateral unity of their structure. This property of the concept is due to the need to serve both the intellectual and the sensual side of human existence. One of the most important groups of concepts that characterize each culture are the so-called ‘values’. Value is what allows us to navigate in the social and cultural environment, realizing our strategic interests. With the help of values, people's behavior is introduced into the framework of certain social principles, subject to the general rules of collective life, cultural patterns. The set of values generally forms the framework for education value orientations of the subject. Value orientations mean the whole complex of value attitudes that determines the general direction of the thesaurus development. The definition of value orientations allows give an explanation of the reasons for accepting or rejecting certain cultural data. Understanding the value orientations of different cultures is one of the most important ways to assess the level of mutual reflections between them.

The image of “highly spiritual” Kazakhstan in Western consciousness was created largely through the works of major Kazakh poets and writers and literary critics. In addition, the kazakh elites subsequently contributed to the formation of the Kazakh idea and the concept of the Kazakh consciousness. The use of the constant “Kazakh consciousness” in ‘Words of Edifications’ by Abai Qunanbaiuly, the first Kazakh historical-epopee ‘The Path of Abai’ (Abai Zholy) by Mukhtar Auezov, the historical trilogy ‘The Nomads’ by Iliyas Yessenberlin, is emphasized where it turns out to be a symbol of the best qualities of the Kazakh character associated with the pursuit of high ideals that have nothing to do with material substances. Thus, the ‘Kazakh consciousness’ has become a symbol of naturalness reflecting the western thinkers ideas addressed to the humankind ‘to acquire knowledge to achieve goals’.

The picture of the world of Kazakh culture, the ‘Kazakh consciouness’ as a ‘super-constant’ that combines a set of other major constants. Kazakh worldview reflected in the works of M. Auezov, I. Yessenberlin and other major Kazakh writers, is characterized primarily through closeness to nature, momentary spontaneity based on the sensual beginning, as opposed to logic, thoughtfulness and rationalism.

Mukhtar Auezov, as one of the most important figures of Kazakh nation, was an intermediate of Kazakh culture to integrate into other cultures. In his novel he described the spiritual values of the Kazakh people and their national traditions at the encyclopaedic level. His novel was highly appreciated by the French writer Louis Aragon “one of the best works of the XX century.” He was first who acquainted the English-speaking reader with the Kazakh culture through ‘The Path of Abai’ was recorded in the middle of the XX century and translated into Russian, and then mainly from the Russian version into many other languages of the world, including South-West Asia, the Middle East, Russia, Central Asia and Southern Europe.

The penetration of Kazakh literature into the English-speaking world was actively promoted by Russian translators from Kazakh into Russian. Abai’s work was famous thanks to Auezov, who was the first to achieve a constant status in the culture of the English-speaking world. The significance of his contribution to the history of European culture was recognized by leading anthropologists and historians (S. Sabol, T. Winner, N. Caffee). In accordance with their statements, Abai managed to move from the local to the international, universal level of culture. Abai’s works were published in ‘Soviet Literature’, ‘International Literature’ journals during the Soviet epoch, which were spread over the US countries, England and France. The English-speaking

world claimed that his work overturns all ideas about the life of the Kazakhs and the changes taking place in it.

Kazakhstan, having vast geographical areas, is surrounded on all sides by countries and cultures of various content. Interaction with them, of course, was and is inevitable, but the relationship with them is more absorbent than adaptive. The Kazakh thesaurus easily absorbs artifacts, constants and concepts of other cultures, but most often does not allow them to the center of the 'own' area. Incoming cultural codes reach the realm of the 'the others', where they can be used as needed for the national progress, but no more. The "Kazakh consciousness" is nothing more than the desire of the Kazakh thesaurus to absorb the widest possible range of cultural material and use it for the future perspectives of the nation. This is not promoted only the size of the country, but also its geographical position, linking West, East, South and North. At the level of cultural mutual reflections, an active dialogue of cultures is recorded through a significant number of common literary constants. The central constants of the Kazakh cultural and literary world, through the works of Abai and the novel by 'Abai Zholy' written by Mukhtar Auezov, managed to penetrate into the center of the cultural space of the English-speaking culture and "settle" in it. This is evidenced numerous reprints of their works and publications dedicated to them in various media.

It can be argued that cultural constants in general have a higher ability to penetrate the thesauri of other cultures, more easily transcending the political boundaries and protective membranes of the thesauri of cultures. Thus, the study confirms the unique function of literature and culture as an invaluable medium in the transmission of cultural values.

The integration of Kazakhstani culture into the world cultural space is taking place through the cultural legacy and it should become one of the important aspects and priorities in the foreign policy of the Republic representing Kazakhstani culture to the international community. Cultural synthesis is not assimilation. It retains the main positive content of each of the components while making a leap into a new quality that leads from ethnic, regional isolation to universal humankind. This marks the formation of a truly unified world culture in the vastness of the global ecumene.

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